

What's Love got to do with it?

Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together.

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July 2023

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy.

Declaration

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Abstract

Scottish educational guidance promotes ‘family learning’ programmes to encourage partnership with parents and families to improve educational attainment and economic stability (OECD, 2018, Scottish Government, 2012). However, real partnership is an ongoing challenge in Scottish education (The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016). Effective ‘family learning’ recognises parents as educators and includes mutual dialogue between families and supporting agencies (Grant, 1989; MacKenzie, 2010; Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014).

Yet, recent reviews and research studies on ‘family learning’ highlight limited dialogue suggesting a need for wider “consultation with practitioners, parents/families, children or young people” (Scottish Government, 2016b:16) a point supported by Cara and Brooks (2012:9) and The National Parent Forum of Scotland (2016:20). Contradictory policy discourse, lack of dialogue and a lack of research with families to understand ‘family learning’ in Scotland limits partnerships between families and educational professionals.

This qualitative research study addresses three key questions firstly, what ‘family learning’ means; secondly, where ‘family learning’ happens, and, finally, what ‘family learning’ requires to be most effective. Focus groups and one to one interview’s provided data from twenty-four sources including teachers, early years’ practitioners, and families. Participants held varying beliefs of ‘family learning’ as formal and informal, and provided information that highlighted key elements as important in developing understanding of what is needed in conceptualising ‘family learning’. Findings highlight specific qualities within three key themes of difference, development, and connection as important in effective ‘family learning’. Findings contribute to a ‘wealth model’ (NIACE, 2013; Scottish Government, 2016) of partnership and practice where

understanding and recognition is made of the learning and skills present in families.

The research asserts scope for future debate in considering 'family learning' out with formal education and of the qualities needed for 'professional' practice.

The research findings shift focus from outcomes (academic achievement, economic gain) to processes that enhance the affective development of partnership for high quality 'family learning'.

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Acknowledgements

It was interesting that writing acknowledgements for completion of this thesis was one of the most difficult. I suppose giving thanks to those who have supported me in a way that, in the words of one of my research participants, “accepts us for who we are and not as who we should be”, is a joy and raises my emotions. Of course, as an academic piece of work it could not have been achieved without the help and support of my supervision team Dr. Annette Coburn and Dr. Conny Gollek, the task of supervising a rebel who struggles with academia with a preference for keeping it simple, I know, was not an easy one.

My sincere thanks go also to my colleagues Professor Khadija Mohammed, Joyce Leslie who epitomise ‘Compassionate Love’ in their kind support. To Dr. Robert McGill, Dr. Nancy Allan and Dr. Andrew Killen who helped me to explore wider considerations in the gentlest of ways. To Ambreen Malik, Dean Armstrong and Laura Lindsay who provided constant inspiration and support. Each of these individuals and many more have given me relentless encouragement to build belief that the study was valid and that I could achieve it at all. In both counts I have had consistent doubt.

And finally, in the nature of the thesis topic, my appreciation sits firmly with my families, those who have listened, cared, loved, and taught me along the way, there are many. Most importantly, Matthew, Daisy, Sophie, Scarlett and my wee Ellie and Tommy, I forever acknowledge the contribution you make to my existence, my cup runneth over.

Information about me.

Clarke and Hoggit (2009) encourage reflection at the beginning of the study to ask ourselves why we have an interest in this topic. They encourage us to ask what investment we have in the study and does the investment we have influence how we conduct the research. The following information provides reflections that have guided this study.

My family learning began growing up in a family that fostered children where I learned early on of the tragic impact of childhood experiences and the powerful effect that love or the lack of love has on children and adults in their ability to thrive. I learned that, whilst it would be expected that love would be gained in the family that you lived with, that this was not always a guarantee. I also learned that love and family can be gained elsewhere. In the words of bell hooks:

I know that I survived and thrived despite the pain of childhood precisely because there were loving individuals among our extended family who nurtured me and gave me a sense of hope and possibility. This story is common. Surviving and triumphing over dysfunctional nuclear families may depend on the presence of what psychoanalyst Alice Miller calls “enlightened witnesses.” Practically every adult who experienced unnecessary suffering in childhood has a story to tell about someone whose kindness, tenderness, and concern restored their sense of hope. This could only happen because families existed as part of larger communities..... (hooks, 2000:131).

The explanation provided by Bell hooks, resonated with my own experiences and of how “enlightened witnesses” in my own life helped me to thrive. When first introduced to the concept of ‘family learning’ my first thoughts were of what I and others had learned within my family, of who was involved and of what specific qualities were most effective in helping all to thrive. In this regard, I was aware of the range of individuals, blood, and non-blood relatives,

who showed love towards me and others and considered this to be an essential element. I was also aware of the impact that a lack of love has on human ability to thrive. My own experience has influenced my passion to work with children and families with completion of a BA in Early Education with first class honours, an accomplishment not often considered as achievable for individuals like me, with parents who have no academic qualifications, who lived within areas of low socio-economic status and who have suffered trauma in their life. My experiences have also highlighted that loving caring support has a transformative quality for individuals to thrive. The experiences influence the person that I am and the actions that I take in supporting others with understanding that loving support can be difficult and overshadowed by neoliberal influences. This understanding relates to various roles I assume in my life. For example, in my role as a parent to three daughters where personal and family values are often in contention to that of school and religious expectations, as a student and lecturer where ‘success’ in learning is positioned within subjective and economic plans, as a practitioner and lecturer in early education where my value of ‘love’ for children and adults in how it aids their learning and development sits in opposition to other colleagues who consider their role as meeting the expectations of curriculum plans and not including actions that demonstrate ‘love’ to children and families. Throughout my academic studies, I have been curious of why inequalities and partnership working seem to be a persistent challenge within Scottish education. It seems pertinent to question if there is something that we are missing. The study began with an interest of ‘family learning’ being considered as an approach in Scottish education with consideration if others found this differed to their own beliefs too. There was also an interest to explore if ‘love’ was considered as an important characteristic of ‘family learning’ amongst families and of whether ‘love’ could or should feature within ‘professional’ roles of those supporting children and families.

Presentations and publications related to this work.

November 2017	SERA Conference	Henderson, S, Gollek, C. Rainey, H., Gifford, E. Gilmour, L. (2017) 'Progress towards defining Family Learning for a Children's Workforce in a Post-Brexit Scotland'.
June 2019	UWS Bridging Connections Learning and Teaching Conference	Presentation of research via poster: Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together'.
November 2022	SERA Conference	Presentation of research study: 'Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together?'
June 2023	BA Childhood Practice development Forum.	Presentation of research study: What's Love got to do with it? 'Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together?'
October 2023	Resilience Learning Partnership Staff Development Forum	Presentation of research study: What's Love got to do with it? 'Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together?'
November 2023	SERA Conference	Presentation of research study: What's Love got to do with it? 'Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together?'
October 2024	UWS/HVL Conference.	Presentation of research study: What's Love got to do with it? 'Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together?'

I will be satisfied if among the readers of this work there are those sufficiently critical to correct mistakes and misunderstandings, to deepen affirmations and to point out aspects I have not perceived. From these pages I hope at least the following will endure: my trust in the people, and my faith in men and in the creation of a world in which it will be easier to love. (Freire. 1972:19)

1 Chapter 1 Introduction to the study.

Rationale

Mackenzie (2010) noted a lack of literature around the subject of ‘family learning’ in Scotland. This situation has remained until a review of ‘family learning’ practice conducted by the Scottish Government in 2016. Development of practice guidance made within ‘The Review of ‘Family Learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b) notes that partnership with parents is a crucial element of a ‘family learning’ approach. Advice is given that the "early engagement process and techniques are crucial in developing relationships and trust" (Scottish Government, 2016b:11). Whilst the review provides examples of how relationships with parents may be achieved in practice it lacks clarity on the qualities or attitudes that enhance ‘family learning’ relationships. Furthermore, this review and other research (Cara and Brooks, 2012:9; The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016:20) found that they had presented a narrow focus suggesting a need for wider “consultation with practitioners, parents, families, children or young people” (Scottish Government, 2016b:16).

Preceding practice guidance highlights the importance for ‘family learning’ programmes to include “strengths, needs, and interests of families” (Scottish Government, 2018:7). Whilst advice is repeated that parental partnership building is an important aspect for effective ‘family learning’ programmes, it was notably absent within the review of ‘family learning’ practice conducted previously. Additionally, the absence of meaningful discussions with families negates the importance of dialogue suggested within literature about ‘family learning’ (Grant, 1989, MacKenzie, 2010, Cara and Brooks, 2012, Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014, Scottish Government, 2016b, Whyte and Karabon, 2016). Meanwhile, Freire (1972:62) advocates that “dialogue cannot exist, however, in

the absence of a profound love for the world and for men” raising question of why partnership working, and dialogue is lacking between Scottish education and families.

Literature on the sociology of the family shows affective loving practice as a consistent characteristic of family. Gerhardt (2015) proposes that affection is so important for human development that he argues for affectionate practice to exist in areas out with the family. Yet, Cara and Brooks (2012:9) show a lack of research that, involves the views of parents and children or that gains knowledge of the benefits gained from both formal and informal learning. They also highlight a “lack of research identifying wider benefits [with] the so-called ‘softer’ benefits having received less attention and were very often side-lined”. Taggart (2016) also highlights an absence of sociological discussions that consider the importance of research that explore adult child relationships. De Lissa (1949:143) emphasised the need which some children must show affection to their teachers whilst Cousins (2017:17) notes that children “must not be disappointed but must be sure of her response”. Page (2011) adds that parents want their children to feel loved by professionals who take care of them. However, Bernstein (1971,2000) proposed that “subject expertise and the position that accompanies this” are more important than relational aspects of educational practitioner practice (Hargreaves et al, 2017:2). Zembylas (2007:355) supports this viewpoint in highlighting that pedagogical practice has been driven by content knowledge rather than “emotional and affective aspects”. Others note that education in general lacks reference to the importance of affective practice for learning (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015, White & Karabon, 2016, Cousins, 2017). Cousins (2017) specifically highlights the importance of love in pedagogy for learning. Yet, practitioners who took part within her study highlight that loving practice was instinctive and not resulting from practice guidance or training. The argument that training of educational practitioners

rarely includes exploration of the importance of a caring, compassionate loving pedagogy as supported by Taggart (2016), Page (2018) and Malcolm (2022). The distinct lack of discussion around loving pedagogy within professional training and guidance alongside the suggested importance that families place on affective practice presents a requirement for further exploration.

This study aimed to examine whether the present promotion of a ‘family learning’ approach in Scottish schools lacks appreciation of what ‘family learning’ means for families living in Scotland. The study specifically aimed to show what families regard as crucial factors of ‘family learning’ and whether they believe that these factors should be an aspect of professional ‘family learning’ practice. Whilst this study will address the gap in knowledge around the subject of ‘family learning’ in Scotland it also supports Holloway (2014:380) in acknowledging that “questions about the bio-logical, social and physic are emerging which have the potential to inform fruitful future debate in geographies of children, youth and families”.

Outline of thesis

This thesis builds on the work of Doreen Grant (1972), Fehr, Sprecher and Underwood (2009) and of feminist sociological thinking alongside the aim of the Scottish Government in considering what is needed for “human flourishing” (hooks, 2000; Fehr et al, 2009:9, Scottish Government, 2016a). The thesis aims to contribute to “Realising the Ambition of making Scotland the best place to grow up” (Education Scotland, 2020:9). The review of literature maintains a focus on the means in which human flourishing is achieved by drawing upon socio-constructionist theory (Burr, 1995, Elder-Vass, 2012) and Compassionate Love theory (Underwood, 2009) the recognition that individual development is influenced by the society in which one lives whilst society is influenced by the development of its people.

Pierre Bourdieu’s theories of habitus, field, and capital (Bourdieu,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017) are also identified as useful in considering the qualities that aid human flourishing whilst also encouraging consideration of who and what influences the qualities needed to thrive in Scottish society in the 21st century. In relation to Bourdieu’s theory, the ability to thrive relates to development of confidence and belief of the contribution that we make to wider society or as Bourdieu describes it, development of ‘habitus. Development of positive ‘habitus’ provides opportunities to develop a range of ‘capital’ that in turn allows access to whichever ‘field’ we need to navigate in life. The concept of ‘field’ may be society in general or the education system or ‘family learning’ itself whatever that may be (Bourdieu,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017).

Family and learning are recognised as key contributors to our ability to thrive in society and as such, provide a basis for consideration of the promotion of ‘family learning/’ as an approach within services supporting children and

families (Thorpe and Schmuller,1954, Hooks, 2000, Scottish Government, 2016b).

In consideration of the importance of love for learning and development (Lanas and Zembylas 2015, Taggart, 2016, White & Karabon, 2016, Cousins, 2017, Page, 2018, Malcolm, 2022) it was pertinent to explore if love was considered as an element of ‘family learning’ practice and as such, prompted a review of policy and practice guidance. A review of Scottish policy and practice guidance relating to ‘family learning’ practice showed limited reference to love until 2010 where ‘Pre-Birth to Three’ (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010) discussed the importance of love for the development of children in their early years. The Care Review (Scottish Government, 2016) also highlighted the importance of love in the lives of care experienced children with ‘Realising the Ambition’ (Education Scotland, 2020) making additional reference to love as key for children’s development. However, reference to love is made in terms of experiences out with formal institutions and not discussed as an expectation of ‘professional’ practice.

Whilst important, love is identified as a concept that is often difficult to define and specifically difficult in relation to ‘professional’ roles (Page, 2011, 2018; Morris, 2021, Malcolm,2022). This thesis considers ‘love’ in the context of human flourishing in drawing upon ‘Compassionate Love Theory’ developed by Fehr et al (2009) through research for the World Health Organisation (WHO) which considered what humans need to flourish and promotes ‘love’ as:

the attitudes and actions related to giving of self for the good of the other... a self-giving caring love that values the other highly and has the intention of giving full life to the other. A degree of emotional engagement, as appropriate, emphasises the enhancement of human flourishing...[and] ... also promotes actions that lessen any delusions of superiority (Underwood 2009:4,7).

The thesis specifically examines how ideologies promoted within key societal institutions of government, education, and family (Parsons, 1956, Morgan, 1975) promote and disseminate normative and acceptable viewpoints of both family and learning and consider how these viewpoints support or hinder our ability to thrive. The topic has presented wide ranging complexity in consideration of the interrelationship between individual personality, culture, society, and power (Underwood, 2009, Smart, 2011) in gaining an ability to thrive in life. As such, exploration has been limited to maintain a key focus on research within the period of 1990's through to present day recognised as a key period of change for families, government, and education.

The thesis considers historical influences on how ideas about family and learning are constructed. Historical viewpoints that perpetuate power and hierarchy in educational practice were identified as the context in which neoliberal market driven politics encourage a narrow view of how we consider both family and learning. The literature offered a compelling argument that perpetuation of hierarchy and ideals that are driven by an economic focus, create barriers in supporting learning and development. A social system that is driven by economic forces can be detrimental to supporting learning for life. The current focus on learning for working life and making money to sustain the market driven economy undervalues earlier conceptions of family and its importance in developing and nurturing social contexts that could sustain a more socially just, loving, and caring society. Barriers are created by promoting deficit views of individual capability with limited regard for the responsibility that wider society has in creation of personal circumstance and beliefs of ability.

A specific review of Scottish educational policy discourse is identified as contributing to promotion of judgement and creating a society that; perpetuates

power and hierarchy, lacks recognition of contribution and the ability to meet the needs of all people living within it. In contrast to the Scottish Government's aim of social justice for all (Education Scotland, 2018) Scottish Government educational policy perpetuates a deficit stance of children and families whilst considering a narrow view of family and learning which maintains a status quo and barrier to justice (Biesta, 2006, Priestley and Humes, 2010. Scottish Government, 2016b, Gillies, 2018). The following section provides an outline of the chapters and their content in questioning, 'What has love got to do with it? Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together'.

The thesis is presented in seven chapters. This first chapter has introduced the study by highlighting gaps in knowledge and understanding around the subject of family learning in Scotland providing a rationale for the study. This chapter is followed by chapter two which provides a review of literature on aspects relevant to the aims for this study.

Chapter two begins with an outline of the aim presented by the World Health Organisation (WHO) of developing a theory of practice which would aid "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:9). This section outlines the history and development of Compassionate Love theory as a means to enhance life where actions "centre on the good of another" (Underwood, 2009:3) echoing the purpose of 'family learning' outlined in literature. The section presents the key constructs of 'Compassionate Love' theory highlighting that actions to enhance the life of others must be cognisant of the individual alongside the multiple factors that affect their ability to thrive. Compassionate love theory is useful for this study as it encourages research which questions the why 'family learning' whilst naming actions that are important for 'family learning'. The theory encourages evaluation of approaches in line with key constructs such as the need for selfless

actions that focus on the good of the other in the first instance. Additionally, the theory endorses the need for actions to aid human flourishing as requiring levels of cognitive understanding that show depth of self and of the other person promoting the ability to respect rather than pity or judge. The section also outlines that the theory equally highlights a need to be open and receptive to the needs of others with an ability to respond from the core of ones being as important. Finally, the section ends by responding to the limited detail of what qualities may be key for effective ‘family learning’ by highlighting the specific values to aid human flourishing highlighted by Underwood (2009). Underwood, notes; the ability to care, to build trust, to help and support, to understand alongside the ability to be honest as important qualities of loving practice in helping others to thrive. Consideration of the theory in this section provides a foundation on which to review literature about ‘family learning’.

The chapter continues with an overview of historical and contemporary perspectives of family and learning; it provides understanding of how family constructs and ways of learning have changed. The family is identified as a key influence on individual lives where specific morals and values are gained. The section highlights that morals and values of families often sit in compliance and in contrast to that of other influential social institutions such as education and religion. The section also names specific qualities experienced within families and institutions for learning that can be either beneficial or detrimental in an ability to learn, thrive and flourish.

Consideration of influences for ‘family learning’ follows with an overview of International, UK and Scottish research or policy directives throughout the period of focus for this thesis. The section shows the history of why ‘family learning’ has developed as an approach across various countries and of what aim was to be gained. The section is presented in four parts. The first part considers the history and development of ‘family learning’ as an approach in education. The review of

literature identifies ‘Family Learning’ as an educational approach which consider families from both strengths-based and deficit-based perspectives. The section continues in providing an overview of the influences for development of the approach as presented within international and UK research studies. The section concludes with an overview of how ‘family learning’ is currently perceived in Scotland. The section notes ‘family learning’ as one method of early intervention and preventative approaches used in Scottish schools. The section highlights that the approach relies on strong partnership with families. However, partnership working between Scottish schools and families has again been a constant challenge. A key aspect raised from this chapter is that supporting families to gain successful outcomes in life has been a persistent challenge where neoliberal economic focus has promoted power and hierarchy for learning over genuine care and understanding within Scottish education that has resulted in consistent poor outcomes from many.

Chapter three provides the details underpinning the research design for this study. The chapter shows that the design of the research was set within theory influenced by the review of literature relating to the study. The chapter outlines the principles of Bourdieu’s theory of ‘habitus, capital and field’ as providing a theoretical framework to inform the research design. The chapter outlines my ontological, epistemological and socio-constructionist standpoint that knowledge is gained and shared amongst others and is constantly changing. This standpoint, earlier research, and the theoretical framework helped to inform the choice that a hermeneutic phenomenological approach was the best fit for this study. The approach gave the opportunity for participants to share their lived experience of family learning and of the aspects they considered most important whilst acknowledging that research provides an interpretation of the findings gained. Chapter three also outlines details of the research methods, ethical considerations, alongside consideration of research positionality.

Chapter four also acknowledges researcher positionality whilst outlining the methods used for reducing the impact of positionality in the process used for analysis of data gained from focus groups and one to one interviews. Chapter four presents the stages involved in analysis where groups of important aspects were continually refined to finally identify three key themes of difference, development and connection. The themes provided the frame for the following discussion chapter.

Chapter five includes three sections. Each section provides a discussion of each of the key themes that have arose from the findings. Section one discusses the theme of difference where participants presented different views of ‘family learning’ as happening in formal settings such as education and informal settings such as home. Differing views named different people, places and expectations involved in ‘family learning’.

The second section of chapter five presents discussion on the theme of development. Participants considered the most effective ‘family learning’, wherever it happened, aimed to develop all involved in a way that would enhance their life. However, participants found that influences from family and social institutions such as educational settings held differing expectations of what learning would be most beneficial. Development was also considered in terms of ‘family learning’ in the diverse ways of communicating and learning.

Finally, the third section provides discussion on the third theme of connection. Discussion of this theme presents participants views of ‘family learning’ as connections between people and organisations. Wider family connections were aspects relating to this theme alongside the specific qualities needed for most effective connections and therefore ‘family learning’ that provides successful outcomes.

Chapter six outlines the creation of ‘Learning Relations’ as an alternative model for practice and alternative title for ‘family learning’ whilst chapter seven presents the concluding chapter for the study providing summary of new knowledge gained in relation to the aims and objectives of the research. The chapter considers the impact of the contribution to knowledge in answering the question of, ‘What’s love got to do with ‘family learning’ and understanding of how families learn’. The chapter provides recommendations for future ‘family learning’ policy, practice, and research.

Glossary of terms used throughout the thesis.

I have used various terms throughout the thesis. The following details the context in which the terms have been used when relating to the topic for this research.

Terms	Context
Influence	Any person or organisation that can affect decisions, beliefs and behaviours of individuals and families. For example, for this thesis these were identified as governments, educational settings such as school, early learning and childcare settings, religion and communities.
Society	This term is used to consider the social world that we live within. It is used in consideration of the influences that the social world presents for the people that live within it whilst also recognising that the people influence the social world in which they live. The thesis specifically relates to the social conditions that Scottish people live within.
Socialisation	The way in which social institutions encourage specific behaviours or actions appropriate to societal norms and ideologies. Institutions in this thesis relate to families, educational settings, government, and religion.
Practitioner	This term is used to describe individuals working within Early Learning and Childcare (ELCC) services in supporting children and families living in Scotland.
Teacher	This term is used to describe individuals working within educational settings such as schools.
Education	Whilst agreement is made with Smith, Dewey and Freire in questioning how we perceive what 'education' is and of who decides, the term is used throughout this thesis to describe the general understanding of the planned curriculum for learning that informs approaches for teaching and learning within educational settings such as schools and ELCC.
Learning	This term is used in throughout this thesis to describe the knowledge that is believed to help us, as human beings, to be able to thrive and flourish in the social world that we live within.
Love	This term is used in this thesis in terms of the definition presented within 'Compassionate Love Theory', as the attitudes and actions related to giving of self for the good of the other... a self-giving caring love that values the other highly and has the intention of giving full life to the other. A degree of emotional engagement, as appropriate, emphasises the enhancement of human flourishing...[and] ... also promotes

	actions that lessen any delusions of superiority (Underwood 2009:4,7).
Services	Any organisation providing support for children and families
Service user	Any person who uses services to gain support for learning or other aspects in their life that is affecting their ability to thrive.
Stakeholder	Any person working within services to provide support for children and families or children and families who will receive help from the support provided by services

Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full title
CYPIC	Children and Young People Improvement Collaborative
DSES	The Daily Spiritual Experiences Scale.
ELCC	Early Learning and Childcare
EPPE	Effective Provision of Pre-School Education.
FAST	Families and Schools Together.
GIRFEC	Getting it Right For Every Child.
IYF	International Year of the Family
NAGCELL	National Advisory Group for Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning.
NIACE	National Institute for Adult and Continuing Education.
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development.
OFSTED	Office for Standards in Education.
OSC	Out of School Care
PEEP	Parents as Early Education Partners.
RAFA	Raising Attainment For All
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation.
WHO	World Health Organisation
WHOQOL	The World Health Organisation Quality of Life Group

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2 Literature Review

Introduction

The chapter is split into three distinct sections; section one considers the theory of Compassionate Love. Section two considers the concepts of family and learning with section three considering the concept of ‘family learning’.

The first section explores the theory of Compassionate Love as a foundation for human flourishing. The section begins with an overview of how and why Compassionate Love theory was developed. Review of literature highlights that the theory and model of “compassionate love captures aspects addressing human suffering and encourage[s] human flourishing” (Fehr et al 2009:9).

The section provides an overview of recommended qualities useful for considering ‘family learning’ practice. For example, there is consideration of the four key constructs of “free choice for the other”, “some degree of cognitive understanding”, “openness and receptivity” and “response of the heart” (Underwood, 2009: 8). Underwood defines the constructs, outlining that selfless actions exist for the best interests of another individual. Secondly, that cognitive understanding provides a deep understanding of self and of the other person. This understanding provides the knowledge of what is required to improve the life of the other and requires that individuals are respected rather than pitied. Thirdly, openness and receptivity are identified as key qualities for practice informed by compassionate love. Lastly, it is suggested that personal and affective behaviour should be a key driver for any compassionate love action. However, Underwood (2009:7) notes that actions driven within a compassionate love model may be constrained by “biological, social, environmental and

cultural factors” which may be useful in considering the feasibility or challenges faced in application of the theory for effective ‘family learning’.

The second section of the chapter is in two parts considering the concepts of family and learning. It begins by offering a brief history of definitions and expectations of family as a key contributor to the development of society. An exploration of changing perspectives and constructs of responsibility led to a more contemporary viewpoint of ‘families’ in recognition that opportunities for societal development rests as a collaborative effort and requires a shared approach from all involved in support of children and adults (hooks, 2000; Williams, 2004; Morgan, 2011, Elkjaer, 2018)). The section of the chapter continues in exploration of thinking around the concept of learning. The review of literature places a specific focus on how beliefs of learning are influenced and of how these influences affect individual ability to thrive in today’s world. Exploration includes theoretical perspectives of; Thorpe and Schmuller (1954), Packer and Goicoechea (2000), Schunk (2012) and Illeris (2018) in considering how learning is defined and of who or what influence learning. The section shows that aspects relating to the concept of learning are set amidst constant negotiation of personal, cultural, and societal expectations (Thorpe and Schmuller, 1954; Grant, 1989, Smart, 2011, Elkjaer, 2018, Jarvis, 2018). Specific focus is made on how learning is viewed in terms of development of people and of what we require to be able to thrive in life in comparison to the motivations of learning as a tool to enhance economic stability of Scotland, of how this affects the development of Scottish society, the people who live within it and fulfilment of social justice.

The third section of the chapter explores the development of ‘family learning’ across the world and the United Kingdom in promotion of lifelong learning and literacy. The section also outlines the claimed benefits for both the individual and nation where development of literacy and learning across the lifespan is

highlighted as providing opportunities for employment. Practical methods of enhancing lifelong learning and literacy are identified as; to improve the home learning environment (HLE), to raise aspirations of families and to improve parenting skills through ‘family learning’. A critical review of these claims and methods is made in the consideration of the perpetuation of poor outcomes for many families in many countries. In addition, consideration is made of the contradictory nature of the deficit view of individuals and their families presented in the need that it is the practice of families and not supporting services that needs to be addressed. This is an interesting viewpoint when recent research and government policy note the importance of considering ‘family learning’ as a ‘wealth model’ (NIACE, 2013, Nutbrown et al, 2015, Scottish Government, 2016b) values the contribution that families make in the learning process and thus development of society. The section considers which perspective influences contemporary ‘family learning’ practice most and of how beneficial this is for human flourishing.

Section three of the Literature review chapter continues in considering how influences for ‘family learning’ are understood in Scotland. The section explains that ‘family learning’ is considered as an early intervention approach within Scottish education with a view that ‘family learning’ and associated practice contributes to the aim of gaining social justice (Buffton,1999, Education Scotland, 2018, Haggart,2000, Harding and Ghezalayagh,2014, OFSTED, 2009, National Institute for Adult Continuing Education (NIACE) 2013, Scottish Government, 2016b). Yet, the section identifies a gap in knowledge around ‘family learning’ where little research has included the view of families. The ‘Review of Family Learning’ conducted by Scottish Government (2016b) also failed to include the views of all families living in Scotland to inform current ‘family learning’ practice providing scope for further exploration.

The gap in research on ‘family learning’ provides the impetus for further research to develop a broader view from the perspectives of families and individuals who work to support them, such as, teachers and practitioners working in Early Learning and Childcare (ELCC) services. The research study aims to understand what ‘family learning’ is, of where ‘family learning’ happens and what ‘family learning’ requires informing practice in a way that is driven from the requirements of families in the first instance rather than the needs of Scottish economic development.

2.1 Considering Compassionate Love Theory.

2.1.1 Development and Purpose of Compassionate Love Theory.

Compassionate love theory (Fehr et al. 2009) developed from a project started by The World Health Organisation (WHO). The WHO aimed to develop a tool that could provide a broad measure of quality of life (Saxena et al, 2002). Guidance was given that any measurement of quality of life should include consideration of “an individual’s perception of their position in life, in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns” (The World Health Organisation Quality of Life (WHOQOL) Group). Additionally, it was noted that quality of life for individuals could be affected by a variety of health, social and environmental factors (WHOQOL, 1993, 1995:153). Consequently, Underwood et al (2002) developed ‘The Daily Spiritual Experiences Scale’ (DSES) as a measurement tool that would fulfil the first aims of the WHO in measuring quality of life.

Developments of the DSES continued as a key interest of the WHO conference in 2006 (WHOQOI, SRPB Group 2006:8) which included participation from a variety of religious, non-religious, health and social scientific backgrounds.

Discussions established that quality of life included contributions from personal, spiritual, or religious beliefs. Developmental research conducted by Saxena et al (2002) found that each of these beliefs, when considered in relation to quality of life, held a unique feature of “loving kindness or love for others” (Fehr et al 2009:8). The DSES scale was further developed to create a theory that would encompass all the aspects that had been named in establishing quality of life.

The theory and model of “compassionate love” which “captures aspects addressing human suffering and encourage[s] human flourishing” (Fehr et al 2009:9) was influenced in promotion of quality of life and by Jean Vanier in stating.

To be pitied does not elevate us as human beings. But to be respected in the midst of the imperfections of being human, to be known for who we are and still valued, enables us to truly flourish (Vanier, 1998).

Underwood defines compassionate love theory as

the attitudes and actions related to giving of self for the good of the other... a self-giving caring love that values the other highly and has the intention of giving full life to the other. A degree of emotional engagement, as appropriate, emphasises the enhancement of human flourishing (2009:4).

Compassionate love theory also promotes actions that lessen any “delusions of superiority’ (Underwood, 2009 p7). Thoughts and actions relating to compassionate love include expressions and words. These thoughts and actions focus on kindness and an interest in improving conditions for others. Sprecher and Fehr (2005) note that whilst these actions may be innate characteristics of a person’s character, situations may mean that consistency of actions cannot be guaranteed.

2.1.2 Constructs and qualities of Compassionate Love theory.

Underwood explains that actions driven within a compassionate love model may be constrained by “biological, social, environmental and cultural factors” (2009:7) and are embedded and guided within four key core constructs.

Compassionate love should exist in the first instance as “free choice for the other” in which selfless actions exist for the best interests of another individual. Secondly, she highlights that there is “some degree of cognitive understanding”. Where the cognitive understanding provides a deep understanding of self and of the other person. This understanding provides the knowledge of what is needed to improve the life of the other and requires that individuals are respected rather than pitied. Thirdly, Underwood notes that “openness and receptivity” are key aspects of actions that impart compassionate love theory. Lastly, she highlights that “response of the heart” should be a key influence for any compassionate love action. Underwood uses the word heart in terms of “Coeur, meaning the core of ones being”. Actions are described as having “heartfelt affective” qualities which engage “emotional understanding and engagement” (2009: 8).

Compassionate love is described by participants, during research undertaken by Fehr and Sprecher, as “a kind of love”. A love identified as including “caring, trust, helping, understanding, honesty and support” (Fehr et al, 2009:31). A “self-giving, caring love that values the other highly and has the intention of giving full life to the other” (Fehr et al, 2009: xi). It may also be useful to consider the difficulties of affective practice in ‘professional’ roles highlighted by Page (2018). Learning the skill of having deep cognitive understanding of self and others relates to the development of ‘Professional love’ which provides an interesting model to aid training practitioners to be reflexive in practice as a means of gaining this depth of understanding (Page, 2018: 135). In addition, the work of Huyton (2009) is interesting here. Huyton highlights the ‘emotional labour’ created in caring for others so intensely and of what is required in

support of those caring. The research conducted by Jan Huyton (2009:2) provides an interesting context for considering the burden that a compassionate love approach may present. Huyton considered the concepts of ‘emotion work’ and ‘emotional labour’ in terms of the impact on university lecturers when supporting students. The concepts are interesting to consider in relation to an expectation of compassionate loving practice and the skills needed of those working in caring roles to address effects of ‘emotional labour’ that may transpire.

Mother Theresa reminds us that compassionate love begins in a place where “the future of humanity” emerges, the family (Fehr et al, 2009:27). It is a practice that mirrors the reasoning behind what ‘ideal’ families do.

Compassionate love practice also mirrors the “value” which individuals in families place on other family members. It reflects the way in which ‘ideal’ families are “giving life to the other” (Fehr et al, 2009:27). Meanwhile, compassionate love is described as a love which is set apart from other types of love, such as maternal or romantic love. It is defined as a “universal” love that can be “experienced in all types of relationships and settings” (Fehr et al, 2009: xi).

2.1.3 Compassionate Love theory and ‘Family Learning’

The development of compassionate love theory and model of working has encouraged research that is concerned with two notions of the original DSES created by Underwood. Research which concerns itself with compassionate love theory encourages questioning of ‘*what*’ motivates actions and ‘*why*’ particular actions are needed. Underwood also noted that practice of compassionate love is not straightforward as it is affected by culture, social contexts, and environment. Additionally, research shows that perceptions of what compassionate love is differs from person to person. Practice of compassionate love may be hindered

between strangers as opposed to being easier amongst individuals who know each other well. Research conducted by Oman (2010) has explored a wide variety of research and literature on motivations for compassionate love that consider application of compassionate love from a myriad of contexts. The research highlights the benefits that can be gained where compassionate love exists, however, Oman's study also notes the challenges affecting opportunities for compassionate love. For example, the study highlights challenges in fulfilling compassionate love towards others as affected by internal and external factors. He highlights that ability to be compassionate towards others is affected by the innate "behavioural system" (Oman, 2010:36) created from the levels of attachment we form in early years of life. For example, he explains

"people with secure social attachments should find it easier to perceive and respond to other people's suffering, compared with those who have insecure attachments"
(Osman, 2010:36)

It might also be important to consider the impact of neoliberalism highlighted by Moss and Mitchell (2023) in that selfless actions may be difficult in a neoliberalist society where individual needs, as opposed to the needs of others, are considered most important. In addition, it might be useful to note that in these circumstances, motivations for actions focus on the self in the first instance. Thus, conflicting expectations of promoting compassionate love within an individualistic world may present challenges for practice.

Finally, 'family learning' as an approach is described in Scottish practice guidance as a wealth model of practice (Scottish Government, 2016). A wealth model acknowledges existing strengths and builds upon skills and knowledge. A wealth model is relational to compassionate love in that it "ultimately centres on the good of another" (Underwood, 2009:3). However, Leggo (2004:29) notes

that school education is often driven by “a measure of excellence that renders many students mediocre”. Williams (2004:71,17) also notes that within the “networks of affection” which many families create, being non-judgemental is a crucial factor. The following section of the chapter explores the concepts of family and learning in exploration of factors that are important for both, consideration of the constructs and principles of compassionate love theory will be maintained throughout preceding review of literature.

2.2 Family and Learning.

This section on family and learning is in two parts. In part one, entitled 'Family', the roles and expectations of families are discussed, this is followed by consideration of how family is constructed and finally, part one ends by examining how judgement impacts the family in contemporary social contexts. In part two, entitled 'Learning', key theories on learning are introduced and this is followed by examination of definitions and the purpose of learning. Part two ends by discussing influences on learning, which offers ideas on how we learn best, and highlights barriers that get in the way of learning.

2.2.1 Definitions of Family

Ideologies of family have presented a range of influences and expectations of family as a contributor to wider society. Development of ideologies within society is complex. Berger and Kellner (1964) suggest that the industrial revolution promoted institutionalisation and encouraged ideologies such as the “nuclear family” as a distinct institution responsible for specific societal functions. Morgan (1975) adds that an ideology is a designated set of standard concepts which have in some way become widely disseminated and thus believed to be the norm to which any other form is measured.

Parson's functionalist perspective defined the family as a "nuclear unit which reflected a very simple social system" (Parsons, 1956: viii). The nuclear family is described as consisting of a mother, father and one or two children that promote "ideal" family values in the socialisation of family members (Parsons, 1956; hooks, 2000, Hall, 2016). Barrett and McIntosh (1982:106) defined socialisation as the "funnel" which conveyed stereotypical ideas from one generation to another. For example, they noted, "feminine and masculine subjectivities were ingrained in personalities" during this period of socialisation.

However, Berger and Kellner also highlighted the need presented by main public institutions for strict control of individual behaviour and criticised the promotion of ideals, such as the nuclear family and marriage, by suggesting it presented a "narrowing and stabilisation of identity" (Berger and Kellner, 1964:317). Development of identity and the influences that affect it, present an interesting aspect for this thesis. Biesta et al (2008) define identity as how we develop a sense of who we are and of what we can do. Research conducted by Carpentieri (2012) highlights that negative educational experiences have affected self-confidence, esteem, and self-efficacy of many adults. Findings highlighted by Carpentieri (2012) encourage further exploration of whether negative educational experiences still exist as barriers to learning and partnership with families. The findings from the 2012 study also encourage consideration of other negative experiences that affect opportunity for "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:4) and of how these relate to 'family learning'.

The review of literature posed further consideration of whether historical views of family as a key function in promoting acceptable societal behaviours was still an influencing factor within services that support families in Scotland. For example, staff working in supporting services such as, community education, schools or ELCC, may hold beliefs and judgements of family roles in terms of

normative expectations. Therefore, it is interesting to consider how, a sense of self or identity is affected by judgement of supporting agencies where families do not meet expectations that are imposed by others and not considered as key factors by families themselves.

Bell hooks (2000:129) argues that the promotion of family as a small distinct group is an element of capitalism and patriarchy. Bell hooks, argues that there are key dominating structures that look to segregate people into smaller more manageable groups making “abuses of power more possible”. In these dominating structures, fathers held complete rule over the family unit whilst mothers as opposed to fathers took care of the children and were completely dependent on the male. Devault (1999) supported the idea that pervasive gendered roles were promoted within families in explaining that care and feeding the family was often the responsibility of the mother. These points led consideration of whether family support services ‘manage and segregate’ specific families by highlighting requirement of support in terms of vulnerability or inadequacy. However, the main motivation for this action could be in securing a rationale for their service and role. If this is the case, these actions would sit in contradiction to ‘Compassionate Love theory’ where motivations for actions are not, in the first instance, for the good of families. This type of thinking may render power in a variety of contexts and more specifically on “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). The first of these concerns considers the effect on families where a support service or employee of that service is making a service user feel inadequate as contradictory in terms of the existence of the service in the first instance. Secondly, it would be concerning if services or their employees create circumstances to ensure security for themselves through creating a belief of need in others as this practice would be conducive to a deficit-based approach (Levitas, 2005) Thirdly, whilst Devault (1999) highlights the promotion of gendered roles, the

point encourages consideration of general promotion of hierarchy where services enthuse an importance of themselves or their service over the children or families who use that service (Hartas, 2014).

2.2.2 Family constructs and qualities.

Key shifts in sociological thinking about the family occurred during the 1940's which were identified as having a major influence in societal perceptions of family and of what purpose the family served (May and Dawson, 2018). Burgess and Locke (1945) suggest that the view of family had begun a transformation from being an "institution to a companionship" where issues of the social world, such as, behaviour of children, were often considered a consequence of poor family practice. Burgess and Locke highlighted that families were drawing on the strengths of close relationships amongst blood related family members and friends to challenge criticisms that inability for "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:4) were not only resulting from what families do. Families were now questioning the actions of other institutions, such as education, in affecting an ability to thrive (Burgess and Locke, 1945:274).

Chambers (2012) supports that family life has continually changed since 1940 presenting quite different family constructs and practice today. Chambers (2012) refers to the variety of relational and home lives that exist amongst society today. See Table 1 below as an example of how Scottish family life has changed over the past decade. The table shows that between the period of 1960 and today; marriage between opposite sex couples has decreased by 38%. However, we can see the steady increase of marriage between same sex couples initiated by The Marriage and Civil Partnership (Scotland) Act (2014). An additional change for families during the period of focus has been the changes

in birth rates across age ranges of mothers, married couples, and unmarried couples which may also be linked to rising employment rates of women.

Table 1: Changing Scottish family constructions 1960-2020.

Year		1960	1970	1980	1990	2000	2010	2014	2015	2016	2017	2020
Married opposite sex couples		40,103	43,203	38,501	34,672	30,367	28,480	No data	No data	No data	No data	25,095
Marriage same sex couples.		No data	No data	No data	No data	No data	No data	367	1671	998	982	423
Births of children by age of mother.	Age 0-19	No data	No data	No data	5523	4599	3755	2446	2126	1974	1838	1281
	Age 40+				717	1162	2178	2223	2099	2193	2065	2068
Births to married women aged 20-24		1961-1971 =59631		1981-1991 =30,259		1991-2001=10296	2011-20=2401					
Births to unmarried women aged 20-24		1961-71 4007		1981-1991 10783		1991-2000=13792	2011-20=14533					
Births to unmarried women aged 40-44		1961-71= 277		1981-1991= 163		1991-2000 = 453	2011-20=1638					
Women in employment Ages 16-74 (part time, full time or students)		1,024,468	1,164,021	1,400,379	1,529,695	1,578,608	1309029					1,999,2000

(National Records of Scotland, 2022)

In addition, research conducted by Glasgow university demonstrates continuing diversity across Scottish families. Smith (2024: np) notes that “Scotland’s growing diversity is ... producing a ‘mosaic of differently mixed areas’”. As a result of the changing constructs of family, Williams (2004) suggests the use of

the word “families” as a description where family now includes a wide range of individuals providing support for one another. A particularly recurring message throughout twenty first century sociological studies support the idea of family as companionship where it is also noted that friendships play an important part in families (Pahl and Spencer, 2004, Smart, 2007, Cronin, 2015). Families now recognise friends as members due to the changing patterns to married life and couple cohabitation (Jamieson et al, 2006). Pahl and Spencer (2004:202) highlight choice and relationships as a key aspect of family today in which friends are “given or chosen” and who may be either kin or non-kin, with commitment remaining an important element of these friendships in gaining appropriate support to enhance “human flourishing” (Hooks, 2000, Smart, 2007, Underwood, 2009:4)

Whilst families today accept a wide community of members, Morgan (1975:331) concurs that families create their own “free area” in which individuals express themselves emotionally. Williams (2004) names important qualities for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) in families as gained through, “reciprocity, mutual respect, informality and being non-judgemental” (Williams, 2004:71) as important amongst “networks of affection” that families create (Williams, 2004:17). Furthermore, Fivush (2008) adds that family memories provide a crucial contribution of family for the development of self-identity. Whilst Evans and Thomas (2009) as well as Millar and Ridge (2013) add that development of identity is gained through family values and morals being shared through history of an intergenerational community of family members. These points echo the claim posed by Biesta (2008) that family narratives play a key role in how we develop identity. Cronin (2015) also highlights that characteristics of “trust, emotion, children and belonging exist as key elements of family communities” (Cronin, 2015:1170).

Meanwhile, contemporary feminist views offer additional insight into the reality of family lives. The 1990's saw a questioning of influential ideologies and the morality of promoting patriarchy within family units and wider society (Hall, 2016). Finch and Mason (1993) note that negotiation is a constant practice amongst families due to differing morals and values. Whilst Alexander and Clyne (1995) add that expectations set by influential powers and conflicting values amongst several factors, mean that home is often a site of violence and abuse for some (Alexander and Clyne, 1995). hooks adds that the nuclear family was often dysfunctional and therefore far from "ideal" (hooks, 2000:129) while Hall (2016) asserts that children and adults learn how to "do family" in the home, however, noting that learning how to "do family" is not always positive in terms of gaining the ability to thrive. Conflict may develop because of individual moral and values sitting in contrast to that of "moralising powers, such as school educators, peers or friends" (Hall 2016:1024). In respect that family does not always provide the 'ideal' conditions in which its members can flourish it may be important to consider how and where individuals can find support out with the family home, highlighting again the need for community families (hooks, 2000, Cronin, 2015).

More recent studies of family identify the complexity of family life in arguing that consideration of family must include the non-human and non-relational elements of families, such as "anything that participates in the action of family life can be considered a member of the "family assemblage" (Price-Robertson and Duff, 2018:1). This concept argues that most studies of family life separate human and nonhuman elements as separate and distinct. For example, this includes family members and what they do as separate entities to the world around the family and the influence it has. In this respect Price-Robertson and Duff argue that when considering families, we must consider that family members exist in collaboration with the "objects, habits, spaces, technologies,

discourses and affects” that inhabit daily life (Price-Robertson and Duff, 2018:15). When considering families in this way, the socio-constructionist positioning of this thesis can be related to the idea of ‘family assemblage’ where it is acknowledged that family life is influenced by the world in which it exists whilst development of family acts as an influence on that world. For example, Price-Robertson and Duff (2018) recall the point made by Longhurst (2016) that family life today relies on social media and digital devices for modern family communication and to gain support. As such, consideration is made of how developments in digital technology and social media have influenced families and of how families have influenced dissemination of different ideologies. In respect of the complexity of the varied family characteristics outlined here, Morgan (2011:23) supports the notion presented by Williams (2004) and earlier by hooks (2000), that family cannot be considered as a single unit, but the plurality of members can be acknowledged in use of the term “families” and “family communities” by adding the term “family practices” to encompass wider contexts for actions that are deemed familial.

2.2.3 The impact of judgement on families.

Historic key elements of family ‘ideals’, such as marriage, declined during the 1960’s and 70’s and resulted in a major shift in family constructions and practices. Examples of this can be seen in wider acceptance of same sex partnerships, women taking up paid employment, children being born to unmarried mothers, and respect for the privacy of families than expectation of community participation (Anderson, 1980). Legislation and policy during this period show some degree of acceptance of these changes. However, whilst there appears some acceptance of the changes in family practice and constructs, it may be interesting to consider whether historical judgement and expectations still exist amongst society today and if these affect families positively in gaining

ability to thrive or negatively in creating barriers. For example, Anderson (1980) and Chambers (2012) note that family changes are considered by some as a “demise of morals” when measured against the ideals such as that of the nuclear family (Parson, 1956). Wainwright and Marandet (2017) add that increased fluidity and change in families has spurred debate on whether families lack appropriate features and behaviours today.

Berger and Kellner (1964) highlight that the resulting outcome of perpetuating judgement, is families retracting to a “private sphere”. The private sphere Berger and Kellner, elaborate is an “area of individual choice and even autonomy. A fact which they argued has important consequences for the shaping of identity in modern society” (Berger and Kellner, 1964:306). Cooper adds that the family environment provides sanctity in which an individual “can feel at home most of the time” (Cooper, 1971:304). Meanwhile, Cooper adds that the resulting outcome of perpetuating judgement is not only that families create and protect their own private spheres of unique family life but that they teach their children ways in which to “succumb” to the expectations of wider society (Cooper, 1971:290). Goldsack (1999) elaborates further in explaining that families often create “shields to public scrutiny” (Goldsack, 1999:121). In considering these points, the instinctive nature of families to protect and guide family members in ways that will aid an ability to flourish within the world that they live is noted. In addition, this thesis considers the effect that judgement and learning to “succumb” has on opportunities for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4).

In response to normative expectations, Smart (2011) also argues that families develop ways in which to portray images of a lifestyle that are not always an exact representation of how family life is really being lived adding that everyday practice of families also includes secrets. She notes that acknowledgement of family secrets as an integral part of families provides

significant “understanding of the complex relationships between power, the personal, the cultural and the social” (Smart, 2011:539). hooks (2000) adds that family secrets can create barriers to developing trusting family communities which she argues is key for the development of children and families in gaining what they require to thrive and flourish. These points are interesting when considering reasons why partnership with families has been challenging in Scottish schools. If families, feel that they or their actions are being judged by others based on historical normative ‘ideals’, families may present a false representation of family life or avoid any interaction. If this is the case, then ‘family learning’ approaches within Scottish education may struggle to develop trusting, honest relationships or, communities of families that include support services, and ultimately opportunities to support families in their ability to thrive.

More recently, Giddens and Sutton (2017) add that ideas of family as an institution supposes an organisation which exists for a religious, educational, professional, or social purpose which suggests that the family has a role in some, if not all, of these areas. This builds on Freire’s point (1972:123) demonstrating the importance of cultural and social contexts that influence families in explaining that “the parent – child relationship in the home usually reflects the objective cultural conditions of the surrounding social structure”. Thus, any expectations on families fulfilling societal roles, and family life are shaped and affected by the political, religious, and educational values of the day. These values frame judgement of how well families contribute to the aims of political, religious, and educational expectations.

The aspects raised here provide consideration of an ongoing cycle of effect where societal expectations of children and families create judgements when normative expectations are not met. In turn, these expectations may lead to judgements that lack consideration of how wider society and influential

institutions have contributed to creating barriers for families to learn and achieve expectations. The reality of family life, awareness of judgement, resulting secrecy and false representation of family life that ensures the fulfilment of each member of society and their ability to thrive, presents further consideration for services that aim to support families and children.

2.2.4 Summary

This section shows some of the important aspects of everyday life for families of the twenty first century. Issues of power are a recurring focus for sociological study of this time. Power, as an aspect of families and society ran as a thread throughout the period of focus.

Socialisation of children was highlighted as a key role for the family within Parson's (1956) functionalist perspective with Barrett and McIntosh (1982:106) describing socialisation as the "funnel" which conveys stereotypical ideas from one generation to another. Morgan (1975) demonstrates the power which families hold in promoting notions of rank and hierarchy in suggesting family as site where perpetuation of power exists and operates.

Sociological aspects of the family present power in both positive and negative ways. The difference of power is interesting for this thesis in considering the qualities that are beneficial alongside those that create barriers in contribution to the "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:4). For example, the importance of relationships and family memories, argued by Fivush (2008) as powerful in contributing to the development of self-identity. In addition, Morgan (1975, 2011) notes that families demonstrate power of choice when family practice, whilst not trouble free, retains key affective characteristics that include "notions of duty, reciprocity, and closeness". Furthermore, Smart (2011:539) emphasises the power of family secrets and their relationship with "the personal, social,

cultural and power” itself. The points made by Morgan and Smart, again, highlight that there may be influences on development of identity that have the power to enhance our ability to thrive or not.

However, the power of influence cannot be confined to families alone. Berger and Kellner (1964) show the power which employment and institutional expectations have in their ability to invade the “private sphere” of family (Berger and Kellner, 1964). Perry-Jenkins and Wadsworth (2017) consider how working aspects of family life are markedly different to that of how family life is perceived. Noted within their study is the changing power relations between men and women in families over the last century and more, in relation to the increase of females in families gaining employment. Furthermore, they note that work and family often result in trade- offs which are implemented within various stages of family life and are often affected by cultural factors (Perry-Jenkins and Wadsworth, 2017:226).

Whilst public institutions can be identified as being powerful influences in family life (Hall, 2016), it is noted that judgements from others have not always had the power to restrict changes in the way in which families want to live. Meanwhile, Cooper adds that the major changes in families of the twentieth century alongside the power of societal judgement in shaping family practice has resulted in children learning how to “succumb” to expectations of family and wider society. He highlights that conforming to societal expectations fulfils a human requirement of “continual validation of individual identity and place through significant others” (Cooper, 1971:290). It is interesting to consider families as communities (hooks, 2000, Williams, 2004, Morgan, 2011) and of who significant others may be in our lives, of how or what actions affect validation of individual identity and of how this validation impacts on future opportunities or “human flourishing” (Underwood 2009:4). The following section will consider the role of learning as a key element of family and societal

expectation and a way in which validation of identity and place as, the means in which to flourish, may be gained or lost.

2.2.5 Learning

The second part of section one examines learning theory to better understand how children and families are influenced and influential in terms of gaining knowledge that provides ability for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). The part considers how beliefs of learning develop or affect confidence in understanding the contribution we make to wider society. This part will examine learning to enhance human life whilst also exploring differing beliefs and influences on what, where and how we learn best to help establish a concept of ‘family learning’ that is most useful for us to thrive. Consideration will be made of developments in learning theories that have occurred and of how these theories have been influential for the development of individuals living in Scotland. As with the development of families, theories of learning have been influenced by societal focus and values and have presented a range of ongoing changes in approaches to support learning (Illeris, 2018).

Learning theories aim to show essential aspects of the processes of learning (Thorpe and Schmuller, 1954) and have evolved from a variety of epistemological viewpoints of how knowledge is gained. For example, Piaget (1964) and Bruner (1996) both consider learning from a cognitivist stance where brain function is highlighted in creating and maintaining knowledge. Skinner (1953) and Thorndike (Walberg, 1992) approached learning from a behaviourist position where individual learning could be motivated and manipulated through reward and punishment.

Bandura (1971), Vygotsky (Kozulin et al, 2003), Wenger (Blackmore, 2010), Lave and Heron (Illeris, 2018) and Elkjaer (2018) all consider learning from a

social perspective in that they recognise the internal and external factors which affect individual learning. Hall (2016:1024) notes that learning is an aspect of our lives gained through “interconnectedness with others”. Social learning theories gained focus during the 1960s and have maintained a constant influence in understanding how individuals learn and develop best (Illeris, 2018) In terms of this point, we can assert that opportunities for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) are gained through interaction with the social world. However, Illeris (2018) highlights that many theories of learning do not consider all the complexities of learning, such as, the circumstances that affect learning and the effect that subsequent learning has in altering future circumstances. Illeris (2018) calls for consideration of learning that includes wide ranging external and internal aspects that continually change and affect learning. In response to the call made by Illeris (2018) the following section will explore the external and internal aspects that affect learning and our ability for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). The first section will consider definitions of learning with a focus on the innate requirement as humans that we must learn and of who or what influences learning opportunities appropriate to what we need to flourish. The second section continues in exploring influences on where and how we learn best.

2.2.6 Definitions of Learning.

Thorpe and Schmuller (1954) highlight that producing one singular definition of learning is problematic as it depends on the epistemological viewpoint in which learning is considered. In other words, defining learning depends on how we suppose that knowledge of a particular topic is assumed, of how we determine knowledge gained as a “truth” or if there can ever be a definitive “truth” about anything (Packer and Goicoechea, 2000: 227). Schunk (2012:3) states that, “learning is an enduring change in behaviour or in the capacity to behave in a given fashion, which results from practice or other forms of experience”.

For example, approaching a definition of learning within a structuralist as opposed to a functionalist standpoint will present varying perspectives of what learning is or of how learning is confirmed. Definitions of learning that sit within a structuralist viewpoint, for example to that of Piaget (1972), note the cognitive process of learning and that “learning begins in the body and takes place through the brain” (Illeris, 2018:13). Learning considered from a cognitive perspective, views learning as a process in which the brain breaks information down into separate structures and combines or relates these structures to form new understandings or learning (Schunk, 2012). Observable changes in behaviour evidence the individual’s response to a stimulus and, as a result, cognitive function.

Whereas, considering learning from a functionalist epistemology offers a pragmatic view of learning. Consideration is made of the purpose of learning to survive or “flourish” (Underwood, 2009:4) within the world in which we live. A functionalist perspective considers the environment alongside mental processes highlighting that the mind and body function as one unit and not separately. Schunk (2012:10) cites the theory of John Dewey (1867-1949) in summing up the combined effect of external and internal factors, that we learn because of life experiences whilst life experiences exist because of learning. His view of learning shows that learning holds a purpose, not just for the individual, but also for the world in which the individual lives. He considered learning as a natural perpetual cycle of human life. Therefore, Dewey insisted that consideration of learning should be made within the complex life cycle in which it is situated as life cycles include and create internal and external experiences. In relation to the focus of this thesis of what learning provides “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) we must consider what characteristics of experience are most beneficial or detrimental.

Illeris (2018) argues that individual characteristics, emotions, culture, and political influences, to name a few, interplay in learning experiences. Thorpe and Schmuller (1954) support this view and add that definitions of learning “must also include all the conditions that influence and are influenced by this process” (Thorpe and Schmuller, 1954:27). Elkjaer (2018) cites Lave and Wenger (1991) in defining learning as participation within communities of people where learning is gained for either a specific purpose or as a general consequence of social interaction. Considering learning as an outcome of community participation, for example experiences gained; in families, communities, educational settings, youth clubs, church or via social media provides an interesting viewpoint when combined with the collective idea of families and therefore a concept of how families learn and of therefore what ‘family learning’ may be. Overall, learning is ascertained in different ways depending on the context in which we are considering learning from. Considering learning from a cognitive perspective defines the process in terms of changes made in the brain while consideration of learning from a functionalist perspective maintains focus on the purpose of learning. It is the differing perspectives on the purpose of learning that will be considered in more detail in this thesis as influences on learning provide opportunities for “human flourishing” for all (Underwood, 2009:4).

2.2.7 Purpose of learning

Learning is an innate characteristic. Donaldson notes, “how strong a need we have to communicate achievement to our fellow man and see it confirmed in their eyes” (Donaldson, 1987:116). Humans innately wish to, not only, understand the world in which they exist but also to be of use within it. They wish to become, capable, autonomous, and competent. Babies begin their

learning journey to understand their surroundings. Developing ability is the biological need in which babies are motivated to master an understanding of surroundings to survive (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010, Zeedyk, 2022). Donaldson (1987) elaborates that learning is intrinsic to assert control, with children having an instinctive need to learn and control their world for themselves. These arguments suggest that humans instinctively aim to gain learning that allow them to understand and gain control in the world they inhabit as a means for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). Developments in the understandings of learning add that a “strong case could be made... for the view that learning is but one means for stimulating the human personality to its fullest expression” (Thorpe & Schmuller, 1954:9), suggesting individual requirements to flourish. Donaldson also notes a collective purpose and responsibility for learning when she argued that children have unwittingly acquired the responsibility of continuing the human legacy of contribution to our developing society. Donaldson asserts that being responsible for this task is something that children are unaware of and require guidance (Donaldson, 1987). Illeris (2018) supports the idea of learning as individual and for a collective purpose in the need for development of a balanced mind whilst adding that learning allows compassion for others. This point is interesting in terms of this thesis, where consideration is made of whether it is a specific type of learning that allows compassion for others in providing “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) and if there are motivations for learning that impede this aim. In exploration of the application of compassionate love theory. As noted previously Oman (2010) highlighted that attachment in early years of life can affect the innate ability to be compassionate toward others (Oman, 2010:36).

2.2.8 Influences on where and how we learn best.

Thorpe and Schmuller (1954) highlight the importance of context in which a definition of learning is set. Thorpe and Schmuller (1954:7) state that learning takes place in a variety of places and at various times, “present or past”. They also suggest that learning differs in being “one kind or another...throughout the span of life”. In various contexts, the notion of “experience” for learning has also resulted in a variety of interpretations (Illeris, 2018). Kolb (1984) regarded experience as the basis for learning in which individuals transform experience, and thus create a process of learning (Kolb, 1984:38). Jarvis (1987) also shares the view that individuals learn through the transformation of experience. Jarvis developed a hypothesis that learning exists throughout an individual’s lifetime through a combination of processes of the body and mind which are transformed either “cognitively, emotively or practically” resulting in evidence of learning in a “more experienced person” (Illeris, 2018:27).

Illeris (2018) furthers the view of experience for learning in citing the assertion made by John Dewey that whilst learning is related to everything that is included in human existence, such as individualistic qualities, thought, emotions and societal impacts, it is not always driven by a direct intent to learn. Dewey’s experience for learning suggests that individuals learn during everyday experiences. Illeris has provided a perfect example of what this means by explaining that “there is a difference between enjoying a picture for its aesthetic value than studying a painting as an art reviewer” (Illeris, 2018:83). Learning in this context becomes something that fulfils an individual by providing enjoyment as well as knowledge without an expectation enforced by others. This relates to experiences for learning that aid “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) and raises debate of what constitutes acceptable

experience for the most effective learning, who decides and how do different perspectives on learning affect the ability to flourish (Illeris, 2018).

The many facets of learning need consideration and the learning that is most meaningful in serving a purpose for “stimulating the human personality to its fullest expression” (Thorpe & Schmuller, 1954:9). However, expectations of what fullest expression of personality is, or in other words, what learning is valued for human flourishing may differ amongst individuals and those influencing and guiding learning, such as governments, schools, or families, presenting conflict of purpose. As such, Jarvis (2018) encourages acknowledgement that learning is experientially situated and as human beings with individual personalities, ideas and perceptions. Like family, learning exists in constant negotiation with the personal, culture and the social (Smart, 2011:539). Grant (1989) adds that thought and language should be key in negotiations amongst influencing factors for learning where various values of learning are considered.

Whilst a view of learning as a collaborative act supports the social element of Dewey’s theoretical position, Elkjaer (2018) encourages additional consideration of the emotional aspects of learning where “concepts, thinking, commitment and passion” (Elkjaer, 2018:80) are important characteristics for the learning process promoting reflection of what is required for learning to take place. Illeris (2018:12) supports this viewpoint in adding that for learning to take place there is a requirement of “feelings, emotions, motivations and volition”. Schmidt (2012:21) bolsters the argument that the learning process requires consideration of emotive elements when noting that, whilst a behaviourist viewpoint refutes the need to regard internal aspects such as “thoughts or feelings” in the process of learning he highlights that these theorists must have used thought and feelings to develop their learning theory. In terms of what is required for “human flourishing”, the need that learning

processes require consideration of the “feelings, emotions, passion, motivations and commitment” of individuals and families can then be contemplated (Elkjaer, 2018; Illeris, 2018).

2.2.9 Who or what influences learning.

Learning is affected by psychological, biological and social conditions (Illeris, 2018:27). Shonkoff and Fisher (2013:1635) relate to the biological and social aspect when noting that genetics form part of the foundations for the construction of the brain and of future learning abilities. They suggest that situational experiences combined with genetics provide platforms for learning (2013:1635). However, Illeris (2018) cites Gardiner’s argument (1983, 1993, 1999) that considering learning abilities from a perspective of genetics may cause barriers for learning opportunities where a lack of ability is assumed by the teacher and embedded within the individual. If this point is valid in today’s social world it presents a critical point for this thesis if opportunities for learning to aid “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) are diminished where perceptions of limited ability exist, or are promoted and understood by individuals or families. If the purpose of learning is to achieve the “fullest expression of human personality” (Thorpe & Schmuller, 1954:9), a “balanced mind” (Illeris, 2018) in contribution to developing society (Donaldson, 1987) then it is useful to consider, who or what influences learning. It may be useful to question who or what sets an appropriate measure for these or indeed of what learning is appropriate. The following section presents various influences and differing contexts of what these measures are and of what characteristics are required.

Pike (2007) highlights that contradictory morals and values are experienced through a variety of sources and environments, such as, different morals and

values presented between families and school. This argument echoes the claim made by Jarvis (2018) that individual learning exists in constant negotiation with the demands, expectations and opportunities provided by others. For example, structuralism considered that human thoughts and ideas exist as single units but create associations between each unit. As such, structuralism deemed that further understanding of the human mind is gained by examining and testing the mind and body as a separate component. This type of thinking provided inspiration for psychologist Thorndike (Walberg, 1992) to argue that education should be based on behaviourist theories of learning where behaviours altered by the environment demonstrated knowing and understanding. For example, Skinner's (1953) behaviourist theory suggests that as humans we respond to experience. Behaviourist thinking which dominated the first half of the twentieth century, encouraged manipulation of 'appropriate' responses through praise and reinforcement or punishment to encourage or diminish specific behaviours and learning. However, a behaviourist view relates to "nurture" in how we encourage desired behaviour but negates "nature" where instinctive human intuition is not considered as an integral element of the learning process. Considering that all behaviours are learned disregards "nature" or innate human abilities, thoughts, feelings, and beliefs in the learning process and therefore lacks consideration of the effect that behaviourist thinking may have on individual development or opportunity for "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:4). In relation to who or what influences learning, this section has demonstrated learning is influenced by innate and external factors. A critical point highlighted here in relation to this thesis is that abilities for learning cannot be considered based on genetics or in other words in terms of "nature" in the context of who one's parents are or of where one lives. Learning should be considered in terms of "nurturing" opportunities that present learning for every child, adult, and family. In essence, the section contributes to 'family learning' as "nature" and "nurture" working hand in hand (Sameroff, 2010).

2.2.10 Barriers to learning.

Donaldson (1987) provided explanation that learning can be affected by individual experiences which negate predictions and result in disappointment. Donaldson (1987:112) highlights that disappointment has different effects on individual learning. Response to the experience may propel individual inquiry as to why the result was different to prediction, whilst, to another the experience could result in the complete avoidance of the situation. Additionally, Donaldson (1987) suggests that learners should always be encouraged to view every opportunity in a positive manner and as a learning experience. She advises that where results have not been as expected, it is important for further learning to incite individuals to investigate why results are different. Being able to cope with challenging situations is often valued as a positive skill within much of society and specifically within formal learning such as school. However, Illeris (2018:19) highlights that support for individuals who are finding learning difficult is often limited yet appropriate support can provide transformative learning experiences where individuals develop a range of useful meaningful skills such as “independence, creativity, responsibility and flexibility” as skills pertinent to achieve “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4)

Illeris, also highlights that some motivations, influence, and experiences present barriers to learning. For example, the modern superfast digital world alongside societal demands, such as, neoliberal materialistic values. He argues that these drive attitudes for employment and learning for external gain to aid development of society and the economy (Scottish Government, 2016a; OECD, 2018) “encroach on life situations and possibilities” and can create “ambivalence to learning” (Illeris, 2018:18). An interesting point noted by Donaldson (1987), relates to the argument that Illeris is making in that learning encouraged for the acquisition of material gain alone can only provide two outcomes. The first will be for those who acquire the “prize” will be “winners”

and secondly, those who do not, are the “losers”. The latter outcome presents learners who lack any intrinsic appreciation for the experience or of how it has contributed to their knowledge. Regarded, as a “loser” could be a punishment that spans a lifetime. Shonkoff and Fisher, add that lifetime effects on learning are also gained in hostile experiences noting that these can have a negative impact on ability to learn (Shonkoff & Fisher, 2013). Carpentieri (2012) highlight the impact that negative experiences have on self-esteem and belief of ability to learn calling for time and patience as crucial elements to build confidence for learning. Meanwhile, Hargreaves et al (2013:4) also add that fear is a particular experience which impacts on cognitive development, whilst a lack of love and unpredictable relationships with key individuals having negative effects on individuals fulfilling their potential.

These points are interesting to consider in terms of the aims and objectives for learning as set within educational establishments driven by political ideologies, of what is valued as ‘successful’ learning. It is interesting to consider the effect that these may have; on perceptions held about learning that is valued amongst wider society, of the expectations and the ensuing actions of those supporting learners due to the pressure of expectation and on the impact on “human flourishing (Underwood, 2009:4).

2.2.11 What aids learning?

The United Nations Right of the Child state that children have a right to development of self, aided within a family environment which promotes “happiness, love and understanding” (UNICEF, 1990:3). Deacon (2011:13) adds that learning and development in early childhood experiences should include “time, effort, attention and love” (Deacon, 2011:14). Zeedyk (2022:22) highlights that love is often referred to as attachment to main caregivers with Winston and Chicot (2016:12) noting the benefits of a secure attachment with

key caregivers as a requirement for development of “social skills, emotional skills and learning itself”. In consideration that love in families is identified as an important aspect for development in early childhood (UNICEF, 1990, Zeedyk, 2022; Deacon, 2012) and support for learning and development is lifelong (Hartas, 2014), the thesis raises questioning of whether love should be regarded as an important characteristic for learning at all ages to ensure “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). Yet, Page (2011, 2018), Morris (2021) and Malcolm (2022) highlight a difficulty in use of the term ‘love’ in relation to formal learning environments such as school or ELCC. Morris (2021:127) conducted research on the difficulties that practitioners working in ELCC in England found in balancing professional expectations, fear of accusation of child abuse with children’s need for ‘affection’ and identified settings creating ‘no touch’ policies and practitioners practicing “subversive tactics” as the only option. The importance of specific qualities for learning that aid human flourishing and contribution to developing society (Donaldson, 1987) presents an extension to the argument posed by Dewey (Schunk, 2012) that the most effective learning for development of individuals and society should be set amidst loving experiences.

It is interesting to consider whether supporting agencies or families that use them consider the idea of family as something that exists out with the agency or if agencies consider themselves as part of the family community. Agencies that support families in Scotland are regarded as ‘professional services’ with expectations that ‘professionals’ who provide the service are expected to maintain formal roles governed by rules and boundaries (SSSC, 2015; SSSC, 2016; Wingrave and McMahon, 2016; GTC, 2021). In consideration of ‘professional’ expectations, this thesis questions whether it is possible that services be considered as community families and if so that they could present the affective qualities of “networks of affection” outlined by Williams

(2004:71). In terms of fulfilling the requirements of all families living in Scotland today in a way that is meaningful for them, it may be useful to question whether there is a real need for addressing the formality of professional services and the perpetuation of power that this presents.

An interesting point is also made by Fejes & Nicoll (2008: xii) in that our need to create “totality and truth” about such complex ever-changing aspects such as learning has created weak “discourses” that are narrow in scope. This suggestion indicates that it may be unhelpful to limit ideas around what learning is and of where it happens, or as Fejes & Nicoll put it, as “one kind or another”. Therefore, for everyone, family and wider society, meaningful learning may; mean quite different things, require specific approaches to support, fulfil distinct aspects, and continually change throughout the span of experience in their lives.

2.2.12 Summary

Thorpe and Schmuller (1954) claim that a definitive definition of learning cannot be made. Defining learning is difficult due to the complex nature of the process, how we gain new knowledge and skills, who takes part in the process, how the learning process is influenced by external and internal factors (Schunk, 2012, Illeris, 2018). Learning is affected and influenced by various sides highlighting a need to consider both nature and nurture as companions in the learning process rather than as aspects that operate independently of the other (Sameroff, 2010). To achieve learning, key elements are shown, these are described as secure relationships, understanding, attention, time and love (UNICEF, 1990, Deacon, 2011, Winston and Chicot, 2016, Page, 2011, 2018, Morris, 2021, Malcolm, 2022, Zeedyk, 2022). Added consideration should be given of both the role that nurture, and nature play in the process (Sameroff, 2010, Winston & Chicot, 2016).

Learning for individuals living in today's world is gained and influenced by a variety of places and people, such as, families, communities, educational settings, youth clubs, church, social media. Experiences and environments for learning described in literature as "communities" (hooks, 2000 Williams, 2004, Morgan, 2011, Elkjaer, 2018). However, each community promote specific morals, values, and expectations of which the individual finds themselves in constant negotiation. Innate abilities, beliefs and interests are highlighted in the learning process contributing to negotiation or conflict.

Learning fulfils both individual and a collective requirements. Skills gained may be social, physical, emotional, psychological, and allow the individual to gain control, understand their place in the world and of how they contribute (Deacon, 2011, Illeris, 2018). The following section considers how politics and research have been influential in how individuals and families begin to understand their place in the world. Specific consideration is given to whether the influence for action is beneficial or detrimental in an ability to thrive.

2.3 Family Learning

Introduction

In consideration of “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) as a key focus for this thesis, the review of literature and research related to ‘family learning’ must begin with questioning motivations for action (Fehr et al 2009). As such, this section of the literature review continues in considering the motivations for ‘family learning’ presented within research from across the globe. The section shows the history of why ‘family learning’ was developed as an approach and of what aims it would fulfil. As this study is positioned within a socio-constructionist viewpoint (Burr, 1995, Elder-Vass, 2012) it asserts that relationships between society and those who live within it interact on a continuous basis. A key focus is made in the notion that society affects the lives of those who live within it whilst the interactions of people affect the development of society. As such, consideration is made of how development of ‘family learning’ as an approach relates to this point and ultimately how well it achieves human flourishing.

The section highlights the influence of international research for the promotion of ‘family learning’ within the United Kingdom and Scotland. Information is presented in four parts considering in the first instance the history and development of ‘family learning’. The section continues in presenting the findings of research studies that provide an overview of international viewpoints as influential in the promotion of ‘family learning’ within the United Kingdom.

The section concludes with explanation of how earlier international and UK research has influenced how ‘family learning’ is perceived in Scotland and of the political influence that drives promotion of ‘family learning’. This concluding section notes ‘family learning’ as one method of early intervention

and preventative approaches used in educational settings in Scotland. The section highlights that the approach relies on strong partnership with families. However, it shows that partnership working between Scottish schools and families has been a constant challenge. An added key aspect raised from review of literature in this context is that supporting families to gain successful outcomes in life has been an additional persistent challenge. The review of literature asserts that a neoliberal economic focus has promoted power and hierarchy for learning over genuine care and understanding within Scottish education that has resulted in consistent poor outcomes for many. Consideration is made throughout of how current understanding of ‘family learning’ and the resulting approaches adopted in Scotland relate to the principles of compassionate love (Fehr et al. 2009) in development of ‘habitus’, ‘capital’ as providing access to the ‘field’ (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017).

2.3.1 The History and Development of Family Learning.

Human capital a motivation for action

Development of the economy and society of a country was concerned with the accumulation of human capital during the 1960’s (Carpentieri, 2012).

Developing human capital describes where individuals acquire “knowledge, skills, competencies and attributes” (The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, CERI/OECD, 2001:18). Responsibility and ability to increase resources of people is embedded in political aims and objectives which also promote ideologies amongst society. Ideologies promote judgements within society of how well children and families contribute to political aims and objectives.

Education is identified as a vehicle for achieving political aims and as such a place where judgement held amongst wider societal institutions affects the treatment of individuals out with his family (Morgan, 1975; Williams, 2004). For example, judgements include whether a family's home life is a suitable environment for learning appropriate social and ethical standards. Media and advertisement are often identified as a means of circulating the short fallings of family amongst wider society. However, we might question how key influences disseminated within religion, politics and education have added to ideas of the failings of family with little regard of the responsibility of these influential institutions alongside the ideologies and actions they promote.

Becker notes that education is a specific source of "increasing the resources in people" (Becker, 1993 p.11). Meanwhile, Smith (2015) highlights that education is often regarded as "schooling" which he claims cannot be regarded as education, as learning in schools is promoted by teachers completing a plan that has been created and motivated by the aims of others. Whereas Dewey (1916) argued that education should be "a process of living and not a preparation for future living". In other words, education should be a way of living and learning with others as opposed to showing them the way. Freire (1973) describes education as "banking" when there is a deposit of specific knowledge. Smith also adds that in deciding what others should learn we run the risk of treating people as "objects to be acted upon rather than people to be related to" (Smith, 2015: n.p.). These points are interesting in terms of who has been influential in promoting perceptions of what is valued as 'ideal' learning and of where and who provides 'education' that is most effective for all to flourish.

It may be useful to question if government ideologies, not only, present power over the life of families but more specifically impede rather than provide the ideal conditions in which all society can develop. For example, the conditions

that contribute to development of ‘habitus’ or confidence of ability, ‘capital’ that allows acceptance that everyone has something to contribute, and finally that these two will provide equal access to ‘field’ in gaining the ability to thrive in a way that is conducive to all members of society (Bourdieu,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017). The section will firstly consider the motivations for addressing perceived critical issues affecting economic development.

International influence in promoting lifelong learning and literacy for developing human capital.

The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) add that cultures worldwide have always encouraged lifelong learning and improvement in literacy, particularly amongst families, as it is “the most ancient of educational traditions” (UNESCO, 2015:7). This seems to highlight that education or learning have always existed as an element of families as part of the innate understanding that it is what we need to survive.

As such, a key ‘partner’ for the goal was recognised in families. 1994 saw the establishment of The UN International Year of the Family (IYF) which increased awareness of building a more family friendly society. The United Nations aimed through the IYF was to ensure that governments realise the importance of families for “social progress and development” and address the problems that they endure. The IYF was also to highlight that many initiatives aim to meet the rights of the individual, such as children and women, but fail to recognise the importance of families as “a basic unit of society”. The UN highlights the crucial function that families provide in, preserving and disseminating cultural values, education, training, emotional, financial, and material support of family members to allow growth and development. In this regard, it might be considered that influential institutions such as education,

religion and governments may have a lot to learn from families. However, promotion of the positive contribution that families can make across many societal areas has not always been recognised where many family ‘issues’, seen as negatively affecting development of society and the economy, have become a key focus for practice.

Meanwhile, Deforges and Abouchaar (2003) added that governments across the world understood that, increasing educational attainment and later successful outcomes in life, needs the support of families. Deforges and Abouchaar (2003) note that quality of schools was measured in part by the level of parental participation the school achieves. Participation was described across various school activities such as, being involved in making decisions and evaluating school processes or volunteering to help in activities or support in classrooms (2003:52). Meanwhile, the review of research studies evaluating the efficacy of programmes promoting parental involvement in various countries shows a range of successful outcomes. However, many studies are also highlighted as being poorly designed with findings described as subjective and lacking validity (Deforges and Aboucher, 2003, Cara and Brooks, 2012. Freedman, 2022)

Vaccarino et al (2006) explored how we can develop lifelong learning, literacy and work in partnership with families. The study utilised action research explaining that choosing this approach shows a commitment to finding ways of understanding the situation of others whilst also reflecting on how to improve practice more generally but also of self, in an overall bid to enhance life for all. Self-reflection and collaboration with the community that the research relates to were key elements for this approach to gain depth of understanding. Whilst these principles seemed appealing in relation to the design for this study, it was noted that action research aims to makes immediate changes. Considering the inquiry to be had in establishing what ‘family learning’ meant for all families living in Scotland, meaningful action was something that would need to be a

secondary step. Meanwhile, it was noted that the principles of inquiry should value and include the people that the research relates to. This fact was interesting in relation to the lack of consultation with families within The review of Family Learning in Scotland. The lack of consultation with people for a ‘family learning’ approach provided some inspiration for design of this study where it would be important to gain the views of families living in Scotland in the research (Scottish Government, 2016b).

Vaccarino et al (2006) conducted their study in New Zealand with the Wanganui community to find what changes the community would like to happen in terms of developing literacy. The study explored development of literacy across various stages and experiences of the life course. It included review of adult literacy, literacy as an element of family learning and development of literacy in the workplace. The study presents critique of the narrow perspectives that literacy is often viewed within. This point echoed the argument posed by Fejes & Nicoll (2008: xii) that the need for “totality and truth” often creates narrow viewpoints of important social factors. Vaccarino et al (2006) cite a definition of literacy as noted by the OECD (2000:x) as “the ability to understand and employ printed information in daily activities, at home, at work and in the community – to achieve one’s goals, and to develop one’s knowledge and potential”. Vaccarino et al (2006:57) present a critical review of this definition in noting that it presents a deficit perspective where development of literacy is positioned within such a narrow context. Literacy, they argue, should be recognised as multiple literacies that exist and are useful for living in the twenty-first century. For example, “listening, speaking, reading, writing, numeracy and critical thinking, interwoven with the knowledge of social and cultural practices”. Agreement on this point is also noted by Biesta in his research during 2008.

Vaccarino et al (2006) also add that training provision involved in the study highlighted that it aimed to make students “more literate in the fullest sense of the word” which they described as being aware of what they didn’t know, what they had learned and how that learning could relate to employment and the world around them. In essence the programme considered valuable learning and literacy as that which was meaningful to the students (Vaccarino et al, 2006:27). The second initiative within the research study was in development of literacy through a ‘family learning’ project, The aim of the project was to establish how ‘family learning’ could aid the work of the school in terms of developing literacy whilst also identifying what ‘good family learning’ practice looked like. An interesting definition of ‘family learning’ is presented in the following statement that highlights

The home is a child’s first school and the parent or caregiver the child’s first and most important teacher. The concept of family learning builds on this natural learning bond. Family learning comprises the different ways parents, children and extended family members use literacy during their day-to-day tasks and activities at home and in their communities (Vaccarino et al, 2006:39).

Vaccarino et al (2006) also note the socio-economic status of the community being considered which was an interesting aspect for this study where judgements may be made of ability based on where people live. However, Vaccarino et al (2006:40) explain that the values of the school aimed to always reflect cultural “aspirations and high values of the parent community” to help students find their talents. The mission and values of the school include qualities of practice as “learning for life in a supportive environment where values of ‘PRIDE’ are gained through; “Peacefulness (Maungarongo), Respect (Taumatatanga), Integrity (Rangatiratanga), Determination (Manwanui) and Excellence (Taumatatanga)”. Learning for life was also achieved through holistic support for the family where the school considers the interconnectedness between health, behaviour and learning. Funding was

prioritised to reduce class sizes, employment of more teachers and to gain the specialist advice from relative agencies. The head teacher was also praised within a review of school provision in promoting a whole school pastoral and inclusive practice that involves the community in regular review of teaching and learning as part of the ‘family learning’ approach.

The aim of the research for this element was primarily to improve practice for the development of children’s literacy, numeracy and communication. A further aim was to; demonstrate to families the valuable contribution they make in the learning process, to highlight the benefits of taking time with family members for building relationships, to increase opportunities for families to read together and to provide opportunities to share ideas for learning activities. The programme included an invite to parents to attend a reading workshop in school where a teacher and the school principal were in attendance. Whilst a few parents attended the first session the second had only one parent with the third having no parents attending at all. On reflection, the researchers and head teacher considered that the instruction or activity may have been too difficult, timing of the programme may have also posed challenges where families had other commitments. It may also be important to note here that whilst the school claims to be centred around the needs of families that consultation with them does not seem to have been an element for establishing the need for this initiative. Lack of consultation may have resulted in the creation of a programme that was not seen to be a priority for families.

The third area of focus was on the development of literacy was in relation to the skills needed for the workforce. Vaccarino et al (2006) highlight the need for lifelong learning in developing different skills required of a changing labour market where “physical capital” was no longer a key skill due to reduction and changes in manufacturing alongside the increase of technology. Broad knowledge, literacy, numeracy and the ability to adapt were recognised as

important in achieving “prosperity and social inclusion”. An interesting reference is made to the focus on economic competition with workers being recognised as the means in which to gain success. In this we are reminded of seeing the value of people as merely ‘human capital’. Vaccarino et al (2006:50) note

Our current knowledge economy requires skilled workers in particular to have. knowledge as well as personal competencies to gain new skills quickly, to perform individually, to work well in groups, as well as deal with change as a part of life.

To fulfil the needs of the knowledge economy, to gain new skills quickly would mean one thing, a need for growth of services and programmes that could deliver. We might also consider that this need presents opportunity to develop the ‘business’ of education and of how this may be beneficial for those who can perform or detrimental for those who cannot. For example, as noted previously Illeris (2018) highlighted concerns on the expectations that learning needs be gained in short periods of time. It may also be useful to consider that these scenarios provide little time to support foundational competencies needed for learning to happen. The idea of education as a ‘business’ can be linked to the promotion of lifelong learning. Biesta’s ‘Learning Lives Project’ (2008) explains that educational policy has been motivated by the promotion of lifelong learning since the 1970’s. The focus on the “knowledge economy” as highlighted by Vaccarino et al (2006) is described by Biesta (2008:15) as a “new educational order” responsible for contributing to economic development. Biesta highlights that this new order has shifted a focus to value learning gained in educational settings.

The Learning Lives project aimed to consider learning from a broader perspective in exploring the complexities related to learning across a lifetime whilst considering effective strategies to ensure opportunities for learning,

development of learning dispositions and the empowerment of adults. In this respect we can consider the contribution that this aim may make in the notion of “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). Biesta (2008) was interested in the history and biographies of learning through an individual’s life and how this contributed to their identity. In this regard we can see a more personal concern for the individual and of how this contrasts with the focus on learning for economic development.

The study design “combined retrospective life-history research, longitudinal interpretative life course research and quantitative survey research”. Qualitative research methods included interviews that allowed participants to tell them about their lives. It was useful to know that the interviews also allowed researchers to gain elaboration of points and to clarify understanding. The qualitative data was analysed thematically. Quantitative data retrieved from a longitudinal yearly survey from the British Household Panel Survey (BHPS) provided an overview of multiple subsets depicting changes in adult participation in formal learning. The volume of data presented within Biesta’s study is described as providing robust research evidence. An added interesting point gained from the design of this study was acknowledgement that considering learning from a broad perspective required various research considerations. For example, considering learning in the biography of participants relates to construction of knowledge. Considering ethnography and the observation of learners relates to learning as participation while acquisition of learning might relate to analysis of data. Awareness of how different contexts require consideration of the methods used was useful for thinking about the research design for this study.

The findings from the research conducted by Biesta (2008) show that learning exists in everyone’s life. Three key understandings found learning as: from life, as learning through life and finally learning through generations. In this respect

we can consider how learning as ‘capital’ may be gained from various sources and experiences throughout life (Bourdieu, 1993, 2000. Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017). Biesta (2008) notes that learning happens in the daily routines of life, from coping with major events whilst also contributing to the instigation and managements of key changes. The study equally shows that motivation to seek specific learning or of what learning is valued differs for many adults. A finding that is interesting for this study is that different perspectives between individuals and educational policies of what constitutes valuable learning affects motivations for learning. For many, learning is not just part of daily life, only needed for survival or to develop an economy, the study highlights that formal and informal learning are essential in contributing to identity (Biesta, 2008:18). Development of identity can be related to Bourdieu’s theory of ‘habitus’ (Bourdieu, 1990. 1993, 2000. Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017) when described as the “dispositions” individuals form in relation to the self, life and learning which they note can aid or create barriers to learning (Biesta, 2008:18).

The study also highlighted the importance of life stories and that opportunities for story telling are important for the development of self, this understanding encouraged development of a theory of “narrative learning” (Biesta, 2006:19). Participation in opportunities for learning were also recognised as either low level or high-level participation which Biesta noted as enhancing development of agency and identity. However, once again it is highlighted that these opportunities are best gained over the long term and not something that should be rushed. This point is interesting when considering the urgency noted previously of the new “knowledge economy...for competencies and skills to be gained quickly” (Vaccarino, 2006:50) and of the impact on development of agency and identity this will have. In addition, Biesta (2008) calls for future research to consider effects and planning of any learning opportunities from a longitudinal perspective and not focus on benefits that may only be short term.

Agency from Biesta's study relates to how we may be empowered through life, he argues that this can be driven innately, happen naturally from the life experiences we have or be a result of the actions of others toward us. He also highlights that learning and agency are inextricably linked where learning experiences can contribute positively to the agency we develop or conversely, deplete agency. Learning through formal education is recognised as having power in each of these scenarios but is positioned within a multitude of factors or as has been established previously, in constant negotiation of the personal, cultural, and societal expectations (Thorpe and Schmuller, 1954; Kolb, 1984; Jarvis, 1987; Grant, 1989, Finch, 1993; Pike, 2007; Smart, 2011, Elkjaer, 2018. Jarvis, 2018). If 'family learning' or "human flourishing" is about developing agency it may be useful that support for this needs to include awareness and skill in this negotiation.

In relation to Bourdieu's theories of habitus, capital and field as underpinning theoretical concepts for this study, the following points are interesting. Biesta (2008) describes a learning 'position' or habitus, as a socially constructed aspect. For example, this may be that a learning 'position' is set within perspectives of ability in relation to gender, ethnicity or ability relating to age. The learning 'position' of the learner, or in relation to 'family learning' might consider 'learners', is interrelated with dispositions for learning. Additionally, learning as these interrelated factors is positioned within "cultural learning practices" of where learning opportunities are gained, for example, family, school and the workplace. Biesta (2008:20) relates to these learning cultures as relational "Bourdieuian fields" which present power in either enabling or constraining learning or 'capital' as dependent on the forces at play. For 'family learning' we might consider the expectations promoted in forces as the global drive for economic development through lifelong learning and literacy collectively as the cultural field that 'family learning' is situated within. In

consideration of the focus for this study we might equally consider Biesta's presentation of how learning is achieved, motivated and affected and of whether this cultural field is conducive for 'human flourishing' (Underwood, 2009:4).

Whilst Biesta (2006) had mainly focussed on learning for individual development, others have considered learning from a wider socio constructionist perspective. A useful study for considering effective practice in promotion of lifelong learning, literacy and other academic subjects was conducted by Brooks et al (2008). The extensive "meta- study" reviewed educational programmes across the world with an aim to establish effective 'family learning' practice. The research specifically focussed on development of literacy, language and numeracy (FLLN) alongside gaining an understanding of the wider outcomes for 'family learning' (WFL) that these programmes may achieve. Like the research conducted by Biesta (2006), design of the study also employed both qualitative and quantitative methodologies in exploring a wide range of research studies depicting 'family learning' approaches of the "UK, Canada, Germany, Nepal, New Zealand, South Africa, Turkey, Uganda, the USA, and from a six-nation initiative led by Malta which also involved Belgium, England, Italy, Lithuania and Romania" (Brooks et al, 2006:9). Another interesting feature of the Brooks et al study is the broad consideration of family, literacy and numeracy and of how these are enhanced within family as informal and formal learning communities where respect for cultural diversity is a core principle of the approach. The following sections presents some of the programmes and approaches found across the world and in the UK.

2.3.2 Family Learning' across the world.

In review of what is effective practice for developing literacy, language and numeracy in families, Brooks et al (2006) provide a comprehensive overview of various perspectives and programmes that exist across the world. The focus for the review included inclusive programmes that valued how literacy, language and numeracy were developed within the home and in the community. An additional key interest for the review of programmes included any that valued development of partnerships between those delivering the programme and those taking part. Research design and evidence of successful outcomes was also an element of interest. Whilst many programmes have been conducted some time ago, it is useful to consider these in terms of how influential they have been in how 'family learning' is considered in the UK today. It is also useful to consider what lessons can be learned from the approaches taken.

An interesting point in relation to Biesta's theory of 'narrative learning' for developing sense of identity and agency, was that many of the programmes across the globe have included options to capture stories of families. These options have involved opportunities for capturing stories via digital means which they note offers exciting creative ways for current practice today. In addition, recommendation is made for future research methods with families where evaluation incorporates visual methods and storytelling. This suggestion was particularly interesting for the aims of this current research study.

Brooks et al highlight a variety of approaches driven by a range of epistemologies with research evaluations adopting qualitative methods for findings. On reflection of 'multiple literacies' as present in daily life (Biesta, 2006) we can view the range of programmes across the world as motivated from the two distinct perspectives (Brooks et al, 2008, Spacey et al, 2008).

Programmes that are designed to relate to the needs of families and community and that involve parents in the cocreation of them. In this respect we might consider these as ‘wider family learning’(WFL). Conversely, we can see programmes that are designed specifically to relate to the needs of educational settings and that are designed by schools or teachers with the specific aim in mind. In these we can name programmes as ‘Family Literacy Language and Numeracy (FLLN). Meanwhile Brooks et al (2008) highlight that “particularly impressive results” were gained where programmes are designed to work with families within their own home. The following provides an account of various approaches taken in different countries. These can be considered in terms of how influential they have been on how ‘family learning’ is considered in the UK and more specifically in Scotland in 2023 (2008:29).

‘Family Learning’ programmes in Turkey- combined focus of school attainment, child development and parenting.

Turkey is noted as taking a broad view of the role parents have within their families and society (Brooks et al, 2006). Informed by socio cultural and cognitive theory the Mother-Child Education Program (MOCEP) approach considered the role of mothers in not only developing children’s cognitive ability but also in their role as taking care of family members health and well-being. The underpinning epistemology was an ‘ecological’ perspective of learning where the home and community environments are recognised alongside school as contributing to the process. The ‘MOCEP’ programme aimed to support both cognitive and general development and well-being of children and involved home visits. In respect of the stress related to low socio-economic conditions and the behaviours that this may bring, the programme targeted specific families. For example, the approach also included an aim to raise awareness of the impact of shouting and severe discipline on children’s confidence and ability to learn. However, address of these negative elements

seems only to be considered as something that happens in the home. In development, the approach continued to form a focus on early literacy and numeracy as a readiness for school for children in their early years. The programme also created a unique branch which aimed to inform fathers on effective parenting, including protecting children from abuse, equitable child rearing roles and awareness of the importance of play for academic development.

Evaluation of the 'MOCEP' programme employed pre and post evaluation of participating families alongside comparison to a control group. The evaluation found increased literacy and numeracy of children taking part in the programme, a decrease in negative discipline used by mothers and improved relationships reported between mothers and their children. Meanwhile, the study design created negative outcomes of reduced self-esteem amongst some mothers and was considered to have been caused by the questioning of disciplinary practices of families. Researchers felt that the negative outcomes of some programmes may have been because mothers felt judged and considered themselves 'bad' parents thus affecting their self-esteem (Brooks et al, 2008:35). Review of the design for this research was interesting in encouraging consideration of how questions would be created to ensure participants did not feel judged in the responses given.

'Family Learning' in Nepal - Focus on local realities, empowerment of females, disadvantaged families and opportunities for storytelling through digital technology.

Exploration how Nepalese voluntary organisations added to development of literacy for the empowerment of women and girls. Motivating factors for some programmes were the low uptake of education amongst females in Nepal.

Programmes helped to build knowledge and understanding of health issues and the value in women and girls pursuing formal education. One programme provided much needed information in the form of a ‘baby book’ which also provided space to record key stages and events. Other programmes focussed on the importance of women in the role of improving children’s literacy with activities improving communication between home and school via a notebook.

Creative ‘visual literacy’ methods were employed in the development of literacy skills where participants were encouraged to create videos allowing stories to be told. Whilst other initiatives provided opportunities for children to develop their own stories in records of family history. Brooks et al (2008:36) cite the work of Robinson Plant who evaluated literacy programmes in Nepal during 1995 through qualitative methods as earlier evaluations had only ever been statistical in nature. Robinson Plant highlighted that when literacy is grounded in “local realities and is dialogical in method” disadvantaged groups can gain empowerment from gaining opportunities for their stories to be acknowledged and heard.

Family Learning’ in Malta – Focus on empowerment of cultural diversity and literacy through digital communication and storytelling.

In terms of partnership working, cultural diversity of families, the fast-paced progress and use of technology in ‘family learning’, the Maltese ‘Parent Empowerment for Family Literacy Project (PEFaL) project is of significant interest. The programme began in early 2000’s and involved six different nations in development of family literacy. The programme was motivated by a shared concern for marginalised families who may be missed in ‘family learning’ programmes due to language and other access difficulties. A key

feature of the programme was the need for recognition and support of multiple cultures and languages of families across different countries through digital communication.

The programme also included an activity that encouraged families to design a story telling bag that could be used with children. The range of cultural diversity offered a range of resources that could be used across multiple countries in support of literacy (Brooks et al, 2006: 32). This relates back to the work of Biesta (2006) in this respect where opportunities for ‘narrative learning’ are gained through digital technology. We can also consider the ‘wider family learning’ that these opportunities present in terms of development of identity and agency whilst expanding the view of literacy for the twenty-first century where development of digital literacy is a key skill.

‘Family Learning’ in South Africa – focus on learner and community centred programmes employing principles of the Freirean inspired ‘REFLECT’ approach.

Development of literacy was seen by the rural community of KwaZulu-Natal in Southern Africa as the means to improve life through education which was recognised as enhancing knowledge to improve health and wellbeing alongside offering increased employment opportunities. The community was recognised as having low levels of literacy with limited access to resources. The initiative aimed to broaden understanding and reduce judgement held by many that people choose not to read, and we might add perceived not to seek learning. Instead, the community library project highlighted that with no resources and opportunities, learning in a broad range of topics is limited. The project aimed to increase access to books for the community to enhance literacy development.

Meanwhile an interesting point is found in the epistemology at the heart of this programme as built upon the principles of the Regenerated Freirean Literacy through Empowering Community Techniques (REFLECT). The approach draws on “the fundamental principles ... that poor communities have knowledge and that development programmes which aim to empower them must be built on that knowledge” (Spacey et al, 2008:19). The approach is influenced by the work of Paulo Freire and was developed through research by ACTIONAID in 1993. Another principle behind the approach considers that prevention is more effective than intervention. Empowering communities with the skills to adapt to change and cope with challenge is seen as action that is most useful for successful outcomes. Crucially the approach values dialogue and is described as learner centred participation in enhancing literacy for the “social, cultural and political concerns of communities”. The approach also notes the importance of including children and adults in the promotion of literacy as the foundation for development in the home and community. The research has created a ‘Mother manual’ which *guides* facilitators to work with families rather than instructing and is noted as being employed in many countries (Spacey et al 2008:19). An interesting comparison can be drawn to the UK ‘PEEP’ programme and in this regard, ‘REFLECT’ might have provided considerable influence.

Considering these principles, the programme in KwaZulu-Natal recognised existing literacies of children and adults whilst assuming the responsibility that provision of support should enhance opportunities for both adults and children. Brooks et al (2008:35) explain that a further foundational belief driving the programme was that learning should be relevant to improving that which is meaningful for the current context of the community. The project design created literacy groups within various communities with a member from each community trained to lead the literacy activities. Activities were held within

family homes and community settings. We can consider the several benefits of this approach where participants may already have close relationships with each other and that facilitators would know their community well and could respond well in that respect. The first goal was to enhance opportunities for adults and children to read together, however, it developed into a programme that included support for adult literacy with additional opportunities to share what annual community events had been most important to participants. Understanding what is important for the community is reminiscent of the approach taken by Doreen Grant in Govan, Glasgow during the late 1980's (Grant, 1989).

Intergenerational evaluation involved children and adults and employed several ways of, games, oral stories and drawing to gain feedback. Evaluations of programmes over several years found that; interactions between adults and children when reading was longer and more detailed, relationships between family members improved and issues could be discussed more easily.

Participants also learned; English, how to sign their own name and how to care for friends and family who were sick. Participants were also motivated to work more in schools and communities in supporting others in their learning with teenagers reported as using libraries more often.

'Partnership' in the United States of America for development of economic development, lifelong learning, literacy and parenting skills.

Research conducted in the US during the 1960's highlighted that families were considered from a deficit perspective. Family circumstances and the adverse childhood experiences that they created were seen to be a key factor negatively affecting economic development. Research explored the development of 'early intervention' in the form of educational programmes that would provide support and guidance. Brooks et al (2008:12) note that the focus on lifelong learning, literacy and education in the US led to the concept of 'family literacy' during

the late 1980's with the development of programmes that would enhance all these aspects by targeting families. In some cases, the programmes saw specific areas and more specifically certain families as the main targets.

The 'Kenan model' was developed to address the needs, which may be considered as being perceived in some cases, of specific families. The approach included separate elements of adult education in working to develop parents' educational skills, early child education in working to develop children's educational skills with added opportunities to bring adults and children together for improvement of interactions for learning. It may be useful to note the possible influence of these US programmes in motivations for programmes in other countries. US initiatives may also have influenced use of particular discourse where intervention supported a focus of targeting "vulnerable and disadvantaged" children and families who were perceived to be at substantial risk of 'school failure'.

Additional reference is made to developing "parent capacity" to provide nurture, protection, and "effective" parenting (Woolfson, Durkin, and King, 2010:3). The discourse indicates a high regard for success within education alongside judgement of the skill parents lack. The motivations for actions may be claimed as "for the good of the other" (Fehr, Sprecher and Underwood, 2009:9), however, it may also be important to consider that there will be many factors impeding educational performance and parental ability to provide consistent care and of whether training of practitioners involved in such programmes have awareness and understanding, rather than judgement, as recognised as an important quality.

Whilst we consider the negative influence US practice may present alongside the reporting of limited robust research design and reliable findings (Deforges and Aboucher, 2002, Brooks et al, 2008; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Freedman, 2022), the work of Sanders and Epstein (2000) in the United States (US)

presents an alternative perspective and suggestion for effective partnership with families. Deforge and Abouchaar (2003) highlight that the extensive research and work had culminated in development of a National Network promoting partnership between schools and families across the US. The Sanders and Epstein study highlighted interesting guidance in relation to this study. They note that effective programmes for parental involvement and partnership working needs to consider a wide variety of factors and include a proactive, rather than reactive, comprehensive approach involving teachers, parents and members of the community with programmes embedded as a whole school approach.

Guidance includes promotion of sensitive approaches that consider the effects of; poverty, abuse, behaviour of children, mental health issues, low self-esteem or social capital, negative views of education that families may hold, and the barriers presented by schools in the ability for families to work in partnership. Guidance also includes avoidance of positioning responsibility of working with parents to family support workers suggesting that responsibility should be shared across whole school. They also recommend that the design of programmes have some element of research included to capture what works best at the time of the programme rather than capturing this information years later (Deforges and Abouchaar, 2002:88).

Meanwhile, Whyte and Karabon (2016) add consideration of the elements of power in education through the 'Funds of Knowledge' programme conducted within the US and questioned whether these aspects of power cause barriers in communication between pupils, parents, and teachers. Whyte and Karabon, explained that both teachers and parents had preconceived notions of power between each of them, developing judgements based within a sociological grounding. They suggest that these notions and judgements should be the focus for communication between teachers and parents, where they are diminished

amidst reciprocal dialogue and partnership building. Lareau (2000) adds that partnership between home and school require equality to be shared between the two (Whyte and Karabon, 2016).

Longo et al (2017) explain, that living in poverty can inhibit positive parental practices and the ability to provide key stimuli for children's learning, such as "materials, time and energy" (Longo et al, 2017 p.2273). However, they note findings from the "Three- Cities study", based in Boston, which acknowledged the importance of "sensitive caregiving" for the fostering of successful academic outcomes and which can supersede the effects of poverty (Coley, 2011). An interesting point for this research was in noting that investment for learning, or motivations for actions, is either in the form of material "resources" or of "behaviours" such as, direction and affection. This may produce successful outcomes where Kalil & Deliere (2004:12) argue that experiencing a sense of warmth within relationships provides successful outcomes for child development and learning. This point is interesting when considering whether 'family learning' requires these as qualities of practice encompassing 'love' and understanding within support for children and families to develop 'habitus, capital and access to the field' for all.

Brooks et al (2008:29) explained that the 'FLAME' project in Chicago during the late 1990's, like 'MOCEP' in Turkey, considered a broad role of parents and aimed to empower Hispanic mothers, who would often remain at home unless accompanied by their husbands. The programme recognised the benefit of integrating new families into the wider community and saw the value of mothers in this role. The programme also aimed to support of families where there may be language difficulties which was recognised in creating barriers to accessing or success in formal schooling in the US. This shows that the programme recognises the fundamental elements that were needed for families of diverse cultural backgrounds in preparation for future learning.

Like many ‘family learning’ initiatives, the Canadian ‘LAPS’ programme ran over a number of weekly sessions. However, an interesting element of the approach was rather than educational guidance, the programme focussed on parenting advice that would enhance what we might consider as foundations for future learning. For example, parents would learn about managing anger, behaviour, conflict alongside guidance for nutrition, safety, child development, communication, listening and building self-esteem in children. In addition, development of the initiative developed a distinct programme that would support families where English was a second language (EAL) and to inform practitioners of the cultural sensitivities required when supporting diverse cultural backgrounds (Brooks et al, 2008:32). In terms of the diversity of families living all over the world this consideration is viewed positively.

Family support in Sweden and Norway focussing on holistic family design in policies and practice.

Simpson (2018:2) provides an account of how families are supported within Norway and Sweden. These countries are identified as having the lowest rates of inequality and poverty in the world and as such may provide some useful inspiration for practice here in the UK. Holistic support for a range of aspects related to learning and well-being are provided within one centre by what is described as the “four legs of provision; midwifery; child health nursing; early years education; and social work”. The study also notes a comprehensive approach to policy making in ensuring children’s rights are integrated across various policy frameworks.

The design of the service is noted to be “preventative” where families are empowered with knowledge and understanding and supported to reduce ‘issues’ from happening. Opportunities to build strong relationships are also described as gained through consistency of health visitors support over a number of years. Simpson noted the usefulness of being able to access support for other family needs where various organisations were co-located in the same setting. Early educational settings were staffed by both practitioners to support educational development and social workers who could provide help with any other needs. The settings were described as “open kindergartens” where parents were free to ‘drop in’ as they pleased. This arrangement is noted as being particularly beneficial for partnership working. An interesting point was that childcare was funded well by the government which relates to developments in Scotland for extension of funded childcare hours being made available to families (Scottish Government, 2017b). A particular observation was made in the increased number of fathers who attended the centres which Simpson (2018) attributed to the generous paternity leave available in some of the countries.

Various programmes were used to support families for specific needs; however, these were implemented in the knowledge that they had been successful in other settings. Evaluations had been conducted by university researchers who created a central database for settings to choose from. Examples of approaches used were ABC, ‘Triple P’ and the ‘Incredible years and the International Child Development Programme (ICDP). Simpson notes that practitioners questioned why they would need intervention when it is much more effective to “walk alongside families” (Simpson, 2018:21). This presented quite a different and interesting perspective than has been noted in other studies. A particular value was placed in respecting families and the need for families to build strong relationships when caring for the children, as a result, the ‘open kindergarten’, holistic support and integrated policy framework seemed to provide extended

family networks. This seemed relative to the idea of families as community promoted by (hooks, 2000). In consideration that these countries have low levels of inequality and poverty the approaches taken may be important for informing ‘family learning’ practice in fulfilling “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:7).

2.3.3 'Family Learning in the United Kingdom.

Development of the UK economy as motivation for action.

An interesting development of influence for learning and the lives of families living in the UK was made during 1975 in the creation and agreement within the OECD Support Fund Act which agreed to funding being accepted and given from UK government funds to the Organisation for Economic Development (OECD). The agreement made with the OECD maintained considerable influence on both economic and educational affairs influencing government policies. Meanwhile, Segal (2014) provides a scathing account of how neoliberalist government ideologies of the conservative party and later political decisions affected the lives of many families living in the United Kingdom. Under Thatcherism, a priority focus of economic growth was achieved through privatisation, tax reduction for those already wealthy and benefit cuts for those who need financial support. Segal (2014) highlights that this type of governance produce only one kind of flourishing, that of capitalism which did little to improve lives for everyone. This presents an ideal opportunity to consider how government powers and decisions have major impact on the lives of families living in the UK. Strangleman (2018) demonstrates how economic gain from coal mining rose post war, ensconcing social change amongst families and communities. However, deindustrialisation saw the demise of the coal industry resulting in the closure of many coal pits across the whole of the UK. Closure of coal pits presented major changes for many communities and families where unemployment affected health and wellbeing resulting in poverty for many, the effects of which still exist today in communities across the UK. The effects of government decisions based solely on economic growth and the lessons learned from the demise of the coal industry presents a clear example of how generations of families and communities are affected at government level.

Strangleman (2018) summarises the impact when noting that sociological studies were beginning to evidence that:

The closure of industry had left a toxic mix of environmental, social, economic, health, educational and cultural issues which would not be easy or quick to fix (Strangleman, 2018:33).

Opportunity for social justice and human flourishing, during this period of conservative rule, was reported as limited to only a few families who could navigate and survive the capitalist system that had been created. Strangleman (2018) outlines that ability to survive or not created divisions amongst families and communities. On reflection, it is interesting to consider whether this legacy has also created ‘deficit’ perspectives of families where socio economic status is believed to render them unable contribute effectively to learning process or to the economy. Freedman (2022) explains that the focus in supporting families as a key driver for societal change continued in England. He highlights the commitment to families by the Labour government as evident in the name change of government units from The Department of Education and Skills to The Department for Children and Schools and families. Development and promotion of ‘family learning’ as an approach for intervention called for integration, collaboration, and partnerships as vital. However, achievement of this ‘ideal’ may be questionable. The following section outlines the UK drive for human capital as fulfilling the continuing economic focus.

Human capital, Lifelong learning and literacy as motivations for action in the UK.

Throughout this section the influence of international economic focus can be seen to be developed through enhancing human capital, lifelong learning and literacy across the United Kingdom. In terms of the focus for this study, the

following statement of how quality of life is enhanced and of how education is seen to contribute, is of relevance

The purpose of education is life enhancing it contributes to the whole quality of life In the next century, the economically successful nations will be those which will become learning societies: all are committed, through effective education and training, to lifelong learning. So, to be a successful nation in a competitive world, and to maintain a cohesive society and a rich culture, we must invest in education to develop our greatest resource our people (Fryer, 1997:35)

The Economic and Social Research Council's Learning Society Initiative showed that the UK's progress in education, training and lifelong learning was inadequate when considering the ability to perform within the global economic market (Fryer, 1997:1). Inability to perform within the global market was found by Reich (1991) as affecting equity in standard of living across all of society. In address of this predicament, The National Advisory Group for Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning (NAGCELL) was formed with the aim of promoting a culture of lifelong learning across the UK. Promoting a culture of lifelong learning would include encouragement for families to continually develop skills relevant to industry and employment which would improve lives for themselves, their children and the lives of all other people living in the UK. Active citizenship was at the core of the responsibility placed on families to improve their own situation and that of their community.

Meanwhile, it is noted that whilst establishments, such as, schools, colleges and universities, were also expected to contribute to the encouragement of a lifelong learning culture, Fryer (1997:24) highlights learning that was valued was not to be restricted to only that which leads to qualifications. An interesting point relating to the wide variety of key learning that should be recognised (Biesta, 2008, Brook et al, 2008)) was made in the guidance for those in charge of funding to “cherish equally those many forms of learning” (Fryer, 1997:58). In

addition, the promotion of lifelong learning showed a need for a fundamental change in attitudes amongst those funding and providing learning, Fryer noted

The challenges are legion, and many of them present both threats and opportunities. But the most important challenge is to recognise that high quality learning is not the exclusive preserve of the educational institution or the training centre. Much learning has always happened outside these locations, and change, including curricular and technological change is making, it easier for such learning to happen. We increasingly need flexibility in the times, locations and forms of learning so that they better suit the needs of individuals (Fryer,1997:15)

Widening participation was a key aim of the lifelong learning strategy with achievement to be gained through building confidence and self-esteem of all learners. The report acknowledges “systematic inequalities and exclusion” as an added challenge where individuals had developed “understandable” distrust of institutions seen as having created and perpetuated their situation. An interesting point is made in noting where individuals do not succeed in their first attempt, then opportunities are often limited in assumption that they either lack interest or ability. Change was also highlighted in the demand of respect for the diversity of race, ethnicity, culture, values, beliefs and traditions of families living within the United Kingdom.

‘Family learning’ initiatives were recognised as ways to promote a lifelong learning culture and in securing educational achievement, as such, advice was given that they should be supported widely within local government and local authority funding streams, planning and training of staff to deliver the programmes. Limited funding and commitment from governments and local authorities is noted by families as affecting their motivation. This guidance may have related to the argument posed by Alexander and Clyne (1995:11) that ‘family learning’ was the “Cinderella of public education” due to the limited progress made from the International Year of the Family in 1994. They claim that whilst ‘family learning’ was recognised as a key contributor for public education, it was:

rarely invited to the public spending ball ...[and] ... at the “strike of midnight of the IYF.... all that was left was a golden slipper of recommendations and family learning went back to its rags in the ashes of society”.

In reference to families being involved in support for learning, Alexander and Clyne, (1995) provide various definitions of what ‘family learning’ was. They described ‘family learning’ as informal learning gained within families where influences for learning is gained from media, religion, sport and leisure clubs, libraries etc. This definition is interesting in terms of the point raised by Price-Robertson and Duff (2018) in consideration that family must be considered in terms of the ‘assemblage’ of factors that create and influence family and its members.

In addition, ‘family learning’ was also described as; opportunities where family members are encouraged to learn together within public services and institutions, such as church and schools and through generations of family members who they note are influenced by religious and educational systems. Finally, ‘partnership initiatives’ were identified as ‘family learning’, however, Alexander and Clyne (1995) note that partnerships were generally motivated by the aims of the promoting agency, for example, the aims of school, health services or community education. Description of practice variation was described as ‘patchy’ calling for ‘family learning’ to be focussed on meeting the holistic requirements of all families in what they want to learn. We can recall that the work of Biesta in 2008 noted previously as making the same point and presume that improvements had not been made in this regard.

In address of challenging family circumstances, the UK took inspiration from research within the US in creation of ‘Sure Start ‘centres with wide ranging programmes of family support set up across the UK. However, Glass (2006) raised concerns around the motivations for the centres as being political propaganda which ultimately affected funding and long-term success of these

centres in achieving ongoing benefits for families. Melhuish et al (2011) highlighted that a key aim of the centres, and subsequent measure of success, was development of 'human capital' as contributory to UK economy.

Brooks et al (2008) also comment on UK 'Sure Start' programmes noting that whilst they targeted specific areas and families in the assumption of required support, the programmes are reported to have helped build relationships between parents and their children, provided wider opportunities for play whilst also helping prepare children for school. Approaches used in the programme depict further inspiration taken from the United States in the promotion of 'dialogic reading' between parents and children to improve literacy. The approach encourages, questioning and repeating child responses during shared reading activities.

An interesting element arising from evaluation was that, whilst numbers of fathers involved in 'Sure Start' programmes was low, fathers were recognised as contributing to development of digital literacy of children where interactions between male carers and children in the home often included shared play with computer games. This acknowledgement relates to the idea of multiple literacies present in everyday family life (Biesta, 2006, Brooks et al, 2008). Evaluation identified the programmes as effective because of the involvement and support gained from multiple agencies, however, limited evidence of robust improvements in literacy resulted in reduction of funding with political views of the cost effectiveness of the programme resulting in eventual closure. (Brooks et al, 2008, Woolfson, Durkin, and King, 2010) In fact, the challenge of demonstrating cost effectiveness and performativity remained a key concern in the feasibility for many programmes. Power over funding was often in the hands of international, national or local governing bodies.

However, it may also be useful to consider that whilst research may show that families had benefitted from Sure Start centres, concern is raised of how

influence from the US in particular use of specific discourse may have been in contrast to the preventive approach taken in Norway and Sweden. In consideration of the successful outcomes of low inequality and poverty noted in Norway and Sweden by Simpson (2018) it may be useful to consider if the ‘deficit’ view of families affected successful performance of these settings.

For example, it is suggested that discourse, such as, ‘early intervention, vulnerable and disadvantage’ promote othering, encourage a shift of blame on families and therefore promotes perceptions of inadequacy. In addition, it seems pertinent to note that these types of approach appear pathogenic in aiming to fix issues after the impact of effect, failing to address the conditions that have caused the family circumstances in the first place. Alongside, a concern of deficit discourse and the perceptions it may foster amongst support workers, suggestion is made that a salutogenic approach, as a holistic understanding of the wide-ranging conditions that impede the ability to thrive, is required. Addressing the aspects that contribute to stress within the family, such as poverty and mental health issues, could avoid the need for interventions of the state (Mittelmark et al,2020).

In addition, the claims and recommendations posed by Alexander and Clyne in 1995 may be influential for the guidance being presented by Fryer later in 1997. For example, Fryer continues in recognising that encouraging motivations of people, who have been affected by previous negative experiences in education, needs a workforce who have appropriate skills, time, clear communication, opportunity for trial and error, support of funding and are able to work amicably recognising the value to be had when the needs of families are the main priority. Or as Fryer (1997:21) states a workforce who are not “fighting for their own neck of the woods, to the neglect of the whole forest”. Guidance outlined the importance of addressing the many obstacles that get in the way for people to participate or gain ‘successes’. Specific guidance noted that programmes be

designed in all aspects, such as content and access, to meet the needs of learners and not institutions or organisations (Fryer, 1997:6). The report encourages learning institutions to learn from our mistakes, build on the evidence and positive practice that exist, specifically noting examples and attitudes in community learning initiatives.

The benefits to be gained from lifelong learning are highlighted as empowerment of individuals to address their own situation by having the confidence to challenge social exclusion, often experienced in educational settings. Promotion of lifelong learning aimed to build self-esteem, self-awareness, values and attitudes to aid communication skills, problem-solving, handling conflict and dealing with stress. These skills would allow families and communities to drive 'family learning' to fulfil their own needs and interests across multiple generations (Fryer, 1997:57). However, it is unclear what the motivations for action are genuinely driven by. For example, whilst the aim of lifelong learning and all that it presents claims to be of benefit to families, 'family learning' in this sense would also undoubtedly benefit the state in terms of reducing economic costs in supporting families and communities whilst also enhancing economic gains of money filtering into the system through educational funding, fees and employment. The challenge noted here may be twofold, will historical institutions, and those who work within them, be able to accept the notion of sharing power for learning with families and as Buffton (1999) also questioned, would families be able to withstand the resistance that may ensue.

'Family Learning' to aid UK economy through development of human capital, lifelong learning, literacy and parenting skills.

The Labour government of 1997 demonstrated the motivation for 'family learning' as part of the lifelong learning agenda forming a key part of their government policy for England in noting:

Family learning is a powerful tool for reaching some of the most disadvantaged in our society. It has the potential to reinforce the role of the family and change attitudes to education, helping build strong local communities and widening participation in learning (Freedman, 2022:6).

Reflection of the statement highlighting the need to change attitudes to education presents questioning that it implies families do not value education or that the education system requires to change to include families in educational plans and provision. Meanwhile, the statement also makes clear the aim of assisting families who are ‘disadvantaged’, in noting that widening participation is required, this point supports the claim made by Fryer (1997) that the education system had not always offered equal opportunities. The National Advisory Group for Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning NAGCELL (1998) suggested that ‘family learning’ programmes should be concerned with development of existing skills by providing challenge and objectives. Research within England has outlined similar definitions of ‘family learning’ alongside guidance of what ‘family learning’ should include. Most definitions of ‘family learning’ include interpretations of an intervention and preventative approach in minimising poor outcomes for children and families. The approach serves to aid, the individual, the wider community, and a country’s economic situation. (Buffton, 1999, Haggart, 2000. OFSTED, 2009. Brasset Grundy, 2002, Vaccarino et al, 2007, Cara and Brooks, 2012, Carpentieri, 2012, National Institute for Adult Continuing Education (NIACE), 2013, Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014, Wainwright and Marandet, 2017). Meanwhile Cara and Brooks (2012:5) also call for ‘family learning’ to be considered as simply “a type of learning”. Harding and Ghezalayagh (2014) note that identifying what is required in ‘family learning programmes’ lies in discussion and communication with families. ‘The Campaign for Learning’ (Spacey et al, 2008) highlighted possible influence from the US in guidance that ‘family learning’ needs opportunities in which adults, children and carers can learn both, together and

individually. Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Education (HMIE) (2009) support this view by stating that 'family learning' programmes require sources of encouragement which incite families to learn together, particularly throughout generations to foster a desire for continual learning (HMIE, 2009).

Braslett-Grundy (2002) identified 'family learning' as an integral element for the lifelong learning agenda and undertook a small research study on behalf of the UK Department for Education and Skills (DfES). The study aimed to establish parents' perspectives of 'family learning'. Perspectives were gained through focus groups followed by two one-to-one interviews involving parents who had been involved in a programme for families where English was a second language, parents who had not, teachers and some children. Limitations for the study were its small scale, possible gender bias in views where all but one of the participants were female. In addition, the programmes that parents did attend were delivered during the day and focussed on developing literacy and numeracy only. This fact created challenges where children missed other classes and teachers found it difficult to access useful resources such as information technology. The study presented a variety of definitions for 'family learning' with most identifying it as planned programmes that promote adults and children to learn together.

However, alternative definitions were noted in citing the work of The National Institute for Adult Continuing Education (NIACE) and the Scottish Council Foundation (2000 that 'family learning' should be recognised as "mostly intergenerational, can be formal or informal, can be undertaken outside formal institutions or in conjunction with them, and with or without professional support" (Braslett- Grundy, 2002:5). This definition echoed the perspective of participants in the study. The findings highlighted that both sets of parents who had participated in 'family learning' initiatives and those who had not, viewed 'family learning' in broad terms recognising that it included many people and

happened in a variety of places. For example, ‘family learning’ was recognised by parents as homework, family outings, visits to museums or libraries, involving grandparents or other family members.

Parents who did not attend planned programmes identified key barriers to them participating suggesting that previous bad experiences of the education system had left them feeling demotivated to get involved. They suggested improved marketing of programmes with clear information that; the course was free, what the course was about, the intended benefits, that it was delivered in a variety of venues with additional information on any funding for travel. The parents who did not attend programmes also noted that they should be planned and delivered by practitioners who were respectful, supportive, non-judgemental and unthreatening. Programmes should have childcare provided or incorporated in the plan to allow participation, as parents did note concerns at having to leave their children with strangers. They also highlighted that they would prefer programmes that were relevant to their needs, such as, support from social services, that programmes should be small, informal and delivered by someone and that they knew and felt comfortable with. Additional barriers to attending planned programmes were mental health issues and other family commitments.

Meanwhile, both sets of parents could identify benefits that could be gained from ‘family learning’ programmes. Parents who had attended explained that they gained knowledge of the education system, ideas of how to extend learning for their child in everyday experiences, knowledge to share with other family members, gained opportunities to meet new people building wider support networks and opportunity to achieve a qualification encouraging them to pursue further training through increased confidence. Parents and teachers also noted benefits for children in developing literacy, concentration, motivation, relationships with others, improved behaviour, opportunities to talk in their first language and share stories and respect for their parents.

As we have already considered ‘Family learning’ as an approach to enhance educational attainment aims to encourage children and parents to learn together. Programmes are either those that have a specific focus for outcomes in ‘Family Literacy, Language and Numeracy’ (FLLN) with some programmes achieving various other beneficial outcomes that have not been the targeted area. These elements are described as ‘Wider Family Learning’ (WFL) outcomes (Spacey et al. 2008). WFL outcomes may relate to the idea that any programme seeking to develop individual social responsibility will ultimately strengthen the overall capabilities of local communities (Brassett-Grundy, 2002). Strengthened community capabilities are described by Harding and Ghezalayagh as being “new skills, increased confidence and understanding, improved communication, changed behaviours and changed relationships with the community and family” (2014:10). Wainwright and Marandet (2017:224) add that benefits of ‘family learning’ include development of “self –reliance and responsibility” amongst individuals which in turn encourages wider communications and interactions for the benefit of the community in which they live.

However, many of the ‘family learning’ studies have identified that more research is required to identify the ‘wider benefits’ of family learning programmes. In addition, many studies have noted that evaluations of ‘family learning’ programmes are extremely difficult to measure with many findings described as unreliable. The complexity of ‘family learning’ and the feasibility of ever knowing for certain why certain outcomes have transpired alongside poor research design lacking the use of a control group for comparison have posed questioning over the reliability of research data. Lack of robust evidence is noted as having affected opportunities for consistent funding and government support (Deforges and Aboucher, 2002, Brooks et al, 2008; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Freedman, 2022).

Research highlights that FLLN programmes continued to evolve in the UK from the mid 1990's. Progression demonstrated, a preference for programmes that included two generations of a family (e.g. parents and children) and had a focus on developing literacy and numeracy as being most effective in enhancing learning for all. The design of these programmes was influenced by the US Kenan model which includes opportunities for separate adult and child learning followed by joint delivery sessions. (Brooke et al, 2008:47). Promotion of these were driven by the UK's 'Basic Skills Agency' described as holding a "powerful role in initiating and evaluating FLLN programmes". As a result, an array of initiatives was encouraged to include all members of the family. Partnerships between trained practitioners skilled in supporting learning across various ages and all members of the family were a key feature of ensuring sustainable effective practice. An additional interesting point was the differing views of how literacy is developed. FLLN programmes work with families and children to enhance reading and writing skills. This might be considered as viewing families from a deficit perspective where the very existence of the programme denotes that these skills are lacking, and expert support is needed. In contrast, it may be considered that a 'family literacy' perspective considers literacy from a strength-based viewpoint in the recognition that multiple literacies exist in everyday family life. In this context families may be seen as experts and of what they can teach in terms of family literacy and how this knowledge and understanding is useful for enhancing 'family learning' practice. Interestingly, Brooks et al (2008:58) highlight that differing political views of what or who enhances learning best affected delivery and distribution of funding. They note that Wales remained guided by The Basic Skills agency and had taken a "cradle to grave community approach" whereas England had shifted focus and funding to development of programmes delivered by schools and other organisations, this is described as presenting inconsistent level of

effectiveness across England. Variations in delivery and focus for ‘family learning’ programmes across the UK and other countries include either expectation that families will attend a programme run with the community for a few hours spanning a 12-week period whilst others were delivered through home visits.

Examples of UK programmes featured ‘Skills for Families’ which focussed on development of FLLN and delivered by various organisations. The organisations were also encouraged to explore new ways of working, for example, expanding FLLN support through childminders or getting fathers involved, however, whilst evaluations noted that the programme provided opportunities for partnership working, expected performance and related funding remained a constant concern. ‘Keeping Up with Children Early Start’ aimed to support parental understanding of methods used in schools for development of literacy and numeracy. Brooks et al note that cultural diversity of families was met by adapting content and resources to meet the needs of families and the community. Evaluation of the programme claimed that parents and children developed increased confidence. The ‘Early Start’ programme aimed to enhance literacy and language in promoting activities to be replicated at home. Evaluations of this programme asserted that providing examples and ‘modelling’ for parents aided successful outcomes.

A change of direction of influence from the UK to the United States was gained within an early programme promoting learning in maths. ‘IMPACT’ encouraged partnerships with children, teachers and parents to enhance numeracy skills through the recognition of opportunities for learning maths and numeracy in everyday activities. The partnership approach involved, teacher training, ideas from parents to help identify informal activities which could be completed at home with children and where outcomes were shared between

parents and teacher. The programme and approach were considered effective and adopted across many schools in the UK, Canada and the US.

Additional influence to be had in the UK was found in the ‘The Raising Early Achievement in Literacy’(REAL) programme. The programme also presented partnership working where Nutbrown, Hannon and Morgan, as researchers from the university of Sheffield, worked alongside parents and teachers during the late 1990’s in collaboration to develop a programme that would help support literacy development through identifying that, where parental involvement in literacy development of children already existed, there were opportunities to enhance literacy for all (Brooks et al, 2008: 55).

Across two phases the research began with discussions between researchers, parents and teachers to develop a model of working that would be useful in practice and at home. From this initial element of the study, the ‘ORIM’ model was developed. “Opportunities, Recognition, Interaction and Modelling” were identified as key components to support literacy development. The model encourages parents and teachers to recognise opportunities for literacy development in everyday life, recognise when it happens and how they contribute to it, encourage regular interaction between children and adults where examples can be shared to aid enhancement of literacy. An interesting element of the model included use of a ‘jigsaw’ to encourage parents and teachers to identify what they were already doing whilst identifying additional ideas for activities that could provide further opportunities for development. The second phase of the study developed partnership working where teachers visited families’ homes whilst also organising events within settings in which literacy resources and ideas were shared.

Evaluation of the model was gained through quantitative evidence that was described to be “statistically significant” whilst teachers and parents noted ‘ORIM’ as useful in providing enjoyment for children and parents alongside

progression in literacy. The research and model provided additional inspiration from the UK in employment for other programmes, such as the UK “Families and Schools Together’ (FAST) discussed below and the Canadian ‘Parents’ Roles Interacting with Teacher Support’ (PRINTS). Evaluation of both these projects also recognised positive outcomes.

Description of the purpose of ‘family learning’ was also in support for families in matters relating to health, well-being and parenting skills fulfilled through ‘Sure Start’ centres and creation of parental support advisors based within every school which are reported as reducing school absenteeism. Additional third-party organisations provided programmes, such as, Save the Children’s ‘Families and Schools Together’ (FAST) and the later ‘Families Connect’ alongside ‘Triple P’ positive parenting programme provided guidance and support for families. Meanwhile, Freedman (2022) critiques consistency of support noting that there is no coordination between these programmes, describing ‘family learning’ provision as “patchy” adding that there is limited robust evaluation of how they impact the lives of children and families (Rennie et al, 2021; Freedman, 2022:28). This argument highlights what we may now view as a historical challenge as concerns over consistency in support services have been highlighted previously by Alexander and Clyne (1995) and Biesta (2008). In addition, robust evaluation and evidence of the benefits ‘family learning’ programmes provide has also be noted as inconclusive (Deforges and Aboucher, 2002, Brooks et al, 2008; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Freedman, 2022).

However, in addition to ‘patchy’ provision, future governance of the Tory party was concerned that educational services were being distracted from their key function by expectations to work with and support families and quickly reverted the government division back to ‘The Department for education and skills’ which reduced the expectation and funding for schools and local authorities to provide ‘family learning’ support. From this account, the motivations for

‘family learning’ in England seems to be for families to improve educational attainment and parenting skills. Once again the point made by Biesta (2008) can be considered that withdrawal of funding being seen by families as powerful institutions lacking genuine commitment or care and can affect the motivations of families to get involved with initiatives or work in partnership.

‘Family Learning’ as partnerships for building the economy through development of lifelong learning, literacy, education and parenting skills.

Power and Whitty, (1999) cite the work of Giddens (1998) and identify a shift in governance to work with communities and families as the ‘third way’. They describe early government approaches during the 1960’s through until 1970’s as the first way, bureaucratic and controlling. The second way of governance was driven by economic development with the third and current shift to collaborating with communities and families as an alternative attempt to improve the economy and lives. A defining focus for new ways of working was on collaboration and education. Holloway (2014) notes that New Labour recognised education as a major contributor for economic and social policy. As such, political decisions recognised the potential that families could provide for society in supporting education. Although, Wainwright and Marandet (2017: 226) suggest, that whilst this change of approach appears a positive, it also appears convenient in times of austerity where money will be saved by the state when the burden is shared across society.

Involving families in education has been a focus as a means of improving educational attainment. Power and Whitty, (1999) explained that the ‘third way’ of governance encouraged involvement of communities and families within political decisions and actions. Acknowledgement is made that previous

approaches had failed in achieving the expected enhancement of economic development and life for everyone. The ‘third way’ of governance also promoted partnership and collaboration amongst various parties to ensure successful educational results to enhance the economy. However, Powell and Smith (1999: 544) questioned how we can be sure that “players are partners in any meaningful way” encouraging consideration of whether the ‘third way’ merely perpetuates power and a combination of historic bureaucratic neoliberalist values.

The focus on how to ensure ‘success’ in educational outcomes and partnership with parents can be traced back to the ‘Plowden report’ of 1967. The report highlighted the importance of a child centred approach and the need to collaborate with parents noting that “one of the essentials for educational advance is a close partnership between [schools and parents] for every child's education” (Freedman, 2022:5). Alexander and Clyne (1995) add that many schools created family rooms and hosted family workshops with community services providing youth and adult education. Alexander and Clyne also add that the content of the education provided was influenced heavily by religion and health services with much of the funding for these services being cut during the 1990’s because of different aims and objectives of government.

In addition, Tessa Blackstone (1967) reviewed the Plowden report shortly after its publication and critiques the findings and suggestion made. Blackstone (1967) adds various critical arguments in response to the three areas of effect identified within the Plowden report. The three key aspects identified as contributing to attainment in learning at school were home circumstance, school practice with social class of parents and their attitudes to school being listed as most important. Interestingly, Meanwhile, Blackstone notes that sociological

studies identify that social class of parents is an inadequate predictor of success in school in highlighting that as contrary to the notion that social class is a predictor of ability, sociologists have been perplexed by “working class over achievers” and “middle class under achievers”. In addition, this relates to the findings of the EPPE study conducted by Sylva et al thirty-seven years later in 2004 which noted that social class of parents was not a predictor of ability. Siraj-Blatchford (2010) also reiterated that social class of parents should not be considered as an indication of ability.

A key recommendation made within the Plowden report is of building relationships with parents to develop parental understanding of the school system and how they could help their child achieve success within it. The rationale for collaborating with parents was to address several factors affecting educational attainment. However, Blackstone notes that whilst the Plowden report promotes partnership with parents as an essential improvement for educational provision, the report did not suggest the need for partnership with parents to be formalised within a legal obligation. Blackstone (1967) added that addressing issues of attainment also requires review of educational systems in assuming responsibility. She urged that educational establishments review the effectiveness of practice that; grouped children by ability, lacked provision to meet individual support or positioned teachers who had limited knowledge and ability to support specific educational barriers. The advice that teachers may not be equipped to provide relevant support for all children is interesting as Illeris (2018:19) also highlights this as a contemporary challenge.

Blackstone also questioned size of schools and the ability for large cost saving schools to build partnerships with all families and therefore achieve the suggested success in attainment. Blackstone’s guidance in 1967 regarding development of large schools as cost saving, is interesting in relation to the development of ‘super schools’ in Scotland today where it might be questioned

how relatively small staff groups can build meaningful partnerships with the multitude of parents and support required of increased pupil populations. The critical arguments posed by Blackstone in 1967 are useful as they relate to elements of educational practice today. It may be considered if perpetual promotion that families lack ability to contribute to learning are influential in developing deficit views of the contribution that families make to learning and to difficulties in building partnerships where judgement not understanding is present. From the review of literature, there are continual recommendations to consider the developments required in educational practice in addressing any challenges for educational attainment or partnership working.

2003 saw continuation by the UK Department for Education and Skills in establishing how to develop “self-fulfilment and citizenship”. Development of attitudes, values and knowledge and attainment in school, are highlighted as needed for successful ‘child outcomes’ and recognised as important for lifelong learning. Excellence in UK schools identified that involving parents in the work of the school would be useful. Parental involvement was outlined as working in partnership to share information and consider parents views. Working in partnership provided opportunities for parents to be involved in school governance, inspection and policies. Desforges and Abouchaar (2003:12) conducted the review of research literature to gain understanding of what worked well and of what we can learn from effective approaches. The review identified that achieving positive ‘child outcomes’ involves a variety of support with parental involvement with children’s learning being recognised as one such way.

Parental involvement was also viewed as ‘good parenting’ where parents supported learning at home, collaborated with teachers, attended and contributed to the work of the school. The review of literature also highlighted challenges in parental involvement with children’s learning as being affected by

poverty, health and self-confidence. Previous experiences in school, negative interactions with teachers or simply not viewing that their role as a parent includes getting involved with the work of the school were listed as additional factors. In address and support of individual family circumstance, targeted programmes were developed to encourage specific families to get involved and aimed to increase levels of human and social capital.

Meanwhile, Desforges and Abouchaar (2003:12) highlight that establishing a conclusive argument on the effectiveness of parental involvement in improving attainment at school was difficult due to the wide variety of influences and impacts on children's development with a recommendation that the interaction between all of the factors needs to be acknowledged. This point echoes the argument posed by Smart (2011:539) for awareness of the negotiations between the personal, culture and the social. As noted previously many studies highlight that review of quantitative studies presented unreliable findings due to a variety of reasons. (Deforges and Aboucher, 2003, Brooks et al, 2008; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Freedman, 2022). For example, poor research design was identified in the lack of consideration made of the interrelationships between factors that may affect educational attainment, poor design in measuring data and the use of historical data alongside subjective viewpoints of what worked or of what benefits were gained. Deforges and Abouchaar (2003) also claim that parental involvement in the work of schools does not always seem to be beneficial for children's attainment but can be helpful in other ways, such, building connections with the community.

The review also indicates that it is parental interest in learning and support at home that helps to aid developing foundations for school learning, progression and motivation for children's learning that can stay with them throughout their lives. They note that the success of parental involvement in the home as most effective because it is "more enduring, pervasive and direct", in comparison,

they note that parental involvement with learning in schools is not (Deforges and Abouchaar, 2003:31). In this regard it may be useful to consider exactly how and where development of ‘habitus’ and therefore the ability to gain ‘capital’ happen to allow access to the ‘field’ (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017). However, whilst Deforges and Abouchaar (2003:76) heed caution in taking guidance from research studies as to what element of parental or family involvement is most effective in ensuring successful learning and child outcomes, they did identify the work of Sanders and Epstein in the US, noted previously, which they highlight included robust design and therefore more reliable findings.

Cara and Brooks (2012) noted that forty-five years after the Plowden report and Tessa Blackstone’s critique, policy initiatives continue to target specific families in an aim to develop positive attitudes to education amongst ‘disadvantaged’ families in assumption that these families lacked any value of learning gained in education. Holloway (2014) highlights an example of the influence this thinking has had in research conducted in England where perceptions held by head teachers of “ideal parenting” were of those who have ability to support children’s learning based on the socio-economic status of families. Holloway notes that perceptions encouraged different approaches in working with families of perceived differing abilities to contribute. The study reported that for families of high socio-economic status, headteachers acknowledged an “assumed busy schedule and high competency of parents” and aimed to encourage more time in sharing their skills and knowledge with their children. This approach sat in contrast to working with families of low socio-economic status where they adopted “a future-orientated perspective on childhood seen in wider Government policy... to enhance children’s future social mobility by ensuring their access to activities which develop social and cultural capital” Holloway (2014:385). However, on reflection of the

perceptions held by headteachers we might question if limited opportunities for participation are still affecting practice today. Meanwhile, The National Parent Forum of Scotland (2016) and Cassidy (2018) highlighted that attitudinal change amongst educational staff for building partnerships and raising attainment has been a historic and contemporary difficulty. The conflicting viewpoints highlight further ongoing challenges around if and why such perceptions remain and of how these may be addressed.

Early Education to improve the economy through development of lifelong learning, literacy, education, partnership working, parenting skills, and the Home Learning environment (HLE)

The Effective Provision of Pre-School Education [EPPE] Project conducted by Sylva et al (2004, ii) explored the effectiveness of pre-school education with consideration of home learning for children's development and preparation for future education. A particular focus for the study was to compare development of children across the trajectory of ages three until seven and of children who attended pre-school care settings as opposed to those who did not. The study included assessment of the children, information from teacher, practitioners and parents on developmental progress achieved. The research also included observations of the support provided by pre-school staff and home learning environment.

A finding from the study was that pre-school education was beneficial in preparing young children for school and helped to alleviate some of the effects of 'disadvantage' for 'vulnerable' children. However, the findings also noted that the home learning environment and not income, education, or occupation of parents, was the most crucial factor in the social and intellectual development of children noting that "what parents do is more important than who parents are". However, one might question if findings of this review may be an additional

influential source for educational settings to position blame on families for difficulties with learning or low attainment in school. Suggestion is made that address of difficulties with learning are where pre-school experiences provided quality provision. Qualities of provision were described as when “staff showed warmth and were responsive to the individual needs of children” (Sylva et al, 2004: iv) which relates to the qualities of ‘ideal’ families outlined previously in this thesis.

However, it stands to reason whether warmth and responsiveness should not be extended to working with all ages to ensure quality across communities or families of support (hooks, 2000, Williams, 2004, Morgan, 2011). Additionally, it may be useful to consider if the use of the word ‘warmth’ is a more convenient and safer term for ‘love’ in relation to ‘professional’ services and whether, if this is the case, that alternative phrases to ‘love’ are used throughout policy presenting a more nuanced but nonetheless presentation of the importance of love for human development. Whilst the study has provided robust evidence of the benefit of pre-school in reducing the impact of “disadvantaged” backgrounds it may, alongside research and practice from the US, have been influential in the development of the focus of early intervention and preparing children for school within early education. Once again, we might consider that the focus on educational attainment, as beneficial for government aims, may be detrimental for some where children and families struggle to ‘perform’ as expected. In addition, promoting a focus on educational attainment in the exceedingly early years of children’s lives may also limit opportunities for free play and exploration which is recognised as equally beneficial for children (Education Scotland, 2020). The points being raised in this study highlight the complexity of training and skills required in staff working within education and care settings. A further, interesting element of quality provision was noted in the need for centres to combine care and education of young

children with support and opportunities to share knowledge and understanding with families. Various research studies (Deforges and Abouchaar, 2003, Biesta, 2008, Brooks et al, 2008) recommended that practice needs holistic approaches of support.

2.3.4 'Family Learning' in Scotland

Social justice as motivations for actions in Scotland.

In the reformation of a Scottish government after a period of 300 years, Mc Crone (1992:28) suggested that an opportunity had arisen for a state which could become original in its political thinking. As a devolved nation, he noted that Scotland has gained the opportunity to change, presenting a very different Scotland for the future. In defending its right for devolution, Mooney and Scott (2012:2) highlight that the Scottish government argued the case that they should have the right to be able to generate solutions for the distinctive problems of its own nation.

Keating (2010:28) added that devolution presented a shift in power between the UK government and Scotland, noting that Scotland already intended to share power amongst society in the formation of the 'Scottish Constitutional Convention', described by Keating as a partnership which "mobilised a swathe of Scottish civil society" (2010:29). Shared decision making was recognised as a trait historic to Scotland and was used to promote devolution as a vehicle which could continue to drive social justice for Scotland as a country and for its people. The aim of devolution and social justice is claimed by the current Scottish Nationalist Party as providing a "second or new" Enlightenment in development of a society that meets diversity of support through rational, logical thinking (Mooney and Scott, 2012, 2016).

From 1999 a reformed Scottish government aimed to address the distinct inequalities experienced by families living in Scotland by providing social justice through several means. Key values of social justice are identified as “tolerance, pluralism, inclusivity and democracy” (Mooney and Scott, 2012:30). The Scottish government aim to achieve this through redress of factors contributing to poverty amongst families living in Scotland by improving the economy, education, and employment (Scottish Executive, 2000, Scottish Government, 2016). Devolved powers have presented some autonomy for the Scottish government where decisions could be made around health, education and training, social work, housing, some transport, law, and home affairs. However, it is argued that reserved powers of the UK government in terms of “economic and fiscal policy, social security employment legislation, reproductive health policy, equal opportunities, some transport, immigration and nationality” (Wasall and Hill, 2002:174) impedes the freedom of the Scottish government to achieve “pluralism” as a shared source of authority between the Scottish Government and families living in Scotland and ultimately social justice for all (Mooney and Scott, 2012:9).

Policy history showed that social justice remained a key motivation for the Scottish government. For example, ‘Social Justice ...a Scotland where everyone matters Annual Report’ (Scottish Executive, 2000) presented aims to address poverty, social exclusion, employment, and education. Meanwhile, the same aims are outlined some sixteen years later in the ‘Fairer Scotland Action Plan’ (Scottish Government, 2016c). Mooney and Scott (2016) also highlight Scottish government claims that decisions made by the UK government on reserved matters such as most welfare benefits have made provision of social justice more difficult for the new Scottish Government. In review of devolved and reserved matters, we can see that autonomy is only achievable in some aspects of social benefits given over to the Scottish Government. The main contention

is that power over social benefits, such as universal credit, which help families on low income or who cannot work, child benefit, state pensions and pension credits remain reserved matters for the UK government.

Walsall and Hill (2002:174) support this claim in raising concern of the ability to provide a cohesive joined up legislative policy framework that provides justice when social and care issues are governed separately to those relating to economy and work. This argument maintains relevance some twenty years later where the devolved arrangements of the UK and Scottish governments provide challenge in enabling “social justice” or “human flourishing” for all families living in Scotland. However, the claim of limited power may be convenient particularly if the Scottish government perpetuate and echo some of the neoliberalist ideologies where economic development is still a key focus. For example, the UK OECD Support Fund Act (1975) sits interestingly with the creation of the Scottish Development Agency Act (1975) which aimed to improve the Scottish economy and environment and may signify a specific focus of economic development for preceding government aims and objectives.

Economic development as motivations for action in Scotland.

Whilst governing powers will argue that the decisions, they make are for the benefit of the people in achieving social justice, the dilemma posed by Fehr et al (2009) on what is required for human flourishing is apt. They argue that motivation of actions for “the good of the other in the first instance” (Fehr et al, 2009:4) is a crucial element in fulfilling what is needed for true human flourishing. This raises questions of whether government actions are for the benefit of people as a primary aim with the economy benefitting as a secondary result. Conversely, we might question whether motivations for government actions are based on economic development as a primary focus which may

result in benefits for people or be at the detriment for some. For example, a focus on economic development as a primary concern may affect development of 'habitus' and therefore the ability to develop 'capital' to allow access to the 'field' (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017), for those who cannot perform. Ulterior motivations present a situation described by Freire as "false generosity" (Freire, 1972: 18).

In relation to this point, it is interesting to note that in the year of devolution Scotland's first minister Donald Dewar presented "The way Forward: A Framework for the Economic Development of Scotland" (Scottish Executive, 1999) as a precursor to "Social Justice- A Scotland where everyone matters" (Scottish Executive, 2000). It may be pertinent to consider whether presentation of an economic plan as a first concern demonstrates a choice that economic success is the motivator for action and not necessarily the most important requirements of all Scottish people. This choice may be led by the desire for Scotland to become independent of UK rule ((Scottish Government, 2016b) and may be bolstered by the Scottish government with an argument that economic success and independence is the vehicle in which social justice will be gained. This consideration may relate to Freire's (1972:18) point of "false generosity" and raises question of whether a Scottish Government aim of social justice can be achieved as genuine generosity grounded in motivation and "actions for the good of the other in the first instance" (Fehr et al, 2009:9)

Sen (2009: xiii) adds guidance on how justice is achieved in highlighting the importance of "public discussion" to establish aspects that relate to the life that we choose or as he puts it "democracy as government by discussion". It is noted that the Scottish government seem to have applied this thinking within the 'Fairer Scotland Action Plan' (Scottish Government, 2016c) which identifies the need for a collective responsibility and collaborative approach. The policy

claims to have been informed and created by discussions from across Scottish society noting,

It takes all of us to build a fairer Scotland. Government can't do it on its own, nor would we want to. We want to work together with the people of Scotland, particularly those living in poverty, with communities, with business and industry, and with all public and third sector organisations. This will not be an easy or simple task, but if we all pull together and do our utmost, we can and we will succeed. And the prize is a precious one – by 2030, a fair, smart, inclusive Scotland, where everyone can feel at home, where fair work helps businesses to thrive and create jobs, where poverty rates are amongst the lowest in Europe, and where there is genuinely equal opportunity for all. (Scottish Government, 2016c:1)

Whilst the quote presents an initial positive message, on deeper analysis, a specific discourse can be found. The message is highlighting; a shared responsibility but also possibly a lack of recognition of the responsibility government has in creating a fair basis for all families. The quote continues with a focus on “those” living in poverty which pervades the legislative and policy frameworks of support for families living in Scotland. However, it may be pertinent to question if the focus and depiction of poverty creates discrimination where beliefs of limited ability and contribution are promoted.

On additional reflection of the quote made within the ‘Fairer Scotland Action Plan’ it is also interesting to note the perpetuation of economic development in the need to ensure that “business” thrives. A more explicit link between this, and “human flourishing” may have been beneficial (Underwood, 2009:4) as the key driver for the success of business. However, inability to present human flourishing as a key concern or ‘capital’ to be gained from fulfilment of basic human requirements may be considered as having less value in our 21st century world. Therefore, concern is raised where this is the case with an additional argument that human flourishing as a primary concern will be the foundation for any success to be gained in a fair and just society. In response to this notion, the

reference to providing a place where everyone can feel at home is noted. On reflection of what home might feel like, it may be useful to return to the literature around families and more specifically of the qualities related to a sense of family and home and how we create that for all Scottish society. The qualities that relate to human flourishing, sense of families and home remains a primary concern for this thesis. In acknowledgement of how a fair and just society can be achieved alongside the importance placed that everyone should feel at home, it is interesting to explore how challenges in these areas are addressed or not as the case may be.

It may be useful to stop and consider the current view of people as ‘human capital’ in terms of their ability to contribute to development of the economy. If we do, then we must include consideration of the role that society, and the systems within it, have in affecting ability of contribution. If we fail to claim responsibility in the inequality experienced by others, then we perpetuate a cycle of injustice. On reflection of the range of major influences on family life in Scotland that has ensued complex level of effect, concern is raised that at the most fundamental level, as human beings, we need to acknowledge that our actions affect others and assume responsibility to support that comes from a humanistic place (Taggart, 2016) as a main focus rather than a place of economic concern to ensure “human flourishing” (Fehr et al, 2009:4). It is clear from the following timeline that the lives of all families living in Scotland have been at the mercy, or we might question without mercy at times, of various political views and subsequent actions.

Professional care and Integrated services as motivations for actions

In exploring the actions taken to achieve a fair and just society we can see that, where possible, there have been attempts to address inequalities that exist within

Scotland. The reformed Scottish government gained power over decisions around civil justice which includes family law, policing, housing, health and social care which includes management of the National Health Service and Social Care services. Key legislation in this respect was the Regulation of Care (Scotland) Act 2001 which aimed to improve standards of social care through registration and expectation of care provision provided by local authorities, and more specifically, social care workers looking after children, young people, and the elderly. This act was supported with creation of the Scottish Social Services Council (SSSC) responsible for the management of social care worker registration, creation of standard codes of practice for ‘professional’ services with monitoring of care provision alongside the Care Inspectorate.

Whilst with good intention, it may be that the promotion of service workers supporting families as ‘professionals’ has promoted power as an acceptable element of practice provided within influential institutions such as education and created barriers where specific perceptions of what professional practice can include. For example, code of practice 3.10 states that “as a social service worker, practitioners should not only recognise the power and authority that they have but ensure that they use it responsibly” (SSSC, 2016 np). The Regulation of Care Act (Scotland) 2001 was followed by ‘For all Scotland’s Children (Scottish Executive, 2001) promoting integrated working amongst social care services as a key requirement of support for families. However, difficulty with integrated working has also been identified where hierarchy amongst ‘professional’ services has been difficult and, in some instances, this has been to the detriment of the care of children, as demonstrated from the deaths of Victoria Climbe (Laming, 2003), Daniel Pelka (Coventry LSCB, 2013), Peter Connelly (Department of Education, 2010) and Liam Fee (Scottish Government, 2017d). Unfortunately, these cases provide a small example of the

failings of the safeguarding of children because of hierarchy amongst ‘professional’ services.

‘Learning with care’ (Scottish Executive, 2001) highlighted that elements of legislation were, once again, not being fulfilled by children and family support services. In addition, the report highlighted the effects of adverse childhood experiences on educational performance of ‘looked after young people’ and the importance of care in meeting these specific needs, placing a shared responsibility to be met by local authorities, schools, and social work departments to ensure that ‘looked after young people’ progress in education. In addition, The Children (Leaving Care) Act 2000 meant that children could leave the care system at the age of 16 with local authorities being expected to ‘befriend’ the child as a measure of assuring their welfare. However, Hiles et al (2013) whilst noting the importance of this support also highlighted that plans to end befriending were often poorly managed leaving young people in distress adding to inabilities in forming further relationships.

On reflection, whilst there appears to be an intention to ensure the care of children through legislation, these examples provide evidence that legislation may benefit from being coupled with integrated working that echoes; “communities of practice” and “networks of affection” (Hooks, 2000 Williams, 2004; Morgan, 2011; Elkjaer, 2018). It may also be beneficial that integrated working includes regular dialogue between all parties involved, to ensure that children and families gain the appropriate qualities of care that they require.

Children’s Rights as motivations for actions in Scotland.

The UK ratification to the United Nation Convention of the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) and its related standards in 1991 provided impetus for specific legislation and policy within Scotland. Alignment to the UNCRC encouraged

that the standards were used to inform decisions, but did not present any legal obligation, in any area relating to enhancement of children's lives. However, as a devolved government, Scotland demonstrates a commitment to the lives of children through a keenness to apply the UNCRC within the legal system and policy framework. 'It's Everyone's Job to make Sure I'm All Right' (Scottish Executive, 2002) promoted the need for integrated working as necessary for the safeguarding of children. 'Getting it Right for Every Child' (Scottish Executive, 2004) continued the promotion of the importance of integrated working and remains a key policy for supporting children and families. The Children Act of 2004 had created the role of a children's commissioner who had the responsibility of ensuring children's rights were met.

'Extraordinary Lives' commissioned by the Scottish government in 2006 continued in the quest to ensure that children within the care system in Scotland, now referred to as 'looked after' children, gained appropriate care which was the responsibility of local authority. The report outlined that expectations and beliefs of the ability of these children were often low with the review aiming to ensure equity of opportunity for all children. The Equality Act of 2006 presents key legislation outlining a legal obligation; to ensure equal opportunity, human rights, respect, dignity, and a sense of worth for everyone living in Scotland. The Act aims to ensure that prejudice or discrimination is deterred within Scottish society and that everyone gains the ability to achieve their potential. In addition, the formation of the Commission for Equality and Human Rights aims to ensure that all children and families gain the aspects outlined within the Equality Act (2006). Whilst we can see an alignment with the research and ambition conducted by Fehr et al (2009) for the WHO on a commitment for human flourishing, the Scottish Government maintain the argument that reserved powers over welfare benefits impede the ability for human rights for all to be met.

Consultation as motivation for action in Scotland

A change of leadership within the SNP party in 2007 saw a key change in the use of the term Scottish Executive being replaced with the title Scottish Government and creation of the ‘National Performance Framework’ (Scottish Executive, 2007) which aimed to consult with and meet the support required of Scottish people. ‘The National Performance Framework’ tracks progress of how well plans are meeting the needs of Scottish people (Scottish Government, 2017a). The framework was informed by research in asking ‘What Sort of Scotland Do You Want to Live In?’ (Carnegie Trust, 2017) consulting with a range of Scottish society to establish what kind of country people wanted Scotland to be. The consultation resulted in development of three key social policies in 2008 aiming to improve the lives of children and families in Scotland. ‘Equally Well’ (Scottish Government, 2008) outlined the importance and promotion of health and wellbeing. ‘Achieving Our Potential’ (Scottish Government, 2008) promoted the plan for employment with ‘The Early Years Framework’ (Scottish Government, 2008) providing a pivotal policy which again highlighted the importance of integrated working and early intervention. The policy presented ten priorities for transformational change in the enhancement of the lives of children and families. The policy framework to enhance the lives of families living in Scotland was supported with ‘The Commission on Scottish Devolution’ (Calman Commission) (Scottish Government, 2008) which would review the financial arrangements set within the devolved powers between the UK and Scottish Government as set within the Scotland Act 1998 to attempt to gain more autonomy for the Scottish Government to address the impacts on Scottish family life.

‘The Christie Commission’ (Scottish Government, 2011a) also aimed to eradicate poverty supporting the Child Poverty Act (2010) by reviewing future

delivery of public services to address inequality by shifting from intervention to a preventative approach. The commission recognised that major institutional and structural change is difficult to achieve and highlighted that there are many contributing factors. Prevention of inequality would be gained through; collaboration with people and communities to gain understanding of support required. Additional measures included further integration of support services in achieving positive outcomes for all families with transparency of actions and communication using technology. Motivations of actions were twofold; the improvement of people's circumstance and to reduce cost.

In respect of the aim of prevention and need for collaboration, the early years of children's lives were identified as crucial in preventing continuation of inequality and poor outcomes resulting in the 'Child Poverty Strategy for Scotland' (Scottish Government, 2011b) and creation of 'The Early Years Collaborative' (Scottish Government, 2012) which promoted partnership working between the national health care service, police, local government and third sector voluntary organisations in achieving aims to eradicate the effects of poverty within the principles of Getting It Right For Every Child (GIRFEC) (Scottish Government, 2008).

However, a review of the historic aim and challenges of partnership working across agencies in eradicating child poverty is provided within the 'Local action to tackle child poverty in Scotland' (McKendrick and Sinclair, 2012) commissioned by Save the Children. The review demonstrates that local authorities believed action was already being taken and therefore failed to create any targeted plans of action to address issues relating to child poverty and its affects within local areas. The report outlines various issues where blame or responsibility is being shifted from one institution to another (government to local authorities) intimating a lack of shared responsibility, lack of ownership or commitment to the cause.

Relationships as motivation for actions in Scotland.

On a more positive note, an addition to these measures is made in identification of the key qualities required in provision of care to improve the lives of families living in Scotland with the publication of ‘Common Core of Skills, Knowledge & Understanding and Values for the “Children’s Workforce” In Scotland’ (Scottish Government, 2012). The Common Core presents more evidence of the depth and persistence of Scottish Government aims in their attempts to achieve social justice. The detailed guidance outlines what is needed from supporting institutions. A continued attempt for consultation is evidenced in the formation of core skills having been formed from “the perspectives of children, young people, and their families ... describing what is fundamentally important to them” (Scottish Government, 2012:2).

The ‘Common Core’ encourages settings and service workers to consider how well they incorporate these skills in practice. The four main essential characteristics are that provision of care; is non-discriminatory, respects the views of the child, includes decisions that are always in the best interests of the child and finally that provision of care respects the right to life, survival, and development. Each of the four characteristics have relationships in two specific contexts as their core. Firstly, relationships with children, young people, and their families and secondly relationships between fellow workers (Scottish Government, 2012:7).

These characteristics of care are interesting in the context of this thesis and in consideration of what governments promote in support of human flourishing and of how this aligns with the qualities of families explored in section one. In comparing the qualities of the Common Core to that of families we can see similarities where “reciprocity, respect” (Williams, 2004) and “communities of care” (Hooks, 2000:131) are promoted. Meanwhile, it is equally interesting to

note that the common core is limited in identifying qualities of ‘professional’ care that promote “networks of affection and emotion” highlighted as key for learning and development of children and families (Williams, 2004:71; Cronin, 2015:1170). Difficulties in using emotive language such as ‘love’ as a quality needed in practice in relation to ‘professional’ support services has been highlighted by Page (2011, 2018), Morris (2021) and Malcolm (2022), who note the importance of love for early education and development. Additionally, it may be useful to consider the impact of practice that negates affective and emotive qualities if these are also important for the flourishing of children and families.

Meanwhile, The National Parenting Strategy (Scottish Government 2012a) and the Early Years Collaborative (Scottish Government, 2012b) both provided additional means of advancing political aims and objectives into practice through partnership working where the importance of parents and care in children’s early years was highlighted as key in addressing the continuum of poor outcomes. Promotion of integration of services and partnerships to support children and families was continued with the Public Bodies (Joint Working) (Scotland) Act 2014.

Building the Ambition as motivation for action in Scotland.

The Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014 attempted to embed the rights of children in the Scottish legal system and Scottish society by placing a responsibility on Scottish ministers and local authorities to ensure promotion of the importance of children’s rights and well-being with additional expectation of reporting the actions they had taken every three years. The Act is supported with the announcement and policy of ‘Building the Ambition’ (Scottish Government, 2014:5) “to make Scotland the best place in the world to grow up” embedding ‘Getting It Right For Every Child’ (GIRFEC) (Scottish Government

(2008) as central to this Act and guidance for practice. GIRFEC principles encourage all agencies and workers supporting children and their families to apply eight indicators of safety, health, achieving, nurtured, active, responsible, respected and included (SHANARRI) as a holistic measure ensuring children's health and wellbeing. In the context of the well-being indicators, 'achievement' is linked to promotion of 'Raising Attainment for All' (RAFA) (Scottish Government, 2014) which forms a key focus for the well-being of Scottish children and therefore Scottish education. However, the aims of the Children and Young People (Scotland) Act 2014 are described as both, "ineffective" and "contrary to the UNCRC" where McCall-Smith (2021:6) highlight that "there remained no legal obligation".

Meanwhile, the Scottish government demonstrate further dedication to the rights of children with the introduction and subsequent passing of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (Incorporation) (Scotland) Bill in 2021 which would ensure that children rights are enacted within Scottish law. However, the UK government have deemed that any aspects relating to children rights linked to reserved matters cannot be enacted within Scotland's legal system, once again indicating limitations and power over family lives being shared across UK and Scottish governments. Meanwhile, in respect of considering motivations for actions, it is useful to note the first minister of Scotland highlighting again in the '2016-2017 Plan for Scotland' (Scottish Government, 2016a) that a plan for prosperity was to be built for Scotland as a nation, through development of a maintainable economic status which in turn would provide equity for every individual. The plan envisaged Scotland that is "vibrant, open, inclusive and outward looking" (Scottish Government, 2016a:3). Further legislation and policies continued the aim of enhancing the lives of families living in Scotland. The Scotland Act 2016 continued the cause to gain power over decision making and financial decisions that directly affect Scottish

society. In addition, a wide range of educational policies, outlined later, aimed to contribute to the plan for prosperity.

‘The Promise’ as motivation for action in Scotland.

An interesting development in relation to the focus for this thesis of whether love should be a concern in terms of “human flourishing” (Fehr et al, 2009:4) is made within ‘The Care Review’ (Scottish Government, 2016). This thesis asserts that important characteristics for human flourishing can be linked to Bourdieu’s theory and the development of confidence or ‘habitus’ as a belief of the contribution that we make to wider society. Development of positive ‘habitus’ offers opportunity to develop a range of ‘capital’ that in turn allows access to whichever ‘field’ we require to navigate in life. It was therefore interesting to see that ‘love’ featured as a crucial element of practice of those supporting children and families in providing the ‘habitus required to thrive. The Care Review of 2016 sought the views of 5,500 care experienced children and workers across Scotland to gain an understanding of what was needed to allow care experienced children to be able to flourish. The review was the first of many policies that refers to ‘love’ as an important aspect for the growth and development of children. ‘Pre-Birth to Three’ (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010) and Joining the Dots (Deacon, 2011) were two of very few policies relating to the importance of love for children in their early years. The findings of the Care Review provide a fundamental plan of what is required and most importantly ‘The Promise’ to the care of children living in Scotland. However, the promise is made to the “most vulnerable children”, and we might question if the promise should be extended to all children and families.

Nevertheless, recognition is made that the review provides an interesting return and extension to qualities of care initially outlined within the ‘Common Core’ (Scottish Government, 2012). These policies present the fundamental basic

qualities important for human flourishing as highlighted by the children and workers involved. The Care Review of 2016 also identified short fallings of previous reviews and actions in achieving the aims of meeting children's needs and makes a promise to the demand from children noting:

It is clear that Scotland must not aim to fix a broken system but set a higher collective ambition that enables loving, supportive and nurturing relationships as a basis on which to thrive (Scottish Government, 2016:6).

The Scottish Government add to the recognition that aspects such as poverty impact greatly on children and families lives by also acknowledging that on a more fundamental basic level that bureaucratic unfeeling systems, and the practice they encourage amongst society and more specifically those working to support children and families, have additional impact on the lives of people living in Scotland. 'The Promise' presents a commitment in developing this as the new ambition for children and young people. In this respect the Care Review has provided a key contribution to the rationale and purpose of this thesis of considering what qualities are required in services that support children and families to ensure human flourishing of Scottish people. Continuation of the aim of eradicating child poverty is applied through the Child Poverty (Scotland) Act 2017 which extends the timeframe to 2030, demonstrating the ongoing difficulty in meeting the original objective of ending child poverty by 2020. Further attempts to promote the collective responsibility for this is outlined in 'Protecting Scotland's Children and Young People: It is Still Everyone's Job' (Scottish Government. 2017d).

Meanwhile, a 10-year review of progression outlined in 'What works Scotland Christie Commission 10 years on' (Scottish Government, 2020) highlights inconsistent delivery across local authorities promoting the need for further tailored provision to meet the support needed across communities. The review also highlights challenges that require to be addressed which include that

change is often difficult for major institutions where shifts in cultural “mindsets, practices and interaction” is required. Encouraging and providing opportunity for genuine participation of people is highlighted as one of these key shifts where organisational culture presents many obstacles (Scottish Government, 2020:7). This is an interesting point when considering the difficulty in developing partnerships and meeting the support required by all families living in Scotland rather than the needs of institutional services (Grant, 1989; MacKenzie, 2010; The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016).

The following section provides consideration of Scottish education as a key influence in the lives of families and learning. The section will explore Scottish education system in terms of enhancement or barriers to human flourishing through consideration of motivations for educational approach and of how these affect the lives of families living in Scotland.

Developing Scottish education as motivation for action.

This section will consider the influence that Scottish education has had on families living in Scotland in two parts. Firstly, it will consider a brief historical overview of Scottish education demonstrating the ideologies that, maintain the foundations of educational purpose and practice as a key influence for society in Scotland of the 21st century. The second section will explore more contemporary Scottish education and consider the legislative framework that underpins educational practice today. Exploration will include the claim made by Scottish education of learning and of how this claim promotes; a limited view of learning, a hierarchy on learning in deciding what we learn, how we learn and who we learn best with.

History of Scottish Education.

Learning for people living in Scotland has, and continues to be, influenced by two major institutions (Inglis, 1894, Anderson, 2018, Gillies, 2018).

Historically in Scotland, religious authorities played a significant role in influencing what learning was appropriate (Inglis, 1894, Anderson, 2018).

Secondly, the political agendas of Scottish governments have also influenced perceptions of where most of the learning takes place in addition to why and what Scottish citizens should learn (Gillies, 2018). As a result, institutional influence has created a specific view of learning as the way in which Scottish citizens can effectively contribute to Scottish society. Anderson (1980) and Chambers (2012) highlight that historical teaching in education often contributed to dissemination of acceptable and unacceptable behaviours through lessons that focussed on “manners, organised games and mechanical learning operations” which they note restricted open displays of affection whilst lacking any opportunity for impulsive resourcefulness or imaginative play (Cooper 1971).

To extend the historical span of this thesis for a moment, The Education (Scotland) Act (1872) is recognised as fulfilling an aim for “national and public education to impose cultural uniformity”. The 1872 Act, not only, promoted learning to improve academic ability but also for learning as a means for controlling social responsibility and effectiveness of the state (Anderson 2018:99). In addition, education was identified as a site that should “concern itself with fostering in him [the child] the qualities, skills and attitudes which will make him useful to society...” (Scottish Education Department, 1965:17). Jamieson (1999) argues that the views of societal institutions lack consideration of the responsibility that wider society had in any demise of morals and unacceptable behaviours. This is an interesting point considering the learning

gained from corporal punishment used in Scottish schools up until the mid-1980's where children were physically punished to ensure conformity.

Concerned at the focus and methods used to repair the ills of families of the day and the impact which it would have on the development of children, in despair Cooper questioned, "how do we recover this lost potential?" (1971:290).

However, experiences in Scottish education from this time may have done little in contributing to guidance of exemplary morals and acceptable behaviour and has entrenched a lack of trust and respect of educational provision amongst some families living in Scotland. It may also be pertinent to consider how historical educational approaches remain influential in practice today. Whilst institutional goals have and still affect perceptions of what, how and of where people learn in Scotland, Anderson notes that institutional influence for learning has created a "tradition of national education and a cultural disposition, with religious, political and social roots, to value educational achievement" (2018:107).

Contemporary education in Scotland.

Whilst religious institutions throughout Scottish history have guided what is suitable to learn (Inglis, 1894), learning in Scotland today remains heavily influenced and shaped by the ambitions and situation of the current governance of the Scottish Nationalist Party (SNP). The Standards in Scotland's Schools Act of 2000 builds on The Education (Scotland) Act of 1980 in setting the scene of a government view that children's learning is most appropriate as school education (Gillies, 2018), however, the act provides additional recognition of the role that families can play in learning.

Both legislations mean that whilst school education is preferred, acknowledgement of the rights of parents mean that they do not have to sign

their child up to school but are expected to provide the child with an education that meets expectations outlined within “Guidance on Home Education” (Scottish Government, 2008:3). Parents who choose to home school children must do so in agreement with the local education authority who are legally responsible for monitoring of educational provision.

Education of children is grounded in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child articles 12 and 28 (UNCRC, 1991) which highlight a child’s right to education and the opportunity to have their views heard in relation to matters relating to them. Interestingly guidance is not grounded in curriculum content followed by schools but provides a more general scope that educational provision should ensure:

Development of the personality, talents and mental and physical abilities of the child or young person to their fullest potential... to prepare the children for life in a modern civilised society...and enable them to achieve their full potential...[and] that education is suitable if it primarily equips a child for life within the community of which he is a member, rather than the way of life in the wider country as a whole, as long as it does not foreclose the child’s options in later years to adopt some other form of life if he wishes to do so. (Scottish Government, 2008:6).

The Scottish government aims to promote opportunities for all through educational provision. However, Gillies (2018) stresses that as a minority government the SNP party are in constant defence of political decisions particularly around education. A key area for political criticism has been educational attainment which Gillies (2018:110) argues “should be shared with all who have gone before” as differences in attainment amongst Scottish school pupils has been a historical issue. It may be useful to consider this historical legacy in terms of the persistent difficulty in building partnerships with families. However, in their bid to improve areas that other political parties have criticised and also failed to improve, such as educational attainment, Gillies claims that the current SNP government have developed educational policies that have

lacked thorough consideration and consultation with all relevant stakeholders (Gillies, 2018). An example of limited consultation for political decisions began with a National Debate on Scottish education in 2002 (Munn et al 2004) which provided opportunities for public input and information for a governmental review group to formulate the principles and plan of a new 'Curriculum for Excellence' (Scottish Executive, 2004) providing guidance for the education of children from 3-18. The resulting review lacked input from teachers and practitioners who would be implementing the plan. The review also lacked further consultation with the general public that what had been planned was suitable or representative of the previous concerns gained within the debate in 2002 (Gillies, 2018). Priestley and Hume, warn that "a reform programme which fails to take account of antecedents, or learn the lessons of the past, runs the risk of promoting innovation without real change" (Priestley and Humes, 2010:358). The result has been a Scottish educational curriculum depicted by Priestley and Hume in 2010 as broken and unacceptable and described by Gillies (2018,2019) as maintaining a chequered progress since 2004.

Whilst we could explore the developments made within the Curriculum for Excellence since, the following directs focus back to the nature of this thesis on what children and families require to thrive and of how Scotland's education system aims to provide that. Biesta (2006) notes that "the job of the curriculum is to unlock potential, to enable human beings to come into presence" (cited in Priestley and Humes, 2010:358). The Scottish curriculum aims to unlock individual potential by promoting the acquisition of four key capacities in Scottish pupils. These capacities are for all Scottish children to be "successful learners, confident individuals, effective contributors and responsible citizens".

A difficulty with these aims is of who decides what success in learning looks like or when a student becomes a confident individual and contributes effectively and of who or what determines them to be a responsible citizen. Judgement of what is a valuable characteristic to have learned is identified as a key factor for human development of self-value or from Bourdieu's theoretical standpoint, 'habitus' (Bourdieu, 1990). Donaldson notes, that negative learning encounters exist from experiences that teach us that we must possess certain skills to be valued more as an individual. She suggests that inflicting judgement on others breaks down self-esteem. The following quote whilst directed at motivations for children's learning may also be relevant to motivations for learning amongst adults and families "If we do not genuinely respect and value children, I am afraid they will come to know" (Donaldson, 1987:114).

Achievement within each of the four capacities of the curriculum for excellence, is confirmed by experiences and outcomes when the learner can fulfil the many "I have...." and "I can...." statements created within the curriculum (Scottish Executive 2006a:12). However, Priestley and Hume (2010) suggest that whilst the use of 'I' presents a view of the learner as the key focus, it is not representative of pupils and therefore fulfilment of learning experiences is subjective. Attainment and non-attainment of these aims remains, like learning in Scottish education, a condition measured by governing institutions and of the perception of success held by the teacher.

Realising the Ambition with Early Education as a motivation for action.

The UK EPPE study (Sylva et al, 2004) has provided guidance and rationale for the development of Early Education and Childcare (ELCC) in Scotland as a means of enhancing the lives of children and families by ensuring success in

preparing them for future education. The Scottish Executive added to the findings of the EPPE study in establishing what is required to care for children in early education with ‘A National Review of the Early years workforce’ in 2007. The review outlined an aim to ensure provision of funded flexible childcare services that would enhance “children’s development, learning and behaviour” (Scottish Executive, 2007:1) through collaboration of services and practitioners who are academically qualified as ‘professional’ support services to meet the range of needs of children and families.

The original Standard for Childhood Practice (QAA, 2007) specified knowledge, skills and values whilst presenting a framework of requirements expected to be promoted by those managing and leading childcare services. ‘Making the Difference’ (Education Scotland, 2012) reported on how qualifications had impacted positively on the development of children and highlighted effective qualities as; collaboration across ‘professional’ services, knowledge and understanding of approaches to support children and how they learn best, leadership and continual skills development across teams, reflection, and self-evaluation. The Standard for Childhood Practice has since been revised to align with developments in Scottish legislation and policy (SSSC, 2015).

Meanwhile, Wingrave and McMahon (2016:713) discuss ‘professionalisation’ and qualifications framework created as an aim to improve support in childcare services in Scotland. Consideration is made of the traditional understandings of ‘professional’ roles in line with how ‘professional’ practice is viewed in terms of childcare. Citing the work of Helsby (1996) they outline that a professional is distinguished by expert knowledge and skills that set them apart from those who have less capabilities. In this respect, it is useful to consider the focus on education (as schooling) is often also driven by practitioners to gain the status that teachers traditionally receive. Care seems to be something which does not

require high levels of professionalism or qualifications and therefore leads to little status. If status is desired, practitioners may feel a requirement to provide more than what parents might be able to - hence a strong focus on literacy and numeracy and educational attainment and a rationale for ‘professionalisation’ of the childcare workforce. A key concern is of how the drive for professionalisation, and status affects ability to build relationships with families.

Wingrave and McMahon (2016) outline the concerns raised amongst practitioners; that the focus on educational attainment overshadowed the importance of care as a precursor for children’s ability to learn. These points raise further consideration of how actions within Scottish education to enhance support services may be, albeit unintentionally, perpetuating power and hierarchy amongst service workers, other organisations, and families. The concerns raised by participants within the research conducted by Wingrave and McMahon (2016) raise questioning around the motivations and promotion of preparing children in educational ability for literacy and numeracy in their early years. Further questioning is raised of how educational focus fulfils or affects the innate needs of children who require loving care as a foundation for learning (Deacon, 2010; Learning and teaching Scotland, 2010; Page, 2011, 2018; Malcolm, 2022).

As noted previously, supporting families and children was also to be gained through one of three key policies of social reform in 2008. ‘The Early Years Framework’ (Scottish Government, 2008a) aimed to address the effects of poverty and disadvantage through ten elements of transformational change. These elements aimed to address; fragmentation of service and lack of value of the contribution that parents, families, and communities can make in achieving better outcomes for children. The description of the lack of value placed on the

contribution that parents and families make is interesting when considering preceding legislation and policies.

Nevertheless, an aim to empower and build a culture of family and community learning is identified in breaking the cycles of poor outcomes resulting from poverty. Important aspects of how the elements of transformational change will be achieved are; improving skills and knowledge through education across parents and practitioners, a renewed focus on building relationships and collaborations across agencies and between practitioners and families, recognition of the importance of play for children's learning with provision of appropriate space, environments and resources that allow learning through play and finally a focus on the pre-natal and post-natal support provided for families. Guidance was provided in the latter area within 'Pre-Birth to Three' (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010) and 'Joining the Dots' (Deacon, 2011). As mentioned previously in this thesis, both are two of the few policies referring specifically to the importance of 'love' for early child development and provide examples of what 'love' in early educational practice looks like. For example,

Babies look for both verbal and non-verbal messages that communicate respect, value and love. These important messages can be demonstrated by staff in many ways, such as ensuring that children are always greeted with a warm welcome upon arrival at the early years setting (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010:65)

'Joining the Dots', adds to this debate with an independent review commissioned by the Scottish Government of how we can improve the lives of Scottish people (Deacon, 2011). The review highlights that circumstances in Scottish family life can affect the ability for children to gain or feel love and this can have further impacts on children's ability to thrive. Deacon argues that whilst 'love' may be regarded by many as "fuzzy" and, we can presume by this term she echoes the arguments posed by (Page,2011,2018) and Malcolm (2022) that love in

‘professional’ roles is hard to define, she urges that ‘love’ is fundamentally important for children’s development that ‘professional’ services must ensure that children gain ‘love’ whilst in their care.

Once again, we are encouraged to consider the feasibility of the incorporation of ‘love’ within formal professional services and if this were something that families would want, if practitioners feel that they should be providing ‘love’ as a quality of support for not only children but for all ages. As human beings, the importance of ‘love’ continues through the lifespan and is needed in all interactions between children, young people, and adults. In respect of the importance of ‘love’ for everyone, Morris (2021) raises additional consideration of the challenges in being ‘loving’ with children and adults we do not know, and if ‘love’ is important in the care of children and families then we must raise the question, how do we overcome these challenges.

The aim of improving the lives of children, families and Scottish society is further bolstered by the announcement of ‘Building the Ambition’ (Scottish Government, 2014:5) “to make Scotland the best place in the world to grow up”. This ambition recognised that; learning and care in the early years of a child’s life, families, prevention, and intervention are crucial elements in how we will achieve this aim. Qualities of effective support are described as “caring and nurturing”. Further methods of addressing the effects of poverty in Scotland and to improve life chances for everyone is attempted within the ‘Raising Attainment for All’ (RAFA) programme (Scottish Government, 2014). However, it is questionable as to whether the initiative aids or perpetuates a deficit discourse of families and the contribution they make to learning. For example, the programme notes an aim to raise standards in school and reduce gaps in school achievement in providing disadvantaged children and families with help for learning.

A concern here is the premise in a discourse that encourages perceptions amongst educational staff that learning does not or cannot happen amongst less well-off families. Consideration is made that the continual use of the term ‘disadvantaged’ throughout policies and legislation promotes notions of othering where particular families are presented as lacking in capacity or ‘needy’ and therefore that more should be done for them, particularly in terms of learning. Yet, Siraj- Blatchford (2010) notes that aspirations and ambition are as prevalent in families who are less well off than others.

A specific and interesting focus on what qualities of support are required in supporting children and families in the combination of care in early years and educational attainment is presented within ‘An Independent Review of the Scottish Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) Workforce and Out of School Care (OSC) Workforce/’ (Siraj and Kingston, 2015). The review outlines thirty–one recommendations for the most effective care and support required in development of the well-being of children and families as a foundation for the development of “Scotland’s future”. There are several recommendations made for development of the childcare workforce, however, this thesis is concerned with the specific qualities of practice that are outlined as important. As such, it draws attention to recommendation eight which outlines specific skills, attributes, dispositions, and knowledge required for supporting children and families. Recommendations for effective qualities draws on the work of Howes et al (2008) who state that support services lack skills to provide emotional support. An interesting point is raised within the review in terms of the need for building relationships as “sensitive and responsive interactions”. However, the relationships being referred to, are initially between practitioners as students developing their knowledge and understanding and their tutors with explanation that these should serve as exemplars for most effective interactions in supporting children and families.

An additional point of interest is the reference to ‘professional identity’ of the childcare workforce in consideration of what is outlined as acceptable within ‘professional’ roles. The focus for professional practice is based on the development of practitioners and the status of childcare workers with the wider body of ‘professional’ services and does not outline specific qualities that are acceptable or unacceptable in professional services. Once again, it is important to consider how promotion of ‘professional’ status affects perceptions amongst those working in support of children and families in respect of what is suitable. For example, whilst ‘love’ is highlighted as an important quality for development of humans, it might be useful to know whether children, families and support workers would expect ‘love’ as a quality of professional support and what this would look like.

A variety of legislation and policies followed throughout 2016 continuing in the aim of education and collaboration of support services being the most effective way of enhancing the lives of children and families living in Scotland. The Education (Scotland) Act 2016 includes provisions for strategic planning to consider socio-economic barriers to learning and once again utilises the guidance outlined by the UNCRC in promotion that children should be able to make decisions for themselves. ‘The Children and Young People Improvement Collaborative’(CYPIC) (Scottish Government, 2016) combined aims of the Early Years Collaborative (Scottish Government, 2012c) and Raising Attainment for All (RAFA) (Scottish Government, 2014) whilst aligning with the Maternity and Children Quality Improvement Collaborative which focuses on maternity, neonatal and paediatric healthcare. The National Improvement Framework (Scottish Government, 2016), The Education Governance Review (Scottish Government, 2016), ‘Delivering Excellence and Equity in Scottish Education: A Delivery Plan for Scotland’ (Scottish Government 2016) and ‘‘Enhancing Learning and Teaching Through the use of Digital

Technology (2016) all focus on the aim of development for Scottish education in raising attainment to ensure the enhancement of the lives of Scottish children and families.

A major development within Scottish education was presented during 2017 with 'A Blueprint for 2020: The expansion of Early Learning and Childcare in Scotland' (Scottish Government, 2017). The plan set out to provide the means for more adults to access training and further education to enhance employment opportunities through the provision of longer free childcare hours. A key element of the plan is to ensure 'quality' care of young children which has driven qualifications of early learning and childcare workforce alongside an increase of early learning and childcare settings and provision. Once again, we must return to the notion of what 'qualities' are considered most effective for 'quality' childcare. Additionally, the rationale must be considered that children living in Scotland are being best served within educational establishments rather than at home with their families.

Increased employment and the effect on families raised by Perry Jenkins and Wadsworth (2017) is particularly pertinent to the current focus of the Scottish government in the expansion of funded childcare. Recent plans of the Scottish Government to expand funded childcare presents a possible meaningful change for many families living in Scotland, where increased funded childcare is proposed as a means of allowing further employment opportunities for family members (Scottish Government, 2017). Employment opportunities will present considerable changes for Scottish family life. Increased hours in alternative childcare settings in Scotland will mean that a range of 'professionals', such as, childminders and early year's practitioners will take care of children whilst more parents in Scotland can access paid employment and contribute to the economy via employment tax.

Meanwhile, Perry-Jenkins and Wadsworth (2017) note a lack of research on the impact that parental employment may have on children whilst highlighting the work of Conger & Elder (1994) who reveal connections between stress of work “family economic stress and marital distress, negative parent–child relations, and diminished child well-being”. Reflection of Bowlby’s attachment theory also includes suggestion that “remote parenting” may have negative impacts on the development of a child. For example, Taggart notes the suggestion made by Bowlby that the effects of the increase of female employment during the war affected attachment with main caregivers where trauma affected children to become “emotionally avoidant or preoccupied”. The response was to provide day care within settings that replicated the home environment (Taggart, 2016:174). However, Roseneil and Budgeon (2004) explore the notion of extending care and intimacy from out with the boundaries of what, has been traditionally, known as family. They call for decentralisation of traditional views of family with additional acknowledgement of the power which the term “family” has in its capacity to affect people both “emotionally and politically” (2004:135). Roseneil and Budgeon (2004) suggest that wider sources than family can provide intimacy and care.

These facts raise consideration of how alternative childcare will affect the notion of families alongside the development of children in how extended childcare in educational settings offer family practices (Morgan, 2011). Roseneil and Budgeon (2004) raise questioning of whether childcare services can be considered families and demonstrate the same qualities, if so, how can we ensure that is achieved. On a final note, we may consider alternative motivations for the expansion of funded childcare as a means for increasing employment which will ultimately contribute to developing the economy of Scotland.

It may be that the most recent development of ‘Realising the Ambition’ (Scottish Government, 2020) provides the answer to considerations of how quality is regarded in services working in support of children and families. The guidance specifies that quality care requires understanding of the interconnected range of factors relating children and families lives that will allow them to thrive. Continuous development of knowledge and understanding is a key requirement for all services and support workers to ensure that individual requirements of children and families are met. The following quote provides additional clarification relating to aspects of quality in highlighting that:

We often talk about the environment in terms of physical spaces, but the key part of the environment for children is the human, social environment of positive nurturing interactions ... For children, now is more important than the futures we plan for them. Rigid ideas of ‘school readiness’ or what children ‘should’ be doing, place too much emphasis on the practitioner’s concerns about the future (Carlton and Winsler, 1999). (Scottish Government, 2020:15).

The guidance also adds explanation of what quality care does not include. Quality care should not involve perceptions that, whilst poverty can affect opportunities, it does not affect ambitions of children and families. In addition, it highlights and questions the ethics and usefulness of supporting services that encourage or promote stigmatisation of children and families. Instead, it is highlighted that quality care will aid to realise ambitions through “professional caring relationships” providing “a sense of being loved and cherished” through partnerships with colleagues, children, and families. (Scottish Government, 2020:38, 32).

It is interesting to note the reference to ‘love’ within this document with consideration of whether the ‘Care Review’ (Scottish Government, 2016) has instigated new understanding of the importance of ‘love’ for human development alongside a need that it is promoted within practice guidance for support services. However, as previously suggested, whilst the Care Review conducted in 2016 highlighted the importance of ‘love’ for care experienced children, it could be

argued that a sense of feeling loved and cherished in its importance for human development is needed for all children, young people, and adults to allow all families living in Scotland to thrive.

In clarification of this point, we may assume ‘love’ in the context of “motivations for actions for the good of the other in the first instance” (Fehr et al, 2009:9) be at the heart of everything we do. Final comment is made to the next section of this thesis where partnerships and relationships are promoted as part of the aim of prevention and intervention promoted within ‘Realising the Ambition’ and much of the Scottish legislative and policy framework reviewed thus far. Partnership with families is encouraged through a programme of intervention referred to in the context of ‘Family Learning’. The following section will consider current understandings of ‘Family Learning’ in Scottish education and how these understandings contribute to achieving social justice and an ability to thrive for Scottish children and families.

‘Family Learning’ as motivation for action in Scotland.

The concluding section of the chapter continues in examining political and institutional influence on families living in Scotland and learning. The section will consider the historical and ongoing aim to enhance the lives of all children and families living in Scotland. Specific focus for the thesis of what humans require to thrive and flourish will provide the context of consideration and of how support within Scottish education, as a key institutional influence on the lives of Scottish children and families, fulfils that need. Before we continue with exploration of this section, it is interesting and necessary to return to the introduction to the thesis and the role of the family within society.

Contemporary sociological studies promote the ideology of “families” as a collective role in developing society and encouragement of “communities of

practice”, rather than family as a stand -alone institution with individual responsibility. The premise of this ideology is interesting to note in relation to development of approaches within Scottish legislation, policies and institutions charged with supporting children and families. An additional point of interest for this section is the ongoing aim and adaptation of approach to enhance the lives of Scottish children and families, yet the inability we have in achieving this aim. Scottish legislation and policy identify integration, collaboration, and partnership as key aspects of supporting children and families, however, power, hierarchy and bureaucracy across key influencing institutions and support agencies are identified as perpetuating the historical challenge.

Education and families are identified as two main influencers to improve Scottish society and the lives of Scottish children and families. Throughout the literature review ‘Compassionate Love theory’ has been applied in considering motivations for actions within Scottish politics. Application of this theory has raised questions of whether “motivations for actions are for the good of the other in the first instance” (Sprecher, Fehr and Underwood, 2009:9) or for the good of the Scottish economy to gain independence from UK rule. Additional consideration highlights that, if this is the case, qualities of childcare and family support services influenced and informed by perpetual neoliberalist market driven politics may be more damaging than good. In addressing the inability of approaches driven by economic concerns to achieve successful outcomes for all families we may consider if we are missing something more fundamental. In this vein it may be pertinent to consider whether child and family support needs to focus, at more basic levels of human requirement, as foundations for social justice and the ability to thrive and flourish.

The following section will consider developments of parental involvement, parental engagement and ‘family learning’ as methods contributing to

intervention and prevention of poor outcomes in the lives of families living in Scotland. A specific focus will be placed on the motivations and subsequent qualities of these methods in how they contribute to social justice in promotion of ‘tolerance, pluralism, inclusivity and democracy’ (Mooney and Scott, 2012:30).

History of partnership working in Scottish Education

In a consistent fashion, this section of the thesis will first consider the historic legacy that has led to ‘family learning’ as an educational approach from 1960’s to present day. The thesis will consider; the foundations of why a ‘Family Learning’ approach is required, how current ‘Family Learning’ approaches are informed and presented within Scottish education and most importantly how current ‘Family Learning’ approaches contribute to social justice in the lives of families living in Scotland and their ability to thrive.

MacKenzie (2010) highlighted that enhancement of the education of Scottish children during the 1960’s was attempted through initiatives which promoted parental involvement in school learning. Involvement of families within Scottish education forms part of the partnerships and collaborations promoted as key elements throughout legislation and policy aimed at improving the lives of children and families in Scotland. Partnership with families has been a challenge within Scottish education and is being addressed through promotion of the approach referred to as ‘Family Learning’. As we know, a central tenant of a ‘Family Learning’ approach is partnership with families in enhancing performance or “attainment” at school (Alexander and Clyne, 1995).

The Scottish ‘Alexander Report’ (Scottish Education Department, 1975) promoted community educators to work with families to increase learning

opportunities that were accessible for all families. The Warnock Report (1978) continued in the recognition of the contribution that families can make in children's educational progress in specific promotion of partnership with parents in supporting children with additional support needs. However, this work presented challenges for community educators where education 'authorities' were less than keen to fulfil the aims of the initiatives. An example of the difficulties faced is depicted in the challenges faced by Doreen Grant attempting to build partnerships between families and schools in an area of Glasgow during the 1970's.

Partnership with parents has been a long-standing issue within the Scottish education system. Doreen Grant, a former head teacher was concerned with why educational outcomes for families living in areas of poverty were often less successful than the outcomes for families from more affluent areas. In her work to address this issue, she describes a constant struggle to develop parental partnership with educational settings during the 1970's within an area of Glasgow (Grant, 1989). Grant provides an account of power and hierarchy as barriers to the aims outlined in legislation and policy when describing her frustrations in attempting to gain support from educational departments to involve families in the work of schools, she noted:

In Lewis Carroll fashion I wrote a story about some of the treatments I had learned to swallow. 'Alice in the Sweet Education Castle' it was called. In this bureaucratic stronghold the simple and naïve Alice found a variety of 'sweets' in charge. Her requests to them were, of course, full of gentle reason. Responses came sometimes from officious Smarties, at other times from Cough Drops, who felt free to cause her eyes to sting with tears. Worst of all were the Sugared Almonds; 'pastel, well-groomed, smooth and impenetrable- with no hint on the surface of the kind of nut that was inside.' The real-life system displayed a large selection of such impervious confections-boxed in by paperwork and tied with red tape! (Grant, 1989:115).

On reflection of the experience had by Doreen Grant we can consider the transparency of the motivations of the Scottish education system of its time and

those who worked within it. Reflection of this includes consideration, once again, of whether drivers for actions are genuinely for the benefit of children and families or if the educational system takes responsibility for failings that it presents in support of children and families and if any of these challenges remain today.

MacKenzie (2010) demonstrates evidence of attempts to work with families to benefit Scottish education. Partnership with families was attempted through initiatives promoting parental involvement in school learning. An example of such programmes was the 'Integrated Community Schools Initiative' (Scottish Executive, 1998) which aimed to develop parental partnership with schools by providing support for families. Family support ranged from, assistance with health issues, financial difficulties, and parenting advice.

The initiative was motivated to enhance family situations in the understanding that children's school attendance, learning opportunities in school and home would increase (MacKenzie, 2010). Commitment in promoting partnership amongst agencies and with families as a means of improving outcomes has been identified as an important aspect of Scottish Government policy as outlined earlier in this section. However, we will specifically focus on how and why partnership with families and 'family learning' has been developed in Scotland and will continue to review specific legislation, policy, and initiatives in line with these aspects.

The Parental Involvement (Scotland) Act (2006) provided a legislative attempt to continue promotion of partnership between parents, families, and the education system. However, partnership from this legislation was limited to the formation of school parent councils that attracted a narrow range of parents and often did not extend to early educational establishments. With the minimal

success that it had, the legislation is described by MacKenzie as, “a lost opportunity” (MacKenzie, 2010:2). A review of the impact of the Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act (2006) was conducted after ten years in 2016 and presented thirty-eight recommendations. The review, whilst identifying some progress, seemed to support the argument made by MacKenzie (2010) that schools have missed opportunities to develop genuine partnerships with parents.

Advice given within the review also suggests that practice needed to include attitudinal change (The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016). Considering attitudes within educational provision as a barrier to building partnerships and raising attainment for all is not new. Cassidy (2018) notes, that although the Primary Education Scotland document the ‘Memorandum’ (Scottish Education Department, 1965) encouraged curriculum learning to include a variety of experiences, teachers were accused of limiting the activities that children needed, arguing that it was “teacher attitudes” that were affecting children’s learning (Cassidy, 2018:37). In consideration that attitudinal change is still being identified as a barrier for partnership working and learning, it is useful to consider how attitudes are influenced.

The recommendations made by the National Parent Forum may highlight and add to some of the issues that exist within the Scottish education system regarding the formation of partnership with parents and Scottish schools. For example, particular reference is made to one of the main questions being posed within the review which asks, “To what extent are parents informed by and involved with their school and engaged in their child’s learning?” The review continues to highlight within the summary that, “parental involvement in its widest sense, such as the engagement of parents with their children in day-to-day activities, and the resultant impact on children’s learning, was not considered” (The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016:20), as such, it may

be that school learning is most valued in this instance. To disregard or lack value of the contribution that families make to learning in other ways may affect partnerships to be formed.

An additional consideration is made of the discourse used in recommendation thirty-seven of the review of the impact of the Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act (2006). Advice to schools, notes that “they should provide information for learning and help to broaden understanding amongst parents of what learning can do now and for the future” (The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016: 66). It may be considered that the remarks made within the review once again position family abilities within a deficit model, where it suggests that certain educational skills are missing. Yet, the ‘Review of Family Learning Supporting Excellence and Equity’ conducted by the Scottish Government (2016b:8) as an additional method of promoting partnership working, notes that parents are children’s first and ongoing educators. The suggestion that families’ need shown about learning is therefore contradictory. We may also consider that to suggest that families need to be shown what learning is and what learning can do for the future, encourages aspects of power. Additionally, we may question if the assumption that school learning is more effective than any other learning gained out with school creates; a perpetuation of hierarchy, particularly in terms of learning, and therefore results in barriers to partnership. Hierarchy of what learning is most valued may also affect the ability to thrive where development of ‘habitus’, ‘capital’ and subsequent access to the ‘field’ is limited therefore affecting fulfilment of social justice.

In specific plans for Scottish education, advice has been drawn from the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) which will be incorporated alongside the information gained from the Educational Governance Review (Scottish Government, 2017) and the National Parent

Forum's review of the Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006 (The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016). Each of these sources, site plans for learning in Scottish education amidst European economic influence with additional understanding that families of Scotland will play key roles in these plans. The following section explores the review and promotion of 'Family Learning' and specifically considers how Scottish education views family, learning and of whether motivations for actions are "for the good of the other in the first instance" or for the development of Scottish economy and more specifically, of what qualities are considered important for these actions (Fehr et al, 2009:9).

'Family Learning in Scotland'

There has been little research around the topic of 'family learning' in Scotland. This has provided an ideal opportunity to explore the topic further in direct consideration of the unique position of Scottish society. In addition, the range of literature that is available has provided the impetus for exploring the topic from the specific context of what qualities of practice ensure that 'family learning' is effective for, not only, families living in Scotland but to set a precedence for what an effective model of 'family learning' could or should include.

The work of Doreen Grant, outlined earlier, has provided some critical questioning over whether; educational establishments genuinely want to work with families. if those working within educational settings believe families can contribute to the learning process or more specifically can contribute to the work of the school. Grant suggested that limited attainment in school may be because preconceived notions of ability existed amongst education staff when she noted "the best predictor of children's achievement is their name and address" (Grant, 1989: xi). Jeannie MacKenzie (2010:7) supported the work of

Grant in describing ‘family learning’ as everyday activities of families. In the first instance, MacKenzie states that ‘family learning’ requires “at least one adult and one child in an action which creates learning” (2010:7). She continued in noting that children and family should instigate what ‘family learning’ requires. Grant (1989) provided inspiration for the understandings that MacKenzie (2010) holds about ‘family learning’ and of what MacKenzie believes that family learning needs. Both Grant and MacKenzie stipulate that family learning should recognise; “that parents are educators, that language is powerful, and that education should be a dialogue” (Grant, 1989; MacKenzie, 2010:9). From this view, a key aspect for ‘family learning’ is communication. As such, MacKenzie urges that families must be involved in the design of any programme that claims to promote ‘family learning’.

The Growing up in Scotland study (GUS) (Scottish Executive, 2011b) claimed that children whose parents have lower levels of qualifications generally do less well in school than those from homes where parents have high levels of qualifications (Scottish Government, 2016b:10). The study highlighted specifically, that low levels of adult literacy affect children’s vocabulary development and problem-solving abilities. Furthermore, GUS (2011) emphasised that low levels of literacy may be one factor which has negative impacts on formal learning. The study notes that to address these negative impacts, families need experiences to develop knowledge and understanding of how to access opportunities within formal education (Scottish Executive, 2011b:128). The findings from GUS study may be influential in developing perceptions amongst agencies working to support children and families. Assumptions may be made on ability based on socio economic status of families. The evidence presented with the GUS study has also been cited within ‘The Review of Family Learning’ completed by the Scottish Government (2016b).

The ‘Review of Family Learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b) aimed to add to the promotion of partnership with families as a means of enhancing educational attainment and the Scottish economy. The review cites the research completed by NIACE, (2013) emphasising that ‘family learning’ programmes should sit within a “wealth model” where programmes build upon existing skills and knowledge (Scottish Government, 2016b:10; Education Scotland, 2018). Nutbrown et al (2015) add to this notion in stressing that it is unsuitable to regard ‘family learning’ as a programme which focuses on shortfalls or as a way to fix them.

An additional key observation of the ‘Review of Family Learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b) is that “key stakeholders” referred to are educational staff and not parents, families, or children. The review also notes that it lacked consultation with families and calls for further research that fulfils this lack of communication. Additionally, it is noted, that content of programmes should be “relevant”, but fails to explain to whom this relevance would apply and of what it might be (Scottish government, 2016b:5). These facts raise questioning of how we can claim the term ‘family learning’ if key stakeholders do not include families. Equally, a lack of consultation presents consideration that we do not really know what ‘family learning’ means for families living in Scotland and therefore of what families feel that ‘family learning’ needs. We may also question how a lack of dialogue or consideration of families as key stakeholders in ‘family learning’ demonstrates the values of ‘tolerance, pluralism, inclusivity and democracy’ and ultimately of social justice.

Promotion of working with families is continued within the national action plan on parental involvement and parental engagement in children’s (school) learning, ‘Family learning and learning at home 2018-2021’ (Scottish Government, 2018). The action plan details how partnership with parents for learning will happen. Unfortunately, the word learning refers mainly to learning

that happens in school with little reference made to the value of learning which happens within the home. Improvement plans discuss how schools can get parents to engage in their children's (school) learning. Freedman (2022) highlights that the Scottish plan created provision of link workers similar to that of the parent support advisors initiated in England by the Labour government during the late 1990's.

Engagement and involvement of parents in children's education are key components of a 'family learning' approach in Scotland. However, whilst both are detailed as important, it is highlighted that involvement and engagement are two different things with The National Parent Forum of Scotland (2016:14) calling for clear consistent definition. Goodall and Montgomery (2014:399) suggest that involvement positions families assisting in education establishments which progresses to engagement, where parents develop relationship between themselves and their children's learning. Deforges and Abouchaar (2003) indicate that parental involvement can have the largest impact when encouragement and interest are present between parents and children. Meanwhile, discourse presented within policy and practice guidance may promote perceptions that parents are not already involved and engaged in their child's learning in or out with school. It may be useful to consider how suggestions that parents are not involved or engaged in learning aid or hinder partnerships whilst undermining any policy statements that present appreciation of the contribution that families make in the learning process, once again suggesting "false generosity" (Freire, 1972:18).

It is also noted that family interactions with the education sector may require support (Scottish Government, 2016b). However, it may be equally useful to question if it is important that educational staff are involved and engaged with learning in families. Additionally, it may be important to consider what support

is required to ensure involvement and engagement of staff working in Scottish education with learning in families is effective in contributing to successful outcomes for all. Would engagement of educational staff in learning out with the setting be beneficial for a ‘family learning’ approach to build genuine partnerships and more specifically of what qualities engagement and involvement with learning in families would require. Reasons for hesitance of interaction may be complex, and further consideration may present some of the possible reasons. It may also be useful for research to identify issues around lack of parental involvement and engagement with school settings.

Education Scotland (2018) provides further guidance for a ‘family learning’ approach and highlights some key elements of the benefits of ‘family learning’, who can provide ‘family learning’ initiatives and what should be considered. The focus for ‘family learning’ is situated again within educational learning for children, young people and adults and is identified as helping to close the educational attainment gap and to encourage adults to gain skills that will assist them in gaining further learning, training, and employment. Meanwhile, a positive value of learning at home is acknowledged in the rationale behind ‘family learning’ initiatives as providing a “bridge between informal home learning and formal school learning” (Education Scotland, 2018:8).

Encouragement is made for ‘family learning’ to be also included in Early Learning and Childcare (ELCC) settings, schools, colleges, community learning and development, and projects of voluntary organisations. Further guidance is given that initiatives should be based on a range of considerations that is reflective of the aspects related to influences on family life. Considerations should include collaboration of other agencies and services who help to support learning for children and families. Services are listed as, libraries, museums, community education, health, drug, and alcohol services.

However, guidance notes that planning of initiatives should draw upon data and evidence that demonstrates what works and on information gained from strengths of families and of what they require. Yet, UK research has noted difficulty in knowing exactly what works best due to a lack of studies with robust research designs to produce reliable findings. Lack of consultation with families living in Scotland may also pose gaps in knowing what works best for them. In addition, the useful data is described as local neighbourhood statistics which may highlight support required, for example, the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD), statistics on attainment, achievement, and attendance at school (Scottish Government, 2023). Meanwhile, it is important to consider the use of SIMD as an indicator of support needed where we can question alongside Clelland and Hill (2019) the reliability of statistics as a demonstration of what families require. Use of SIMD may promote assumptions or perceptions of ability undermining the previous guidance from Blackstone (1967) and Siraj-Blatchford (2010) that social class or qualifications of parents should not be used as indicators of ability.

‘Family learning’ continues as the way of how Scotland is now “Realising the Ambition of making Scotland the best place in the world to grow up” (Education Scotland, 2020:9). The view of ‘family learning’ in contributing to this aim is still considered as partnership working with educational institutions as an approach that aims to improve life for children and families by providing planned programmes [or initiatives] that target educational attainment suggested as the way in which family life will be improved.

More recent research conducted by Tett and MacLeod (2020) has presented an interesting contribution to the questioning and debate on ‘family learning’ practice in Scotland. Retrospective research here includes one to one interviews with head teachers, family learning link workers and parents who participated in delivery of ‘family learning’ ten years previously in one city in Scotland. The

study highlighted how specific approaches benefitted or hindered genuine partnership working. Tett and Macleod raise a critical point relating to the motivations for action in that Scottish policy has a combined focus on closing the educational attainment gap alongside improvement of parenting skills (Education Scotland, 2016:4). Both aspects of policy focus identify deficits that may be seen as relating only to the abilities of children and families and not our educational system and all that entails. Before some of the key findings from this research study are explored, it may be useful to also consider the following point.

As noted in international and UK research, literacy amongst ‘family’ members is identified as the key to education and development of a country’s economy (UNESCO, 2015:7). The Scottish Government (2016a) noted that an estimated quarter of adults in Scotland may experience literacy difficulties. This fact may provide some explanation of why some parents do not become involved with schools as Nutbrown et al. (2015) highlight that ‘families’ may be viewed negatively, particularly when successful learning is gauged within the context of performance amidst formal learning curricula programmes. Considering learning within outcomes which are curriculum based may site ‘families’ as deficient in their ability to provide success in learning. Whilst there may be many causes of difficulties in literacy, it is interesting that most of these adults have experience within Scottish and other education systems. Therefore, it may be worth considering if school experience has contributed to learning difficulties. Consideration of these areas may provide an alternative viewpoint which identifies other areas for improvement rather than family difficulties being seen as something which; they or their family are solely to be blamed for and something which is continually seen as a problem which relates only to the family.

The study may have also identified answers as to why partnership with families may remain a challenge within certain educational establishments in Scotland. The work of Tett and Macleod has highlighted, once again, that attitudes toward working with families held by educational staff create key challenges in building partnerships for learning (The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016, Cassidy, 2018, Tett and MacLeod, 2020). The study highlighted varying attitudes of head teachers to working with families for the enhancement of learning noting the impact of these attitudes on partnerships. The research also noted the key role that ‘family learning’ link workers had in aiding the “bridge between informal home learning and formal school learning” as noted previously as the purpose of ‘family learning’ by Education Scotland (2018:8). The bridge is described by Tett and Macleod as “home school partnerships” (HSP’s). Tett and Macleod’s work notes that for ‘family learning’ to be a bridge between learning at home and school there needs to be, for now, someone who ‘mediates’ the differing attitudes of individuals positioned on either side of the bridge. (Tett and MacLeod, 2020:454) The need for this mediation is interesting in consideration that partnership with families is a legal responsibility of Scottish schools (Scottish Executive, 2006) and yet we are reminded of Jeannie McKenzie’s view that it was a “lost opportunity” (MacKenzie, 2010:2).

An additional interesting point arising for the research of Tett and Macleod is that the work has highlighted continuing power dynamics in the space between learning at home and school (2020:453). They demonstrate key stakeholders in the tripartite partnership as head teachers, family learning workers and parents. Interestingly the stakeholders in this partnership did not include teachers as they argue that the opportunity for genuine partnership working lies in the attitudes of the head teachers in working with families. The study draws on the differing power dynamics and conceptualisation of partnership working as either nominal, traditional or authentic as outlined by Auerbach (2010).

Professional skill and expertise for learning.

Tett and Macleod's work remind us of the point raised by Whyte and Karabon (2014) in their research exploring 'funds of knowledge' where understanding of power is held by both educational staff and families of who has expertise for learning. Whilst this recent Scottish study highlights variation amongst schools with some excellent examples of how partnerships are enhanced, they note that assumption of expertise as 'professionals' is recognised in causing barriers to working in partnership, raising additional questioning of where educational staff and families gain this viewpoint from.

A key and interesting aspect of power dynamics related to partnership working was of how each stakeholder perceive their role (Tett and Macleod, 2020: 452). For example, it is worth noting the current responsibility of Scottish educational establishments and staff to produce improvements in educational attainment (Scottish Government, 2014). Understanding of this role and the pressure of the expectation may encourage specific agenda's motivated only in ways that are believed to guarantee the desired 'successful outcome'. Successful outcomes of raising attainment we presume will validate the role of any head teacher, teacher, 'family learning' link worker, practitioner or setting. Power in this regard is positioned within government aims and objectives. However, once again we return to the perception of how educational staff perceive successful outcomes as attainment and of how it can be achieved within the expected time span. In line with the focus of 'human flourishing' for his thesis we may again consider the impact of this aim on those who are seen not able to contribute.

For example, Auerbach (2010) highlights the view of teachers as experts that give knowledge to families. This is also key in relation to how cultural diversity and socio-economic status amongst families is viewed or can be supported to perform as required. In that vein, it may also be useful to consider the understandings held by parents of their role in supporting their child, of what

they see as important and of how that is achieved. In terms of who has power of what is most important for ‘human flourishing’ and how it is achieved or if power in that decision can be shared, may be important for partnerships to be built.

Meanwhile, Tett and MacLeod claim that distribution of power in the learning process is needed for partnerships to be formed between educational staff and families. Recognising the valuable contribution that families make is noted as key. However, they present different contexts for this recognition to be built and of how ‘family learning’ workers have developed specific skills and approaches that help to navigate this aspect. Building recognition of the contribution to learning that families make is needed in the perceptions held by both families and headteachers. When recognition is achieved and valued by both, more “authentic” partnerships are gained. The benefits of such partnerships are outlined by one of the head teachers involved in the study. He notes that results in educational attainment “went through the roof”. (Tett and MacLeod, 2020:458).

An additional point of interest to this study is the qualities outlined by ‘family learning’ workers as essential for positive partnership working. Participants in this study highlighted the benefits of *knowing the community*. This point was reminiscent of the work of Doreen Grant (1989) where her initial action in supporting families living in Govan was motivated by *caring* and getting to *understand* the needs of the community and of how they contribute to the work of the school. This study, some thirty-one years later, has also highlighted similarities to the challenges faced by Grant where mediation between families and schools is a requirement to; encourage schools to see the positive contribution that families make to learning, to “demystify information” where technical jargon is used amongst professional services and to develop awareness in families that they contribute to learning in positive ways. Tett and Macleod

echo the work of Marandet and Wainright (2017) in noting the *support* and *friendships* developed between ‘family learning’ link workers and families. They build on the idea of ‘family learning’ and ‘bridging’ where bridging is considered as a way of sharing power more evenly. Families are *empowered* by the value placed in the contribution they make to learning thus creating positive recognition and confidence to approach and work with schools. We can relate this practice with Bourdieu’s theory of how ‘habitus and ‘capital’ can be gained and how these contribute to the process of partnership working. The findings also note that effective partnerships are enhanced through *shared respect, goals and recognition* that we all have a contribution to make (Tett and MacLeod, 2020:452).

Mediation between schools and families included ‘family learning’ link workers planning family social events to help build relationships between school staff and families. Other approaches included home visits to get to know families and sharing this knowledge with teachers who gained a wider perspective of why families may not have ‘performed’ as expected. Some link workers discussed how they helped families conform to school expectations whilst others-built confidence in families to challenge the requests or demands made by schools where they were unrealistic or meaningless to the family.

In addition, findings noted specific elements raised by families as not conducive to being respected or for building the desire to work in partnership. These were when interactions with school staff included reliving previous bad school experiences, being talked down to or spoken to like a child, held little regard for any skills that the parents had, ignoring parents knowledge of their child, using language that was difficult to understand, seemed to be motivated by ‘ticking boxes’ relating to the work of the school, were rushed with little time or interest to discuss matters fully. A participant in the study also noted that “Teachers also had to be educated to understand that ‘a child’s attainment and wellbeing is not

only about cognitive abilities' but also about the affective domain". (Tett and MacLeod, 2020:460). This point relates to many of the points raised in the literature review, most strikingly to families either succumbing to expectations or retreating to their own 'private sphere' (Cooper, 1971:290) Training focussed on expertise rather than the importance of affection for learning and how we can achieve this in 'professional' roles (Hargreaves et al, 2017:2).

In contrast the following were noted as the ways that effective partnerships were gained. Participants in the Tett and MacLeod (2020) study highlighted that informal approaches were welcomed where families could talk freely with educational staff, where respect was given of the skills families held with encouragement to share, where there was a genuine interest in getting to know families and in understanding the needs of the families and individual children, where programmes were created and informed from these needs; where they were listened to and supported. Tett and MacLeod related to this type of partnership as a "parent-based curriculum" (2020:462)

On reflection of the findings from this study we can see that the specific role of 'family learning' link workers may have been beneficial in some cases where they could mediate between families and schools. The role seems to have provided dedicated time to build the 'bridge' between learning at home and at school, time others such as, headteachers, teachers or practitioners, may not have. However, the role is identified as emotionally labour intensive and challenging in light of the differing perceptions held across school staff and families. This prompts consideration of the impact on individuals who assumed these roles and also what training is required to ensure consistency across the sector where skills, qualities and actions for effective 'family learning' link work is integral within 'professional' role of all educational staff.

'Family Learning' as programmes for learning.

'Family Learning' considered as an intervention and prevention approach is presented in a variety of initiatives across agencies supporting Scottish children and families. For example, online parental guidance is provided via; 'Parentzone' and programmes with Early Learning and Childcare settings and schools, such as 'Stay and Play', 'Book bug', 'Read Write Count' bags, Parents as Early Education Partners (PEEP) and The Peep Learning Together Programme which provides parents with an opportunity to gain a recognised qualification from attending the various courses, Families And Education Together (FAST) and Save the Children's 'Families Connect' programme. The main aim of these 'family learning' programmes is once again to enhance children's academic abilities and therefore performance within school whilst also to enhance parenting capabilities or encouraging parents to pursue further education and employment. It may be important to note that the aims of these 'family learning' programmes continue in addressing the deficient contributions that *children and families* make to government aims and objectives.

Meanwhile, recent research adds to the findings presented by Tett and MacLeod study in 2020 by demonstrating what is required in practice for effective 'family learning'. Research evaluating the impact of the Families Connect programme conducted by Rennie et al (2021) provides an interesting insight into the 'qualities' of the programme and the impact it has on learning for children in their early years of life. 'Qualities' involved in this programme ensure that families are "welcomed, supported, provided with unconditional positive regard, considered equal partners, valued in recognition of the knowledge, experience and skills that they have" (Rennie et al, 2021:3).

In comparison to discourse used within Scottish policy and practice guidance relating to 'family learning' there appears a subtle difference in the language being presented within these programmes. It may be useful to consider if this

also makes a difference to the success of ‘family learning’. The aim of ‘Families Connect’ is similar to other ‘family learning’ programmes in developing children’s skills in literacy, numeracy, social and emotional skills in preparation for learning at school by encouraging parental engagement, skills and knowledge of how to support children learning in their early years. Evaluation of the programme found that parental engagement with their children’s learning improved with children’s social and emotional development being enhanced. Benefits also highlighted improved relationships between parents and their children and schools with parents which is noted to require a commitment to the values or ‘qualities’ of ‘Families Connect’ outlined previously.

However, there was a lack of evidence that the programme had any impact on numeracy and vocabulary abilities of young children with a probable reason cited, that parents explained they felt it more important to concentrate on their child’s social and emotional development as a priority. Continuing developments of the programme include a commitment to future research that “listen and respond to what children and parents are telling us” (Rennie et al, 2021:9). In the context of this thesis, this is an interesting finding and highlights questioning of whether parents' views are listened to well enough and used to inform ‘family learning’. This provides a fitting link for the rationale of research that fulfils the gap in knowledge and understanding of what ‘family learning’ means to families, practitioners and teachers living and working in Scotland. The research aims to gain understanding of what ‘qualities’ are required to support children and families effectively to be able to develop ‘habitus and capital’ required for access to the ‘field’ or the ability for “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4). For example, in reference to Bourdieu’s theory that specific ‘habitus’ accumulates ‘capital’ to access the field (Bourdieu, 1990, 1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017) we might consider how these are affected within Scottish education. Perceptions of ability based on; the area that

children and families live, social class, or level of parental education may promote a self-fulfilling prophecy amongst individuals with support that aids or hinders development of the required 'habitus and ultimately social justice for all.

2.4 Summary of Literature Review

The literature review began in explaining that the thesis was drawing upon socio-constructionist theory (Burr, 1995, Elder-Vass, 2012) and the recognition that individual development is influenced by the society in which one lives whilst society is influenced by the development of its people. The review of literature has highlighted that government, religion, education and families have power of influence over learning. Promotion of 'human capital' and economic development (OECD, 2001, Carpentieri, 2012) across the globe has influenced political aims within the UK and Scotland. Education was recognised as a way of developing 'human capital' (Becker, 1993). Deforges and Abouchaar (2003) and highlighted that governments across the world understood that, increasing educational attainment and later successful outcomes in life, needed partnership with families. International research identified that 'family learning' as an educational approach has derived from a need to develop a countries economic situation through promotion of lifelong learning, literacy and education of its citizens. (Vaccarino et al,2006). Poor levels of these are recognised as originating in families with plans to improve lifelong learning, literacy and educational attainment addressing improvement of the attitudes that families have in continuing learning throughout their lifetime. Encouragement is also made for families to work in partnership with educational services in a bid to enhance skills in literacy, numeracy and language. Partnership working is seen as educational initiatives claiming to enhance the skills of families. However,

research completed by Brooks et al, (2006) highlights narrow views of literacy and most valued learning as only that which happens in educational institutions. Meanwhile, Biesta (2008) noted that learning positions of individuals are affected by narrow views of learning and can impact on development of identity and agency. As a result, Biesta, (2008) encourages appreciation of the multiple literacies that exist within everyday lives of families and encourages opportunities for stories to be shared. Brooks et al (2008:36) cite the work of Robinson Plant in adding that when literacy is grounded in “local realities and is dialogical in method” disadvantaged groups can gain empowerment from gaining opportunities for their stories to be acknowledged and heard. Research has highlighted that ‘family learning’ approaches within the United Kingdom have been influenced from practice in the United States with many studies highlighting the benefits that families gain from participation in ‘family learning’ programmes. Meanwhile, whilst many studies highlight benefits gained from ‘family learning’ programmes, the research studies are considered poor in design with findings described as subjective and lacking validity (Deforges and Aboucher, 2003, Cara and Brooks, 2012. Freedman, 2022).

The review of literature identified that Scottish education aims to support children and families living in Scotland to be able to thrive and gain social justice where values of “tolerance, pluralism, inclusivity and democracy” are key (Mooney and Scott, 2012:30; Scottish Government, 2016a). The review also highlighted a Scottish government aim to achieve social justice through redress of factors contributing to poverty amongst families living in Scotland by improving the economy, education, and employment (Scottish Executive, 2000; Scottish Government, 2016b). Improvement in these areas are attempted in part through ‘family learning’ programmes. Meanwhile, the review of literature demonstrates limited research in Scotland alongside alternative views of ‘family learning’ as normal family activities (MacKenzie, 2010) or simply as a way of

learning (Cara and Brooks, 2012). The ‘Review of Family Learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b) also lacked consultation with families living in Scotland. Collectively these factors demonstrate that a narrow view of ‘family learning’ may also be creating barriers for partnership working where the contributions of families in the learning process are not acknowledged or valued.

In regard that ‘family learning’ is considered a method of improving the lives of families, Pierre Bourdieu’s theories of habitus, field, and capital (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017) were useful in considering the specific elements identified to aid human flourishing whilst also encouraging consideration of who and what influences the qualities required to thrive in Scottish society in the twenty-first century. ‘Compassionate Love Theory’ developed by Fehr et al (2009) was also key in consideration of what is required for human flourishing and helped to identify that motivations for actions in supporting children and families are not consistently “for the good of the other” (Fehr et al, 2009:9).

A lack of research on the subject of ‘family learning’ in Scotland has resulted in limited perceptions of; what ‘family learning’ is, where it happens and what it requires. The development and use of the term ‘family learning’ in Scottish education echoes the point made by Smart (2011) of the interrelationships between individual personality, culture, society, and power in the process of gaining an ability to thrive in life. Freire’s theory of how power and hierarchy create barriers to dialogue was useful in exploring why there are persistent challenges in Scottish education to develop genuine partnerships with families.

Literature has also highlighted that ‘love’ is an important element to allow learning and development (UNICEF, 1990; hooks, 2000; Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2010; Deacon, 2011; Lanias and Zembylas, 2015, Scottish Government, 2016; Winston and Chicot, 2016; Cousins, 2017; Page, 2011, 2018; Scottish Government, 2020; Malcolm, 2022; Zeedyk, 2022) yet the use

of the term 'love' is found to be challenging within policy (Lanas and Zembylas, 2015) and 'professional' supporting roles and has had limited focus as an important element for discussion within training or practice for those working to support families (Page, 2011, 2018; Taggart, 2016; Morris, 2021; Malcolm, 2022).

The interplay between love and power presented within the literature, as crucial elements in which families can flourish or not, were interesting as key contexts in which 'family learning' seems to be couched within. The study aims to explore whether understandings of 'family learning' may highlight the concept as more than an educational approach or early intervention and to establish the qualities that make 'family learning' most effective for "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:4). The review of literature presents an opportunity to address the gap in research and limited input from families living in Scotland on the subject of 'family learning' with an aim to contribute to understanding and development of support for Scottish children and families. The research is also interested in the persistent difficulty in developing partnership with parents that exists within Scottish educational services alongside the persistence of poor outcomes and questions if we are missing specific fundamental 'qualities' that are important for 'family learning'. The following chapter provides the aims and objectives for this study based on the review of literature. The chapter also includes details of the theoretical framework that guides and informs the design for this research study.

3 Research Design.

The research design chapter outlines how the review of literature has highlighted specific aims and questions for the study alongside the theoretical framework that has been identified as useful in considering this topic for the study.

The chapter begins in outlining the methodology that explains how theory and review of previous research has guided the research methods used. Based on review of previous research studies, the section explains why a hermeneutic phenomenological approach and related methods, such as, focus groups and one to one interviews, were most suitable. This section also includes considerations of validity and reliability of the methods used.

Additional explanation on ethical considerations of participant identification, selection, and access is summarised next, such as, how, and why the study plans to include families, educational practitioners and third sector family workers. with additional information outlining the ethical consideration made.

Finally, the last section provides clarification on the final research design that was fit for purpose in responding to research aims and questions

3.1 Developing Aims and Research questions.

A purpose for research provides the basis on which the study can flourish. Once a purpose is established in the literature review, development of research questions leads the specific context in which the design of the study will be positioned (Wahyuni, 2012). However, Alvesson and Sandberg highlight “that a research question typically needs to be supplemented with a detailed and precise statement of purpose” (2012:16). This section provides a summary of the background of this research and resulting statement of research purpose, aims and objectives.

Background for study

Limited literature, dialogue, and research on the topic of ‘family learning’ in Scotland has presented a gap in knowledge and understanding of what ‘family learning’ means to families living in Scotland and therefore what they feel is important for ‘family learning’ (Mackenzie, 2010, Scottish Government, 2016). Yet, practice guidance for services working to support children and families living in Scotland highlights the importance of partnership with families (Scottish Government, 2016b) and for family learning programmes to include “strengths, needs, and interests of families” (Scottish Government, 2018:7). Meanwhile, partnership with families in Scottish education has been a persistent challenge (MacKenzie, 2010, The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016). The lack of discussion negates the importance of dialogue needed for partnership with families to understand what they require (Grant, 1989; Mackenzie, 2010) whilst Freire suggests hierarchy and power are the barriers that result in limited dialogue and genuine partnership (Freire, 1972: 62).

Research conducted by Cara and Brooks (2012:9) identifies a lack of research that; includes the views of parents and children, explores the benefits of learning gained from both informal and formal learning highlighting that the “so-called ‘softer’ benefits have generally received less attention and were very often side-lined”. Whilst literature identifies key elements for development of families and learning, these are described as secure relationships, understanding, attention, time, and love (UNICEF, 1990; Deacon, 2011; Page, 2011; Gerdhardt. 2015; Winston and Chicot, 2016; Page, 2018; Malcolm, 2022; Zeedyk,2022).

Current plans in Scotland to increase childcare in educational settings as a means for families to gain opportunities for further training and employment (Scottish Government, 2020) However, subject expertise and content knowledge are favoured for ‘professional’ services which rarely include exploration of the importance of a caring, compassionate loving pedagogy (Zembylas, 2007; Lanas and Zembylas 2015; Taggart, 2016; White & Karabon, 2016; Cousins, 2017; Hargreaves et al, 2017; Page, 2018; Malcolm, 2022) is coupled with an expectation raised by Page (2011) that parents want their children to feel loved by professionals who take care of them. All the above points provide an impetus for further research that will contribute to knowledge on the subject of ‘family learning’ in Scotland in achieving the following aim and answers to the key research questions.

Aim for the study:

This study aimed to examine whether the present promotion of a ‘family learning’ approach in Scottish schools lacks appreciation of what ‘family learning’ means for all families living in Scotland. The study specifically aims to establish what families regard as important factors of ‘family learning’ and whether they believe

that these factors should be an aspect of professional ‘family learning’ practice. Whilst this study will address the gap in knowledge around the subject of ‘family learning’ in Scotland it is also supports Holloway (2014:380) in acknowledging that “questions about the bio-logical, social and physic are emerging which have the potential to inform fruitful future debate in geographies of children, youth, and families”.

Summary of overall research aim:

This study aims to identify excellent ‘family learning’ practice and develop recommendations for better practice to promote positive relationships between educational establishments and families.

Objectives:

1. To gain understanding of how ‘family learning’ is defined by families and practitioners.
2. To understand how families learn together.
3. To identify why families, learn together.
4. To explore what key aspects are important for ‘family learning’.
5. To understand why these key aspects are important for ‘family learning’.

Research questions:

- What does the term family learning mean?
- Where does family learning happen?
- What is important for family learning?

3.2 Development of the theoretical framework

The literature review has provided the gap in knowledge for this study. ‘Family learning’ is defined in various ways, however, most definitions identify an aim of ‘family learning’ to enhance life for all (Buffton, 1999; Haggart, 2000; OFSTED, 2009; MacKenzie, 2010; Cara and Brook, 2012; National Institute for Adult Continuing Education (NIACE), 2013); Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014; Scottish Government, 2016b; Education Scotland, 2018). ‘Family learning’ is currently considered in Scotland as a method to achieve government aims of social justice and the enhancement of life for all children and families living in

Scotland (Mooney and Scott, 2012:30; Scottish Government, 2016a). ‘Family learning’ as an educational approach in Scotland seeks to enhance life through acquisition of specific learning and skills. However, limited research and consultation with all families living in Scotland presents a gap in knowledge of what ‘family learning’ means to all families, of what they feel is important (MacKenzie, 2010; Scottish Government, 2016b).

The research study is interested in considering the ‘*why of the action*’ (Underwood, 2009) through exploration of the motivations and actions involved for ‘family learning’ practice within the two distinct institutions of Scottish education and families living in Scotland. In the first instance, the study seeks to explore the motivations and actions of ‘family learning’ practice in educational establishments. Secondly, the study seeks to investigate the motivations and actions of ‘family learning’ amongst families living in Scotland as outlined in literature as family practices.

As this study is concerned with *why and how* ‘family learning’ practice is promoted, Bourdieu’s theories of ‘habitus, capital and field’ (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017) are identified as providing theoretical positioning for considering why ‘family learning’ exists alongside exploration of how it is best achieved. This section will explain how these theories have contributed to the design for this study. The section explains why Bourdieu’s theories of habitus, capital and field are useful to conceptualise how ‘family learning’ is understood as a way to enhance life.

3.2.1 Considering Bourdieu’s theory of habitus, field, and capital

Pierre Bourdieu’s habitus, capital, and field theories (Maggio, 2017) were identified as useful aspects in which to explore and question *why* families and

educational settings engaged in ‘family learning’. Webb, Schirato and Danaher (2002) noted Bourdieu’s explanation that his theories are,

tools which are only made visible through the results they yield.... the ground for these tools... lies in research, in the practical, problems and puzzles encountered and generated in the effort to construct a phenomenally diverse set of objects in such a way that they can be treated, thought of comparatively (Bourdieu 1993:47).

Bourdieu’s explanation was particularly apt for this study as ‘family learning’ is being explored from the two areas of families living in Scotland and Scottish education.

Considering the notion of ‘habitus’ in the context of ‘family learning’.

Points raised by Carpentieri (2012) relating to the rationale behind ‘family learning’ in building cultural capital amongst families where “parents provide their children with cultural capital primarily by transmitting the attitudes and knowledge needed to succeed in the educational system” were interesting for this thesis. Succession with the educational system is identified as important when they note the impact of negative experiences in affecting our understanding of what we can achieve. They highlight how negative educational experiences having affected adults in their sense of “self-efficacy”. They related this view to the theory of ‘habitus presented by (Bourdieu, 1990), which resonates with the subjective social constructionist ideologies which families or social groups make (Szeman, 2011).

‘Habitus’, described in the context of this study of individuals and groups existing within wider society, provides the group or individual with “a feel for the game” (Earle, 1999:185). It is the idea that individuals or groups develop in which they situate their existence, their purpose, of what they can or cannot do, should or should not do. Development of ‘habitus’ is influenced by the people, environment, experiences, and history which the individual or group encounters. Habitus is the attitudes and practices which connect individuals together. It allows communication and identification between the group, individuals and by others. Bourdieu states “habitus as an infinite capacity for generating product-thoughts, perceptions, expressions and actions-whose limits are set by historically and socially situated conditions of its production” (Bourdieu, 1990:55).

This study considers how ‘family learning’ is viewed and operates amongst families and educational institutions, such as school. As such, it was important that the history and cultures of all families living in Scotland were considered. This consideration initiated an interest of; how ‘habitus’ is created and held within each group, of the purpose which ‘habitus’ may have, of whether differences in ‘habitus exist amongst individuals and of how these differences may impact on family learning and its aim.

Considering Bourdieu’s notions of ‘capital’ for family learning.

If ‘habitus provides the individual with “a feel for the game” (Earle, 1999, p185) there would need to be an arena in which the game would be played. Bourdieu’s (1993) ‘field’ theory considers society in which individuals exist as a ‘field’ of play, wherein as players, they participate. Like any game there are

rules, influences and unknown factors that will develop because of many distinct aspects. The 'field' is the common ground on which the play occurs.

Boundaries are also made by the most powerful influences over the 'field' of play. The players are assigned roles and expectations of these roles are held by both player and the person, institution or group who controls the game.

Influence and power are established within the 'field' of play through the 'capital' (Bourdieu, 1993) which each player contributes. 'Capital' operates as a currency that may be social, cultural, political, symbolic, or economic depending on the context in which the 'field' of play is viewed (Mutch, 2013). Szeman and Kaposy (2011:81) echo the notion that 'capital' may be material or human attributes which provides access to the 'field' when describing 'capital' as

Accumulated labour (in its materialised form or it's incorporated embodied form) which when appropriated on a private i.e. exclusive basis by agents or groups of agents, enables them to appropriate social energy in the form of reified or living labour (Szeman and Kaposy, 2011:81).

Considering emotional capital in the context of 'family learning'.

A particular interest for this study is Bourdieu's notion of emotional capital. Zembylas (2013 p.444) outlines that "emotional capital as situated in Bourdieu's work provides a rich account of how emotions-as-resources are circulated, accumulated and exchanged for other forms of capital". Zembylas (2007) observe examples of research by Barbalet (1998), Lupton (1998) and Reddy (2001) which have contributed to show that we all as social beings' experience emotions culturally and socially. As a result, they highlight that "interpersonal communication is managed not merely expressed in conformity with collective social norms" (Zembylas, 2007:444). From this example,

Zembylas is describing that whilst emotions are a natural recognised form of social capital they are often controlled within certain social experiences.

Considering the notion of 'field' for 'family learning'.

Mutch (2013) used Bourdieu's field theory during research of curriculum development. She considered field theory when exploring the opinions and notions that curriculum developers used during the construction for curriculum plans. Mutch, considered the political and social influences that affected the process in which the curriculum developers were involved. The process in which Mutch applied Bourdieu's field theory positioned the curriculum development as the 'field'. In consideration that 'family learning' is considered as an approach situated within Scottish education and is related to a plan or 'curriculum' for learning, it is useful to view family learning as the 'field' of study for this research. Considering 'family learning' as the 'field' presents an interesting focus for the study in terms of Bourdieu's description that the

structure of the field is a state of power relations among the agents or institutions engaged in the struggle, or, to put it another way, a state of the distribution of the specific capital which has been accumulated in the course of the previous struggles and which orients subsequent strategies (Bourdieu, 1993:73).

The application of Bourdieu's 'field' theory made by Mutch (2013) has encouraged questioning of who establishes the 'field' of 'family learning'. What external and internal forces affected the 'field'. In addition, thinking of 'family learning' as the 'field' also highlighted that, 'family learning' may be described as two distinct 'fields' within my study. One 'field' explores how 'family learning' was considered amongst families living in Scotland. The other 'field' considers how Scottish education viewed 'family learning'.

Mutch (2013) also considered, who was allowed access to the ‘field’, which principles held most value and why, what ‘capital’ did each member contribute to the field and what external and internal influences were there. Additionally, it was relevant to consider similar research considerations to that. For example, reflecting upon different ‘fields’ of ‘family learning’ was recognised as useful for this study. The notion of ‘field’ and ‘capital’ encouraged thinking around how ‘capital’ was recognised and valued within each ‘field’ of ‘family learning’, who was allowed access or excluded to the ‘field’ and why. In addition, this thinking encouraged exploration of why this may be and of the impact it may have on the ability for “human flourishing” (Fehr et al, 2009:9).

Mutch (2013) identifies that ‘field’ theory has been criticised for being too functionalist (Boham, 1999). As ‘field’ theory assigns roles to each individual or organisation it is criticised for lacking reference to personalities or unique originalities. Additionally, Mutch notes Butler (1999) in criticising ‘field’ theory for not recognising opportunities for social transformation. However, the topic and design of this study demonstrates an attempt to reduce any claims made that ‘field’ theory is individualistic and is therefore unsuitable for qualitative research. The research design aims to gain understanding of viewpoints from different individuals and groups on family learning. The design seeks to gain the individual perceptions of participants and leaves the consideration of the ‘field’ to be wide ranging within the context of the individual and to ‘family learning’. The ‘field’ may be considered as any opportunity in which an individual may find experience for learning, for example, family, family learning, community, society, or school. ‘Field’ theory has been used to consider the foundations in which groups and individual lives exist whilst also considering the complex affects experienced from both micro and macro social platforms.

The following table provides the considerations made when considering the theoretical framework in which to position the study. See Table 2 for details of how key interests arising from review of literature link to theory and create a theoretical framework in which to consider ‘family learning’.

Table 2: Development of theoretical framework.

Initial research interests	Key points arising from literature review.	Key points arising from literature review Freire’s (1972) theory of dialogue	Key points arising from literature review Compassionate love theory (Fehr et al:2009)	Fit with socio-constructionism	Fit with Bourdieu’s theory of ‘habitus, capital and field’
Exploration of how ‘family learning’ is viewed in literature	Family learning is an approach in education.	Freire calls for consideration of the impact on individuals and the social world of perceptions held or promoted that knowledge held by one person or institution is more important/valued than the other.	Fehr et al highlight the need for understanding what is important to families in a bid to provide what they require.	Key institutions within the social world influence learning. Key institutions are government, religion, education and families.	Development of skills in empowering people may help to develop ‘habitus of self and of community. However, perception of humans as capital may affect ‘habitus’ If ‘habitus’ is limited, participation in ‘family learning’ may be affected. Requires a specific approach/perspective to mediate. Family learning can be means of acquiring capital which will aid access to the field.
To consider the aim of ‘family learning’	To develop ‘human capital’ to contribute to production and economy.	Hierarchy and power affect ability to have dialogue and therefore the ability to build	A degree of emotional engagement, as appropriate, emphasises the enhancement	Each institution is influenced and influences the other. Power dynamics affect who or what gains most influence and opportunities to thrive.	Bourdieu also highlights the impact that hierarchy and the ‘capital’ it values affect ‘habitus of individual and the social world and therefore access to

		genuine partnership.	of human flourishing.		the 'field' affecting justice for all.
What is important for 'family learning'.	Needs and promotes partnership and dialogue with families. Yet review of 'family learning' and research identify a lack of consultation with families.	Freire's theory highlights the need for specific qualities for dialogue for partnership and calls for awareness and address of any factors promoting hierarchy and power. E.g. Men who lack humility (or have lost it) cannot come to people, cannot be partners in naming the world" (Freire, 1972: 63).	Attitudes and actions related to giving of self for the good of the other... a self-giving caring love that values the other highly and has the intention of giving full life to the other [and] also promotes actions that lessen any delusions of superiority (Underwood 2009:4,7).	What is needed depends on what is valued by the influencing/ most powerful institution.	Broadening view of 'capital' and what is most valuable allows opportunity to flourish for all.

Development of the theoretical framework helped to identify that knowledge as 'family learning' was socially situated and ever changing in accordance with societal and individual differences, as such the theoretical framework presented the epistemological and ontological positioning for this study.

3.3 Developing the research design.

Methodology differs to the descriptions of the methods as practical steps used in research. As such, methodology provides theoretical foundations for research design (Wahyuni, 2012). This section adds to the theoretical framework in providing the ontological and epistemological positioning that the study

assumes and how these have influenced the design of research methodology and methods.

3.3.1 Asserting a socio-constructionist ontology.

The study is concerned with how we gain knowledge and understanding of ‘family learning’. Specifically, the study aims to explore how the Scottish education system and families living in Scotland make sense of what ‘family learning’ means, where it happens and why it is important. The review of literature has helped to understand how and why these two distinct institutions contribute shared knowledge about ‘family learning’. The literature helped to understand how we collectively form perceptions, communicate and practice ‘family learning’. Additionally, the review of literature helped to understand how particular constructions and practice of ‘family learning’ influences, families living in Scotland, practitioners and teachers working within the Scottish education system and thus, wider Scottish society.

Considering knowledge in transference within family, education and society presented a specific interest for this study in how groups share and understand knowledge. As Burr (1995) suggests, we construct knowledge with and amongst others a variety of aspects, such as, history and culture situate and affect social constructions of knowledge. Constructions of knowledge were also shown in the literature review as complex and grounded in social and cultural experiences of learners (Dewey, 1938; Grant, 1989; Brassett Grundy, 2002; Vaccarino et al, 2007; OFSTED, 2009; MacKenzie, 2010; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Carpentieri, 2012; Schmidt, 2012; Holloway, 2014; Wainwright and Mardet, 2017; Elkjaer, 2018; Illeris, 2018).

The literature review examined the practice of ‘family learning’ with studies on family suggesting that family practice includes affective qualities (Williams,

2004) with Fehr et al (2009) noting that love is an important aspect of human development, yet incorporation of ‘love’ was identified as challenging in relation to ‘professional’ roles (Page, 2011, 2018; Taggart, 2016; Malcolm, 2022). This meant that a socio-constructionist ontological position was required for this research to explore the concept further and the difficulties of ‘love’ being incorporated into professional learning practices.

Considering knowledge as being constructed by individuals within their life experiences relates to the notion that “knowledge is the result of an individual subject’s constructive activity” (Glaserfeld, 1990:37). This viewpoint considers how the individual gains knowledge within the concept of socio-constructivism. However, this research study specifically focuses on how we gain knowledge within family, education, and society. Therefore, a socio-constructionist ontology as supported by Elder-Vass (2012) is a more suitable presentation of my ontological position.

3.3.2 Asserting an interpretive epistemological position.

The review of literature has presented that there can be no “one single truth” as we construct knowledge within a variety of contexts (Wahyuni, 2012:71). History, culture, and individual perceptions affect knowledge. Reality is understood to be equally, socially constructed yet a unique experience for everyone with constructions of reality being dependent on experiences (Elder-Vass, 2012). As researcher understandings may differ to that of any other person, perceptions of knowledge gained within this study will be subjective. As such, an interpretive epistemology guides the design for this study. As an interpretive epistemology guides the study, the research design acknowledges researcher positionality and influence in the process whilst additionally attempts to minimise the effects of this throughout the various stages of the study. For

example, a key element of the methods will include collaboration with participants in clarifying interpretations made by the researcher.

3.3.3 Considering the most suitable research approach.

McNeill and Chapman (2005:18) add, “if we are to explain some event in the social world, our explanations have to take account what the people involved feel and think about it”. They elaborated that to show just what has caused something was not enough and called for researchers to find out why people thought the way they did about specific phenomena. Whilst Vaccarino et al (2007) add that to achieve any change, research requires participation of those whose lives will be affected by the subject. Braun and Clarke (2017) add that research should not only ask individuals the question about what they feel about a particular phenomenon but ask, as researchers that we consider the wider social and political influences that affect why individuals feel what they do about specific matters.

Meanwhile, Denzin and Lincoln (2018: xii) call for critical social science research embedded within a feminist analytical pedagogy which connects the individual to the community and presents “hope with no guarantees”. They continue to advise that as researchers “we must renew our efforts to honour the voices of those who have been silenced by dominant paradigms” which relates to the limited consultation with families within the ‘Review of Family Learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b) and other research studies (Cara and Brooks, 2012) to inform ‘family learning’ approaches. Denzin and Lincoln (2018) also highlight the need for collaborative practice that respects all participants involved in the process.

3.3.4 Considering a quantitative method.

Previous research studies exploring the benefits of ‘family learning’ programmes have identified a lack of research that has assumed a quantitative approach and produced statistics of the wider benefits of these programmes, for example benefits to families that were not the targeted objective of the programme (Cara and Brooks, 2012; Freedman, 2022). They highlight that policy and funding streams value quantitative research data to understand the contribution that ‘family learning’ programmes are making to aims for economic development.

However, Carpentieri (2012) cites points raised by Falk (2001) that political motives often hold a narrow focus of capital alongside limited understanding of the nature and complexity that ‘family learning’ presents. The complexity of ‘family learning’ presents a difficulty in being able to gain reliable statistics that are applicable in all contexts. Nutbrown et al (2015) also stipulate that ‘family learning’ programmes should be informed by what families require. Limited knowledge and understanding of what ‘family learning’ means to all families living in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2016b) presents a need to gain essential information on what families living in Scotland feel is important to be gained from ‘family learning’ before we can plan programmes and evaluate benefits in a statistical manner and that are also meaningful for families.

3.3.5 Considering a qualitative method.

Wahyuni, (2012) suggests that a researcher who employs a qualitative research methodology begins with an interest in the social world and develops a research question. The question leads the researcher to establish the ontological and

epistemological position. This positioning informs the decision of which research methods are suitable to employ (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

Qualitative research can deliver the aspects highlighted by Denzin and Lincoln, (2018) through a design that employs a variety of methods for data collection, and which encourages expression and recording of views that will influence change. Whilst adding that qualitative research methods afford a flexibility that present a “resistance against attempts to impose a single, umbrella like paradigm over the entire project” (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018: xv).

Vaccarino et al (2007) note the need for research to include people that the topic relates to in providing effective information for future practice. An example of this can be gained from the research conducted by Brasset-Grundy (2002) where participants provided rich information on what they felt about ‘family learning’ programmes that they had attended. Detailed information was gained through focus group discussions and one to one interviews. The lack of dialogue with families and the evidence gained from other qualitative studies, demonstrated the relevance of this approach for this study. However, qualitative research presents various considerations for the design of methods used which are detailed in the following sections.

Difficulties with reliability and validity of qualitative research methods

Qualitative research is criticised by quantitative researchers for its inability to be consistently reliable or valid. Concerns raise questions regarding replicability of qualitative research whilst also questioning whether it realistically reflects the subject of study (Wahyuni, 2012:77). Meanwhile, Denzin and Lincoln (2018:5) explain that concerns over research validity and reliability, exist because of cultures of “audit accountability” that prevail within universities governed by neo liberal values. Braun and Clarke (2017) suggest that responsibilities to

examine and inspect for validity and reliability are difficult in social research and can limit the processes accepted within qualitative research. They urge researchers to push the boundaries for qualitative research by including research methods that include aspects that portray daily lived experiences. Whilst Silverman (1983) suggests that interpretative methods “provide us with our only access to another’s reality” (1983:17).

However, Bryman (2016:44) notes that standards for assessing research conducted via qualitative methods require alternative forms. For example, he notes Guba and Lincoln’s (1985) development of four principles for measurement of validity and reliability in qualitative research. Firstly, “credibility” examines the internal aspects of the research process. In this stage, triangulation of data collection, methods and evaluation assesses the validity of the research findings. The design for this study includes methods that are informed by the review of literature and the principles outlined in related theory whilst including methods that confirm understanding alongside a thorough repetitive analysis of the data to ensure findings that are an accurate representation of what participants stated. As qualitative studies are difficult to replicate, Guba and Lincoln suggest a second principle in the measure of “transferability”. However, they do suggest that “transferability” is more applicable to quantitative studies.

Meanwhile, Guba and Lincoln (1985) advise that qualitative research methods include rich descriptions of setting, environment, and participants to allow possible transfer of methods for further studies to compare with other settings. Thirdly, the measure of “dependability” in which the study sits, records the variations that exist or happen throughout the process whilst also providing the questions or tools used throughout the study. As such, the design for this study has incorporated that detailed description of these elements will be included. In

interpretation “there can be no guarantees that different people will share the same meanings” (Holloway et al, 2008:299). However, Guba and Lincoln’s fourth principle for qualitative research suggests “confirmability” which provides the means in which we can attempt to confirm that the findings are true reflections of what participants have said or meant by including research methods that involve participants in validation of researcher interpretation during focus group discussions and one to one interviews.

The importance of reflexivity in qualitative studies

Braun and Clarke (2017) stress the importance of reflexivity within research. They highlight the importance of recognising that the researcher is an individual within the process. Reflection by researchers is an essential element of a qualitative research study as it provides an opportunity to consider their own influences on the study.

For example, Watts and Petrov (2000) suggest that we question if our positionality affects the relationship we have with participants and if so in what way. Whilst Flick (2007) and Clarke and Hoggitt (2009) highlight the importance of reflection at the beginning of the study to ask ourselves; why we have an interest in the topic, what investment do we have in the study and does the investment we have influence how we conduct the research or the outcomes. In reflection of these issues, they state, as researchers, we will increase our understanding of social constructions and reinstate the conscious and unconsciousness within research processes that are often lost.

Meanwhile, Pillow (2003 p.177) notes that “to reflect is to look back over what has been done so as to extract the net meanings which are the capital stock of intelligent dealing with further experiences. It is the heart of intellectual

organisation and of the disciplined mind” (Dewey, 1938). Pillow (2003) concerned with the possibility that as researchers we can focus too much on our own positions, continues in highlighting the importance of reflexive practice. Pillow (2003) reminds us that we should not only be concerned with our own individual reflections but also include collective reflexivity by considering the findings with participants involved in the study. She further explains the importance of doing research “with” participants as opposed to “on” them (2003 p.179). As such, the design of the study will include opportunities where discussions will provide reflection with participants on the aspects raised.

Awareness of Interpretation and subjectivity in qualitative research.

The nature of qualitative research makes it impossible for the researcher to be completely objective. As an individual, the researcher brings to the process their own assumptions and thoughts about the topic. I believed it was important to limit any biases present in my own positionality and was keen to establish relevant methods (Chan et al. 2013). Thoughts and beliefs held by the researcher influence interpretations of what others say and how they act. An interpretive viewpoint recognises the researcher as an individual who has made assumptions based on the social experiences that he or she may have had in their own lives. Assumptions and experiences becoming entangled and affect understandings of data (Wahyuni, 2012 p.71). Therefore, Dwyer and Buckle (2009 p.59) stress the importance of the researcher being aware of his or her own biases which have developed from his or her own experiences. These points provide an awareness and theoretical standpoint that aligns with the ontological, epistemological positionality for this study.

Considering the impact of Positionality in qualitative research.

As noted in the introduction for this thesis, my interest in this topic began with my own reflections of what ‘family learning’ had meant for me. I was aware of how passionate I felt about my understanding of the topic as the experiences gained in my own personal life and of how specific characteristics of ‘family learning’ were either beneficial or not for me and those within my family. My understanding of ‘family learning’ sat in contrast to how the topic was presented in literature which was both surprising and interesting to me. The most surprising element was that ‘family learning’ was a term that had been claimed by influential institutions and was being used in a way that bore little resemblance or reference to the characteristics I believed to have been important in allowing me to thrive in life. As a result of my positionality, I was keen to limit any impact of biases that I may have. In my review of literature, I purposively aimed to identify a range of differing perspectives and consider these with a critical but open view. I was also keen to identify methods and design a range of research questions that would allow participants to answer freely and be open to the various perspectives that they may have. I was particularly keen to ensure that my positionality would not affect analysis of the data and was keen to minimise any influence it may have. My plan was to find qualitative methods that would alleviate these concerns.

3.3.6 Considering an ethnographic approach

Ethnographic research sits within anthropology, as it requires the researcher to immerse themselves within the field of study. Evans-Pritchard, Radcliffe Brown and Malinowski were early twentieth century researchers “who determined the only way of understanding the way of life of people was to go and live amongst

them for an extended period of time” (McNeill and Chapman,2005:3). During this time, participant observation and interviews provide opportunities to collect data. Ethnographic research is a process that allows the researcher to gain an understanding of the lived lives of the participants. However, ethnography does not involve the researcher making or suggesting any changes (Glesne, 1989). Ethnography presents a situation to gain rich data. Meanwhile, Glesne notes the difficulty that researcher familiarisation with participants can have on research findings where “friendship appears to bias data selection and to decrease objectivity” (1989 p.45). As such, initial concerns of how positionality might influence data, highlighted an ethnographic approach as presenting further challenges where participants might feel obliged to answer in particular ways from building relationships with me. Therefore, it was identified that ethnographic methods may add to the complexities in trying to establish a true reflection of what families thought about family learning, as such, it was decided that an ethnographic approach was not suitable.

3.3.7 Considering a phenomenological approach

The design for the study was to not only fulfil calls for research that includes participants who are involved in ‘family learning’ to gain their viewpoints (Vaccarino, 2007; Cara and Brooks, 2012) but to also provide methods which recognise research positionality as a consideration whilst providing ways that minimise any influence it may have on data. Bentz and Shapiro (1998) also note that the researcher must permit data to emerge naturally promoting a suggestion of phenomenology as a useful research approach in this regard. Phenomenology was unfamiliar to me and raised a keen interest to learn more about this method whilst considering its suitability for this study.

Phenomenological philosophy was a central tenet of the ‘Chicago school’ of sociology that developed new ways of thinking around sociological research. McNeill and Chapman (2005 p.19) highlight that philosopher George Mead supported the views of sociologist Max Weber by noting that if “we want to explain social actions; we have first to understand them in the way that the participants do”. I found that this provided a link with my socio-constructionist ontology Berger and Luckmann (1967) and the aim for the study where participant viewpoints of ‘family learning’ will explain how their social interactions create their reality.

Phenomenological research, founded by Chicago school scholar Edmund Husserl and developed by Alfred Schutz, provides a method in which we can gain insights of the reality of everyday life. Groenewald (2004) notes that phenomenological researchers are intrigued to understand experiences of people in their real lives and so design studies which include individuals who have experienced the phenomena being explored. The role of the researcher is to pose the question, listen and “describe” what the participants narrate in relation to the topic (Groenewald 2004: 44). This method was seen as especially useful where it would “allow the essence [of the phenomena] to emerge” (Groenewald, 2004:47) gaining understanding of what family learning means to participants whilst establishing what aspects they felt were important for family learning to happen.

However, Chan et al (2013:1) highlights that phenomenology presents seven separate approaches of “descriptive (transcendental constitutive) phenomenology, naturalistic constitutive phenomenology, existential phenomenology, generative historicist phenomenology, genetic phenomenology, hermeneutic (interpretive) phenomenology, and realistic phenomenology”. However, most of these phenomenological approaches do not acknowledge researcher thoughts on the research topic whilst a hermeneutic

phenomenology recognises that positionality of the researcher naturally influences the data collection and analysis process whilst providing methods for collection and analysis of data that help to minimise researcher influence (Heidegger, 1962). A more detailed explanation of the development of phenomenology follows and provides the rationale for identifying hermeneutic phenomenology as a suitable approach for this study.

There are many similarities between phenomenology and hermeneutic phenomenology. Although, Lavery (2003) notes that both terms are not always used specifically within their own individual principles. Both approaches hold phenomenology or description of lived experience, as a similarity.

Developments within phenomenology now include hermeneutic aspects that has resulted in two distinct research methodological approaches (Lavery, 2003).

The following information presents the key differences between a phenomenological and hermeneutic phenomenological approach to research and as result, the specific methods that are required within gathering of data and its subsequent analysis.

Phenomenological approach.

Research studies that seek to understand phenomena through describing the lived experiences (van Manen, 1997) of participants are conducted within a phenomenological approach (Husserl, 1970). Phenomenological studies draw upon the wide-ranging factors that affect the way in which individuals live their lives and experience different phenomena. In development of his phenomenological approach, Husserl's (1970) focus departed from its original key characteristics. The original purpose of analysis within phenomenology was to provide description and understanding of being. However, Husserl replaced the original analytical purpose by scientific analysis, which formed "a quest for

certainty” (Laverty, 2003: 27). As such, an important aspect of Husserl’s phenomenological methods for analysis required the researcher to ‘bracket’ and remove any predispositions that he or she may have around the phenomena under study (Chan et al, 2013).

Hermeneutic phenomenological approach.

Martin Heidegger (1962) disagreed with Husserl in claiming that the researcher can never fully remove their views and thoughts around phenomena which they are researching or that there can ever be anything certain about human life (Laverty, 2003). Heidegger’s hermeneutic phenomenology highlights that, in the process of analysis, researcher thoughts and ideas influence the interpretations of understandings and meanings within the data. Laverty stipulates the importance that researcher positionality is “embedded and essential to interpretive process” (2003: 28). This may be fulfilled by the researcher making reflective notes after focus groups and one to one interviews or by maintaining a reflective journal throughout the research process which Morgan notes are already “a step toward data analysis” (1997:57-58). Heidegger states that it is important that these notes are included within the data analysis process as they provide a cycle of reflection (Van Manen, 1997).

Heidegger highlights that we maintain an instinctive sense of being from foundations of our history, which includes culture and traditions, time and place. Aspects that embed within us an innate sense of understanding of ‘place’ as humans in the world. However, he notes that as the world is ever changing our ‘place’ is in a constant state of flux (Laverty, 2003).

As the study aimed to gain opinions and ideas of what family learning meant for participants, acknowledgement was made that it would be difficult to remain

objective where positionality could influence the data collection and analysis process. As such, it was identified that a hermeneutic phenomenological approach (Heidegger, 1962) was as a suitable way in which this study may be conducted as the methods applied in this approach provided rich narratives (McNeill and Chapman, 2005). Additionally, a hermeneutic phenomenological approach acknowledges that it is difficult to remove the researcher completely from the process and encourages researcher reflective note taking throughout the research and during data gathering. Note taking serves several purposes; it allows opportunity for the researcher to be aware of any preconceived ideas or biases whilst providing an additional aspect for triangulation of data (Schatzman and Strauss, 1973; Miles and Huberman, 1984; Clarke and Hoggit, 2009).

In line with the theoretical framework that guides this study, a hermeneutic phenomenological approach (Heidegger, 1962) also encourages psychosocial methods within the research process. Taggart argues that psychosocial approaches “attribute significance both to feeling and to critical enquiry can fuel an ethical pedagogy which attends to both the emotional quality of relationships and also to social justice” (Taggart, 2016:175). Psychosocial methods require the researcher to listen carefully to participants. Clarke and Hoggit (2009) present advice on how to achieve the levels of listening required in suggesting that researchers adopt “affective attunement” (Brown, 2000:43) in their manner when conducting discussions with participants. This type of approach encourages the researcher to be open to the participant’s narrative. It allows the researcher to understand another viewpoint whilst providing the possibility for deeper understanding.

In comparison to ethnography, a hermeneutic phenomenological approach was also found to be more suitable to this study as the research study would not be

conducted within a setting in which the researcher would be immersed and be able to observe participants over a long period of time. Furthermore, whilst agreement is made with Clarke and Hoggit (2009) that it is useful for researchers to engage with participants in a manner which presents trust and understanding it is also acknowledged that close relationships may influence participants to answer in a particular way.

3.3.8 Ethical considerations.

Guidance for ethical considerations was gained from (BERA, 2018; SERA,2020) in establishing areas for consideration and research responsibilities. In accordance with guidance provided by Scottish Educational Research Association (SERA) and British Educational Research Association (BERA) the design of the research study was scrutinised within robust criteria as set by the ethics committee of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) and provided with authorisation to proceed. An important aspect outlined within the guidance provided by SERA and BERA is that ethical consideration should be an ongoing process throughout each step of the research process with safeguarding of all involved to be an important and continuous element. The following information provides an outline of each element of ethical considerations made for this study.

Brinkmann and Kvale (2008) provide detailed insight into the ethical consideration for research and particularly research which involves people. They remind us that it is important to consider the '*why*' of the research alongside the '*how*' of research in the methods that are used. In establishing the why, participants should know; the aim, the purpose and who, if anyone, may 'gain' or 'lose' because of the study. Questioning the *how* of research design

should include a main consideration that the study methods or outcomes do not cause any harm to anyone.

Ethical considerations for research include “informed consent, confidentiality, consequences, and the role of the researcher” (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2008:4). Additionally, they criticise that the scope of qualitative research means that it is difficult to ensure ethical approaches can be maintained within all processes. For example, Brinkmann and Kvale (2008:263) note “when we observe and talk to people, analyse what they do and say, and publish our interpretations to the larger public, we are engaged in a process with inescapable ethical aspects”.

Ethical consideration for methods used and informed consent.

The ethical consideration of “consequence” is applicable within this study where the use of focus groups presented difficulties in ensuring complete anonymity for the participants. As a result, “informed consent was included. Participant information sheets detailed; the difficulties of ensuring anonymity, limits placed, where possible, of the people who had access to data and anonymisation of participants during transcription. Guidance was gained from Brinkmann and Kvale, (2008) which encouraged all participants to be provided with an information sheet detailing the rationale for the research study and information that outlined potential risks and advantages for participants who chose to become involved. An additional verbal reminder of research purpose was provided prior to focus group and one to one interviews, with further clarification that the participants were willing to continue.

However, the fact remained that participants may still be able to identify who said what when data is written up. As an additional measure, the design also included that participant gained opportunities, throughout the research process,

to review their own data transcription that would provide a chance in which they could review, amend or withdraw their contribution at any point up until the data had been analysed. I also ensured that participants knew that they could discuss and pose questions about the research study at any point.

Confidentiality

Additional ethical considerations ensured that transcription of data included anonymisation of participant identity by replacing names by pseudonyms (Saunders et al., 2015). Measures to maintain anonymity will also ensure that location of settings will be changed within published work arising from this study.

The data collected was recorded on a password protected computer. The computer remained with myself, the researcher, in either my work or home environment and securely stored in a locked filing cabinet. Listening of the recordings was conducted by myself only. Any notes or entries in research diary used a pseudonym instead of participants real names. Notes were typed and kept on a password protected computer. When data had fulfilled its purpose within the research study, all digitally stored data was deleted and shredded if paper based. Any personal data which was been stored on my laptop has been destroyed after transcription. Personal data and consent forms were stored in a locked filing cabinet in a locked office at UWS which only I had a key for.

3.3.9 Establishing research questions for the study.

Research questions develop from a variety of sources. However, the most popular sources are society, personal experience, existing scientific literature and empirical material (Alvesson and Sandberg, 2012). The research questions for this study have developed from a variety of aspects.

Firstly, whilst ‘family learning’ is widely recognised as an approach to aid educational attainment preceding research has called for wider consultation with families to gain more detailed understanding of what ‘family learning’ means to them (Vaccarino, 2007; MacKenzie, 2010; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Scottish Government, 2016b). In agreement that to ensure family support services are effective we need to gain an understanding of what ‘family learning’ means for families in enabling them to thrive in life. The study wanted to gain understanding of what was important for ‘family learning’. Van Manen provides a good explanation of the motivation for questions in this study

To be human is concerned with meaning- to be human is to be concerned with meaning, to desire meaning is a desire to make sense of our lived experiences. Without desire there is no real motivated question” (Van Manen, 2003:79).

Secondly, the difference between how government policies and practice guidance related to ‘family learning’ to my own personal consideration of what ‘family learning’ means, provided a need for specific questions. My ongoing observations of others throughout my life experiences presented an interest of; why individuals learn, of what is useful to learn and of what supports or hinders learning.

Thirdly, review of literature demonstrated similarities to my own employment experiences within early childhood centres, family centres and schools. Observations of various attitudes to what was important in professional practice that involves children, families and ‘family learning’ noted differences amongst practitioners and teachers who supported children and families. Contrasts in practice would range from what appeared open, friendly, responsive, and relational practitioner behaviours to practice that maintained a distance between practitioners and children or their families. With some practitioners noting that

they felt as professionals, they should not display particularly personal mannerisms in their professional roles.

The following section explains how previous considerations and decision to adopt a qualitative hermeneutic phenomenological approach has informed design of research questions and methods used to gain data. As a qualitative hermeneutic phenomenological design is seen as a suitable fit for this study, guidance is drawn from the principles of this approach for design of questions. Whilst my positionality on 'family learning' believed 'love' to be an essential element I was also keen not to influence participants but rather wanted to see if participants naturally identified 'love' as something that 'family learning' required. Meanwhile, Bailey (1996) raises concern around not using the leading central question with participants that he suggests may imply deception. However, Kvale (1996) confirms that questions used in interview or focus groups are not deceptive if they are not the exact research question but rather allow participants to raise the topic if they feel it important for the answer. Additionally, Bentz and Shapiro (1998:104) highlight that it is important for the researcher to "allow the data to emerge"

A hermeneutic phenomenological approach guides the design of open questions. Clarke & Hoggit (2009) note that careful questioning provides participants the opportunity to elicit rich narratives which are freely thought and not constrained. The aim for the study was to gain "explicit insights of why" participants think the way they do about the subject not just the "what" (Morgan, 2006:123). Free association narrative method (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008) provides four principles which were used in both focus group and interviews. The first principle promotes the use of open-ended questions,

such as, ‘How was?’ Secondly, this method encourages the participant to tell their story by the researcher also posing, ‘Could you tell me about’ questions? Principle three stipulates the avoidance of ‘why’ questioning as the answer is often stereotypical. Finally, the last principle requires the researcher to listen carefully and clarify understanding with language used by participant.

Literature, experiences and observations have highlighted key areas for research. These areas are family learning, learning, family, love, power, societal and political expectations and Scottish education. These areas have formed a collection of individually complex areas that interweave within this study. It has presented a daunting yet interesting topic for research. However, collectively these areas represent the complexity of everyday life and demonstrate areas of consideration in relation to family learning.

Adler and Hanson (2012 p.132) noted that researchers often ask questions which are precise and clear, and which provide the “rigor and relevance” encouraged within research. However, they question whether researchers should be being more daring by “dedicating themselves to investigating large, messy, complex, controversial, and important societal issues” which, they suggest, present an opportunity for making a difference in society. Appendix 1 provides the Interview guide and questions to be posed during focus groups and one to one interviews. The following section provides the details of how participants were accessed alongside the methods used for data collection.

3.3.10 Methods for data collection.

The previous section has outlined the “principles” of design for this study. This section provides details as suggested by Jonker and Pennink (2010: 33) of “additional considerations, considerations which will depend on your basic attitude, the question at hand and of course the ‘overall’ methodological

approach”. Details of each method with the rationale of why they were most suitable is provided. For example, exploration of focus groups, interviews and questionnaires as appropriate methods identified final choices that aligned with my ontological, epistemological, and methodological positioning informed by theory and philosophies that guided this study.

The study aims to address the lack of dialogue with families that exists within Scottish research on the subject of ‘family learning’ (Vaccarino, 2007; Mackenzie, 2010; Cara and Brooks, 2012) and more specifically, within the ‘Review of Family Learning’ conducted by Scottish Government in 2016. Whilst Freire (1972) highlights the importance of dialogue to build relationships he notes the importance of addressing any degree of hierarchy to ensure that open dialogue can occur. Dialogue within hermeneutic phenomenological research methods provide opportunities to gain rich narratives of participants lived experiences in the social world. It provides an understanding around why participants have constructed the knowledge they hold (Wahyuni, 2012).

3.3.11 Focus Groups

Methodology informs method

Kamberelis, Dimitriadis and Welker (2017) explored the reasoning behind the way in which researchers choose to use focus groups. They apply the notion of “figured worlds” (Holland et al., 1998) to understand the different positioning in which researcher’s site themselves, for example, the methodology which informs the study. They note that the elements of ‘figured worlds’ are complex and fluid. The figured worlds which Kamberelis et al. (2017: 696) includes position four which provides distinct combinations of how the researcher perceives; “knowledge and truth”, the “position and agency “of both

participants and researcher within the research process and lastly the way in which the researcher locates “discourse and discursive practice”. Researcher positioning for this study is within ‘figured world four’ (Kamberelis et al. 2017) in which knowledge is a social construction and where language is an essential element in the transference of knowledge.

Within ‘figured world four’ the research process involves the researcher applying reflection alongside endeavours to gain full understanding of meanings presented by participants. Finally, within ‘figured world four’ the researcher would regard the voice of the participant as especially important with findings produced using dialogue. Agency of both researcher and participants is a continual focus in repeated efforts made to “marginalise effects of knowledge and power” within research and as a product of the research study. Finally, a researcher who relates to ‘figured world four’ attempts, through research to “trouble the status quo and lead to social change” (Kamberelis et al. 2017:696). Thus, in respect of the methodology for this study the configuration of figured world four as suggested by Kamberelis et al. (2017) provides further support for the method to be used. As such, I recognised that focus groups would provide the ideal primary method in gathering initial data for this study.

Practical considerations

The use of focus groups for research began around the late 1940’s, became less favourable but was rejuvenated by the work of Lazerfield and Merton who wanted to enhance research data to include why and how participants had answered or responded in a particular fashion. Focus groups provide an alternative method for data gathering, where a topic is researched with a group of individuals. “It is a method used to identify a diversity of experience and perceptions” (Hennink, 2014:13).

Group interaction is a key element of a focus group that persuades participants to talk to one another and share understandings around the research subject. It provides opportunity for gaining insight into how and why people consider the topic in the way that they do (Kitzinger 1995). This contrasts to one-to-one interview scenario where the researcher is often the main source of direction for discussion. Focus groups provide a situation where the researcher often finds himself or herself purely as the listener with minimal input other than to facilitate the discussion by providing short questions to be discussed (Hennink, 2014).

However, Fern (1982) quashed any claims which suggest focus groups are “superior” by explaining that there is “no evidence that focus groups are superior to either unmoderated (nominal) groups or individual interviews of equivalent numbers of subjects in terms of number or quality of ideas generated” (Kidd and Parshall, 2000:294). In addition, Hennink (2014) adds caution in highlighting the danger that focus groups can result in discussions veering off the subject matter and not providing data relevant to the research study. The researcher should only intervene when discussion is not within context of the study, as focus groups should ultimately position the control of the discussion with the participants. Hennink (2014) also warns against the use of focus groups to discuss individual personal experiences.

In reference to these recommendations and hermeneutic phenomenological principles, it was important to include key stages. Firstly, participants were reminded of the purpose of the research study, the questions, and how their input would be used. This included ethical assurances on how participant information would be stored with specific details on how participant anonymity was to be achieved. It also included explanation of how the focus group would

be conducted, with consent gained for audio recording and for data gathered to be included in in my doctoral thesis and in subsequent dissemination events, publications or teaching contexts.

The second stage employed hermeneutic phenomenological methods of ‘free association’ (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008) and ‘gestalt psychology’ (Wertheimer, 1944) in encouraging free discussion around the research topic, which included audio recording of discussions and researcher note taking directly after each focus group discussion. The final stage of a hermeneutic phenomenological approach was to verify interpretations where points were unclear.

Furthermore, researchers should provide an environment that allow participants to feel comfortable and safe and an environment that allows participants to express their feelings and opinions freely (Hennink, 2014). As such, a deliberate decision was made, to use settings that the participants attend on a regular basis and in which they feel comfortable, such as, workplace settings, university campus and settings where ‘family learning’ programmes were conducted. It was important to provide a comfortable environment where participants felt at ease from the offset and would help initiate natural conversation. Experience of participation in a previous research study where pictures were used to help me explain my response through a visual image indicated a useful method of achieving this. The use of visual images helped discussion between me and the researcher alongside a relaxed and natural discussion. The visual images also helped to relate to a wide range of topics. That basis encouraged exploration of literature to gain further understanding around the use of images for initiating research discussions.

Fyfe and Law (1988:2) provide a rationale for using such a visual method suggesting that "depiction, picturing and seeing are ubiquitous features of the

process by which most human beings come to know the world as it really is for them". Meanwhile, a visual inquiry tool 'My Home Life' (NHS Education for Scotland, 2012) developed by Dewar and McBride and endorsed by UWS was recognised as helping to "...open up conversations and gain more meaningful information than questioning alone" (Dewar and McBride, 2017:1378).

The kit consists of approximately seventy generic images that were displayed on a table or floor. Participants were encouraged to choose a picture, which they felt, depicted what family learning meant to them. Each participant was asked to describe his or her picture and explain how their chosen image encapsulated what family learning meant to them. The participants chose another picture that depicted what they felt is important for family learning. The participants were asked again to explain how they felt that the aspect was important for family learning. The participants were also encouraged to provide examples that demonstrate their feelings. Whilst it is difficult to remain passive during focus groups where participants looked to the researcher to guide discussion, overall, the visual images were identified as providing effective methods for gaining rich data for the study and aiding this challenge.

3.3.12 Interviews

The design for this study also included one to one interviews that provided opportunities to gain individual insights into participant thoughts around the subject of family learning (Jupp, 2006). During previous research experience of one-to-one interviews, it was observed that the interview provided an opportunity to gain detailed explanation from participants of their views on specific topics. However, there were certain issues found with the process. Awareness of the power imbalance appeared present between researcher and the participant. Whilst every attempt was made to reduce this, it became apparent

that some participants considered their answer very carefully and felt the need to confirm that they had answered correctly. Rice, (1931:561) sums up this type of interview experience in noting.

A defect of the interview for the purposes of fact finding, in scientific research is then that the questioner takes the lead. That is the subject takes a more or less passive role. Information or points of view of the highest value may not be disclosed because the direction given the interview by the questioner leads away from them. In short data obtained from an interview are as likely to embody the preconceived ideas of the interviewer as the attitudes of the subject interviewed (Hennink, 2014:4)

In design of the interview schedule for this study it was important to employ methods that would again fulfil both the aim for the study and hermeneutic phenomenological principles. As such, like focus groups, the interviews also included three key actions.

Firstly, an introduction that included details of the research study, the questions, and how participant input would be used. This included ethical assurances on how participant information would be stored with specific details on how participant anonymity was to be achieved. It also included explanation of how the interview would be conducted, with consent gained for audio recording and for data gathered to be included in in my doctoral thesis and in subsequent dissemination events, publications or teaching contexts.

The second action employed hermeneutic phenomenological methods of ‘free association’ (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008) and ‘gestalt psychology’ (Wertheimer, 1944) which involve specific interview techniques which use open-ended questions to encourage free discussion around the research topic, which included audio recording of discussions and researcher note taking directly after each interview.

The third action fulfilled aspects of a hermeneutic phenomenological approach in ensuring continual verification between researcher and participants to confirm my interpretations. This also allowed participants to make further comments and time where I could remind the participant of what would happen next (Brinkmann and Kvale, 2008).

To ensure that the participant's input remains central to discussions and also that they were encouraged to relay the aspects of their answers which they felt were important, 'free association narrative' (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008) was identified as appropriate. 'Free association narrative' is an interview method that encourages dialogue between researcher and participant. It is a method which encourages discussions around a particular topic, but which allows respondents to not feel pressured or coerced to respond in a particular way. Participants should not feel that they should be answering for a particular purpose or for what, they think, the researcher wants to hear. Participants will be encouraged to answer questions "freely and within their own meaning frame" providing the "why and not just what?" (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008:297).

Principles of 'gestalt psychology' (Max Wertheimer, 1944) assert the notion that understanding the wider aspects in which a topic is situated is more beneficial than understanding individual component parts. Holloway and Jefferson highlight that research design, guided within these gestalt principles, provides methods that can "hold data together in the mind". For example, through recall of visual memories of participants relaying their stories alongside the researcher notes made directly after the interviews (2008:307).

Four key principles which Holloway and Jefferson (2008) have created for applying 'gestalt' within interviews are to; "use open-ended not closed questions; the more open the better", for example for this study asking, "What

does family learning mean?” may encourage a short answer of “I don’t know?”. Changing the question to “Can you describe what ideas come to mind when you hear the term family learning?” encourages a wider response and free explanation of individual thoughts. Following initial questions with “Can you provide an example of a time in which that happened?” fulfilled the second principle in which participants were encouraged to “elicit stories”.

Thirdly, the avoidance of “why questions” may be perceived as a question in which the participants answer is being judged and therefore may have compelled answers which the participant thought would be better received by the researcher. Lastly, “follow up using respondents’ ordering and phrasing” where the participant’s phrases and terms were used within researcher response to encourage interviewee and interviewer connection (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008: 307).

3.3.13 Reflective memos

To aid interpretation of data, advice from Miles and Huberman (1984: 69) to write personal accounts from discussions with participants directly after focus groups and interviews was useful. Details included actions of participants, for example, what they said or did during the focus groups and interviews. Miles and Huberman stress the importance that these notes include researcher observations, thoughts and feelings. A reflective diary was useful to allow correspondence with data.

Additionally, Schatzman and Strauss (1973) suggest that note taking should focus upon three specific areas. Firstly, observational notes should provide description of factors that occur during focus group or interviews. Secondly, notes should also record methodological issues that have arisen around the methods used. Thirdly, by highlighting apparent themes or conclusions made

during discussions, adds theoretical aspects. For example, reflective notes made at this stage identified initial links or conflicts with the theoretical framework for the study. The notes made after each interview and focus group helped me to recall specific participants and their views which helped with the data analysis process.

3.3.14 Triangulation

The use of both focus groups and interviews and research reflections provided a range of data to compare, contrast providing validation and “confirmation of findings” (Arksey and Knight, 1999: 31; Groenwald, 2004). In addition, Fielding and Fielding (1986) advise that methods should serve two specific purposes. Firstly, one method should provide description and context of the discussion. As such, note taking and researcher reflections recorded this information. Secondly, Fielding and Fielding suggest that one of the methods used “illuminates the process of interaction” (1986: 34).

For this purpose, the design for this study has employed a ‘free association narrative’ (Holloway and Jefferson, 2008) approach for interviews. Free association narrative allowed participants to relay their own individual story of family learning. Individual narratives provided depth to the study through opportunity multiple realities and perspectives have been gained (Flick, 2004:178). Additionally, a hermeneutic approach encouraged detailed description were made of the environment, participants and interactions that occurred during focus groups and one to one interviews (van Manen, 1997). This also served to fulfil the call for methods that present interactive processes made by Fielding and Fielding (1986).

3.4 Identification, selection and accessing participants.

Groenwald (2004) suggests that “the phenomenon dictates the method (not vice-versa) including even the type of participants.” Hycner (1999: 56). As such, the nature of the research topic of family learning, dictated a purposive sample (Daniel, 2012) of participants that needed to have experienced the researched phenomenon. This included both, individuals who had experienced family learning within their own families, practitioners, and teachers who had been involved extensively or not within the provision of family learning in their professional roles.

Accessing some participants would include approaching gatekeepers, “those through whom entry is gained” (Groenwald, 2004:45). In line with ethical research, requests to conduct research with families, teachers and practitioners working in Early Learning and Childcare settings were made to two local authorities within the West coast of Scotland recognised as gatekeepers.

In respect that power was identified as an element of political and educational institutions within the review of literature, it was interesting on two counts where permission to conduct research was declined by one local authority on the basis that schools within the locale were too busy to be involved and secondly that ‘family learning’ was considered as something only happening in schools where request to conduct research was permission to access any service working with children and families.

However, gatekeeper approval for research was gained from the second local authority with consideration of research on ‘family learning’ access being provided to services based within educational settings. The local authority provided access to a team working to promote ‘family learning’ within the local area. The ‘family learning’ team provided contact with a ‘family learning’ support worker who worked in partnership with various schools and provided a

link to a local secondary school which was actively involved in promotion of ‘family learning’ programmes. It is interesting to note the immediate connection of ‘family learning’ as an element of educational provision made by the local authorities, however, access to the setting and services provided an invaluable source for this study.

3.4.1 Participant recruitment

Introductions to the ‘family learning’ service provided access to participants who could relate to ‘family learning’ in various contexts; as an aspect of their professional role as teachers, as ‘family learning’ support workers within Scottish educational establishments, as family members who could relate to ‘family learning’ as a programme to support them and their child and finally participants who considered family learning as something they had experienced within their own families.

Additional recruitment of research participants was gained through the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) BA Childhood Studies (BACS) degree programme. Students completing a final honours year of higher educational study in knowledge and skills for the effective support of children and families. The students had experience of working as professionals within educational and third sector establishments providing support for children and families in Scotland whilst also identifying as family members and provided a further group of relevant participants for the study.

3.4.2 Limitations of participant sample.

The following participant criteria incorporated within the recruitment process attempted to provide a variety of demographic features of age, gender, cultural

backgrounds and professions relating to this study (Flick, 2007) to provide a balanced range of opinions and views of the research subject.

Criteria for participant selection also aimed to include practitioners who had a range of skills (Arksey and Knight, 1999). For example, to gain a mix of participation between practitioners who had either a lot or little experience in implementing a 'family learning' approach in their practice. However, it was understood that it may be challenging to meet all the criteria. For example, gaining a range of participants who included a range of cultural diversity or that were male would be difficult due to lower numbers of employees within Scottish educational services that fulfil these criteria. Whilst attempts would be made to achieve all the criteria, it would be acceptable to fulfil as many as possible. A key element that was missed in enrolment of participants to the study was to gain information of cultural backgrounds and therefore exact understanding of the cultural backgrounds of all participants is unknown.

Criteria for the selection of participants also included that they had to be a member of a family. The study uses the word family in the widest sense in that, participants defined what family meant to them as this was key to the development of findings in response to my research questions. The limitations of participants involved may have presented various biases in terms of; limited perceptions of family learning from differing cultural backgrounds and views from differing aspects related to gender and age.

3.4.3 Participant profiles and description of settings.

Whilst there are limitations for the study in terms of being a true representation of diversity across Scottish society, the study has gained a wide range of experience, knowledge and understanding about the topic from the participants who kindly gave their time for this study.

Tables 3 and 4 below provide descriptions of research participant profiles alongside description of the venue and environment in which the focus groups or interviews took place. Records of the data collection process were completed in line with a hermeneutic phenomenological approach to include researcher reflections. Reflections after focus groups and interviews highlighted the difficulty and skill in applying psychosocial research methods in a bid to; build relationships and trust with participants, confirm meaning, remain impartial and encourage open dialogue. These reflections made me consider the difficulties in developing relationships with people that you do not know and therefore the role of teachers and practitioners and ELCC where this is an important characteristic of their role.

Table 3: Focus Groups: Participant profiles, environment, and initial researcher reflections.

<u>Focus group</u>	Participant Profile	Participant Pseudonyms		Description of where focus place took place
<u>f1</u>	12 secondary school teachers. Mixed gender 2 male and 10 female. All white Scottish? Age ranges from 30-55- nationality and age not confirmed.	1	Ben	Secondary school within large conference room. Table set up in circle and participants sat around table. Conducted during lunch- time with lunch was provided by school.
		2	John	
		3	Fiona	
		4	Annabelle	
		5	Victoria	
		6	Hannah	
		7	Charlotte	
		8	Elizabeth	
		9	Orla	
		10	Mia	
		11	Susannah	
		12	Lucy	
<u>F2</u>	2 parents 1 family learning worker based within community and school. All female All white Scottish?	1	June	Took place: within secondary school setting within large conference room. Table set up in circle and participants sat around table. Conducted after school lunch- time.
		2	Nicole	
		3	Mary	

	Age ranges from 25-55. Nationality and age not confirmed.			
<u>F3</u>	3 early years practitioners. Age range: 23-45. 2 white Scottish? female, 1 white male born and grew up in England but now lives and works in Scotland. Nationality and age not confirmed	1	Donna	Within a meeting room on university campus.
		2	Steven	
		3	Annie	
<u>F4</u>	4 early years practitioners 4 female age range 20-45	1	Belinda	Within a meeting room on university campus.
		2.	Angela	
		3.	Caroline	
		4.	Belinda	

Table 4: Interviews: Participant Profiles and Environment

Interview	Participant profile	Participant Pseudonyms	Description of where interview took place
I1	Also took part in FG3 Practitioner in ELCC based in Glasgow. White Age: 21	Annie	Within small private meeting room on university campus.
I2	Also took part in FG4 Practitioner in ELCC based in Glasgow. White Age: 21	Ashleigh	Within small private meeting room on university campus.
I3	Secondary school teacher Ayrshire. White Age: 40	Scarlett	Within large meeting room on school campus.
I4	Also took part in FG1 Secondary school teacher Ayrshire. White Age:30	Orla	Within large meeting room on school campus
I5	Secondary school teacher Ayrshire. White Age: 40	Anna	Within large meeting room on school campus
I6	Also took part in FG4 Practitioner in ELCC based in Ayrshire. White	Belinda	Within small private meeting room on university campus.

	Age: 40.		
I7	Also took part in FG4 Practitioner in ELCC based in Glasgow White Age: 20's.	Angela	Within small private meeting room on university campus.
I8	Also took part in FG3 Practitioner in ELCC based in Ayrshire. White Age: 20's	Steven	Within small private meeting room on university campus.

3.4.4 Summary of Research design.

Socio constructionism (Berger and Luckmann, 1966) provided the overarching ontology for research design in consideration of knowledge being developed and gained collectively amongst families, communities, and society (Burr, 1995). Whilst an epistemological interpretative positioning presented a rationale for qualitative research as it aims to explore perceptions around a specific phenomenon.

As the study aimed to gain the opinions and ideas of what family learning meant for participants as well as why they felt that way, hermeneutic phenomenological principles (Hiedegger, 1962) were identified as a suitable way in which this study could be conducted where specific approaches applied in focus groups and one to one interviews provided rich narratives (McNeill and Chapman, 2005). Principles for this research method were also applied within analysis of data to ensure rigour and validity of findings.

The gap identified within the literature review assisted in the identification of participants (Groenwald, 2004, Hycner, 1999). As the study, aims to explore the subject of family learning and include families in that exploration, the participant selection was straight forward (Daniel, 2012). Appropriate ethical considerations were applied from guidance gained within literature from the Scottish and British educational research associations (BERA, 2018; SERA, 2020). Review and authorisation for research design was gained from UWS ethics committee.

4 Findings and Analysis

4.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the context that analysis of data was positioned within. The chapter begins with a reminder of the aims and objectives of the study and proceeds with an overview of the principles of analysis as based within a hermeneutic phenomenological approach. A detailed outline of the steps taken in the analysis process and of how key themes were identified.

Aims and objectives

This study aimed to identify excellent ‘family learning’ practice and develop recommendations for better practice to promote positive relationships between educational establishments and families. The objectives in this context were:

1. To gain understanding of how ‘family learning’ is defined by families and practitioners.
2. To understand how families learn together.
3. To identify why families, learn together.
4. To explore what key aspects are important for ‘family learning’.
5. To understand why these key aspects are important for ‘family learning’.

The research questions were:

- What does the term family learning mean?
- Where does family learning happen?
- What is important for family learning?

4.2 Positioning of Findings and analysis

Analysis, within a hermeneutic phenomenological approach interprets meanings in relation to a specific phenomenon within the present world of the researcher and participants, who are creating a new history of the world they occupy, and so offer recent authentic histories of their lived experience. Analysis also includes acknowledgment of the experiences that may have influenced how participants made sense of or create meaning of the phenomenon, as it was understood in that particular time (Chan et al, 2013).

Interpretation and description of a phenomenon that has been completed in human science research is more a process of “insightful invention, discovery or disclosure-grasping and formulating a thematic understanding is not a rule bound process but a free act of seeing meaning”. The use of the word theme merely provides some “control and order” to research writing within a hermeneutical phenomenological approach (van Manen, 2007 p. 78) The word theme is used to depict the constructions of encounters. Theme headings have been used, merely to indicate or suggest key features of the phenomenon as identified by participants.

Analysis of data uncovered the structures that were at the very core of the phenomenon under study (Coffey and Atkinson, 1996). These structures were understood to function as a support on which the phenomenon was reliant. However, I was aware that lived experiences cannot be encapsulated as concrete concepts as they are affected by many changeable aspects such as the individuals involved, the specific situation of that moment, the particular actions which may have been influenced by external aspects, our understandings and meanings.

Maintaining reliability and validity in hermeneutic phenomenology.

Ensuring reliability and validity in qualitative research through ‘credibility, transferability, dependability and conformability’ are mentioned previously (Guba and Lincoln, 1999) yet, these are not able to be applied in every research project. However, a hermeneutic phenomenological approach can contribute to analytical rigour by including four specific analytic values (van Manen, 1997).

The first of which is ‘orientation’ where the researcher becomes involved in the participant worlds through the interest placed during dialogue. Second and thirdly, the writing of data provides ‘strength’ and ‘richness’ in the way it allows the meanings of participant’s narratives to be presented to the reader. As such, the analysis of data was completed manually to gain deep insight into the views of the participants. Nvivo was considered as a method of analysis but felt that depth of understanding would not been gained where data was digitally analysed. In respect that a lack of dialogue exists around the subject of ‘family learning’ there was an obligation to allow participant voices to be listened to and considered in a detailed manner. The steps taken in the analysis process were lengthy but provided not only a depth of understanding but a confidence that the findings in this study provided a true reflection of participant views.

Fourthly, the researcher provides the reader with ‘depth’ of understanding by eliciting the very core of participants view of the phenomena being studied. Langdrige (2007) also identifies quality of analysis through the inclusion of all data findings, the persuasive nature of how the findings is written and that participants have confirmed that interpretations are accurate. Meanwhile, Lavery (2003) adds that analysis process which consists of a repetitive cycle of reading data, writing to group similar themes in interpretation of meaning.

4.3 Process of Analysis

4.3.1 Limiting positionality

As noted throughout the previous research design chapter, awareness of the impact that researcher positionality may have been a key consideration throughout each stage of the research design. In terms of the process of analysis and collation of findings, consideration of positionality was equally important. Acknowledgement of researcher positionality is essential in the process of interpretation (Laverty 2003 p.28). Awareness of our own positionality is noted as useful in understanding that our positions on topics are socially constructed, it also helps to recognise the conscious and unconsciousness within research processes that are often lost (Flick, 2007; Clarke and Hoggit, 2009). However, I was keen to limit any impact of biases that I may have. An initial step in doing this was the design of questions asked. Design of questions used during focus groups and interviews allowed participants to answer freely and be open to the various perspectives that they had.

4.3.2 Reflexivity as the first stage in analysing data.

In address and recognition of how my positionality could affect research findings, I employed reflexivity during focus groups and interviews to begin the initial stage of analysis “with” participants where design of questions helped to consider how ideas around ‘family learning’ were formed (Pillow. 2003:179). This process helped in gaining depth of understanding of how participants viewed ‘family learning’ and of what had influenced their view. This method maintained a focus on participant viewpoints whilst also limiting the impact of my own researcher positionality in making assumptions of what participants had said based on biased opinion (Morgan,1997:58).

4.3.3 Deductive analysis of reflective diary as the second stage of the analysis process.

Notes on the points raised in the reflective discussions during focus groups and interviews were captured in a reflective diary. My reflections of participant views began to identify links with research questions, theories and key elements raised in literature related to the study. In this sense I could identify the process of deductive analysis as I was beginning to see connections to predetermined codes depicted within the research questions. (Bingham and Witkowsky:2022). For example, I could identify data that presented various view of what family learning was, I also aware of data that outlined where family learning happened or of the aspects that family learning needed. In reflection I was beginning to recognise how data could be organised. I could see data that was explaining the diverse ways that family learning was viewed alongside the shared view in the purpose of family learning which could relate to Bourdieu's theories of habitus, capital and field. During this stage of analysis, I could also identify that participants were explaining aspects that were important for family learning with some relating to the principles of Compassionate Love Theory.

4.3.4 Inductive analysis as the third stage of the analysis process.

Meanwhile, as the design for the study was a hermeneutic phenomenology it was important to recognise that, whilst I had confirmed understanding of what participants were explaining during the focus groups and interviews, analysis of data is always an interpretation of the "disclosures of meanings" presented by participants (Van Manen, 2003:88).

Transcription of data.

A process of inductive analysis began in listening to and manually typing the data presented in the recorded focus groups and interviews. Four focus groups that involved a total of 22 participants and eight interviews which included 8 participants-6 of whom had taken part in focus group (with 2 participants who had not.). The process also included some further deductive analysis in the organisation of data by source, for example, interview 1, 2 etc or Focus group 1. 2 etc. (Bingham and Witkowsky:2022). Initial listening, reading and organising the data helped to establish some of the common ideas that were being made or referred to.

4.3.5 Identification of initial codes as fourth stage of analysis

Transcriptions were then re-read, and open coding of the words and phrases being presented were analysed to begin to group common ideas as initial codes.

4.3.6 Grouping common ideas into initial codes as fifth stage of analysis.

Common ideas were then grouped together. The groupings helped me to interpret “something telling, something meaningful something thematic” (van Manen, 2007 p.79) to identify what was the very essence of the phenomena by comparing parts of data and reorganising to form whole aspects as initial codes.

The phrases identified as common ideas were colour coded within each of the transcribed data sources to identify the specific initial code that they sat within.

These were family learning is, aim of family learning, differences in family learning, ways of learning, what is family what is education, people involved in

family learning, where family learning happens, challenges for family learning, family learning needs, the benefit of certain aspects within family learning practice and negative aspects of family learning.

The initial codes were then aligned with research questions and objectives. (See Appendix 2 for an exemplar of the original document. See also table 5 below).

Table 5: Initial data analysis.

<p>Research question 1: what does the term family-learning mean?</p> <p>Objective: to gain understanding of how families and practitioners define family learning.</p> <p>Objective: to establish how families learn together.</p> <p>Objective: to establish why families learn together.</p>	<p>Family learning is:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Differences in family learning. 2. What is family? 3. What is education? 4. Ways of learning 5. Aim of family learning
<p>Research question: where does family learning happen?</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Different places 2. People involved in family learning.
<p>Research question: What is important for family learning?</p> <p>Objective: to explore what key aspects are important for family learning.</p> <p>Objective: to establish why these key aspects are important for family learning.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Family learning needs 2. Family learning practice 3. The benefit of certain aspects within family learning 4. Negative aspects of family learning. 5. Challenges for family learning

4.3.7 Organisation of initial codes as sixth stage of analysis

As a method of managing and organising analysis of the extensive data. The following steps were taken.

Before I organised phrases from their original source, each colour coded initial code from each source was given an identification number for easy retrieval and use in the discussion chapter.

For example, all phrases that related to a common idea and recognised within an initial code e.g. family learning is within interview one was given the identification reference numbers of I1 i.e. interview 1.

For all common ideas that sat within another initial code e.g. aim of family learning was given the identification number I1.

All comments from each source were then organised into a chart for each initial code by source. This allowed me to see the variety of comments and ideas relating to the initial code.

The same process was completed for all common ideas as initial codes across all interview data I1.I2.I3 etc or for focus group data F1, F2, F3 etc. Charts were created for each. (See Table 6 below for the example of what common ideas from interviews 1 to 4 were grouped as family learning is).

Table 6: Example of topic grouping from Interviews 1-4 from data analysis process step 4.

Topics from interviews	Codes from first one to one interview (I1)	Codes from second one to one interview(I2)	Codes from third one to one interview(I3)	Codes from fourth one to one interview(I4)
Family learning is	<u>I1</u> depends on the setting in which family learning is being considered. <u>I1 generational learning</u>	<u>I2</u> about people coming together. <u>I2</u> finding someone that will support you.	I3 something that happens in school, parental partnership I3 teachers, families and	I4 parental partnership family members supporting the topics taught at school in the home environment

	stories being shared throughout generations of learning	<u>I2</u> building all the little relationships that support it.	young people working together for the benefit of the young person. Community I3 a sense of community	I4 homework families adding to learning from school. <u>I4</u> Families having days out walking with one another. Families taking their time to be sociable with one another Mums teaching their children how to count at home through playing games Sharing learning amongst children and adults
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*This table shows an example of coding, and the colour used to identify the findings related to answers for the first question posed in four one to one interviews

4.3.8 Reorganisation of initial codes as seventh stage of analysis

All colour coded data was then positioned in tables that organised the comments from each source under headers for each research question and related initial code. The process of analysis was exceptionally long, however it provided useful opportunity to review the data multiple times allowing; refinement, opportunity to gain depth of understanding for each source i.e. identification of participant quotes that could be used in the discussion chapter. Continual review of the data during his process also allowed me to see how initial codes might be

grouped into themes. (See Appendix 3,4 &5 for an exemplar from the original tables).

4.3.9 Identification of final themes as the eighth stage of thematic analysis.

In the continual refinement of data analysis, three final key themes of; difference, connection and development were identified. Table 7 below provides a summary of how final themes were identified.

Table 7: Identification of three main themes from data analysis

Key research questions	Related research objectives	Initial codes	Development of themes	Final Key Themes.
Research question 1: What does the term family-learning mean?	Objective: To gain understanding of how families and practitioners define family learning.	Family learning is Differences in family learning. what is family? what is education?	Family Learning is Education Family Learning is Family Family Learning is Learning Family Learning is connections in relationships. Building connections. Family learning happens in connections between people. Family learning happens in development of people, families, communities and society	Differences Connections Development
	Objective: To establish how families learn together.	Ways of learning	Learning connections Building connections. Family Learning crosses borders. Family learning happens in connections between people. Family learning needs acceptance of difference Family learning needs connections. Family learning needs development.	

	Objective: To establish why families, learn together.	Aim of family learning	<p>Learning connections</p> <p>Building connections.</p> <p>Family learning happens in connections between people.</p> <p>Family learning happens in development of people, families, communities and society</p> <p>Family learning needs acceptance of difference</p> <p>Family learning needs connections.</p> <p>Family learning needs development.</p>	
Research question: Where does family learning happen?	Objective: To gain understanding of how families and practitioners define family learning.	<p>Where family learning happens</p> <p>People involved in family learning.</p>	<p>Learning connections</p> <p>Family Learning crosses borders.</p> <p>Family learning happens in different places.</p> <p>Family learning needs acceptance of difference</p> <p>Family learning happens in connections between people.</p> <p>Family learning needs connections.</p> <p>Family learning happens in development of people, families, communities and society</p>	
Research question: what is important for family learning?	Objective: To explore what key aspects are important for family learning.	Family learning requires family learning practice	<p>Learning connections</p> <p>Building connections.</p> <p>Family Learning crosses borders.</p> <p>Family learning happens in different places.</p> <p>Family learning happens in connections between people.</p> <p>Family learning happens in development of people, families, communities and society</p> <p>Family learning needs acceptance of difference</p> <p>Family learning needs connections.</p> <p>Family learning needs development.</p>	

	Objective: To establish why these key aspects are important for family learning.	Benefit of certain aspects within family learning Challenges for family learning	Learning connections Family Learning embraces difference Building connections. Family Learning crosses borders. Family learning happens in different places. Family learning needs development. Family learning needs acceptance of difference Family learning happens in connections between people. Family learning happens in development of people, families, communities and society Family learning needs connections.	
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4.3.10 Summary of Analysis and findings and plan for discussion.

A plan for discussion of data was created in line with the findings gained from the analysis of data. The discussion of findings would be presented within the three key themes and in relation to the research questions, theoretical framework and review of literature which highlighted both aspects of power and love as related to how family learning is perceived (see Table 8).

Table 8: Linking three key themes to literature.

<p>Question 1: What is family learning?</p> <p>The first question for this study presented the following objectives: to gain an understanding of how families and practitioners define family learning as well as an aim of establishing how and why families learn together. Answers to this question sat across the three main themes of difference, connection and development.</p> <p>Question 2</p> <p>Where does family learning happen?</p>
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Once again, the three key themes of difference, connections and development related to where participants felt family learning happened. Firstly, as participants considered family learning as different things they believed therefore believed that ‘Family learning happens in different places.

Question 3

What does family learning need?

This question fulfilled two objectives for the study in exploring what aspects are important for family learning along with gaining why participants felt that these aspects were important. Participant responses to this question presented answers that again fall into the three key themes of difference, connection and development. Family learning needs acceptance of difference, family learning needs connections between people. Family learning needs caring to develop ways that will achieve success for every individual.

Research question.	Question 1 What is family learning?	Question 2 Where does family learning happen?	Question 3 What does family learning need	How data relates to the two main aspects highlighted in Literature Review: Power and Love
Themes	Answers included:	Answers included:	Answers included:	
Different Family learning as different fields.	Family learning as education.	Family learning happens in EECC and schools.	Families to understand learning in terms of the aim and objectives of EECC and schools.	Participants indicate that the Scottish education system demonstrates power in how family learning is regarded in ELC settings and schools. Family learning in education systems and families presents power over individual learning. Education systems and families have power over what, where and how we learn. As such, children and families require specific capital required to access family learning within the different fields. The Institutional and familial field. Lack of the required capital perpetuates perceptions of deficit
	Family learning as family	Family learning happens in family homes.	Family learning needs individuals to gain what they need for a good life.	
	Family learning as something that crosses between different environments	Family learning happens in both school and family. Family learning happens in communities. Family learning happens in children’s hobby groups such as brownies, girl guides, dancing, boys brigade and churches	Family learning needs opportunities to experience a variety of places for learning.	

	Family learning as a different kind of learning to learning in education.			habitus amongst individuals and institutions.
	Family learning is embracing difference	Family learning happens in different ways.	Family learning needs acceptance of difference.	
Connection	Family learning as connections between people for learning	Family learning happens in connections between people.	Family learning needs connections.	<p>The capital required to develop habitus for individual success.</p> <p>Participants discussed family learning as needing power in a different context.</p> <p>Family learning has power to develop individuals, families, communities, societies, education for learning.</p> <p>Achieving ‘success’ (a better quality of life) for everyone requires specific qualities.</p> <p>Family learning needs a particular kind of power to accept difference.</p> <p>Family learning needs a particular kind of power to make connections for learning to happen.</p> <p>Family learning needs a particular kind of power for development.</p> <p>For family learning to achieve ‘success’ (as a better quality of life) it requires power through connections between individuals that are built from loving, caring relationships.</p>

				<p>In families, family learning that provides the 'success' is driven by a love for the individual. That your role as family (whatever form that takes) is to allow family members to gain 'success' in life.</p> <p>Family learning that provides successful results (a better quality of life) has to be driven by a love of learning and a view that it is a privilege to share learning (giving and receiving) with others and not to assume authority on learning or of what 'success' in life looks like.</p>
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5 Discussion.

5.1 Introduction.

As part of the introduction to this chapter, it may be useful to provide a reminder of the participants and settings involved in collection of the data as a context for the responses gained and the subsequent discussion. The data was gained from four focus groups and eight one to one interviews which were conducted within a secondary school and university meeting rooms. Participants involved in this study were employed by various Scottish local council's as secondary and primary school teachers, 'family learning' support workers and practitioners working in early learning and childcare settings. Participants also included parents who had attended 'family learning' workshops provided by primary and secondary schools. Whilst some of these participants responded to research questions in relation to their employment role in Scottish education and held a shared understanding of 'family learning' as an approach in education to aid academic attainment, many also considered 'family learning' from the perspective of their families.

The chapter will discuss each of the key themes in terms of the answers that participants gave to each of the research questions asked and in relation to aspects highlighted throughout literature relating to 'family learning'.

Responses to the research questions contributed to the objectives of the study in gaining an understanding of how teachers and practitioners working in Scottish educational settings and families perceive the concept of 'family learning'. The study presents participant views of why families learn together and of what is required to ensure learning is most effective in enabling everyone to thrive and flourish. The study identified three main themes of difference, connection and development.

The findings from this study demonstrates that perceptions of ‘family learning’ exist in complex overlapping contexts. The chapter links analysis of findings in terms of the theoretical framework relating to Bourdieu’s theories of ‘field, capital and habitus’ (Webb et al, 2008),

Family Learning as ‘difference’.

This section demonstrates the different perceptions held by participants when they considered where family learning happens from both personal and professional capacities as family members and as teachers in secondary education or practitioners in early education. Participants perceived ‘family learning’ in different ways with various perceptions of what ‘family learning’ is, which included family learning as education, as family, as something that crosses between different environments, as a different kind of learning depending on what context ‘family learning’ was being considered within. As participants considered ‘family learning’ as different things, they believed therefore that ‘family learning’ happens in different places. Participants explained that ‘family learning’ occurred in schools, nurseries, family homes, communities, children’s hobby groups such as brownies, girl guides, dancing, boys brigade and churches. Differing views presented different values to aid development of ‘habitus’ required for success or indeed the ‘capital’ that is required to access specific ‘fields’ (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017). Overall, a key aspect of this theme was that an important ‘family learning’ characteristic in ensuring an ability to thrive, and flourish was an acceptance of difference.

Meanwhile, the lack of cultural diversity amongst the participants in this study has not captured differences of how ‘Family Learning’ is considered within diverse ethnic, cultural, and linguistic backgrounds and the intersecting

identities. Therefore, it may be questioned whether the findings relating to this theme demonstrate a true reflection of the differences that exist for all families living in Scotland and of what is needed to ensure acceptance of difference. In this respect, the study recognises these limitations and need for further research in this area. The findings from research completed by Biesta (2006) and Brooks et al (2008) may also help in identifying considerations for approaches and skills required in practice to meet diversity of needs for all families.

Family Learning as 'development'.

The second section of the chapter provides participants views of 'family learning' as development. The study has highlighted a link between the purpose of 'family learning' and Bourdieu's concept of 'habitus' (Maggio, 2017) where individuals gain experiences in which they develop a sense of self that enhances their life. Considering 'family learning' as development, relates to Bourdieu's thinking around 'capital' where individuals, do not only gain personally, but are able to contribute positively to wider society (Webb et al, 2008: xii). However, all perceptions highlighted 'family learning' as situated within 'fields' of institutional and familial influence, both presenting elements of power over individuals influenced by the 'field' in which they are situated.

Participants considered the aim of 'family learning' as and within development across a variety of contexts, for example, in terms of development of people, families, education, communities and society. An interesting concept of this theme was that participants recognised that a key characteristic of 'family learning' was a need for continual development of what 'family learning' means across these contexts and in respect of the ever-changing world.

Family Learning as connections.

The third section of the chapter presents analysis of the final theme demonstrating that, whilst participants viewed ‘family learning’ as a development process, they noted specific characteristics needed for development as connections between different environments and people, such as, family, education, and communities. A similar view of ‘Compassionate Love theory’ (Fehr et al, 2009) arose from participant data demonstrating a requirement that ‘family learning’ connections are built on foundations of relationships, care, compassion, empathy, and consideration for others. Participants considered these aspects collectively as ‘love’.

5.2 Different ‘fields’ of ‘Family Learning’.

5.2.1 Family learning as education.

“Do you want my ideas of family learning with a teacher hat or with a mum hat on?”

Orla

When asked what family learning is, Orla’s response immediately presented that she considered ‘family learning’ as different in terms of what role she assumed. I was interested to find out what the difference was and asked her to explain how she considered ‘family learning’ from both perspectives. Orla explained:

I think of [school] homework. It was interesting in the [focus] group, my interpretation of it was, as a family how do you add to the learning and do you know what, I just went to homework and how do I support my children with homework. Because everything else you take for granted is actually possibly a learning experience, so I went straight to homework...I instantly went to the structured school set. Maybe it’s just because of the stage of my children. When I think about my children doing homework, [I think] come on let’s have some time together and we will do your homework together and [they say] eh oh I don’t want to I want to go out with my friends. No come on we need to get this done and it begins to get a bit harsher, and we sit down and it’s oh, you’re not understanding and no mum you’re not listening to me. You know and it ends up sometimes with a well I can’t help you anymore and you will have to explain to your teacher how you were stuck, but then, it ultimately gets put back to the teacher.

Orla

Orla seemed to consider learning as happening in school and ‘family learning’ was how families helped their children achieve that learning. Her comments also identify an understanding of responsibility as a parent to support her children’s learning but also that there were differences in what was important to complete, homework or socialising with friends, alongside understanding

around the homework subject and a lack of listening between child and adult that caused some tension.

Orla's last comment also highlights an expectation that the teacher will ultimately be the expert in resolving any issues with learning about specific educational topics as part of their teaching role. Consideration was made if this was because of the associated expertise of the role of a schoolteacher in ensuring 'success' in learning at school (Wingrave and McMahon, 2016, GTC, 2021). It was interesting when Orla also related to "everything else" in terms of the 'family learning' that colleagues had referred to in focus groups, such as days at the beach or holidaying with family and questioned that these could be "possibly a learning experience". Yet, MacKenzie (2010) and Brasset-Grundy (2002) both highlight that 'family learning' can be informal and happen out with formal institutions for learning such as school. As a teacher in secondary education, Orla's questioning encouraged me to consider if alternative viewpoints of 'family learning' are included within teaching qualifications and guidance for practice and again gave rationale for the study.

Scarlett agreed with Orla on reflection of colleague views that 'family learning' was activities and experiences with families at home and on holidays or day trips, Scarlett and Orla both considered that what happened in families was a function of the family and not specifically as 'family learning'. Scarlett's comments seem to align with Orla's in highlighting a key difference between 'family learning' in education as being a "structured school set" whereas 'family learning' with families was less obvious in describing it as "organic" or as Orla describes it as "sub-conscious" learning. Scarlett and Orla explain their different view of what 'family learning' is in noting that:

What happened organically you know being part of a family I didn't see that as family learning because that was just part of how we rolled. It was just all meshed into one.

Scarlett

It's just a kind of sub-conscious sharing of learning where nobody realises that there is any learning going on.

Orla

On reflection of the different way that 'family learning' was being considered raised thoughts of learning as 'capital' that would aid 'success' in life and therefore of what learning would be most effective for this, the "structured school set" or the "organic sub-conscious" learning. It seemed that Orla viewed school learning as more important in providing 'success' and considered the plan for learning within educational provision.

The idea of gaining 'success' through doing well in school was outlined by Mary, who attended school 'family learning' programmes. Mary demonstrated a value of learning in school when describing 'family learning' as partnership with schools to encourage children to learn alongside their parents as an aid to improve educational performance. Performing well within school was presented as something Mary's family would be proud of. Mary became sad and cried when thinking about what 'family learning' is when she explained that doing well, in terms of learning at school, was important and regarded highly throughout generations of her family, past and present. Mary's statement presents a sense of the influence and power that families and school have over learning and of the ways in which 'success' is achieved. Mary described 'family learning' as:

Trying to get them [children] to try and set goals together, like family goals. We try to have family goals and say right we are going go away to Wales.....so we need to hold all our cash in [save money], we can't spend money. And then having to explain, that you are not getting that new thing until you've [completed schoolwork]. If you get a good school report, you will get [rewarded with a gift] and if you get a good school report next year you will get [a reward]. So, that kind of eggs him on to think that mums giving me a reward for every time I come in with a good term, a good thing, a good report...Our family means a lot to us. And all our relatives here and not

here all mean a lot to us as well. They would be really quite proud of any effort that was made at school.

Mary

Mary's comment raised consideration of societal expectations of the family outlined by Giddens and Sutton (2017) that doing well in school regards the family as contributing positively to society alongside the Freirean (1972:123) view that "the parent – child relationship in the home usually reflects the objective cultural conditions of the surrounding social structure". Comments by Orla and Mary also made me consider the points raised in review of literature that societal institutions present powerful influence for learning through a "tradition of national education and a cultural disposition, with religious, political and social roots, to value educational achievement" (Hall, 2016; Anderson, 2018:107).

Yet we might question if education provides the most useful learning to provide 'success' and consider the ongoing difference in attainment between pupils in Scottish education, unemployment and persistent poverty that exists in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2014). Reflections have also encouraged questioning of the reasons presented by Scottish government for poor outcomes being linked to a cycle of poverty and the limited ability as a devolved government to address poverty in Scotland (Mooney and Scott, 2016). This questioning considers if we have developed a narrow view of who, where and what contributes to 'success' and if this narrow view is contributing to poor outcomes.

5.2.2 'Family learning' as a 'field' for targeted intervention.

Scarlett's comments and account of 'family learning' present an interesting consideration of how 'family learning' is being viewed as a programme in schools that is for specific families and presents a narrow view and a lack of transparency when she described that:

The first parent's programme I was involved in was a different group of parents. Parents that probably, were not my perception of the target audience. It is obviously all parents and carers and all families but the first group, I kind of thought that they very much knew everything, and they were in to just check us out to see if we were good enough, there was that. And as it [the parenting programme] has progressed... it's kind of the parents and carers that we really need to get in, we don't need them. Although we need all parents and carers, we absolutely do we need that mix but...

Scarlett

Donna provides additional consideration of the impact of 'family learning' being considered as an approach in schools that targets specific families. However, Donna's account presents a contrast to the how schools and parents view the purpose of 'family learning'. Once again, these differences may provide useful consideration for future practice and development of genuine partnerships for learning in Scotland. Donna explained:

I think family learning sounds quite patronising, and it puts people off, maybe it's a different way of expressing it [that is needed]. It's just to help them being there to help them to make the best of their lives. I remember when I had kids at primary school and I wasn't working at the time and there was a lot of initiatives, it was the home school partnerships ... they would offer courses, and I jumped at the chance ... I did first aid I did lots of things. But there was only five other people did it out of a whole school not just because their working. I think people just think, oh this is a load of rubbish and all. And the woman that organised it said that it's always people that shouldn't be coming to these things that tend to come, not that she didn't want us to be there, but she says that she tried to engage other people. She's involved in all other schools ...and I think it's quite challenging and maybe that family learning label doesn't help.

Donna

Steven elaborates on the content and purpose of ‘family learning’ programmes being patronising, which Donna agreed with. He states:

We will teach you how to be a good parent. When it’s 22-year-old people that have just left university ...children.

Steven.

On reflection of these comments, we might consider again why schools want to work with families. More specifically, we must ask if government and school performance targets, such as pupil attainment levels, are the key influence for why schools are applying a ‘third way’ (Power and Whitty, 1999) of gaining the assistance of families to achieve their aims and objectives to raise educational attainment. The principle of ‘Compassionate Love Theory’ (Fehr et al, 2009:9) is useful in this instance in questioning whether motivations for actions are for the good of the other in the first instance. For example, it may be pertinent to consider whether ‘family learning’ initiatives are based on what families want or what educational establishments require.

In identifying specific families as ‘the target audience’ we must question what the ‘target’ is. The comments seem to be highlighting that families are being targeted because they lack specific skills and that involvement in the programme would provide them which is contradictory to the guidance provided by Nutbrown et al (2015) that family learning should not be about assuming, identifying or fixing what families do not know. Awareness of being targeted due to a perceived lack of skills may contribute to Donna’s view that initiatives classed as ‘family learning’ are “patronising” and if this ‘deficit view’ of families contributes to the difficulties outlined in literature of building

partnerships between families and educational settings (MacKenzie, 2010; The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016). In addition, if ‘family learning’ approaches are planned programmes created by educational settings with an aim to target specific families for specific skills that did not include the views and existing skills of families, they would be contrary to ‘family learning’ as a ‘wealth model’ as outlined in guidance (NIACE,2013; Nutbrown et al, 2015; Scottish Government, 2016b; Education Scotland, 2018).

Alexander and Clyne (1995) and MacKenzie (2010) also highlighted that to create genuine partnerships with families, programmes should include families in planning to ensure a focus on their requirements and what they want to learn. Interestingly, practice guidance within ‘the Review of family learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b:5) did note that “programmes should be relevant” but failed to note relevance to whom, which may be open to interpretation. On further reflection, we must question whether perceptions held amongst educational staff, consider that experiences within educational systems have contributed to requirements of support today. For example, the argument posed by Grant (1989) is useful here. Grant claimed that family surname and where families lived, instigated preconceived notions of ability affecting ‘success’ in school whilst Nutbrown et al (2015) cautioned that learning amongst families should not be gauged within formal curricula programmes.

5.2.3 Family Learning as challenging education.

Nicole highlighted a likely reason families do not get involved with schools when she explains that experiences in school were not always good. Nicole describes experiences she, and others may have, had previously at school which have affected them. Nicole’s point which relates to findings in research completed by Carpentieri (2012) that educational experiences created

dispositional barriers and motivations for learning amongst families. Nicole continues to explain that approaches in education are different now but highlighted that experiences in education may have left unpleasant memories with some parents and families when she describes:

School is a bit different now, like I can think back to be put on the spot and made to stand up and give the answer to something. That doesn't happen now. You get so many parents who haven't been back in school, and they don't want to come in, and they have that anxiety about being back here and having the Mrs S shouting. That to get over that and see that maybe sitting in maths and the teacher coming over and saying, "don't worry about it sit with S that's next to you and he'll maybe help you" or "I'll see you at the end of the class" or whatever. And you'll never be made to stand up in front of the rest of the class when you didn't know the answer because that's a horrible feeling. Even as an adult if someone made you do that that would be awful.

Nicole.

Nicole's comments encouraged me to consider the negative experiences that some parent's and families have had in Scottish education. The use of the phrase "a bit different" is equally noted posing consideration if there are still remnants of traditional educational methods present in schools today. In this regard, my own daughter's regular recall of shouting and expectation of conformity being common techniques in maintaining control in her secondary school today support this consideration and encourage thinking around why this practice remains and of what is needed to change it.

Nicole highlights the impact, influence and power that educational practice has had in individuals lives when she identifies the "anxiety" that some families have with being involved with school initiatives. Nicole's explanation also made me consider my own experience of being belted with a leather strap as a means of maintaining discipline and ensuring conformity and achievement which had been used in Scottish schools up until the late 1980's, and of how

this and many other unpleasant experiences may present a major barrier to families being involved with educational initiatives or programmes. Previous experiences may not encourage empathy for the plight of the school where ‘family learning’ is considered a partnership to support the work of the education system.

If we continually regard individuals as lacking specific abilities that education will fix, it is as Jamieson (1999) suggested, missing acknowledgement of the contribution that societal institutions have in the difficulty to achieve social justice. Whilst participants had noted differences in education Angela also highlighted a difference in family attitudes toward education when she explains:

I think more recently education systems appreciating family. Family have always, well some families, have always appreciated that education system...But some families now refuse to send their children to school and home school them because they don't think it's [learning at school] good enough. They are not learning what they should be... [what parents want their children to learn].

Angela

Caroline reiterated the difference between school learning and of what families feel should be learned when she discussed motivations for learning within the education system:

Your learning different things from your parents. You're learning different skills; you're learning values and morals of your parents that might even be different from the education system. Which is a bit of a problem as well because the education system educates the children on the beliefs of that day, of society at that time or bring in new systems or educate that might not necessarily tie in with the family values and morals.

Caroline

Mary and Angela, who were best friends, participated within a focus group. Both highlighted that whilst there may be differences between what is learned in education to what you learn from your family, they also highlight that different morals and values that exist amongst families affect what family members learn. Mary begins by describing her experience in a catholic school:

Your family will teach you their culture there going to teach you their religion maybe. They are going to teach you their views, their opinions. In a non-denominational nursery, we would have thought about lots of different religions, lots of different values the nurseries values. Is that more important to learn than your families' values? I was brought up catholic and went to catholic schools. Came out of high school and my best friend [Angela] has not been brought up catholic and that's weird to me because everyone I have been around growing up has had these catholic views. I was talking about a girl that I knew who was given her last rights as a baby which I thought was something that everyone said, and she was like "what does that mean"? Basically, she almost died as a baby but the way I would say it is that she was given her last rights cos I thought that everyone said that. Like marriage is a sacrament and things like that. That's the thing my family taught me, they taught me my religion. ... Your family never taught you that religion but your dads catholic.

Mary

Yeah, you say weird catholic things and I am like I don't know what that is. She says some stuff and I am like sacrament? I am like what's that? They... [Angela's dad's family] ... tried to ... [teach me about catholic religion] ... but mum didn't let them.

Angela

These comments resonate with the point made by Pike (2007) that contradictory morals and values exist between families and schools whilst demonstrating a possible reason for limited family participation in school initiatives and a rationale for communication. Angela and Mary note that whilst learning gained in an educational setting differs from learning gained in your family, they also

highlight that different people provide expertise and wider views for learning that she, as a parent, did not possess or want to give, supporting the point made by Wingrave and McMahon (2016) that as ‘professionals’ teachers and practitioners may have knowledge and skills that families do not have. Whilst Angela identified that learning in school or nursery was different to learning at home, she struggled to decide which was better.

Participant comments also support the guidance provided by Brasnet Grundy (2002) and Education Scotland (2018) in highlighting that there may be a requirement for ‘family learning’ to be considered as skills gained from both informal and formal learning opportunities supporting when she explains:

I think that there is definitely different learning from what you get at home to what you get at nursery. But I don't know if I could pinpoint to say what would be better. I could love my daughter and give her the morals, you work for things, and this is how you respect people, and this is how you treat people. But if I do not know the first thing about her development and I haven't done a degree in child development, who are then going to teach her about developing her physical skills, her problem solving and all things that they are going to need.

Angela

Caroline highlighted a difficulty in perceptions of ‘professional’ opinions to that of the family in relation to children’s learning and development. Caroline’s story presents consideration of the findings from research of a requirement that services who support families should “listen and respond to what children and parents are telling us” (Rennie et al, 2021:9). Caroline’s story relates to ‘professionalisation’ outlined in the literature review and a possible negative impact that sets individuals working in educational establishments apart in being perceived, by both parents and ‘professionals’, to be more skilled and knowledgeable (Whyte and Karabon ,2016; Wingrave and McMahon, 2016). In this scenario, we could question whether, ‘professionals’ always know what is

best for learning. Caroline recalled a story about her son progressing from nursery to school and the lifelong impact of the wrong decisions that were made:

He [Caroline's son] was born in February and my nursery, it was a private nursery he was in because we were working, and they said he was ready for school. I was like, what do you think is he ready to go to school this year? And they said he was ready, and to be honest he wasn't ready; he wasn't ready emotionally. I was just taking their advice I didn't know; I wasn't working in education at that time, I didn't know this going back eighteen years. I think that they were telling me he was ready because he was wee boy that was just full of energy. It was not that he had additional needs or anything, he was just a wee boy that [required a lot of work or did not conform to expectations]. He's studying sports and fitness at college now. So, they took that decision so and I wasn't sure, and I thought I don't know but I will leave it to you. They don't always know best but as parents we can tend to go with what they say. As a parent, you tend to think, you are the professional. So, he just went downhill all the way through school. He went into school, a very difficult class, and now he's like so quiet. Like it has affected him.

Caroline

Caroline's story resonated with me. A similar experience had presented itself with my own daughter. In hindsight and with the knowledge of child development that I have now, I can see that my daughter was not ready to progress from nursery to school. As a result, my daughters early school experience began with teachers considering her as of less ability in terms of learning in school. Such children were placed in the classroom in groups according to ability. At the age of five, I recall her and her friend stating which children were in the 'top' group for reading and who were in the 'bottom'. Reflection of this scenario related to the guidance provided by Blackstone (1967) who raised concern at the impact of grouping children by ability. On reflection of what has transpired throughout my daughters 28 years, I know that this obvious positioning throughout school compounded a conviction of perceived lack of ability and has ultimately persisted throughout her school, work and life experiences. These experiences have resulted in a complete lack

of confidence or belief in her ability alongside a sense that, as parents, we have let her down.

On reflection of Caroline's story and of how it resonates with my own experience made me think about how children, young people, parents and families have become reliant on professional provision and judgements for learning provided by educational settings and staff. It is pertinent to consider how these opinions affect 'habitus', ability to gain relevant 'capital' which allows access to the 'field' whatever context these may be positioned within (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017). Once again, we can recall the question raised by Cooper (1971:290) in the review of literature of "how do we recover this lost potential?"

This section has demonstrated that some participants perceive 'family learning' to support the work of schools or ELCC settings. 'Family learning' was described as a way in which children and parents would learn from educational settings. This perspective mirrored the definitions and purpose of 'family learning' outlined in international literature and Scottish policy and practice guidance where 'family learning' is viewed as a way to improve educational attainment and outcomes for families in improving opportunities for employment (Thorpe and Schmuller, 1954; Buffton, 1999; Haggart, 2000; OFSTED, 2009; Spacey et al. 2008; MacKenzie, 2010, Woolfson, Durkin and King, 2010; Scottish Government, 2012a; National Institute for Adult Continuing Education (NIACE), 2013; Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014; Scottish Government, 2016b; Education Scotland, 2018; Freedman, 2022).

Participants explained that family involvement with learning in education was generally helping with homework or where parents were invited to attend events that were being run within the school. The focus of the events would be to

provide parents with information on what learning in the school and ELCC was about and to provide parents with the necessary skills to support that learning, for example, how to help with homework. Participants identified a ‘family learning’ approach as beneficial for both schools and families as it is seen to lessen conflict in families over schoolwork through development of confidence and ability in being able to help children’s learning in school.

Participant comments suggest that ‘family learning’ from an educational perspective, targeted specific learning and a “target audience” in fulfilment of a “structured school set” or plan. On reflection, I would like to have asked participants if and how families were involved in creating plans for the ‘family learning’ programmes to ensure that content was relevant for families in line with practice guidance relating to effective development of ‘family learning’ programmes (MacKenzie, 2010; Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014; Education Scotland, 2018).

Participants shared understanding of family learning as education as an approach within early education settings and schools to support learning. However, participants felt that a lot of parents and families avoided school initiatives which is consistent with literature (MacKenzie, 2010; The National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016: 66) and presents opportunity to understand why families did not get involved with the work of educational settings. One participant suggested that ‘family learning’ as a title was “patronising” highlighting consideration of why families may feel this way. Meanwhile, it may be that lack of consultation in establishing what families want affects participation as outlined in ‘family learning’ programmes in Vaccarino’s 2006 study in New Zealand.

Recollection on the history and motives around the use of ‘family learning’ to describe educational programmes reminds of the work of Alexander and Clyne. Alexander and Clyne (1995) noted that the rationale for ‘family learning’

programmes was to enhance attainment in school, a focus repeated within the policy framework in Scotland. On reflection, we must consider whether the narrow view and claim of the term may present resentment amongst families that this is not what ‘family learning’ means to them. Additional consideration of the lack of consultation with families outlined within the ‘Review of Family Learning’ (Scottish Government, 2016b) perpetuates; limited understanding of what ‘family learning’ means for families resulting in programmes that are irrelevant to families whilst refuting the need for dialogue for effective ‘family learning’ called for by (Grant, 1989; Lareau, 2000; MacKenzie, 2010, Harding and Ghezalayagh, 2014; Education Scotland, 2018). All these factors ultimately affect opportunities to develop genuine partnerships with families that share mutual respect for the contribution families make to the learning process (Nutbrown, 1999; Nutbrown et al, 2015).

Explanations given by participants for limited involvement of families in educational programmes could also be because of ‘traditional’ school methods and that resulting experiences had not promoted a positive image of education for many families. Participants did feel that approaches in education were now different to traditional methods and changes were for the better, but that change in educational practice was inconsistent within and across educational settings aligning with the findings of ‘What works Scotland Christie Commission 10 years on’ (Scottish Government, 2020) highlighting a need for further development and again a rationale for this study.

In comparison to the above perceptions of ‘family learning’, many participants described ‘family learning’ as happening in families. For example, Jenny explained her reflections on listening to other participant viewpoints and why she had chosen a picture of a family jumping in the sunset as an example of what ‘family learning’ is:

My initial thought came from my experience as a practitioner. Being involved in parental involvement things in the nursery. And then, when I actually looked into it and took part in the focus groups, I thought actually that's just a tiny, tiny part of it. Family learning is not just about bringing parents into the nursery or the school and learning in there. A lot of learning goes on just a day at the beach. You know how simple that is and how little it costs once you're there. I think it just related to me as a family.

Jenny

The following section provides a differing view of 'family learning' as family that contributes to a broader understanding of this term.

5.2.4 Family learning as family.

Ashleigh also initially considered 'family learning' as experiences that had happened within the early education setting that she worked in but explained that listening to others had made her think about 'family learning' more broadly. She explained:

The first time I heard about family learning I was working in a nursery in a two- to three-year-old room and there were parents coming in for a course and someone coming in for the council and I thought that was all family learning was. I have now learned that I have experienced family learning, everybody has experienced it, and it is more out with the educational side of it, and it is everywhere. The picture [a picture of a duck guiding ducklings to water] reminds me of family learning in the sense of your parent's guide you and the people, the adults around you, as a child they guide you. That's what family is there for, to guide you to do your best.

Ashleigh

During focus group discussions, John and Steven explained that 'family learning' is when a family, which includes adults and children, discover things together. They provided memories of times that they regarded as 'family learning':

As a child discovering things being out in the wild. Just family activities, probably as a boy at the beach with my own family. Yeah, doing things with the family on holiday.

John

Making peppermint creams with my dad ... making memories together.

Steven

However, Claire and Steven highlighted that different family circumstances mean that 'family learning' experiences are different for all families:

It hit home because the children I am working with, some of them have never even seen a beach... So, we've got a beach in our garden just now. A wee kind of paddling pool with water in it and then some sand. That's their beach but I thought that's a shame none of them will ever get to go to the beach and get to build sandcastles and getting their ice creams.

Clare

It depends where you live, geographically. I grew up in England, right next to London and the nearest beach was about 200 miles away.

Steven

In initial considerations of what family learning was, Orla highlighted that, she was surprised to hear participants talking about family learning as activities they had with their families, as she immediately thought of learning from an educational point of view. On reflection of this Orla and Angela explain, during

subsequent interviews, that family activities presented learning in an unconscious way. They described learning in family as:

A lot of walks, we all love nature and actually you know that's learning. To take your time and be sociable, you know there is quite a different slant on what is relaxed social natural organic family learning'.

Orla

Family learning, it is more the unconscious you just pick up the things.

Angela

Angela also highlighted that learning in her family was gained from different members which related to the idea of families and communities for learning highlighted by hooks (2000) Williams (2004) and Morgan (2011).

You go to different people for different things. I am not going to phone my dad up and talk about women's health. My auntie is reflexologist so if I want to know tips about that, she'll give me that. I will phone my nan who she is a wordly woman and if I've got things that maybe my mum will go oh phone your gran or something like that. I would go to a lecturer for advice on uni. I am not going to phone my mum and say oh what's Vrooms theory, I am going to ask my lecturer.

Most participants defined 'family learning' as family interactions with emphasis that experiences had within each family were different. For many, 'family learning' was the things that happened within their own family describing them specifically as own experiences that are different for each person. A key aspect of 'family learning' as a natural element of family is that it is shared amongst generations and communities of different people who were not necessarily

blood related. The next section extends how participants considered family learning in a generational context.

5.2.5 Family Learning as capital shared through generations.

Nicole explains why she chose a picture of two hands, one older and one younger, to depict what ‘family learning’ means to her:

I liked that the fact that it is an older person. It doesn't necessarily need to be your big sister or your mum or your auntie or your gran or whoever. There are so many people that you can learn from and are there to support you. I like as well that it is an older person as there is so much to learn from them. That family learning might have looked very different from this person's day in age as it is from this person (pointing to the two different hands in photo).

Nicole

Angela also added that family and learning could be experienced with various people and continues throughout life when she told ‘nan’s’ story:

You never stop learning ever, you never stop learning from those around you. My nan at 82 recently decided that she was going to join the gym, and she was learning about how health and exercise and fitness and all of that at that age. So, she has her little gym buddies who are her family, and she is learning through that.

Angela

Mary explains how family traditions informed learning amongst families and are passed throughout different generations where care is reciprocated. She states:

Family learning is learning from older people and older people learning from younger people. So, it's [family learning] like, my grandparents brought me up, my gran has got Alzheimer's now, and I am caring for her. I am doing for her what she did for me when I was wee. We just call it the circle of life in our house, you know you live and unfortunately people pass away but that means that other people are born into the world, the world becomes, you know, you'll have your children and that's a big family circle sort of thing.

Mary

Donna explained that experience provides the skills to be able to teach other family members. She also reminds us that family groups are different where some do not have a range of generations to continue traditions and share learning:

It's life experience though they've done it, everything the parents have gone through they've already done so they've got a different perspective, and they know that everything will be okay...whereas a parent might just be thinking this is the way it's got to be. They're all learning from each other. That in itself is family learning. If you're lucky enough to have the three generations.

Donna

Claire and Steven add to the differences in families being able to gain learning from different generations:

When I see the children, I am working with every day in practice who they think they don't even have a granny...I think that again is a societal change. Because my grandparents were already retired by the time my parents were working. So, I was with them a lot, I was raised how they were raised, and how my parents were raised. I definitely think that's how I would want my children to be raised with my mum and dad, really close to their grandparents and things like that. Whereas now I think a lot of that is fizzling out almost. It's sad to see because we can learn a lot from people. I think definitely children are missing out, some people would say they're not missing anything, but on seeing my upbringing I would say they are missing out on that valuable family unit. I have friends who grew up the same age as me who never had that either and it's not done them any harm.

Claire

And grandparents are like your friends as well, aren't they?

Steven

Steven went on to emphasise that 'family learning' experiences throughout generations has a continuous and complex effect on what adults and children learn. He also explains that experiences differ for individual family members

and families, therefore ‘family learning’ becomes unique to each family group as other people join and interact. Steven explained:

I wouldn't say I am a very trusting person but that's because my mum is not a trusting person, my mum and dad, they like to keep themselves to themselves. I think I may have developed a bit of that from them and it's a bit harder for me to build that trust with people. My mum had a bad family support network, so her dad wasn't really in the picture and would see her every second Sunday. Her mother wasn't the best kind of mother and wasn't the best support network, so I think that has formed her identity which has helped form ours. I think of how resilient my mum became that she developed what she would call “a thick skin” but she would make sure that we can all trust her. My dad's mum passed away, but my mum probably took it worse than my dad because my mum didn't have quite a good family unit. Her dad left her mum and then my nana had three new husbands, my mum had three new stepdads. It was just not a good unit. Then she met my gran, and my gran was a gran, she did the cooking she had a nice home, she would always be there with my papa and that laughing away and that was my mum finally in a secure family unit. I see a family group as parents and children that is as far as it goes. Then the children they become part of another family unit with their parents so it almost like a chain. So, although it [family learning] will transfer through it, each family will have their own.

Steven

Jenny also made an interesting observation that generational learning; remains with you even after the person is gone or can cause conflict where generations differ in their opinions and highlighted hierarchy amongst family roles. She explained that as a child her grandparents had taken care of her and her siblings to allow her parents to go to work. Whilst spending time with her gran, Jenny described that she had gained a lot of guidance that she still draws upon today. During our conversation, Jenny described how she would often question advice given by her mum with what her gran would have said, where her mum would reply “but I'm your mum, she's your gran”. Jenny also highlighted that the guidance and influence gained in her childhood from her grandparent still provides her with support:

I always think what would my gran say. What would my gran do? We are now eight years down the line [since gran died] and I'm still saying my gran wouldn't have said that.

Jenny

Angela, explained that 'family learning' for her was when she learned the history of her family when she noted:

We could be walking round London, and my mum would show me that's the building that your nans brother grew up in. Obviously, there I am learning locations, geography. I am learning about all different things, but you just care more because it's more focussed on you. If my nan was involved, she was alive during the war and stuff, so you would hear all the stories about, how my grandad died before I was born, and you hear Oh yeah and we used to do this.

Angela

It was interesting that Angela cared more about the learning because it was personal to her. This highlights connections with the importance of memories for developing identity and understandings of family morals, values and capability highlighted in literature (Fivush, 2008; Biesta, 2008; Evans and Thomas, 2009; Millar and Ridge, 2013). It also provides guidance for practice in highlighting the importance of personal connection alongside an innate awareness to seek what and who can fulfil personal requirements are characteristics of 'family learning' that aid human flourishing. Meanwhile, Carol commented "I don't think a lot of families are so appreciative of older people these days ..." with Jenny adding "Yeah, a lot of people think of them as a burden" highlighting that differences exist in changing family values. The following section provides explanation that family expectations often differed.

5.2.6 Family learning as different expectations.

Participants talked about the importance families placed on sharing cultural and religious beliefs amongst their family members. Mary and Jenny also gave examples of learning family values when they explained:

We were brought up we worked for money, we worked for the things we wanted. We didn't just get things given to us.

Mary

I always remember one day in school, it was secondary school, and the teacher was going round the table saying what would you like to be when you grow up and what would you like to be, and it was a teacher, a lawyer or a doctor, whatever. And this wee boy said I am not going to do anything, I am just going to sign on and the teacher said would you not like to go and get a job and earn your own money and he said no, I will just sign on like my mum did. And I was always brought up in a family where that wasn't an option. You would go to work you would get a job you were going to build your own life kind of thing. Whereas for this boy in my class and I was horrified, and I was saying mum can you imagine that he doesn't want to do anything. I always think about him and wonder what he is doing now. In his family learning environment, you just get your money paid in for nothing and you do not need to work you will get money anyway and his mum was still able to have a good lifestyle, whether it was good or whether it was not, she thought it was good.

Jenny

In addition, John added to the idea that 'family learning' differed between families when he highlighted:

Obviously, you've different cultural and religious backgrounds, in a way for people, their family learning could be completely different.

John

Further discussions also highlighted differences within families in terms of beliefs and values. Participants highlighted the difficulties of ‘family learning’, where individuals are torn between innate feelings of duty and self. Participants explained that they did not want to disappoint by not meeting expectations but did not agree with the values and expectations of their families. These points were really interesting in terms of highlighting the power and control that exist in various aspects of our lives. Participants expressed, that the way power and control is experienced is important, in that it can have either a positive or negative impact when they explained:

Everybody’s got different values, opinions. I came from quite a ...let’s say unique family (laughing) and their views were quite straight forward but I’ve chose my own ideas. From a young age I would say no I’m supporting the opposite football team. I have always been strong minded and fought against the grain. And it’s been fine. That worked out because my dad was protestant, and my mum was catholic. That was frowned upon because the two of them got married from both sides of the family. Luckily, I had that in my family, to say no, make your own choices.

My dad’s catholic and my mum is very anti catholic. I was brought up as my mum was like religion is ridiculous and all of that. But my dad would always tell me when I tripped over that’s God’s way of punishing me for being rude. And my dad really wanted all of us to go to chapel and my mum was very against it. Luckily for me I wasn’t really bothered about it but if maybe my dad had been more forceful in that, no we are.

I think it can be confusing if you do have two opposing, well which one? Because my dad’s views are this and my mum's views are this, which one is best for me. Do I go with my dad? Do I pick my mum? It depends how you were brought up. My parents were like, well when you get to a certain age then you decide. It’s not a big issue. And it was that kind of conflicting decision of like how much, I want to be catholic, I want my religion, but do I want to practice it and things like that.

Belinda

That was what it was like for me as well. My whole family were catholic, but my grandparents had us on the weekends and we went to the chapel on the weekends with my grandparents. As we got older, we weren’t going to my grandparents as much and my mum and dad were still working but we could look after ourselves. So, then I wasn’t going to chapel. So, do I still want to go like my grandparents, or do I want to go to chapel, but I can’t get to chapel? If I’ve been taught about the catholic religion

and then gone to school and been taught about evolution and science and I'm like well what one happened. So, then it's like that kind of conflict.

Ashleigh

The points raised in these discussions were fascinating in highlighting the influence that religion had in family life. Most of the participants here also presented a sense of duty to the expectations posed by their families whilst demonstrating that there had some autonomy in choosing what they felt was important for them albeit that choices were difficult. 'Family learning' in these contexts relates to the points raised in literature that families and learning are set amidst constant negotiation of personal, cultural, and societal expectations (Thorpe and Schmuller, 1954; Kolb, 1984, Jarvis, 1987, Grant, 1989, Finch, 1993, Pike, 2007, Smart, 2011, Elkjaer, 2018, Jarvis, 2018). The following conversations provide additional insight in how expectations differed between families, early educational settings and wider society:

It could also be conflicting between family values and then values of wider society or education as well. Because it's like right I've been brought up to think this and why else would I think any other type of way because my family think this. And then I got to nursery, and I am not told it's wrong, but I am told this is how things are done. And I am thinking but this is how I have been brought up and this is my opinion and views. Do I go with fitting into wider society, or do I stick with [family]?

Angela

Yeah, if you're going home and you are doing drugs at home in front of the child where the child is picking up drugs. We're going to teach them you know that's not right, and we don't do that, or we don't hit. We say no you tell a teacher, it's gentle hands. The amount of times [I have heard] in nursery, "well my dad says I have to hit them back" and you're trying to go I know that your dad said that, but we don't do that.

Laura

I know people that I grew up with would get battered if they got beat up in school. Their dad would beat them up and say you should have fought them back. How dare you embarrass us that you did not fight back, and they will go to school fight back and then get into trouble with the teacher. That's why it is important for your education for your early years to involve families so much. You need to know what I am dealing with here. What is this child's home life like in the sense of what are these families' opinions. What are these families' views.

Angela

It's like working with the families to go well do you know what I understand that you want this to happen but look how it is affecting the child. Because really, they are only wanting what's best for the child even in the sense well you should have hit them back. That's because they don't want their child being hit. If you then work with the families to then go well this is what we can do where it doesn't get to that stage.

Laura

You don't want to be a disappointment. You can make people anxious.

Caroline

The following discussion demonstrates a difference in terms of judgement and understanding demonstrated by the participants. Claire and Debbie highlighted judgement of families in their roles as practitioners in early education where family practice did not meet their expectations.

The area I work in is deprived its very rough and a lot of the parents have, not the wrong views, but very different views from myself and it definitely has an impact on the children. My mum works in a school as well and she'll say we're getting them in, and they can't even tie their shoelace. I would say I never learned that at school I learned that at home. I learned that from you. But a lot of parents just think, a lot of parents now, no criticising but I feel a lot think they are so entitled to schools and nurseries and things teaching their children everything. It's not that their bad parents it's just that they are very different views.

Claire

A lot of the time they don't get that that's their job because it's maybe, whatever their background is.

Debbie

Yet, Steven presented an alternative viewpoint in understanding that societal expectation of families to be working more has affected the things that they do with their children:

It can be so difficult when you've got two parents working full time Monday to Friday and at weekends they're not wanting to go out to the beach, they're not wanting to go here. that's their chill out time the only time that they get.

Steven

It is useful to consider how these differing viewpoints would affect the support provided to families and considered the points raised in literature again, where Steven's understanding related to the need for thought, language and understanding that Doreen Grant (1989) called for. A more understanding approach may also reduce the effects of judgement and conflicting views that encourage experiences (Alexander and Clyne, 1995) that are not conducive to "human flourishing" (Underwood, 2009:9). Steven's comments also made me consider the current aim of increasing childcare in ELCC in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2020) and of how increased employment will affect the ability to thrive where economic focus super cedes and limits consideration of the challenges that this initiative may present for family practice in Scotland.

5.2.7 Summary of 'Family learning' as difference.

This study has provided differing views of where and how 'family learning' is gained. When considering 'family learning' in education, participants related to

activities that would support the work of school. Activities were helping with homework or attending initiatives that were provided by schools to help families to learn specific things.

Meanwhile, participants described ‘family learning’ as activities outdoors where adults and children discovered things during family days to the beach, walks outdoors and holidays where memories were made. ‘Family learning’ as a natural feature of family life was described as personal, unique, and ever changing due to the nature of generational change, experiences, guidance influencing constant change and lifelong learning. Whilst family traditions presenting expectations and a sense of obligation with differences of how power and control were presented in having positive or negative impacts. In contrast to ‘family learning’ as a structured school set or an approach in education, the learning during family activities was described as “unconscious, relaxed, social, natural and organic”. In explaining different views of ‘family learning’ participants also presented awareness of considering differing cultural values and practice, however, it would have been useful to hear directly from families across the range of cultural diversity who could extend the different views and needs in relation to ‘family learning’ captured here.

A key point made by Jenny was that “family learning is not just about bringing parents into the nursery or the school and learning in there”. In line with Jenny’s point here and with the varying considerations of what ‘family learning’ is the next section explores the purpose of ‘family learning’ and of thinking around how societal changes are influencing development of ‘family learning’ whether it is considered as an approach in education or as a natural function of families.

5.3 Family Learning as Development.

Throughout many discussions and stories, participants referred to the notion of what was ‘best’ or ‘good’ in terms of the aim of ‘family learning’. Participants discussed ways of how families provided the ‘best’ for their children and other family members. Belinda explained that when she considered ‘family learning’, she thought about what she had learned in her family. When asked if ‘family learning’ could happen in schools she answered:

I would say it is slightly different, but it can achieve the same outcomes if done right.

Belinda

It was interesting to reflect on the point that ‘family learning’ achieved outcomes considering what these were and of what “done right” looked like in terms of ‘family learning’. Further discussion with Belinda gained an insight into what she meant by outcomes and that providing these were a responsibility of family. Belinda explained that ‘family learning’ in her family allowed her:

To be more independent for the days when they are not there or vice versa. Life skills because you need them. They want you to get through life. There is no point being taught and then you go out into the big wide world at a certain age ... and you could cope with life a wee bit more comfortably. I think my parents just knew that if they could do it then so could I could do it. Relationships with your family help you to form relationships out with your family circle, like friends, work colleagues. You need to know what is right or wrong so that you know the healthy relationships to go into as well, like picking the right partner. It’s protection, because they are parents, that is their job.

Belinda

Belinda's explanation made me think about outcomes as 'habitus' where 'family learning' helps you to learn what is right and wrong, which made me reflect on the previous section on differing expectations where different influences present different measures of what is right and wrong. However, Belinda is stating that in her perspective where 'family learning' is a responsibility and happens at home within her own family to ensure that family members have what they require to be able to thrive in life. Belinda's point that an ability to build relationships was also a key aspect in being able to do that was interesting as building relationships is highlighted through literature as significant factor for learning and development (De Lissa, 1949; Fivush, 2008; Deacon, 2011; Hargreaves, 2013; Zeedyk, 2022), partnership working (Cara and Brook, 2012; Scottish Government, 2012b) and for family itself (Burgess and Locke, 1945; Smart, 2011; Morgan, 2011). Meanwhile, Belinda's perspective highlighted the importance of her families view of what is right and wrong and related to the formation of her 'habitus'.

Angela also supported the idea of 'family learning' at home with her family and as learning gained in education where she gained everyday skills which I considered as 'capital'. It was interesting to see how Angela described learning in school as education and different, she seemed to identify that educational learning was more focused on specific topics with 'family learning' initiatives like 'Stay and Play' fulfilling that focus. This raised consideration of whether parents or children had been involved in deciding what focus would be most useful for them and wished I had asked this question. Angela explained:

Family learning is everything, isn't it, because how do you learn everything? How do you learn to talk, walk? I guess that is from the people around you, isn't it? That is from the family. How do you learn to cook, how do you learn to get dressed? That is at home... I think the stuff you learn at home and within the family setting is more like your life skills and the stuff in your educational settings is like your educational kind of things. But then parents are coming in [to educational settings] and you are

learning when you come and do stay and play. You know you come and do your drawing, you are doing your painting, like learning about a topic.

Angela

5.3.1 Family learning as developing individuals.

Jenny added to the idea that ‘family learning’ is about development of individuals. However, she describes that often the choice of how family members want to develop is not always theirs. Her recall of her own experiences highlight that educational qualifications were valued in terms of development of family members which presented different ‘capital’ in aiding the ability to thrive. The description also highlights the power and influence that families have on the choices that children make to reach their “full potential” whilst also demonstrating the different opportunities for children to develop as they choose. On reflection we might consider the use of the term of achieving “full potential” as being related to educational achievement and gaining ‘professional’ employment and skills and considered if these were desired outcomes of ‘family learning’ and a result of the influence that government aims and objectives have driven. It may be that academic expectations present “pressure” within families’, with consideration of how this affects “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:9).

Jenny did not seem to be troubled in explaining that she was considered less academic and had gained the label of “ditsy blonde” with her ability to talk as the skill that had gained her employment. However, when reflecting on this discussion, it was intriguing to consider why Jenny accepted the label and perception of her ability which signified that less value was placed on her aptitude in connecting with people as a skill. Yet, Jenny was one participant who stood out to me in the open and honest quality she presented during focus

group and interview discussions making it extremely easy to connect with her. On reflection, Jenny's story presented the impact of judgement and value present within our society and of how these may affect development of 'habitus'. Jenny's comments also reminded me of the findings from previous research that a limited view of 'capital' may affect development of self and society (Mackenzie, 2010; Carpinteri, 2012; Cara and Brooks, 2012). Jenny explained:

My sister was very academic, and it was very much you will leave school, and you will go to university. I always felt there was a lot of pressure on her, and she didn't really feel it because she is dead laid back. But I was like you are really pressuring her. But I did not feel that for me personally there was that pressure for me to go and achieve. I was always the ditsy blond one that talked myself into a job.

But my sister was very academic, and my mum and dad always wanted her to achieve her full potential because they knew she was always capable of going on to be something like midwife or my dad always wanted her to be an accountant. She had to say no, this is my life, and this is what I want to do. I will go to university, but it's not to do that. This is my life and not yours. A lot of children don't have that relationship with their parent's cos my sister's friend was forced to go and do pharmacy and six months down the line she's out because she hated it. I think that is such a shame cos she was forced into that, and she has wasted that year.

Now when I looked back my mum and dad never went to university when they were young. My mum just had a job, and my dad worked in the steel works and then he worked in a prison in the workshops and obviously there was riots and things. My mum said you need a better job as we have three young children, you cannot be stuck in prison for days on end, what if something hits you or whatever. He then went back to university and got his teaching and stuff and now he is a college lecturer

Jenny

Meanwhile, Carol also adds that learning continues throughout a lifetime. Carol had come to study at university later in life and I wondered if this was influencing how she felt. She seems to be highlighting that there may be times where we realise that we can learn more than we thought we could. I wondered if Carol was influenced by her ability to learn at university where previous perceptions had led her to believe it would be too difficult. Carol's point also

made wonder about the specific elements that help individuals build a sense of confidence or ‘habitus’ in understanding that every contribution is valuable. Carols identifies ‘family learning’ as part of that journey where we can gain a realisation that we learn from a variety of people and in a variety of places every day and throughout our lives.

A lot of people realise that they can learn and that they are learning, they just think that they know. I think that’s part of what’s good about family learning, if people can start to realise that you are learning all the time, it doesn’t just stop at school. You can learn off each other... from children, you’re learning all the time. I didn’t realise that until I went to college, and I was in my twenties and a lecturer said to me there you never stop learning and it’s stuck with me and that’s probably why I’m on this journey now.

Carol

Claire adds to the idea that learning is for individual development and happens throughout life for different situations and in many different places with different people. The argument that Claire was making was interesting in that gaining the ability to develop your own viewpoints was as important as learning maths and English at school whilst again being reminded of the varying ‘capital’ being identified by participants. The comments made me wonder why this was considered as important and thought about the importance of developing ‘habitus’, a sense of autonomy and independence or ‘identity’ as outlined by Biesta et al (2008). I found myself thinking again about what specific characteristics of experiences gained in families and school would be most beneficial for allowing development of own viewpoint. Claire’s points were made in explaining:

I think a lot of people think learning is, you go to school you learn your maths your English and your topics whatever and you leave you get a job and that’s you. But it’s actually every day, progressing skills, you’re developing your mind, your physical

abilities. A lot of people maybe have had horrible things happen to them strokes and they've got to learn to speak again and its crazy how that can happen at any age for various different reasons. A lot of people think it stops at school whereas it definitely doesn't. It's not just about your maths and your English and spelling and reading. It's definitely your own development of skills. your own opinions on things as well, your interpretation and things like that.

Claire

Mary may provide some of the answer that I was looking for when I questioned what is required to gain the ability to develop own identity and interpretation of things. Mary's viewpoint of 'family learning' helps to explain that development of self requires guidance and opportunity to choose when she noted:

I have got two apples balancing on a rock [describing the picture she chose] and I think family learning needs balance. So, you need your parents, but you need your other aspects, so you need your siblings too, so they done this when they were older, [but] I'm not going to do that. You need your cousins your friends, then going into the nursery and stuff but you also need to be guided by these people around you. But I need to be given the opportunity to develop on my own. Yeah, I want your guidance and support but give me that opportunity to build myself on my own. Because it's {family learning} saying that you are good as you are ... you as you, you are still great. You don't need to be someone else to be amazing. You can be you.

Mary

This topic has raised various comments from participants of what is required for development where they noted the need for support, choice and goals. Laura explained that "families always give you goals and strengths to get you to the goals, on your own ability that you don't think you have" indicating that 'habitus' can be gained from your family. Caroline explained "it gives you that support and that ability to try and be whatever you want to be". Whilst Angela stated, "don't tell me what I am going to be", with Mary adding:

Just let me live my life and make my own decisions. support me in the decisions but I need to make my own mistakes sometime to get to where I want to be.

I was struck that participants were relating to 'ideal' family scenario's and aware that no one had mentioned that families do not always provide goals and support although participants acknowledged that choice is not always gained. In this respect, I understood choice to be a key factor of ideal 'family learning'. Meanwhile Carol provides an example of changing family constructions which limits opportunities for support and extends the need for support to be provided by others. Carol describes 'family learning' in developing as a parent:

I was just thinking, as a mother myself, I would go to my mum or my gran for advice. A lot of young girls don't have that, and it takes a lot when they have a first child. You don't have a clue what you're doing. you're learning on the job.

I look at this guinea pig [a picture chosen to explain what family learning means] and my dad used to say you were the guinea pig, I was one of four, we did everything wrong, you were like the trial one. Parents need to be told it is okay to make mistakes, nobody's perfect. and I think, that's a role of 'family learning it's to build the confidence of parents.

You might have a fantastic job and drive a BMW, and you act a certain way but you're still going to be bit insecure about you're parenting. It's teaching them as well; it's getting the balance. It's trying to figure out how to do that because a lot of parents don't have that grandparents and stuff like that. The role of family learning is to be like the grandparents to back them up and say everything's okay, you can do this, whether they know that they need it or not.

Carol

Carol's explanation presented many aspects that are interesting for this study. Carol is essentially saying that we all need help, help in this context could be considered as 'capital', and 'family learning' would normally be gained within generations of one family. However, changing family constructs and lives means the net of support needs to be spread wider and makes me recall the

contemporary ideas of families and communities outlined in literature (hooks, 2000; Williams, 2004; Morgan,2011). Carol also seems to highlight that we often perceive families to be doing well and lack support when they had good jobs and drove nice cars but notes that it is important that ‘family learning’ is “teaching them as well”. Although Carol seems to be aware that providing family support needs to be approached sensitively where they may not want to admit insecurities or that support is required.

I was reminded of the findings highlighted by Holloway (2014) where families found advice from educational settings intrusive and not needed. On reflection I also considered the effect that judgement has on families where they often depict a false representation of how life really is in way of avoiding criticism (Smart, 2011). I could see Carol’s understanding that she needs to be aware and understanding in her practice as a practitioner in ELCC when supporting families and I could see the complexity when working with families in supporting roles. These points provided interesting considerations for the aspects raised by participants that ‘family learning’ is development of partnerships.

5.3.2 Family learning as development of partnerships to aid learning.

Angela and Caroline explain that historically, schools and families assumed distinct roles for learning. Caroline describes the different areas of learning that each took responsibility for, whilst Angela extols an element of power held by educational authorities for learning. However, both note that there seemed to be a change happening where the approaches to support learning were developing to be more of a partnership. I was interested in Angela’s comment that ‘family learning’ was becoming more valued where she related to ‘family learning’ as the core family and I assume the contribution they make to learning. Angela’s

comments made me consider why educational authorities had chosen to use the term ‘family learning’. Caroline notes:

I think years ago it was a case of right you do your job, and we will do our job. Parents would send their children to school, right you do your job, you teach them to read, the three r’s, read write and arithmetic. You teach them to do that, and we will teach them the other life skills that we are able to teach them like cooking, Hoovering, ironing doing the garden and just all the sort of nurturing skills. But there does today seem to be more of a merging of the two. There seems to be a greater need for parental involvement and that could be down to the fact that our children are in education more.

Caroline

I think it is only recently that education has started valuing the family learning. Like the core family wasn’t always taken into account. Because they said, well we are teaching them we are at school we’re the wider education system.

Angela

Nicole also highlighted that, historically decisions around learning in school were taken by educational staff and noted that some schools were now developing their approach to be more inclusive of families to be involved in decisions around their children’s learning in school. Nicole explained:

I think schools are now taking parents views into account more. I think it used to be very much a teacher or depute head teacher, whatever, was very much, this is your goal, and this is how we’re gonna get there. I think now parents and carers have more of an opportunity to say well actually I know my boy would work better in this way or can I sit with guidance, can I do this and work together. It’s not to say that in every school it works and it’s not always going to work, but it’s [working with families] [happening] far more.

Nicole

However, Nicole also seems to note opportunities for further development as working with families is something that is not always done or successful. I wonder why working with families would not be done, considering the history of policy and legislation around working with families in Scotland and of what factors would mean that working with families would not be suitable for some schools. I am reminded of MacKenzie's (2010:2) comment that The Parental Involvement (Scotland) Act of 2006 was a “lost opportunity” and of the thirty-seven recommendations made in the review of the impact of the act conducted by the National Parent Forum in 2016. The inconsistency of partnership across schools highlighted by Nicole also reminded me of the recent review of progression in relation to the Christie Commission of 2010 where inconsistent service and a call for changing mindsets to partnership working was once again, a key recommendation (Scottish Government, 2020:7).

The further developments highlighted by Nicole were also interesting when listening to how Anna perceived ‘family learning’ and working in partnerships to be. Anna described ‘family learning’ as something that benefits both school and families, However, it was very interesting to hear these views as the benefits to families and children she claims are assumptions that may or may not be accurate. To date there is a lack of research that has included the views of families or children or that has identified the wider benefits of family learning programmes in Scotland. (Cara and Brooks, 2012; Scottish Government, 2016b).

I was also interested to hear that there would not be anything negative when Nicole had previously indicated that partnerships between schools and families did not always happen or work. I wondered if Anna’s ‘ideal’ view of ‘family learning’ was based on government policy and practice guidance, evidence gained from families or Anna’s personal opinion or aim of ‘family learning’. I wished I had clarified this during our discussion but did not want to appear

judgemental and affect the rapport we had. I also wondered if positive outcomes relied on specific characteristics of approach. Anna explained:

I mean the school will benefit massively from families being involved and the pupils themselves will massively grow in strength and confidence and things. So, for everybody it is a win-win. There is nothing that is going to be negative in it. Parents will benefit, their relationships will be closer, they will not be fighting about homework the kids will be more engaged, hopefully achieving more so you know it should be a win-win for everybody.

Anna

Whilst further developments may be required, June and Scarlett provide an idea of how partnership with school is beneficial for children's learning and development. June explained:

I think because I've had so much communication and time with them... [teachers]... that we've had regular meetings and all, that they do understand my son a lot better than ...I mean when I was at school you just went to school. I don't even remember, when I was in secondary school if there was a parent's night or whether my parents had anything to do with anything I did at school. I really don't think there was anything there.

June

I suppose the idea of joined up working and everyone working together for the benefit of the young people and it being very much a sense of community as opposed to us and them thing. So, for us with my [teacher] hat on, I suppose thinking about the pupil and the teachers and the family at home you know all kind of joining up, you know, that sort of triangle. So, for me I just thought great idea, better results, more support for young people so we can all get an idea what is going on.

Scarlett

Participants also acknowledged developments in different learning approaches more broadly within the education system which seem to meet Mary's expectations for learning. For example:

It's good that they've...[teachers]... recognised how kids work academically. The curriculum for excellence is much broader. It's a broader spectrum, isn't it? It's much more that they are dealing with all sorts of different things. The good thing is that the kids are, basically... [getting] ...what you want for your kids

Mary

That we nurture your skills to get to that end goal... [success in life] ... rather than the more necessarily traditional route. I think they are much better in doing that now. I think we're much better at doing that whole well-rounded different route to get to your goal, just with the wider achievement stuff and doing different modules with people, like the Jazz awards, the Skills Force. All these kind of extra bits there's many.

Nicole.

However, Mary also emphasised her concern about differences in children's ability to fulfil expectations in education. She demonstrated consideration that 'family learning' in school was a way of helping children to be supported in their school learning. Mary highlights that:

Unfortunately, there are children who are very academic and there are children who are not very academic. And there are ones in the middle who the other ones are just sailing on by and the wee ones down here have got all their wee issues and the teachers time taking up. And they wee souls sitting in the middle are just guddling along. Their guddling along and they need somebody.

That's why I think the family learning team process has been a really good thing because there should be more of it and there should be more contact with school, not on a bad way. Awe you only contact me when somethings bad. What should be happening is teachers should be meeting up with parents for progress and where were going and how were going to get there and what steps were going to go for.

Mary

Valued learning in this example was described as “academic” and which highlighted the power that “academic” learning has in whether an individual gains the ability to thrive and wondered, if this is the case for today’s world, in appreciation of Mary’s concern this thesis questions how we ensure all children and adults are equipped to be successful within these measures. Mary’s comments also made me think of what Carol had highlighted earlier, in relation to partnership working, where there is an assumption of less support being required as presenting situations where assistance to ensure “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4) for all families is missed. Mary’s comments made me also question how one teacher can know or fulfil the requirements of every child in a class of almost thirty children, or if assumptions are made, and of what happens to achieving ‘success’ in school learning because of these assumptions or when families do not get involved with the school.

5.3.3 Family Learning as developing different values and behaviours.

The following discussion, highlighted the developments in family life, values and behaviours. Jenny, Carol, Steven and Caroline raised various issues around changing dynamics within ‘family learning’:

Society changes as well. growing up I learned a lot from grandparents and great grandparents, aunties and uncles as well. we are a really close family unit, and now when I tell my gran things and she’ll be like what? It’s just so different to when they grew up. We can learn a lot about her and a lot of morals about how things were when she grew up. Sometimes she just cannot accept behaviours of people today but it’s just cos it's so different. They have grown up in different worlds from back in the 50’s to 2019 when we are growing up.

Jenny

It's all about things nowadays, it is all about material things and that why a lot of parents are working. It's this, it's probably controversial. it is this equality thing; I think the dynamics have changed so much where before a woman or a person would stay at home and look after the kids and that's totally gone. That's not cool at all. and that's changed dramatically since I was a wee girl, and I think that's had a huge impact on families. I don't know whether it's right or wrong. I don't know everyone's feelings, but I just think that families have changed so much.

Carol

When I was born my dad stayed at home until I went to nursery. The amount of memories and stuff that we would do. We went to the park everyday unless we were going somewhere else.

Steven

A lot of children are put into after school and childcare. there is someone different dealing with them every day. They don't need that new iPad. A lot of children are missing out. I think it's a society thing. Grandparents are working right up until they die and not having that time to spend. I think it's definitely a societal change.

Caroline

The discussion was interesting in highlighting the points raised by Perry Jenkins and Wadsworth (2017) of the "trade-offs" forced upon families by neo liberal political values influencing the drive for employment and the value of material things whilst super ceding time spent with family. Steven also highlighted that female, and male roles had changed in some families where males would stay at home to provide childcare. However, I could sense that time within families was valued here, on reflection of Steven's comments I sensed that memories of the personal time he gained with his dad had stayed with him. Time in this

conversation seemed to be a crucial factor where time changes as well as enhances learning. The impact of less time can be seen in the next section highlighting the resulting developments in communication.

5.3.4 Family learning as developing communication.

Participants also noted how life has changed over the years and commented on the new ways in which ‘family learning’ was gained or communicated. Orla commented on the increase of digital devices within families and of how her daughter was influenced by the online interactions with others. In respect of the following conversations, I could relate to the suggestion made by Price-Robertson and Duff (2018) that family life or in the context of this thesis ‘family learning’ involves a “family assemblage” or a range of things that contribute to communications and support gained within families. In this context, digital devices and social media could be considered as part of this assemblage. Orla’s comments were particularly interesting where she feels that her daughter learned and valued the guidance gained from communication with her peers over social media, questioning “when is it not family learning?” and if the support gained from social media can be classed as family. Participants explained:

I am thinking about my own daughter and the time that she is on a phone and how extended is the family? Because I think there is a lot of learning going on between peers and I think she would rather learn something off of YouTube or her WhatsApp group that she would hold more value to that, in some cases, than with me.

So, I think even not interacting with the core family member. I think there’s a load of other stuff that’s going on that’s still learning, where, when is it not family learning?

I suppose, its maybe, traditional family learning would happen in the home and although maybe it's not family that's in the home but is it not the family or is it? but it's certainly an outside influence.

Orla

I wouldn't consider it as family, but I think it's happening, and I know there's a shift and I'm having to adjust in the room because that's what many small kids [do now], my kids have grown up before all this, so I don't know what it's like now?

Charlotte

For me it's probably a means of communication. For my family learning I would speak to my nieces and nephews via WhatsApp or just message cos it's easier getting them on that than it is if I'm phoning my sister and my brother and have a chat with them and it is they're away with their pals or they're away to football or away swimming. So, I would just send them a message. They might not reply back for two or three days.

But I think in terms of societies changed and the world is changing now. So, in terms of what family learning was for each of us, could be completely different so I think the term has developed. Obviously, you've different cultural and religious backgrounds in a way for people their family learning could be completely different. I think in terms of technology it's had a positive and negative influence in it.

John

The comments made by participants around digital devices sparked a discussion in one focus group around the rise of families using digital devices and social media platforms to communicate. The discussion also raised consideration of individual differences, family differences, family values and of how families might influence, control content or methods of 'family learning'. Whilst Jenny also notes the influence that social media has in the promotion of materialism and the negative impact it can create. In reference to the development of technology in family life Hannah, highlights the expectations and influences of differing family values:

I think it [technology] can lead to conflict. For example, I've got a daughter that's in primary four, whose friend has just got a mobile phone. And she thinks that, so she's got one I'll get one now mummy. And I am like, you don't need a mobile phone in

primary four and am going to be fighting this battle for quite a wee while ... So, they think, oh a should have access to that.

Then you feel as a parent kind of torn. I feel like okay if her friends are getting them am a doing the right thing here or am a doing the wrong thing. I don't want her on games and stuff like that when she's still quite a young child and a want to keep her that way.

I think you've got to accept that what's good for one person might not necessarily be good for the other. And that's the most important thing, you know that some children might communicate with their parents that way and might feel it necessary to talk to their mum on the mobile phone etc. just for a wee bit of re assurance. But from my point of view, I don't want her sitting on technology all the time.

Hannah

There is so much pressure on young people and older people as well looking at social media and all my friends got enough money to go wherever on holiday and such and such's children are doing this and doing that unfortunately the area where I stay there's a lot of young people between the ages of twelve and fifteen committing suicide cos they just cannot deal with the pressures and I think that's such a shame, they've not been guided, not told not what to do, they've not been guided in the right direction. this is where you're going to go in life and this how your life is going to pan out. It might not seem good now, but it will get better, and you've got support to get better.

Jenny

John also commented on the rise of digital devices within family life, of how increased use of mobile phones, I-pads etc. may conflict with family values whilst also highlighting how control was promoted in advertising as an expectation of families and as an expected role of a parent. John also highlights that learning is gained from various places and in many ways when explaining:

You even notice that some business' are starting to tap into that [the use of technology in family life], like Sky App and Sky buddy App where the family could, the mother or the parent, guardian could control and kill all internet devices at the touch of a button. They spent a lot of money advertising that and putting value on family game time. It just pauses the internet. So that when they have a family meal, you can kill the internet. Aldi had done the same over computer games, you contact them and one of

their expert players, would take your child out of the game so that they could go and have their meal.

So, it depends, you know, I think it depends very much on what you see as a parent, what you think is important thing to do. Some families are sitting around the table having dinner, some families are sitting in front of the telly having a family meal, having a conversation talking about general life. Is learning taking place? You don't know. It might be. I think it depends on what you actually do.

Angela also considers technology in allowing options for support whilst Mary and Caroline raise the development of family life where technology has allowed families to live further apart, gaining opportunities to support their families through employment and the use of digital devices.

I feel it's about the people that are around you. I feel like, flipping it the other way. Obviously, all my family is still in London but yet technology, Face timing them every day.

My parents still support me a lot financially, emotionally all of that so I feel like although you might not be physically with, they'll probably still support L [Angela's daughter], you know if I say awe L needs these shoes, they'll still support.

My mum learns from me because you should try and see her trying to unlock her phone or trying to get on the internet or posting things on Facebook.

Angela

My mum's cousins two daughters are my best friends. I would say that they were first cousins because I am closer to them than my actual first cousins. Their more family to me than people that live ten minutes up the road. They don't live in the same country as me, but we communicate so much more.

I put so much more effort into our relationship purely because we don't get to see each other all the time, a monthly catch up or we are phoning each other or just messaging each other. Like through like Facetime, messaging like social media and things like that. Just normal phone calls just to get that connection and then obviously we try and travel and see each other but it's not always easy to do.

Mary

That's probably why some people didn't move away and that's why everyone stayed in the same village because if you move out, we might never see you again might never speak to you again. Because they didn't have the means, whereas now.

Angela

But then a lot of villages had like industries around about to support them too. You don't have the mining and like just bringing a different perspective. I am from a different generation you know so they didn't have to move then, they were able to support their families round about them.

Caroline

5.4 Family Learning 'capital' as Connections.

5.4.1 'Family learning' as wider connections

This section provides a lot of similar and interesting points highlighted from this study around who and what contributes to connections for 'family learning'.

Angela provides a perfect introduction to who most participants felt engaged in 'family learning' connections. I considered these 'family learning' connections as contributing to development of 'habitus and 'capital' that help us to thrive (Bourdieu, 1990,1993, 2000; Earle, 1999, Maggio, 2017). A key idea is that the 'ideal' of 'family' where we are supported to thrive, is and requires to be considered as wider than who we live with or are blood related to. Angela explained:

Family is not just your mum and dad. It's not even like, you've got your grans, my daughter has her uncle and her uncle's girlfriend who is always doing things with her cos she's like a youth worker. I mean when you see families like mum and dad, gran and grandad. it's like everyone behind, like the wider family. I spent loads of time with my uncles and aunties growing up because we are quite a close family, we went to my nans after school. It's not just parental.

Angela

My mum's best friend, I think of as my auntie, and I think that I am probably closer to her than any of my blood related aunties. Family is just people who care about you and people that are constants in your life. I can see friends become family because they're the ones that are there for you. Just because they are blood related doesn't mean that they are always going to be there for you.

Mary

For me, my family unit was great gran, two sets of grandparents, my mum and dad. I only had one official uncle, but I had so many people that I considered family. Mum's friends, dad's friends. you know that I would call auntie when they were just my mum's friend but for me, they were family, and they all had a really big impact on my life. To know they care about you. they're not just mum's friend. They're mum's friend who loves you as much as she loves her own children. She wants to see you and wants to spend time with you and wants to take you to the park, not buy you hundreds of expensive things, just spend time with you and ask about you and things like that. It's maybe not the best term to use, but I've seen a lot of children who I would describe as 'bought children'. They've got the great toys, got iPads, but all they want is a wee cuddle and a story together that's all they need, it's an attachment and they don't have it.

I think a family unit is becoming much more all of that, non-blood relatives. So many parents are working, child into the childminder and the child's attachment is with their childminder not with their gran or their papa, it's with their childminder. They become the family member to that child.

I've got a friend who, their mum and dad work full time, and every day right from primary 1 to 6. Leaving high school, she was at the childminders and when she left school, she was like well, do I stop seeing her now? At seventeen years old she was thinking she's my family, I've seen her every day going to school. We're now three years out of school and she still goes and sees her at least once a week. She's closer to her than she is to her gran cos her gran lives away ... so she says I'm much closer to my childminder than my actual blood relatives. My mum and dad worked full time, and we were at my grans all the time, constantly at my grans, that was our wee unit, and we got older and horrible things started happening and they started passing away and we were all destroyed so the norm was our wee unit and now it was gone, you know.

Claire

These comments support the view of learning as a social experience that happens on a continual basis and with many people (Illeris, 2018). Whilst earlier comments have shown the realities of family today, participants also explained that when life does not present ‘ideal’ qualities that allow us to thrive we instinctively look for it elsewhere. Whilst some participants explained that they understood their role, as a practitioner in early education, teacher, or family support worker, was to provide those qualities I wondered if this perspective was a consensus amongst everyone working within these roles. Participants explained:

It doesn't matter if they are blood related because I've got very good relationships with blood related family and I've got very bad relationships with blood related family. If I can phone you at two o'clock in the morning, regardless of what situation I'm in, or where I am, and you are going to come and help me then, you are my kind of person. It's trust and loyalty and seeing past judgement and there is nothing that you or that other person could do that would break that and that doesn't always come with being blood.

Nicole

Mums, dads, aunts, uncles, grandparents, brothers, sisters you know everyone and out with that their wee secondary families, their school, their nursery and dance clubs or whatever. I take rainbows and guides, all of that all adds up as well. it is not just about what goes on in that house. Because if they don't have it at home, they look for it in the next place, which is school or nursery or wherever. It all adds up and it's just this continuum of family learning in the professional setting and how we are all sort of leading them on the same road. Whatever the best road is, trying to do the best for that individual child.

Jenny

Whilst the following participants agreed that where ‘ideal family’ expectations were not met that we seek them elsewhere and consider places like school to be,

not 'family' but what Steven described as "family like" groups that can influence "who we are" or as described by Susannah where we gain "support". Steven explains his point of view:

Adults, children, grandparents, [although] cousins, aunts and uncles could [be for others} ... they are family as well, but they are a kind of an outer ring of family. It's my mum, dad, sister and my dog, it is who lives in my house with me... [that is family] ... Not like any groups of friends or anything like that. I have had good connections, I have had family like groups, but I wouldn't class them as family. That's unique to me. You do get some support from education about who you are, but the majority comes from your family, but then some comes from the community and the people that you are around. You do learn from other people ... and it builds into your family. Your whole structure kind of builds who you are, and I think it can be changed by other people.

Steven

Steven's description of "outer ring of family" made me think about Bronfenbrenner's bioecological theory where various influences combine with our own personality, values and beliefs to affect who we become (Hayes, N; O'Toole and Halpenny, 2017) whilst relating to Sameroff's argument that nurture, and nature are both important for a 'family learning' process (Sameroff, 2010, Winston & Chicot, 2016). I was also reminded about the point made by Smart (2011) of the interrelationships between individual personality, culture, society, and power in gaining an ability to thrive in life. Other participants supported that where children's home lives are not 'ideal' they may consider the school setting as 'family' where they gain support and care.

It is the summer holidays I would imagine that some pupils will be looking forward to all the experiences they will do with that family. But for some this (school) is a family, what they're not getting at home. I can only imagine that some of them will be feeling this.

Victoria

If a pupil has a family where they can get that [care and support as family] but if they don't then yeah it [school] is.

Orla

We could take the word family away and then put in the word support, then that is it absolutely. It's the same as all your What's app groups, they may not consider it family, but their getting supports their getting help and their able to share stuff that they might not be able to get elsewhere.

Susannah

In the focus for this study the following statements are interesting, in that whilst they agree with other participants that support for learning should and can be gained in places other than family, they also note specific aspects that are important. Nicole explains that we should never be closed to opportunities for learning regardless of age or position as defined by society. Whilst Angela highlights the importance of having multiple opportunities and environments to gain various perspectives that allow us to choose and thrive in a way that is meaningful for us. These ideas of openness and opportunities for learning could present 'capital' that contribute to accessing a multitude of 'fields. Nicole explained:

Just because the person you are sitting with is five doesn't mean that you don't learn from them. And just because the person you are sitting with is a professor or whatever doesn't mean that they are not learning from you. I think that's quite apparent in family learning, that everybody's got their place, but everybody works together.

Nicole

I have learnt all these things from my family, but I have learnt all these things here as well. I had this wonderful friend, or this teacher and I can change ... So, I think that if you only have family learning as one group of people that's you for ever whether it be good or bad. That's never going to break the cycle.

Angela

Meanwhile, I found myself consistently returning to thinking that these aspects also require specific qualities to be most beneficial. The next section presents findings that may help to understand what specific qualities aid our ability to thrive.

5.4.2 Family learning as different connections.

Belinda was quite clear when describing what 'family learning' meant to her. She explained that it was the learning gained amongst her family and at home. Whilst open to the fact that 'family learning' can happen in educational settings, she also felt very strongly that connections in a school and nursery are different to connections in families. When asked why it was different, Belinda said:

Because you are not living it in the house. So, you go to nursery 9 till 5 and you have this great attachment to your practitioner and then you go home to your home life. That can give you that wee boost in life that just clicks, so it is different. Just having it naturally from your family. The connection is different, but then it can be gained and changed in any way because it happens at different stages in your life. I suppose family learning is different. Because family learning I first see as primarily that you are learning from your parents, immediate family and then out with that there is other learning.

Belinda

Whilst Belinda has named differences between 'family learning' in school and at home she has highlighted that connections between children and adults in both are important. Angela, describes different connections in terms of various

levels of 'love', highlighting a challenge in providing 'love' for groups of children where restrictions in nursery differ to that of a parent:

I think you have got two sides to it. If you come from a stable loving home and there are no issues, there is no one going to love that child more than their parents. Even if you have the best nursery workers in the world, I am still going to love my daughter more than you [nursery workers]. I am still going love my daughter more than my sister loves her or my mum loves her because that's my child. I think it is because the love that you feel for a child means that you would do anything for that child.

If I am in a nursery setting where I've got five children in my group...am I to say okay, I will drop everything for this child. Well, no because this child needs it as well and this child needs it. I can't put that one child ahead of these other children in the group.

Angela

Meanwhile, Carol's story provides explanation that love, and care doesn't always happen in either home or care setting. Carols story provides a sign of the impact of not having someone who as Angela explained "would do anything for you":

It's never going be the same as having one person who really cares about you, makes you feel special. For most people it's a parent isn't it. So, I worked with autistic children and these two boys were in care because of their family backgrounds, they both had terrible family backgrounds. One boy was non-verbal, but he would always say mum, mum. For the five years I worked with him. He would always say mum, where's mum. He would get his Makaton symbol and press mum, mum, mum all the time and I thought he knows. He was just dismissed because he's got severe learning difficulties, and he just does that. It's so frustrating, So, obviously that wasn't being addressed but he is in a great foster home now.

Carol

Caroline added to understanding that ‘family learning’ was different when experienced at home due to the “intimate” connections that existed between family members. In explaining the difference between learning in an educational setting and at home she noted:

I think it is more intimate ... usually, there is siblings or whatever, but usually it is a one-on-one kind of thing and you're actually learning how to do everything. Whereas when you are learning in a setting and you have got, even if you have got five or six children, you are taking a turn to mix, or one person mix and one person is pouring that ingredient. You are not enjoying the activity. You can go home and say I baked this cake and maybe put flour and maybe put eggs in.

But then if you do it at home, your mum would teach you, I could then go and do it again. At home it is like this is baking and yeah it is fun. You put one egg and then you put the flour in and that is the recipe that you follow.

Whereas I think if you do it in a setting, it is more about doing your motor skills, because in a childcare setting, we have so many more boxes that we need to tick that it becomes less about the actual thing that you are learning and more about what is going on around it. Whereas at home it is like your mum’s just baking a cake and you are helping and that is fun.

Caroline

Caroline’s explanation also made me consider the expectations of practitioners working in educational settings to ensure that children learn, develop and experience specific things. In respect of specific expectations, there is a plan for learning. In Caroline’s view it seems that the plan for learning and the number of children creates barriers to developing deeper personal connections between children and adults for learning that may be experienced in the home environment.

On reflection I wondered what was different as both scenarios seem to present specific aims for learning, however, I think Caroline is highlighting that experiences for learning within educational settings are shared whereas at home they may be focussed on one child or fewer children with learning being a fuller

cycle in understanding the whole process. I use the term ‘may’ in respect that not every child will gain the experiences outlined here. As a parent I could relate to this where I often worry at the level of detail I provide to my children when explaining something but the rationale behind it is to ensure they learn all that they require, everything they require to be able to thrive. On reflection I began to understand what Caroline seemed to be explaining, that it is difficult to ensure learning for all to thrive when supporting large groups of children or families.

Anna also provides a story about her family that shows not only, how families support each other in learning but how school learning is valued where her mum believed because she had not attended school as expected, that she did not have the capability to help. The belief that schools provide the best or the only way to learn in this instance had influenced belief of ability or ‘habitus’ and I wondered about the lifelong impact this has on people who have not performed well at school yet clearly have a contribution to make. Anna recalled:

I remember years ago, I was doing an English essay, and mum was in and out of school due to bad health, so she never ever felt that she had skills at all you know to help with homework. She would always make sure that I had the homework done she would have got me a tutor if I needed it. But I had written an essay, it was about describe your bedroom and I had just written a description. She was like no that’s rubbish let’s think about it, so she could verbally tell me. You need to say this, and you need to put that in. She was like the minute you walk in the room, the smell of pot-pourri, you know back in the eighties when that was the thing. She is really descriptive in her language. I remember getting a really good result and the teacher reading out my essay. That would never have happened if my mum had never put that wee input into it. So, I suppose that for me gave me a wee bit of confidence in English because I got the achievement recognised. Then I thought do you know maybe I could do this. I got really into English and probably that sparked a bit of interest, but it was with her input.

Anna

Anna's, story highlighted various aspects shown by other participants previously, where confidence in learning is gained in support and encouragement. Anna's comment about having her achievement recognised made me think about Donaldson's (1987:116) argument "how strong a need we have to communicate achievement to our fellow man and see it confirmed in their eyes". I draw similarities between the essence of meaning in this statement to that noted in research by Carpieneri (2012) that learning is motivated by personal connections and that a range of 'capital' is important to achieve learning. Motivation or 'habitus for learning requires consideration of the power and contribution of 'social and emotional capital'. However, the following section provides examples of challenges within educational practice in valuing social and emotional capital to build connections for learning.

5.4.3 Summary of Family Learning as development

This study has highlighted 'family learning' as development in terms of development of the individual, partnerships between families, educational establishments and development of society where changes in employment and technology were seen as key influences.

Participants viewed 'family learning' as the way in which to achieve your "full potential" which made me think about the statement made by Thorpe and Schmuller where the aim of learning is for "stimulating the human personality to its fullest expression" (Thorpe & Schmuller, 1954:9). However, on reflection on who decides what "full potential" is and consideration of participants viewpoints thus far, we can see that educational achievements are valued within families and educational settings and therefore deduced that performing well academically is considered as achieving "full potential". This finding made me think about the response from people in general when someone states that they

are doing well at school. pursuing a degree or like me completing a doctoral study, where it is, as Mary said, “highly regarded”. This viewpoint is fascinating as performance within academia does not ensure employment or guarantee that a person will contribute positively to “human flourishing” of others. It may be useful to consider that this belief is essentially a primal view that the strongest and the fittest will survive. In a world where educational attainment is valued then it is that premise that presents “positive outcomes” and ‘human capital’ that is of more value to the economy (OECD, 2001; Carpentieri, 2012). Meanwhile, participants highlighted the pressure that performance within academia presents. In considering the context for this study against these points I am left wondering what happens to those who cannot perform academically and question how we might address the difficulties to learn within conditions created by others more powerful.

However, development of the individual was also described in terms of learning; right from wrong, how to make the right decisions, how to build relationships, opportunity to develop own opinion, identity, and autonomy to voice own viewpoint or make own decisions and acceptance of who you are not who you need to be. In this sense we should recall the four capacities as an aim of the Scottish curriculum that children become “successful learners, confident individuals, responsible citizens and effective contributors” capacities that are now being considered in terms of their relevance for children today (Education Scotland, 2022). Participants collectively referred to relevant development as “life skills” or “everything you need” in gaining best outcomes. Throughout this section participants found that these aspects of development were gained from a variety of people and within a variety of places.

This study has also highlighted development being made by educational settings to work in partnership with families. Family contribution was identified as being more valued today, however, assumption of support needed, choosing not to be involved and relevant resources were identified as areas where negative judgement developed and therefore barriers to ‘success’ in development of partnership working.

Finally, the study highlighted development of societal views and behaviours and raised questions of how these affected judgement and ability to support children and families. Materialism or ‘neoliberal’ policy was identified as a key influence on family life and as Illeris (2018:18) would argue an “ambivalence to learning” in education for some due to the inability to perform within the standards expected. Employment and owning possessions were highlighted as being more valued than families spending time together. Developments in technology were also identified as solutions and alternative ways that families communicate and gain support where families were forced to seek employment and live elsewhere due to the closure of industry in many areas (Segal, 2014; Stranglemen, 2018). These points bring us nicely to the third and last section of this discussion chapter and the theme of ‘family learning’ as connections.

5.4.4 Family Learning as challenging connections in education.

The difficulty of building connections between teachers and pupils was highlighted by Nicole when she reflects on her experience as a child at school:

When I was at school 80 to 90% of the teachers had no idea who I was, like genuinely wouldn’t have known my name. And it wasn’t because I was particularly quiet or anything it was just; I had never come into contact with them, and they never came into contact with me and that was just that. I don’t necessarily think that’s a good thing.

Nicole

It was easy to relate to the point that Nicole was making, as a lecturer I work with varying sizes of class, without doubt I make stronger connections with students where class numbers are smaller. I gain time to know their names and get to know their story. Comments from students show that smaller groups help successful outcomes for learning where connections allow opportunities for dialogue and deeper understanding. In contrast, I struggle to even know every student name in larger groups.

On further reflection I can also recall supporting a primary school teacher and saw the difficulty that one person has in building connections with twenty-five children and their families alongside the anxiety this created. I saw the teacher shouting across the class of five-year-olds that she would rip their paintings up to show how she felt when they damaged resources in ‘her’ class. We might question what was being learned in this moment.

Participants in this study also recognised that there was, in some instances, less formality in schools which created positive connections between schools, children and families. For example, Mary welcomed a specific characteristic of informality between teachers and parents where she saw it as an important aspect of ‘family learning’ in terms of getting families involved with learning in school:

I think it’s nice to come into the school and everybody says “Hi [sons name]”, “Hi such n such” and it’s lovely. That freedom to come into the family learning team and just walk in and the girls at the desk will say “Oh hello Mrs “What can we do for you today? Or go down to Anna and we go into cookery, and we have Nicole or ask Anna how she’s getting on or Mrs K. It’s that atmosphere. It makes such a difference as you’re not as up tight. You’re not as anxious. When [my son] came from primary to secondary, I wasn’t worried about him at all because I had met the girls, and I thought it was fantastic. It was great thing.

Mary

Mary's argument for informality sits in line with the most useful characteristics identified as 'ideal' families (Morgan, 1975; Pahl and Spencer, 2004; Williams, 2004; Smart, 2007; Cronin, 2015). Mary also suggests having someone based within schools that does not have an official role or title, a "safe guardian". This idea was interesting in relation to this study, of what we need to be able to learn and thrive. We might therefore question if this should be a natural feature of practice and therefore a characteristic for *every* person to develop when working in support roles.

Wherever your child really needs that support that should always be available to them ... There should be a safe guardian. I think that there should be maybe a parent or somewhere that a child thinks right I can go there, and I can talk about this and it's not going to come back to anybody.

If you go to guidance or if you go to head of the year, it becomes official. When you talk about things to people who are official, it becomes all investigated and it all becomes a big drama, rather than being able to just go to somebody and say look I'm having a really crap day.

Mary

I was interested in Mary's point about how informality provided "that atmosphere" where she felt less "up tight or anxious" and could imagine how this helped to build relationships with the teachers and family support workers. Mary's comments also made me consider how formality creates barriers to building connections and providing support for families. I wondered why formality was important in educational settings. Nicole provided explanation that there were different views across schools and limits to informality with parents and children, particularly in terms of teachers in 'senior' positions. She also explained her view of why formality exists for some roles:

Across all the schools that I work in I am always Nicole I'm not Mrs or Miss whatever and I think that makes a huge difference. I know like for Anna (Mary adds, well she's a wee bit different). She wouldn't be Anna for everybody. She would be Anna to you guys' cos she's made that connection with you and not everyone would come in and say that. But I am always Nicole, and I think it's tricky for Anna and the equivalent [as a principal teacher] of her in other schools' cos I think it then becomes tricky for [Mary's son] and it's like, it's pally and nice and has that support and then he has to be in her class. And I can imagine that's quite hard. But for me it instantly breaks down the barrier. I'm not Mrs such n such I'm not formal. It's like this, and don't get me wrong the majority of teachers aren't like that, but I think for some people it creates a superiority, (Mary adds ... Yes! Yes! Yes!) I'm Mrs such n such and I'm a teacher and this is my room.

Nicole

On reflection of the comments made by Mary and Nicole, I could see that both valued informality and saw it as an essential element for building connections with others. I wondered where expectations of formality and informality derive from and consider 'professionalism' as a possible factor for expectations of approach. I was reminded of the work by Wingrave and McMahon (2016:713) where they note that expert knowledge and skills create a 'professional' who is set apart from others.

However, I also recall the question raised by Freire (1972:63) of "How can I enter into dialogue if I regard myself as a case apart from other men". This point reminded of the lack of dialogue with families in the 'Review of Family Learning' (Scottish Government, 2016b) and considered if 'professionalism' creates hierarchy and contributes to difficulties in having dialogue with some. I wondered if this is why we struggle to build partnership with families in Scottish education where, as 'professionals' we become a 'case apart' (Mackenzie, 2010; National Parent Forum of Scotland, 2016).

I was also reminded of the legal expectation of care and blame culture arising from previous child abuse cases which have positioned a requirement for formal processes to be adhered to ensure best outcomes and wonder how and if

informality can be balanced with this expectation (Laming, 2003; Department of Education, 2010; Coventry LSCB, 2013; SSSC,2016; Scottish Government, 2017d, GTCS,2021).

Meanwhile, Ashleigh also stressed that ‘family learning’ at home was different to what happened in educational settings. Ashleigh outlines connections made in ‘family learning’ through “intimate, care and love” and adds to the points made previously that these are difficult to provide in educational settings where you are supporting a lot of children whilst also highlighting that caring was a parental responsibility. This point was interesting in terms of the importance of feeling cared for and loved highlighted by participants, literature and the recent research completed by Page (2018) and Malcolm (2022) who find that considering ‘love’ in ‘professional’ roles is difficult. Reflecting on her role as a practitioner in early education, Ashleigh explained:

In a nursery if you have got forty children all at once you can't be as intimate with them. You need to care about them all equally and love them all equally, but it is just, it doesn't meet, what someone that should care about them as much, like what a parent should.

Ashleigh

Ashleigh also added to her earlier story that ‘family learning’ connections were shared between adults and children throughout generations. She reiterated the role of family members was to care for each other. Caring was given from adults to children and then reciprocated by children. Ashleigh’s comments made me consider the importance of the contribution of children in ‘family learning’ connections as an intergenerational process. She also provided details that ‘family learning’ experiences were motivated for the benefit of all family members, when she described that:

As a child I think I experienced family learning a lot. My parents both worked, my dad had two jobs, and my mum worked full time, so my grandparents watched us a lot. It was like right these children could be in nursery full time, or they could be with family ... It was the whole family working together to make sure the best outcomes happened for everyone. That has really followed on throughout my family to the point of my gran is now the one that needs cared for and now we have got that system of, when can you watch her or when can you watch her? We are now doing for her what she did for us as children. And I think that is my first experience of family learning.

Ashleigh

Ashleigh's example made me consider the plan to expand the hours of childcare provided in Scottish ELCC to 1140 hours per year (Scottish Government, 2020) and of the impact that this may have for future generations and expectations of care. I understand the rationale behind the scheme is to allow more adults to train and gain employment which aims to improve financial situations of families living in Scotland and the economy.

However, I wonder what learning is being gained in terms of responsibility of care. In plans that educational settings will provide more care; I wonder if we will learn that care is a responsibility of others. I also question, if 'love', relationships and specific connections are important for learning and development (UNICEF, 1990; Deacon, 2011; Winston and Chicot, 2016; Page, 2011, 2018; Malcolm, 2022; Zeedyk, 2022) yet difficult to include in 'professional' roles (Taggart, 2016; Page, 2018; Malcolm, 2022) then what impact will this have on future generations. I also question if this care should or could match that of families and include the specific qualities of care most beneficial for learning and development of Scottish society. I was interested to hear Caroline expressing similar concerns:

My fear is that, introducing the 1140 hours is a great and wonderful thing to let parents out to work because it helps the parents who do want to get on which is fantastic and its free childcare. It also helps the kids who are deprived and in poverty. Absolutely, looking at this model, it's a fantastic win-win situation. But I am thinking ahead, I am

thinking right okay this sounds all lovely and wonderful but where is it going? The impact?

It's just for vulnerable twos at the moment, then a few years down the line it then becomes compulsory for two-year-olds and then it becomes compulsory that they [all children] are all in all day, every day like school. Then it becomes no you can't take your child out of nursery to go for a whole family holiday.

I would say that bringing children into nursery all day from the age of two is actually replacing the parents as family. It's a different family. For me parents are the primary source for their children's learning, and they want what's best. I know there is cases where children are not getting that at home, but I would say pretty much on the whole parents want the best for their kids, you learn mostly from your parents and the environment that you are in. I think the family unit is going to be more of a herd mentality.

It's almost like a kind of mass market learning There is a different learning going on in nursery because you are sharing a room with another twenty, thirty sometimes forty children. You are not getting that one-on-one care that you are definitely going to get with your parents. So, I'm (big sigh) kind of against these 1140 hours I really don't think it's best for the child, as I say, for the few, but for the majority I just think that they are missing out and the parents are missing out as well.

Caroline

Caroline's passion about this was clear in the exasperation she displayed when explaining her view. I understood her concern and wondered about the rationale again. The following findings may show other reasons for childcare being supported where challenges to build connections do not only exist within educational settings. The following section highlights some of the challenges in building connections amongst families for learning and consideration of what would be needed to support these challenges.

5.4.5 'Family learning' as challenging connections in families.

Participants share concerns that sometimes connections for learning are not gained in families and talk with sadness that families provide various levels of

support which mean children sometimes have to look elsewhere for the experiences and support normally gained in the family. When asked what ‘family learning’ meant to Annabelle, she showed the picture of a child laughing whilst being thrown in the air and noted:

I want all families to be like this. I know not all families are like that. That’s how I was brought up so that’s how it was done. I think nurture and good relationships is a key for families to grow and develop. I imagine things of how I was brought up and of how what I see on a daily basis in here, you think two ways about it, as such.....every space? As a family.

Annabelle

I think about all of those experiences that I had when I was younger, like learning to write my name and stuff and it was my mum and dad who I can remember sitting, and my mum drawing the wee dots and connecting them all up, but I can’t remember doing that in nursery. So now with children, like am sharing so many of those experiences to children and I think it’s my mum who showed this to me and it should be your mum who is sharing this with you almost which is quite upsetting.

Jenny

Mary’s story offers a range of considerations of what ‘family learning’ is for some and of what is needed to change these situations:

Nobody knows what’s round the corner for anybody and it’s just so sad when people actually judge people. They should really walk in their shoes for a wee while and see what their issues are and what their kid’s issues are. Because lots of kids have lots of issues. I had three wee children that I brought up and they came from a very poor background. They had no mattress they slept on the floor. They had no clothes, quite shocking. I would never like to think anybody should have to live like. It was an eye opener when I went to get them, I thought, Oh my god. All mum could do was drink and all dad could do was drink. So unfortunately for them they grew up messed up.

Not everybody’s family is their support system, so when they go into nursery that key worker could become their family. That’s the person they trust. It’s early intervention,

so if something is happening in that home life then you're the one that is going to protect that child and get that child help, so you become their sense of family, their sense of support.

Mary

June and Nicole also highlight challenges around families understanding each other's needs and the most suitable ways of fulfilling those requirements:

It is like a tug of war with your child. Trying to get on the same page as them, to understand the way they think and feel about things. You want to work as a team to understand their side. Our family learning worker would give us activities to do. Usually, I was more interested in them than he was, I mean I tried. I was like, I can't wait to see how this works out. It was some things that we could do together.

June

Although, I also began to wonder if the tug of war was created in 'family learning' where there were differing views of what was important or valued by whoever was involved and considered the generational differences highlighted in the earlier section. Nicole noted that differences in families were a common observation in her role as a family support worker when she explained:

I think in this job you see a lot of families that aren't always necessarily on the same path ... Like they are working toward the same thing, and they want the same thing but that might be a bit of a battle so you might find that they are on different paths.

Nicole

Meanwhile the following stories highlight different societal influences and opinions that create challenges in building connections amongst families and the lifelong impact that they can have:

I've been working with some foster kids that have turned eighteen and that's them their out. There was one boy he's been with his foster carer since he was seven. He's eighteen and she wants nothing to do with him now, she's like that's you. I couldn't do that without thinking that I was that child's parent. It's so strange because the woman, I mean no harm, she took in the five siblings. They were all related and it was so hard to get them placed together and she took them in. She was the only wanting two foster children, but she took in all five, which is amazing that she did it. But now his siblings are with his foster carer, who is like you're not coming here. You're not eating my food. That's you, get your own house.

Steven

My gran was adopted by another family member. But now she'll talk about growing up she'll go on about, my sister, but not the one I lived with. it's her real sister, her blood sister, and then there's the sister who she grew up with. She has a sister who she never met until she was sixteen years old, and I always thought that's so sad those sisters should have been sharing experiences together and haven't been.

Claire

I had a friend at school who was a twin, and the boys were eleven twelve before they were put into foster care. They were dotted about and causing a lot of disruptive behaviour in people's houses. People were saying I cannot live with these two boys and then they were adopted by a same sex couple, two women. At first, they were like two mums, like, no chance. They always say about the day that they went in and met them, and it just felt right and away they went that day, and they were there ever since until they turned eighteen. It wasn't like you're out on your ear, it was like if you're going to start paying dig money, your more than welcome. That becomes their family, they would always say "my mum said this, or my mum said that" and their friends used to wind them up saying, "oh what one?"

They would call them by their name or whatever but when they were talking about them, they would say their mum and I used to think that was so nice. If they had not had that family unit growing up at eleven and were taken in and loved and cared for and they were helped to get their own flats and things like that. But still their up there every week for family dinners and birthday parties and things like that. It's so

refreshing to see and it's so horrible when you hear stories ... and it does happen, you see it in practice.

Jenny

The stories shared by Steven, Claire and Jenny resonated with my own experience of being brought up in a family that fostered children. I remember the emotional pressure placed on my mum when social work arrived with yet another child. I recall the effect of trauma displayed in the behaviours of the children. I remember how vulnerable they were where they did not have the 'safe guardian' that Mary referred to earlier. Whilst it was expected that the foster home would provide that, it was not always the case. I remember what was learned and the lifelong impact that it had for, not only these children, but for everyone involved.

The earlier findings highlight that family needs to be more than who we live with or who we are blood related to in order for us to gain what is needed for human flourishing. Findings also noted the importance of connections for learning and whilst finding that there are challenges in developing connections for learning within both families and educational settings. The following findings explain what qualities participants felt were important in addressing these challenges.

5.4.6 'Family learning' requires specific qualities for connections.

Participants raised questioning around the importance and the most effective characteristics that aid connections for 'family learning' whilst also highlighting characteristics that were barriers for learning and development.

It needs the right people in place. The school I worked in before, one of the teachers had come in and she was really all about family learning ... So, they would have fun days and bring them in and do 'Book Bug', but they just had fun. They never mentioned family learning they just made it fun. So, they were unaware it was happening, it was just building relationships and giving them a support network.

I think that's the key. You're there and you listen to them and you're being caring and taking time with them cos otherwise it's just putting peoples back up I suppose. It's just like a kind of ethos, a caring ethos in the school. They are aware that to support these kids you need to support the parents as well and be more aware of their needs. People have so much pressure now, a lot of people put so much pressure on themselves to be the same as everybody else. You don't have to be. You've got to understand that you are unique, your families unique and we understand that. I have been lucky that I saw a lot of good practice, at my kid's school and where I work but I have also seen places that aren't so good at it.

So, it's just having the right people, like teaching people that's what they need to do. It's not just about teaching the kids. Some people haven't got it. Some people don't get it. I think it's a quality you either have or you haven't. I think it has to be that you're not just doing the job because you need the money, that you're doing the job because you actually care. It's like a vocation. you want to help people, and you want to help their families, and you will treat everybody the same even though they have different circumstances, and I think that's got to be part of the job.

Carol

There is a need for attachments and knowing someone cares. We've got a young mum who is great mum, and the child is great, but mum really struggles with mental health. She feels that she is destroying this child's life. We are like, listen we're not just here for your daughter we are here for you. If you ever need a cup of tea, you just phone and you come in and you do that.

The head of my centre said you cannot help this child until you help yourself. It's like being in an aircraft and there's an accident and you put on your own life vest before you help anyone else. He said that's true in life, if you're not okay how can you make sure that people around you are okay.

Her sister has taken the child to give mum a bit of respite, to sort herself out. Her parents are not around, so it's her sister and her sister is trying to learn how to be a parent for her own child and now also feels that she's parenting her wee sister as well.

I must say the child is thriving and she's absolutely thriving and mums doing really, really well but she just needs that wee bit of support.

Claire

People who you know care about you. To build other positive relationships. I think it's a sense of belonging. A sense of happiness, that in yourself you feel I belong here I am happy here. If I feel supported, I don't feel worried. It's like that safe place, these people are your safe place.

Angela

I think you need all the pieces in the right place for appropriate family learning. You need a family unit in place, you need support from that family unit, you need encouragement, you need the love. It's what helps you breathe. You need that person, that support, you need to know that someone loves you. If you take one piece out it's incomplete.

Steven

Feeling like you belong somewhere and that you're needed. and if all those pieces are all together, like being in a family unit, if you're lucky enough to be in a family that supports each other and if you come from a family that doesn't have that, you look for it in other different places.

It [family learning] needs people that care. A lot of people that are in these jobs or working with children just don't really care. I've worked with people who are just like, well that's just the way it is. It rubs off and they [children] learn to be the same. I think that you've got to remember that a wee bit of kindness, kids need it, they might not be getting it at home. I just think that you'll be a better practitioner if you have that wee bit of caring side to you.

It [caring] passes on. We want people to be kind. You learn from example. Nobody wants to live in an uncaring world. You've got to pass it on. If you're dealing with families, they might have had a rotten five years or something, somebody takes that wee bit of time and shows that they actually care. It can make a huge impact on their lives.

Donna

Donna's comments made me think about the collective purpose of learning presented by Illeris (2018) where specific learning experiences can help to gain understanding and compassion for others. Donna's argument was simple yet powerful. However, the current focus on educational attainment and academic

performance presents a lot of pressure for all involved with further agreement that ‘family learning’ connections require time. The next section offers the views of participants of other aspects needed.

5.4.7 Family Learning needs time for connections.

You need to listen. listening is the key ... You need to hear what they are saying. They need to believe that they are being listened to.

Orla

Family learning is listening, if you are working with kids or if you’ve got kids in your life that you’ve got to listen to them. The way they are, the actions, the behaviours is all reflected on the kind of family that they come from, so you have to be listening to the parents as well. I’ve worked with a lot of kids that have behaviour problems and all of that and it all stems from their family.

Donna

You need the time to listen, which is a decision, I think. You kind of half listen to a person sometimes, which is fine. But to actually do real listening is crucial.

It’s amazing if you just stop and you take a break and spend time with that young person. I am guilty as well at home there is so many other things that I don’t spend the time at home with that I should. Lots of our young people and our guidance teachers come to us and tell us that their parents don’t talk to them. They’re on their phones or they are out with their friends and out working. Time is something that a lot of young people don’t seem to get. I think everyone’s so much busier, and everyone’s distracted. Parents don’t seem to make time.

I don’t mean that staff don’t, but I mean we’re pressed in terms of being able to spend time with our young people so that’s key as well, and time with the parents. Ideally, I would be able to be off the phone to a parent in five minutes but when I’ve just spent twenty minutes on the phone talking to a parent and I’m thinking I’ve got this and that to do but it was a really worthwhile conversation I’m glad that I made time to speak to this person. So, for me time is key.

Victoria

I found these points relevant to the social conditions that families and supporting agencies now find themselves in, where technology and expectations of performance and employment present barriers for making connections.

I was reminded of research conducted by Wainwright and Marandet (2017) that highlighted a ‘nexus’ of expectation between mothers expected to care, work and attend ‘family learning’ initiatives. I found this concept useful in combination with Bourdieu’s theory of habitus, capital and field. For example, if we consider ‘family learning’ as the ‘field of play’, findings in this study have highlighted; challenges in building connections between people due to differing values of ‘capital’ (MacKenzie, 2010; Szeman and Kaposy, 2011; Cara and Brooks, 2012; Mutch, 2013) for effective ‘family learning’, these affect ‘habitus or ability to perform within the field (Earle, 1999). These factors ultimately present a nexus when combined with the aim of educational attainment, employment and social justice as key values for current Scottish society

5.4.8 Summary of ‘family learning’ as connections

The study has highlighted that participants relate to the definitions of contemporary family life highlighted within the literature where families and communities for learning provide more accurate descriptions than family as a single unit of support (hooks, 2000, Williams, 2004, Morgan, 2011).

An important aspect of this section in terms of the focus for this study, were the qualities that made them ‘family learning’ connections. I could see similarities between what is important for learning. For example, that key elements of secure relationships, understanding, attention, time, and love are important for learning to occur (UNICEF, 1990; Deacon, 2011; Winston and Chicot, 2016; Page, 2011, 2018; Malcolm, 2022; Zeedyk, 2022).

However, in listening to, reviewing, and collating these findings I found myself constantly considering that these ‘ideal’ scenarios did not always exist and was keen to understand what the barriers were and of how participants felt they could be overcome.

Barriers to connections for ‘family learning’ were described as difficulties in educational provision where formal approaches made families feel judged, anxious, and uncomfortable. This was an interesting point as it contrasts with beneficial characteristics of family and for learning (Morgan, 1975; Pahl and Spencer, 2004; Williams, 2004; Smart, 2007; Cronin, 2015). Findings also highlighted difficulties in families affect abilities to make connections and further rationale for providing ‘communities’ of support for learning (hooks, 2000 Williams, 2004; Morgan, 2011; Scottish Government, 2016c; Elkjaer, 2018).

Most importantly, participants found a wide range of characteristics that at times echoed what the literature review had noted whilst also highlighting aspects may be overlooked for ‘family learning’ to ensure “human flourishing” (Underwood,2009:9). Characteristics like those outlined in literature were the requirement for; awareness of both child and parental needs, equity, support, listening, caring and attachment. Alongside the consideration of formality and judgement present in ‘professional’ roles, participants named the following as not specifically considered as key characteristics for effective ‘family learning’ approaches.

Participants noted a requirement to address the difficulties of gaining “time to build connections” as these were often sidelined in favour of meeting other aims and expectations. Time to build connections provides crucial elements for learning, such as, a sense of “belonging, feeling loved, safe and happy.” In addition to gaining time, participants also raised an awareness that the ability to build connections with others is not always a natural skill that is held by people

working in supporting agencies, calling for address of how we might develop this skill in training for roles related to supporting children and families.

6 Development of ‘Learning Relations’ a model of reflection for future practice.

The study began with my own feeling of what family learning meant to me and a review of literature that presented a completely different view of ‘family learning’. I can recall an early conversation and suggestion to my supervision team that ‘love’ could be an important concept to consider for ‘family learning’ and being met by confusion and concern that ‘love’ was a difficult concept to address in academia. Guidance was that I would have to find a theory that would support my approach. The familiar feeling of disdain once again fuelled my motivation and I found ‘Compassionate Love theory’ (Fehr et al, 2009) a theory and model of working to aid ‘human flourishing’ during one of many all-night study sessions.

Preceding review of literature provided confirmation that my ideas were valid in that others felt the same. As a result, they provided key influence and motivation for this study. For example, the ideas presented by Freire (1972) in ‘Pedagogy of the Oppressed’ opened my mind to the complex and powerful world that we are situated within, the work of Jeannie MacKenzie (2010) provided my first confirmation that ‘family learning’ could be considered in different ways. The writing of Doreen Grant and her passion to break down barriers to working in partnership with families in Govan Glasgow, the vision of her connecting with families at the ‘windae’ and my imaginings of the ‘stairhead seminars’ alongside the title of her book has remained a guiding influence for me.

From the analysis of data, I continually tried to envisage a model of working. Love of course would be at its heart. In attempting to capture the history and influences for learning I sketched web like images of figures in lines emanating from a central heart. Each row would depict the various influences and history

of family, government, community, education, religion etc. Between each row would be lines connecting everything together, I called it the ‘Family learning web of influence’. However, I didn’t like the complexity of it, there could be no catchy acronym to be had, and the reference to web and spiders made me fearful of the first impression it might make. A web with a heart seemed slightly sinister. I wanted a simple visual message promoting the importance of love for learning to be explored, of course, through dialogue.

The difficulty of building partnerships and the idea that it was patronising for authorities on education to claim the title ‘family learning, took me back to Doreen Grant’s work and ‘Learning Relations’ believing the title reflects exactly what this study has shown ‘family learning’ to be. In the use of her book title, I felt it right to contact her and ask permission but was saddened to discover that Doreen had passed in 2015. I hope that in my understanding of what Doreen worked tirelessly to achieve, and the contribution made from this study that her work continues. I honour her mission, and that of many others, by creating a principle for a new model of working with families. I present and return to the call made by Denzin and Lincoln (2018 p. xii) in “hope with no guarantee”, a new term for ‘family learning’ and a model of partnership for practice with ‘compassionate love’ as a guiding characteristic.

Learning Relations.

Difference Connection.

The study presents the term and model of ‘Learning Relations’ should be used to consider ‘family learning’ in a much broader sense that it is currently viewed. The model encourages practitioners working to support families to consider the answers to the main research questions for this study of what ‘family learning’ means, of where ‘family learning’ happens and of what ‘family learning’

requires. A 'Learning Relations' model is guided by 'Compassionate Love' in acknowledging influence of the "biological, social, environmental and cultural factors" in the process. The model encourages practice to be guided by the key constructs of 'Compassionate Love' where; motivations for actions are for the other in the first instance whilst demonstrating depth of understanding of positionality of self and for others which encourages respect, openness, receptiveness, and actions that are heartfelt (Underwood,2009:7). The model encourages practitioners to:

- Acknowledge and respect that 'Learning relations' are different for everybody, that 'Learning Relations' happen in different places and require acceptance of different views and requirements.
- Show that 'Learning Relations' are development of individuals, communities, and wider society. That 'Learning Relations' happen and require constant development of approach.
- Consider that 'Learning Relations' are connections between people. Reflection helps to consider how connections for the most effective 'Learning Relations' happen and what these connections require, finding solutions to barriers.

7 Conclusion and Recommendations.

Throughout this study, I have continually questioned the validity of the argument I am trying to make. My colleagues will confirm my continual frustration at having to confirm, what I believe to be quite simple. Yet, I understand that in consideration of the power of economic finances and the subsequent societal values that this promotes, it seems ridiculous as Deacon (2011) had noted previously, to suggest that ‘love’ should be an important currency in the political market and all that this promotes.

However, in reference to the notion of ‘love’ as outlined within ‘Compassionate Love theory’ (Fehr et al, 2009), review of literature on what is required for families and learning to enable social justice in Scotland alongside the personal connection we and participants of this study can make to the importance of love provides validation. Recall of life experience where love provides ‘ideal’ foundations to flourish and contribute, sits in contrast to that where ‘love’ is lacking and provides the premise on which I base the thesis that ‘love’ in any provision in support of families presents an opportunity to lay the foundations of a much wealthier prosperous nation.

The study has shown within the review of literature relating to ‘family learning’, contradictions and challenges between policy and practice alongside a gap in knowledge around the subject where there has been limited dialogue with families to establish what ‘family learning’ means to them. The lack of communication with families presented an ideal rationale for the study and premise to establish aims and main research questions for this study to address the contradictions and challenges in policy and practice.

This chapter begins with a reminder of the rationale, aims and objectives for this study. The chapter continues with a summary of what is known, what is

problematic along with what is needed in terms of future policy, research and practice.

The aim for this study was to fulfil the gap in knowledge around the subject of ‘family learning’. The study findings contribute to finding recommendations for excellent ‘family learning’ practice in promoting positive relationships between educational establishments and families.

The objectives for the study were:

- To gain understanding of how ‘family learning’ is defined by families and practitioners.
- To understand how families learn together.
- To identify why families, learn together.
- To explore what key aspects are important for ‘family learning’.
- To understand why these key aspects are important for ‘family learning’.

The main research questions were:

- What does the term family learning mean?
- Where does family learning happen?
- What is important for family learning?

The following recommendations provide the contribution to knowledge to inform future policy, practice, and research by drawing on the findings from each of the three key themes of difference, development, and connection.

7.1 Policy Recommendations

7.1.1 Policy relating to ‘family learning’: What have we learned?

During the period of focus we can see that a range of legislative and policy frameworks created by UK and Scottish governments and the various political parties who have retained power from 1960 to present day have supported and influenced family life in Scotland. The range of government influence has resulted in a variety of differing aims and goals as set by each governing party which have presented specific expectations of families in supporting learning and development. Current neoliberal politics have presented major changes in family life as economic value promotes a drive for educational attainment, employment and material possessions as key indicators of successful outcomes.

Power and Whitty (1999) noted changes in political approaches with the ‘third way’ promoting partnership with families. The term ‘family learning’ was used to describe a partnership approach to enhance performance or attainment at school. ‘Third way’ strategies sought to find families at risk of poor outcomes and build capacity to secure best outcomes for themselves. Yet, preceding literature has highlighted that a ‘family learning’ approach should be based on ‘wealth’ models and not be considered as a method that will fix family deficits.

Current Scottish government aims for social justice and a drive for economic development has saw a rise in educational approaches to address barriers to achieving ‘social justice’ for individuals, communities and Scottish society through economic progress. Meanwhile the review of literature also highlighted that achieving ‘ideal’ families and learning opportunities requires key characteristics of secure relationships, understanding, attention, time and love.

7.1.2 Policy relating to ‘Family learning’: What is the problem.

The review of literature on ‘family learning’ explained that political focus has continued from the 1960’s with interest on developing ‘human capital’ driving early intervention initiatives. These initiatives saw a focus of healthy development as key for reducing economic cost and regarded as future investment. Levitas (2005) notes that the focus on economic development and who can contribute best has promoted three discourses.

First, a moral underclass discourse identifies family values, behaviour and practices that are believed to contribute to economic development least. I add that the continual reference to ‘disadvantaged’ families throughout the Scottish policy framework and practice guidance for educational services provides added contribution to this discourse. The discourse encourages programmes that target specific families believed to fall into this category and aims to improve behaviours, for example, Solihull, Triple P and PEEP programmes. Findings from my research support that this discourse is influencing ‘family learning’ practice where Scarlett and Donna reported that programmes were targeting families who were considered as lacking skills.

Secondly, a social integrationist discourse, values activities which are seen to contribute to economic production, for example, educational attainment and employment. This discourse relates to current government initiatives such as ‘Raising Attainment for All’ programme and the expansion of childcare in Scotland that support the current perspective and rationale for a ‘family learning’ approach.

Thirdly, a redistributionist discourse identifies the effects of poverty and aims to address social inequalities and is recognised as a positive. However, the use of Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) is questioned as a reliable indicator of support in Scotland and may be perpetuating a deficit view of

families living within particular areas. A particular example is the reliance of SIMD for distribution of Pupil Equity Funding (PEF) amongst Scottish schools alongside limited involvement of families in decisions around how these funds should be spent as perpetuating poor outcomes.

The rationale and motivations for early intervention is also questioned in promoting a requirement for public services minimising privatisation whilst adding that the focus of key periods, such as early years, negates the support needed throughout an individual's lifetime. The literature presents a requirement for an ecological view of the environmental factors that affect families lives where trauma is not always resulting from experiences in families.

This thesis adds that whilst love from families has been identified as important for the ability to thrive, the use of the word 'love' in policy is limited. In addition, whilst policy promotes that families need 'professional' quality support; policy discourse promotes a deficit discourse of families amongst 'professional' services, in addition power is presented as an acceptable quality of practice whilst the use of the word 'love' in 'professional' practice guidance is found to be difficult.

In consideration of all these points, we must reflect on recognising elements that perpetuate power and control over family life whilst showing how they affect genuine partnerships to be built with families. I suggest that political aims are driving particular policy discourse, approaches and perceptions of families in practice that may be missing important factors and therefore contributing to difficulties in building partnership with families in Scottish schools.

7.1.3 Policy relation to 'family learning': What do we need?

I assert that economic focus has promoted measures of contribution and has created negative discourses which positions certain families within a deficit viewpoint amongst educational settings. Government aims of building economic stability presents power over what learning is valued and promoted. As such, specific programmes such as ‘family learning’ have developed to drive academic learning as most valued and to fix what some families lack. The hope is that academic learning will help to gain human flourishing.

However, the belief that only academic learning contributes to successful outcomes, sets individuals apart where success in academia is seen to contribute more to the economy. Where individuals cannot meet expectations or do not value the learning being expected, they may be judged as not contributing and considered from a deficit viewpoint. This thinking creates divides and barriers to genuine, respectful, understanding partnerships and opportunities for all to thrive.

To achieve the specific learning or fix what is needed to aid the economy, we must consider the fundamental internal and external qualities needed to achieve learning that leads to human flourishing, for some that may be different and not always academic learning in the first instance.

Policy needs:

- Informed by further research with families to establish what is needed.
- Review of current discourse and amendments to present a consistent positive discourse of the contribution that families make to the learning process.
- Progression of the current ‘Getting it Right for Every Child’(GIRFEC) approach to ‘Getting it Right for Every Family’ (GIRFEF). Development of the ‘Learning Relations’ model of working outlined in Chapter 7 of thesis aims to show what is needed in a GIRFEF approach.

- Action and public acknowledgement that some historical and current supporting family practice has contributed to barriers for support.
- Action to provide the time and funding required within services to enable proper levels of support needed.

7.2 Recommendations for Research.

7.2.1 Research on ‘family learning’: What do we know?

Government aims have influenced policy to focus on academic shortfalls within families. Yet research reports and reviews have presented conflicting views of whether family background is a predictor of ability. Meanwhile dominant beliefs consider that educational ability to be a factor relating to the socio-economic status of families. Historical reviews had highlighted that family background affect children’s attainment at school, yet sociologists had been perplexed by differences in school achievement of children from different social backgrounds with preceding studies highlighting that social class should not be a predictor of ability.

Further research highlighted gaps in understanding around the wider benefits that ‘family learning’ programmes could provide where funding for research and evaluations were based around government aims. Some research studies found that neoliberalist politics have created a focus on education as the means to develop the economy and has promoted beliefs amongst schools that families living in low socio-economic areas lack ability to contribute and require support. Whilst other studies suggest that the neoliberal economic drive to improve educational attainment and increase employment has presented a nexus where ‘family learning’ programmes and partnership with families also expect that families will have the time to attend settings.

Yet, earlier research studies highlight limited participation of individuals on the subject of ‘family learning’ and therefore limited understanding for the most effective change. The ‘Review of Family Learning’ conducted by Scottish Government also noted that it lacked consultation with families living in Scotland and therefore a limited understanding of what ‘family learning’ means to them or of what is needed from ‘family learning’ to ensure human flourishing.

Other studies note challenges for participation in ‘family learning’ programmes, such as a lack of childcare facilities, and that governments hold narrow views of ‘human capital’ with resulting educational experiences affecting motivations and creating “dispositional barriers” to learning which the studies highlight can only be supported through address of internal and external factors.

Findings from research also encouraged requirement of an ecological perspective of factors affecting learning with calls for ‘social capital’ to be a focus for educational services as ‘human capital’ relies on learning and skills to be shared. The review of research literature noted a distinct lack of research on ‘family learning’ in Scotland with an additional limited focus of ‘social capital’ in relation to ‘family learning’ as often based on developing school systems, presenting a narrow view and the importance of ‘social capital’ amongst families. Research has also highlighted a focus on developing cultural capital of disadvantaged families where there was an assumed lack of educational focussed habitus whilst reporting that “softer” aspects of ‘family learning’ were overlooked. Meanwhile, alternative research had noted the importance of emotional capital for the development of other forms of capital.

7.2.2 Research on ‘family learning’: What is the problem?

Research has highlighted limited participation of families in research studies on ‘family learning’ presenting a narrow focus of ‘family learning’ in terms of what ‘capital’ is most valuable or important to consider in relation to families and learning. Earlier studies have focussed on government aims and evaluating impact of programmes on improvement of literacy and numeracy skills which have also resulted in a limited understanding of how family flourishing has been enabled or of any other unplanned benefits.

My study has fulfilled gaps in knowledge around ‘family learning’ by gaining opinions from participants on what ‘family learning’ means to them, of where they felt it happened and of what was needed for ‘family learning’ to ensure “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:9). Participants highlighted that aims for effective ‘family learning’ were similar to that presented by government and policy where learning and development to aid the ability to thrive was the purpose for ‘family learning’.

However, a key difference was that all participants viewed ‘family learning’ as something that happened in their families and was different to learning that happened in school in that it was natural everyday experiences and not following a curriculum plan. Essential elements for ‘ideal family learning’ were identified by participants as, secure relationships, understanding, attention, a sense of happiness, belonging and love. These elements matched what had been highlighted in literature around what is needed for ‘ideal’ family and learning experiences. However, these characteristics sat in contrast to the principal elements noted in government based ‘family learning’ initiatives. It is interesting to consider if these findings relate to the overlooked “softer” aspects named by Cara and Brooks (2012) and the important “internal factors” noted by Hartas (2014).

An additional important finding from this research was that ‘families’ do not or cannot always provide what is needed to thrive. As such, participant views echoed the sentiment of bell hooks (2000) and noted the requirement for loving family like communities to be experienced in places out with the home, providing an alternative view of ‘family learning’. However, as noted previously, research conducted by Page (2018), Morris (2021) and Malcolm (2022) have highlighted difficulties in considering the concept of ‘love’ alongside ‘professional’ expectations of practitioners and teachers working in educational settings.

An equally important challenge named by participants within my study was the time needed for communication, building relationships and environments that were most effective for ‘family learning’ as loving family like communities. Developments in the way society and family life had changed recognised the increased use of technology to aid communication. However, discussions around the use of technology in daily family life presented interesting questioning of whether ‘social media’ could or should be considered as a characteristic of families and related to the idea where modern families include both human and non-human elements or “family assemblage” as suggested by Price -Robertson and Duff (2018:1).

7.2.3 Research on ‘family learning’: What does future research on ‘family learning’ require?

- Further studies. Whilst this research study has gained new knowledge and understanding on the topic of ‘family learning’, it has only scratched the surface where this study has presented the beginning for a wide range of aspects that require further exploration. The study has, in terms of the

whole Scottish population, involved a small sample that lacks a broad representation of the diverse family cultures living within Scotland.

- Whilst the study has gained an important insight into what is important for ‘family learning’ and the challenges faced in gaining these. Further opportunities for research are found in understanding more deeply what difficulties families face with learning and of what is needed to overcome these.
- Additionally, further exploration is needed to examine the importance of ‘love’ and how we overcome the challenge of ‘love’ in ‘professional family learning’ practice. Further research that gains the views of practitioners and teachers working in family support roles on the application and challenges of applying ‘love’ in practice.
- Other research opportunity is also found in the idea of “family assemblage” in considering the range of human and non-human elements that are key features for ‘family learning’ today whilst providing opportunity to consider ‘family learning’ from alternative contemporary theoretical viewpoints. For example, developments in technology and the influence of social media on ‘family learning’ presents an interesting and contemporary area for exploration.
- In response to earlier research and the findings from this study, there is an opportunity and requirement for a longitudinal study that incorporates various methodologies to address the range of elements related to the subject of ‘family learning’ and human flourishing.

7.3 Practice Recommendations.

7.3.1 Practice relating to ‘Family learning’: What do we know?

As government aims of economic development have influenced how ‘family learning’ is viewed, it has therefore encouraged, not only, a narrow focus for research on the subject but also influenced approaches in educational practice to assume what is regarded as a ‘family learning’ approach. Current ‘family learning’ practice focuses on development of partnership with parents to aid educational attainment and aligns with educational initiatives such as ‘Raising Attainment For All’ (RAFA) (Scottish Government, 2014). ‘Family learning’ is gained through various activities aligned with the aim of educational settings with limited focus or value placed on the contribution that families make in the learning process which sits in contradiction to ‘family learning’ as a wealth model (Nutbrown et al, 2015, Scottish Government, 2016a)

7.3.2 Practice relating to ‘family learning’: What is the problem?

I propose that the narrow view of ‘family learning’ has promoted beliefs amongst practitioners that any issues with educational attainment or non-conformity with expectations within educational settings is resulting from family backgrounds whilst lacking understanding of differing viewpoints or difficulties presented by other social factors.

Limited dialogue with families about ‘family learning’ has presented a narrow view of family where family is viewed as something that exists as independent of social institutions such as educational settings. I also note that current beliefs of ‘family learning’ has also encouraged a limited view of learning that is most effective for human flourishing for all and of the characteristics that are important for ‘family learning’ practice.

For example, an additional important point raised in literature, which I have refrained from getting into in any detail due to the already complex nature of this topic, is the view that ‘education’ is regarded as something that school provides when preparing children for the future. However, the review of literature and findings in this study have shown support of the following points. Dewey (1916) contests that education is simply “a process of living” for now and therefore requires what is important for each of us to do that. Smith adds that learning driven by the motivation of others and set within specific plans cannot be considered education but “banking” as described by Freire (1973). Smith adds that in deciding what others should learn we run the risk of treating people as “objects to be acted upon rather than people to be related to” (Smith, 2015: n.p.).

Whilst this research study challenges the current view of ‘family learning’, I additionally question if current viewpoints of ‘family learning’ contribute to the ongoing difficulties of Scottish educational services to develop partnership with families. On reflection of findings for this study and participant views presented by Donna and Steven that the use of the term “family learning” in educational settings was “patronising”, I question if other families feel this way. I also suggest that description from findings that schools are targeting specific families is judgemental and offensive and does not present positive grounds on which to build genuine partnerships.

7.3.3 Practice relating to ‘family learning’: What is needed for future practice?

This study has shown a wider view of ‘family learning’ of where it happens and of what ‘family learning’ requires. The findings of this study should be used to instigate further training and exploration on the topic of ‘family learning’ in

developing practice that considers family and learning in broader contexts to ensure “human flourishing” (Underwood, 2009:4).

- The study has highlighted a requirement for ‘family learning’ practice to present ‘ideal’ support to mirror that of loving family communities to ensure effective environments for learning that is personal and meaningful for families.
- To achieve this future ‘family learning’ practice should include constant dialogue with families to gain understanding of what they need. Dialogue with families should inform content, planning and implementation of activities to help support them in their ability to thrive.
- The findings for this study also presented a critical point of reflection for future practice.

It [caring] passes on. We want people to be kind. You learn from example. Nobody wants to live in an uncaring world. You’ve got to pass it on. If you’re dealing with families, they might have had a rotten five years or something, somebody takes that wee bit of time and shows that they actually care. It can make a huge impact on their lives.

The statement above calls for understanding of individual circumstance and is important to consider alongside the importance of ‘love’ needed for ‘family learning’ and the difficulties of incorporating in ‘professional’ roles. In response to addressing the difficulties in ELCC practice, Page (2018) has created a model of ‘professional love’ with Malcolm (2022) suggesting a model of ‘love- led’ practice. Added understanding and the promotion of love for learning and development is being driven within the ‘promise’ arising from the Care Review (Scottish Government, 2016) and within the most current induction guidance for practitioners working in ELCC in Scotland (Scottish Government, 2023).

However, all of these relate to the importance of love when caring for young children. As ‘family learning’ extends across various age ranges and contexts. I feel that ‘Compassionate Love theory’ (Sprecher, Fehr and Underwood (2009) present a more suitable influence to incorporate ‘love’ in practice as it reflects the characteristics valued by participants and literature in support of families and learning alongside supporting the aim of ‘family learning’ to ensure the best outcomes for life. To reiterate, ‘Compassionate Love’ is described as “a kind of love”. A love identified as including “caring, trust, helping, understanding, honesty and support” (Fehr et al, 2009:31). A “self-giving, caring love that values the other highly and has the intention of giving full life to the other” (Fehr et al, 2009: xi). Compassionate love is described as a love which is set apart from other types of love, such as maternal or romantic love. It is defined as a “universal” love that can be “experienced in all types of relationships and settings” (Fehr et al, 2009: xi). As such, I propose that future ‘family learning’ practice be underpinned by this theory and model of working.

- Practice requires reflection to overcome challenges of incorporating ‘love’ in settings. It is noted that practice of ‘compassionate love’ is not straightforward as it is affected by culture, social contexts, and environment. Additionally, research shows that perceptions of what compassionate love is differs from person to person. Practice of compassionate love may be hindered between strangers as opposed to being easier amongst individuals who know each other well.
- Future training for those working in ‘professional’ supporting roles requires consideration of ‘love’ as an essential element of practice. This study considers compassionate love in relation to family learning practice for both, families living in Scotland in which close relationships exist and amongst Scottish educational settings in which individuals may not have

close relationships and therefore supports the view of Morris (2021) in suggesting further consideration for training of individuals working in supporting roles to identify possible barriers and ways to overcome the incorporation of ‘love’ in their ‘professional’ role.

- In addition to the above recommendations for practice and points noted in policy recommendations, the study highlights that time, environments and funding are needed to build relationships and provide support for ‘family learning’ practice. The nexus between an expectation of developing employment and training opportunities and partnership with families in future ‘family learning’ approaches also present further consideration for practice in finding alternative methods that continue development of technology as a possible contemporary aspect of families and solution.

Finally, this study has presented ‘power’ and ‘love’ as separate influences on family life and learning in Scotland today. This study calls once again for consideration of these two elements in combination rather than as opposing factors. I echo the sentiments of Martin Luther King when he explains:

One of the great problems of history is that the concepts of love and power have usually been contrasted as opposites—polar opposites—so that love is identified with a resignation of power, and power with a denial of love. ... What is needed is the realization that power without love is reckless and abusive, and that love without power is sentimental and anaemic. Power at its best is love implementing the demands of justice, and justice at its best is love correcting everything that stands against love. (Martin Luther King 1990, p. 247).

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8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix 1: Interview guide.

Study title:

'What's Love got to do with it? Conceptualising family learning: understanding how families learn together?'

Aim: This study aims to identify excellent family learning practice and develop recommendations for better practice to promote positive relationships between educational establishments and families.

Objectives:

- 1. To gain understanding of how family learning is defined by families and practitioners.*
- 2. To understand how families learn together.*
- 3. To identify why families, learn together.*
- 4. To explore what key aspects are important for family learning,*
- 5. To understand why these key aspects are important for family learning.*

Interview questions.

FIRST SECTION: Exploring objectives 1, 2, 3, 4 & 5.

1. When you hear the term family learning, what ideas does it immediately bring to mind? (Objective 1.)
2. Can you think of an occasion when you experienced family learning? What was it like? (Objective 1).
3. So, from the things that you have describedI wonder if you would explain, what individual actions/qualities you think are important for family learning in these instances. (Objective 4)
4. Will you describe for me how these actions/qualities are important for family learning? (Objective 3 & 5)
5. Who do you think benefits from these actions? (Objective 3 & 5)
6. Do you think that these actions might be difficult sometimes? (Objectives 2, 4 & 5.)
7. You have answered that you do/or do not think these actions would be difficult. Can you tell me how you think in this way? (For example, are there family learning experiences which you could provide to demonstrate how you think the actions are/ or are not difficult).? (Objective 4 & 5.)

Thank for input on this section. I would like to confirm with you that I have understood the key points that you have made within this section before moving on to the next topic area.

SECOND SECTION: Exploring objectives 2 &3.

8. How do you think the actions that you have described enhance learning?
(Objectives 2 & 3.)

9. Can you describe what or if other areas of life are enhanced by learning?
(Objective 3).

10. Can you explain to me why you think/or don't think these other areas are
enhanced by learning? Can you explain how you think this way?
(Objective 3).

11. Can you elaborate on how you think this way? Could you provide a
description of an experience that you have had which makes you think
this way? (Objective 3).

Can I confirm with you that I have understood the key points that you have
made within this section before moving on to the next topic area.

*The following third section will only be covered if the participant has
mentioned that some form of communication is important for family
learning.

THIRD SECTION: Exploring objectives 2, 4 &5.

12. You mentioned, for example, talking (or communication or listening), as being important for family learning. Can you explain how you think XXXXX is important? (Objectives 4 & 5).

13. Who might be involved in this XXXX? (Objectives 4 & 5).

14. Can you describe what might stop XXXX from happening? (Objectives 4 & 5).

15. You feel that xxxx is important for family learning. What do you think helps xxxxx to happen? (Objective 2).

16. *Can I confirm with you that I have understood the key points that you have made within this section before we finish?*

Additional information added:

8.2 Appendix 2: Initial data analysis

Appendix 2: Initial analysis aligned with questions and objectives of the study.

Initial analysis identified the following codes		
family learning is aim of family learning differences in family learning ways of learning what is family? what is education? people involved in family learning where family learning happens challenges for family learning family learning needs family learning practice the benefit of certain aspects within family learning negative aspects of family learning		
Codes separated to each research question and related objectives of the study.		
Research question:	Related Objectives:	Codes that relate to question and objective
What does the term family-learning mean?	To gain understanding of how families and practitioners define family learning. To establish how families learn together. To establish why families learn together.	family learning is aim of family learning differences in family learning ways of learning what is family? what is education?
Where does family learning happen?		people involved in family learning where family learning happens
What is important for family learning?	To explore what key aspects are important for family learning. To establish why these key aspects are important for family learning.	challenges for family learning family learning needs family learning practice the benefit of certain aspects within family learning negative aspects of family learning

8.3 Appendix 3: Exemplar of refining data analysis.

Research question: What does the term family-learning mean?					
Objective: To gain understanding of how families and practitioners define family learning.					
Objective: To establish how families learn together.					
Objective: To establish why families learn together.					
FL IS	AIM OF FL	DIFFERENCE IN FL	WAYS OF LEARNING	WHAT IS FAMILY?	WHAT IS EDUC?
<p>I1 DEPENDENT OF CONTEXT i.e. depends on the setting in which FAMILY LEARNING is being considered.</p> <p>I1 DIFFERENT THINGS TO DIFFERENT PEOPLE</p> <p>I6 DIFFERENT FOR EVERYONE DIFFERENT FOR DIFFERENT PEOPLE</p> <p>I1 SOCIETAL EXPECTATIONS</p>	<p>DEVELOPMENT SUCCESS IN LIFE F2 TO BE SUCCESSFUL IN LIFE AND SUCCESSFUL IN JOB.</p> <p>F2 ENCOURAGE CHILDREN TO BE SUCCESSFUL WITHOUT JUDGING THEM TOO MUCH.</p> <p>F2 TO HAVE MONEY TO BE ABLE TO LIVE A COMFORTABLE LIFE.</p> <p>F3 FOR CHILDREN TO GROW AND DEVELOP TO BECOME THE <u>BEST</u> YOU CAN BE.</p> <p>F4.</p>	<p>DIFFERENCES</p> <p>DIFFERENT FAMILIES F1/F3 DIFFERENCE BETWEEN FAMILY VALUES 3</p> <p>F1 FAMILY LEARNING DEPENDS ON CULTURAL AND RELIGIOUS VALUES.</p> <p>F1 DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PARENTS AND CHILDRENS VALUES</p> <p>F1 DIFFERENCES BETWEEN ADULTS AND CHILDREN</p> <p>F4 FAMILY LEARNING IS BASED ON GENERATIONAL TRADITIONS, MORALS AND VALUES.</p>	<p>CHANGES IN LEARNING TECHNOLOGY F1 CHILDREN NOW LEARNING THROUGH PLAYING WITH TECHNOLOGY</p> <p>I4 BY USING THE INTERNET</p> <p>F1 LEARNING THROUGH EXPLORATION</p> <p>IN EXPERIENCES F3 EVERYDAY PROGRESSING YOUR COGNITIVE, PHYSICAL</p>	<p>DIFFERENCES IN FAMILY F1 SCHOOL AS FAMILY FOR SOME CHILDREN.</p> <p>F4 FOR SOME CHILDREN NURSERY STAFF PROVIDE A "SENSE OF FAMILY" AND A "SENSE OF SUPPORT".</p> <p>I7 BORDER CROSSING TO SOME PEOPLE IT MAY BE SOMETHING ELSE IT MAY BE NURSERY/SCHOOL</p>	<p>DIFFERENCES IN EDUCATION AND LEARNING F2 WHAT IS LEARNED IN SCHOOL</p> <p>F2 WIDE RANGE OF TOPICS(CFE) TAUGHT IN SCHOOL</p>

9

I1 PROVIDING INFORMATION OF EXPECTATIONS FOR EMPLOYMENT	TO MAKE SURE THAT YOU ARE HAPPY WITH YOUR LIFE ACHIEVEMENT	F4 WHERE SOME FAMILIES PROVIDE CHOICE AND SOME FAMILIES EXPECT YOU TO CONFORM TO FAMILY TRADITION/CULTURE/VALUES	SKILLS, OPINIONS AND INTERPRETATIONS. F3 LEARNING EVERYDAY MORE THAN	(IF THEY DO NOT RECEIVE CARE OR WHAT A FAMILY WOULD PROVIDE YOU WITH AT	
I1 HELPING TO GAIN 'GOOD'	F4				

Research question: Where does family learning happen?	
WHERE FAMILY LEARNING HAPPENS	PEOPLE INVOLVED IN F LEARNING
<p>DIFFERENCES WITH YOUR FAMILY</p> <p>F1 FAMILY DAYS OUT. F1 ON HOLIDAY. F1 AT HOME F3 IN A FAMILY AT HOME F3 AT HOME IN FAMILIES F4 AT HOME F4 IN FAMILIES AT HOME F4 FAMILY</p> <p>I1/I2 IN THE HOME 3 I1 IN FAMILY EXPERIENCES I4 DURING FAMILY WALKS IN THE WOOD I7 AT HOME</p>	<p>DIFFERENT TIMES OF LIFE INVOLVE DIFFERENT PEOPLE</p> <p>F1 FAMILY LEARNING AS A TEACHER F1 FAMILY LEARNING AS A MUM</p> <p>F1 FAMILY LEARNING AS A PARENT F1 FAMILY LEARNING HAPPENS WHEN YOU ARE A CHILD. F2 FAMILY LEARNING AS A PARENT 1 F2 FAMILY LEARNING AS A CHILD 1 F4 WHEN YOU ARE YOUNGER IT IS YOUR IMMEDIATE FAMILY AS YOU GET OLDER IT MIGHT BE FRIENDS OR A TEACHER</p> <p>FAMILY MEMBERS</p> <p>F2/I1 A VARIETY OF FAMILY MEMBERS LIVING AND NOT LIVING. 3 F2/I1 A YOUNG PERSON 2 F2/I4 MUM AND DAD 2, I4 PARENTS WITH THEIR KIDS 3 F2/I4 GRAN AND GRANDPA 4</p>

Research question: What is important for family learning?				
Objective: To explore what key aspects are important for family learning.				
Objective: To establish why these key aspects are important for family learning.				

CHALLENGES FOR FL	FAMILY LEARNING NEEDS	FL PRACTICE	BENEFITS OF FL	NEGATIVES OF FL
<p>CHANGING SOCIETY</p> <p>CHANGING FAMILIES F1 CHANGES IN SOCIETY MEANS THAT FAMILY LEARNING MEANS SOMETHING DIFFERENT NOW TO BEFORE.(ALSO A DIFFERENCE)</p> <p>F1 TRADITIONAL NOTIONS OF FAMILY ARE CHANGING.</p> <p>CHANGING SOCIETAL NORMS F1 LACK OF UNDERSTANDING BETWEEN YOUNG PEOPLE AND ADULTS.</p> <p>F2 DIFFERENCES BETWEEN GENERATIONS AND SOCIETAL VALUES(ALSO IN DIFFERENCES)</p> <p>F3 LACK OF DISCIPLINE</p>	<p>COMMUNITY</p> <p>I1 FAMILY LEARNING NEEDS TO BE RECOGNISED AS SOMETHING THAT HAPPENS IN A VARIETY OF PLACES WITH VARIOUS PEOPLE.</p> <p>I1 FAMILY LEARNING NEEDS A VARIETY OF PEOPLE TO PROVIDE A NETWORK OF SUPPORT</p> <p>I1 PARTNERSHIP TO GAIN INFORMATION IN COMMUNITY LEARNING OPPORTUNITIES COMMUNITY</p> <p>I6 COMMUNITY FAMILY LEARNING THAT HAPPENS OUTWITH THE</p>	<p>WHERE</p> <p>F3 HAPPENS IN SCHOOLS F3 IS MORE THAN TEACHING KIDS</p> <p>I1 COMMUNITIES PROVIDE FAMILY LEARNING CLASSES</p> <p>INDIVIDUALS, ORGANISATIONS AND COMMUNITIES COMING TOGETHER TO SUPPORT EACH OTHER</p> <p>AIM/ BENEFITS OF PRACTICE TO DEVELOP; SOCIAL SKILLS, BASIC LIFE SKILLS, COPING</p>		

Editor Suggestions: Showing